

**WORKFORCE DEVELOPMENT AND DEMENTIA CARE IN
BANGLADESH: POLICY LEARNING FROM THE SCOTTISH
CONTEXT**

MOHAMMAD MAINUDDIN MOLLAH

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

February 2024

Abstract

Dementia is a neuro-progressive condition and global public health concern, impacting individuals, families, carers, and society. The rising number of people diagnosed with dementia has given rise to calls for countries to develop national dementia action plans and associated strategies for dementia care workforce development. The aim of this study was to investigate Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches to consider their potential application within Bangladesh. A pragmatic sequential mixed study was completed, including an integrative literature review, documentary policy analysis and key informant interviews to explore Scottish dementia policy. This was complimented by a series of nominal group technique (NGT) meetings with cross sectorial stakeholders in Bangladesh. Data collection and analysis were underpinned by an innovative fusion of two structured frameworks for evaluating policy success and policy transfer. Rigour was promoted drawing upon the principles of triangulation and complementarity.

Twenty-two Scottish policy documents and five key informant interviews were analysed to evaluate the process, programme, and political level success of Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches. In addition, twenty-five multi-sectoral stakeholders participated in five NGT discussions in Bangladesh. Findings of the documentary policy analysis and key informant interviews identified important ingredients for success, including stakeholder involvement, a right-based dementia care approach, and commitment for developing and implementing innovative practice models. The NGT findings identified priorities for future dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Bangladesh. These included developing dementia awareness, education and training for health and social care professionals and family carers, early detection, proper diagnosis, and treatment, developing and promoting health and social care systems for people living with dementia. The project managed to successfully integrate findings from Scotland and Bangladesh and how this can lead to more informed approaches to policy transfer in dementia and help to realise current goals for a global joined-up approach.

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Acknowledgements

I am very much grateful to the Almighty Allah for completing the thesis. In preparing this thesis, I have incurred a lot of debts to a number of people and institutions in Scotland and Bangladesh. I would like to acknowledge those who have supported me during my PhD and contributed to this thesis. First and foremost, I would like to express my deepest gratitude to Professor Debbie Tolson, Dr Anna-Jack-Waugh, Dr Nick Jenkins, Professor John Connolly, and Professor Dr Golam Rabbani for guiding me through this journey with unwavering encouragement and cordial support. I would like also to express my grateful appreciation to Dr Constantina Papadopoulou and Dr Eileen Harkess-Murphy for assessing my study progress and providing necessary guidelines. I also express my sincere thanks to Dr Margaret Brown, Dr Louise Ritchie, Dr Rhoda Macrae, Dr Raymond Duffy, Dr Bryan Mitchell, and Susan Holland for providing support to adapt to the new academic environment and continue study with different levels of support from the very beginning of my PhD journey in the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice (ASCPP), at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) as an International PhD student. Sincere thanks go to my fellow PhD students Michael Smith, Angela Gregory, Connor McDonald, Carol Beckwith, Rachel Allen, Yvonne Manson, Margaret Kyeremeh, Vinodhini Murugavel, Adeola-Mary Kayode, and Meghan Bateson for ever-ending support and inspiration to adjust with the new environment, culture and life, and continue study progress.

I am highly indebted to Dhaka University and the Bangabandhu Overseas Scholarship Programme authority for funding this PhD studentship and providing me with the opportunity to conduct the PhD study with all kinds of necessary support during the study period. I am also grateful to the Scottish Dementia Research Consortium (SDRC) for providing me with financial support for purchasing technological equipment to adapt to the COVID-19 pandemic during the study period.

I would like to extend my sincere thanks to all the key dementia policy stakeholders in Scotland and multi-level stakeholder groups in Bangladesh, including family members and informal carers of people living with dementia, health and social care practitioners, academics (educators and researchers), dementia care providers, and policy planners who contributed to the research by sharing their thought and important information with me and spending their invaluable time, without which it would not have been possible to provide flesh and blood to the thesis. I must express the deepest gratitude to Mr Azizul Haque, Secretary General of the

Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh and Mr Rashed Suhrawardy, Secretary General of the Dementia Care Foundation for their kind inspiration and cordial support in recruiting and conducting virtual NGT discussions during the challenging time of COVID-19 restrictions in Bangladesh.

I would like to thank the Doctoral College, International Student Support, HUB, Library, and ITDS teams for providing excellent and prompt support during my study. I must express the deepest gratitude to Margo Stewart, Academic Librarian, School of Health and Life Sciences, at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS), for providing continuous support to learn and use EndNote reference management to develop and format references in my thesis.

I would like to record my appreciation for the support, encouragement, and kind inspiration I received from Professor Dr Muhammad Samad, Houn arable Pro-Vice-Chancellor (Admin.), University of Dhaka and my colleagues in the Institute of Social Welfare and Research (ISWR), University of Dhaka.

I am indebted to my dearest son Sabbeer Mahmood and daughter Sumaiza Moin Arisha, and my beloved wife Subarna Shirin for the continuous company during my stay and study in Scotland and Bangladesh, and at the same time, the sacrifice they made while I was working on the report. Their patience and inspiration have given me the fortitude for the many late-night hours required to complete this thesis. Finally, I am grateful to my mother, Sufia Begum, brothers, sisters, relatives and friends, and late father, Mohammad Habizuddin Mollah, who continued to be the chief and the constant source of inspiration during my whole academic career.

Declaration

This piece of coursework is my own original work and has not been submitted elsewhere in fulfilment of the requirement of this or any other award.

Chapter One: Background and Context of the Study

1.1 Introduction

This study investigates Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches to determine policy learning opportunities for Bangladesh. This introductory chapter situates the study in relation to dementia as an international public health priority, requiring national dementia strategies and frameworks for workforce development. Creating a rationale for the investigation prior to outlining the research design, study aim and objectives. The chapter concludes with an overview of the thesis structure.

1.2 Background

1.2.1 Dementia as an International Public Health Priority

Dementia is a global public health concern, impacting individuals, and having significant economic as well as psychological consequences on families, caregivers, and society at large (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2019a; Gauthier *et al.*, 2021; World Health Organization, 2018). Currently, dementia is considered to be major non-communicable diseases (NCDs) and the largest global cause of disability among older people (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2019a; World Health Organization, 2017a). Dementia is an overarching term associated with neuro-progressive diseases such as Alzheimer's disease. Although considered a condition of old age, dementia diagnosis before the age of 65 years is increasing (Gauthier *et al.*, 2021; World Health Organization, 2017a). Dementia symptoms vary with the underlying disease pathology but commonly involve deterioration in cognition and memory, sensory impairments, and impaired communicative function. Deterioration in brain health over time adding to the complexity of symptoms and increasing dependency of others for activities of daily living. Alzheimer's disease is the most common form of dementia accounting for 60–70% of cases. Other forms include vascular dementia, dementia with Lewy bodies, and a group of diseases that contribute to frontotemporal dementia (World Health Organization, 2017a).

Dementia is a neuro-progressive condition caused by diseases including Alzheimer's disease. Symptoms of dementia include deteriorating brain health, deterioration in cognitive functioning, problems with memory, communication loss, feeling confused and disoriented in time, place and person. Symptoms worsen over time as both brain and bodily health

deteriorates. Although in the early phase of illness it may be possible for individuals with mild dementia to live independently, with the increasing severity of symptoms dependency on others increases over time (Age Scotland, 2022; Scottish Government, 2023a). The advanced phase of illness is associated with full dependency and complex palliative care needs leading to end of life care needs (Tolson et al., 2016).

In some but not all countries dementia care is recognised as an important area of practice (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2019a). A recent survey on attitudes to dementia conducted by Alzheimer's Disease International (ADI) reported that two in every three people believe that dementia is the consequence of normal ageing. One in every four people think that there is nothing to be done to prevent dementia and 62 per cent of healthcare practitioners still believe that dementia is part of normal ageing (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2019b). In many countries, the lack of awareness about dementia and the absence of legal frameworks to protect the rights of people with dementia, create a significant challenge in ensuring equitable access to expert dementia services and acceptance of dementia care in society (World Health Organization, 2018). Although most people with dementia live at home, there are significant variations across countries as well as between urban and rural areas. For example, in Asia and Central and Latin America, almost all people with dementia live in the family home, especially in rural areas (GBD Dementia Forecasting Collaborators, 2022; Pot and Petrea, 2013). However, there is a lack of adequate health resources and policy initiatives in most Asian countries to deal with this continually growing public health challenge, which is often viewed as incurable and without remedy (Kabir *et al.*, 2016).

1.2.2 Global Demographic Projections of Dementia

As an increasing public health concern, in 2019, more than 57.4 million people are found to be affected by dementia worldwide, by 2050, this number will increase to 152.8 million people (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2018; GBD Dementia Forecasting Collaborators, 2022). Nearly 60 per cent of people with dementia live in the low-and middle-income countries (LMICs). By 2050, this proportion will rise steeply in LMICs to an estimated 68 per cent contributing to the numbers of people living with dementia higher than estimates in high-income countries (Prince *et al.*, 2015). It is estimated that by 2050, the number of people in the Asia Pacific Region with dementia will rise to 64.6 million (Kabir *et al.*, 2016). Growth in the number of individuals living with dementia underscores the need for public health planning efforts and policy to address the needs of this group (GBD Dementia Forecasting Collaborators, 2022). Moreover, it is imperative for the low-and middle-income countries (LMICs) to prepare their health and social care workforce and develop service models and

care infrastructures to provide appropriate support for people living with dementia, their families and carers across the illness trajectory (Devi *et al.*, 2019).

1.2.3 The Experiences of Dementia in Bangladesh

Beside this global milieu of dementia care, Bangladesh is going to face a critical condition due to its ever-increasing ageing population. The total population of the country is 168.2 million and life expectancy at birth in 2020 is 72.8 years with male 71.2 years and female 74.5 years (Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2021). In 2021, 8.3 % of the total population in Bangladesh were over the age of sixty years and in 2030 this number is estimated to grow up to 12 % and by 2050, it will increase up to 22 % of the total population (Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, 2021; United Nations, 2019). The common problems faced by the older people in Bangladesh are economic hardships, exclusion and negligence by family as well as society, social isolation, deprivation, socio-economic insecurity, multiple health problems including dementia, lack of expertise in geriatric and inadequate health care facilities for the elderly population (Islam, Sultan and Hossain, 2021; Kabir *et al.*, 2016).

According to ADI Annual Report published in 2021, globally 75% of people with dementia are not diagnosed. This may be as high as 90% in some low and middle-income countries, where stigma and lack of awareness of dementia remain major barriers to diagnosis (Gauthier *et al.*, 2021). In the context of Bangladesh, people living with dementia often go undiagnosed and suffer from lack of proper dementia care (Kabir *et al.*, 2013; Sultana, 2019). Records about the number of people living with dementia in Bangladesh are insubstantial, and there is minimal research conducted in this leading area of public health. It is also possible that data is lacking, and the need is likely to be greater than the current prediction due to the differences shown in different studies (Hossain *et al.*, 2021; ICDDR-B, 2021; Uddin *et al.*, 2019). Global Burden of Diseases (GBD) Dementia Forecasting Collaborators estimated that in Bangladesh 5,70,899 people were living with dementia in 2019, which will increase to 20,91,081 by 2050 (GBD Dementia Forecasting Collaborators, 2022). Whereas, the Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh (ASB) reported that in 2018, almost 4,60,000 people were living with dementia in Bangladesh, which will increase to 8,34,000 by 2030 and 21,91,000 by 2050 (Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh, 2018). In addition, a recent national survey report conducted by the International Centre for Diarrhoeal Disease Research, Bangladesh (ICDDR-B) (2021) on the burden of dementia among older people in Bangladesh estimated that one in every 12 individuals of 60 years or older in Bangladesh have dementia. The study found that the total number of people living with dementia in 2020 is 1.1 million, including 0.28 million males and 0.83 million females. The report projected that the number will increase to 1.37 million in 2025

and could be doubled in 2041 which may increase even further if not intervened effectively. The study did not find any significant variation between rural and urban areas in Bangladesh. The study also found that more than half of the people living with dementia had one or more chronic conditions, including hypertension (52%), depression (54%), and diabetes (8%) (ICDDR-B, 2021).

Further, a study report, jointly conducted by Karolinska Institute, Sweden and the International Centre for Diarrhoeal Disease Research-Bangladesh claimed that the prevalence of possible dementia is 11.5% and diagnosed dementia is 3.6% among the rural older population of the country. The study found that dementia prevalence in Bangladesh was associated with increasing age, lower education, malnourishment, and infrequent participation in social activities. Interestingly, the prevalence of dementia in rural Bangladesh is similar to other countries in the South Asia region but lower than reports from other regions of the world (Palmer *et al.*, 2014). The reasons for this difference are unclear and may be due to under reporting or low diagnosis rates. If the government is not informed about the accurate picture of dementia, it is difficult to formulate dementia care policy and plan to address the future needs of dementia care in Bangladesh. Although the accuracy of dementia statistics in Bangladesh can be challenged, there is no doubt that there are large numbers of people living with dementia who would benefit from dementia care services and practitioners skilled in dementia care.

1.2.4 Services and Workforce to Provide Care to Older People and People Living with Dementia in Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, social awareness about dementia is minimal and most of the people living in the countryside do not get sufficient essential medical services (Kabir *et al.*, 2013; Sultana, 2019; Uddin *et al.*, 2019). The study reported that hospital records related to dementia care are not available and access to medical care is limited in rural Bangladesh (Palmer *et al.*, 2014). According to recent study findings conducted on perceptions of successful ageing among the older people in Bangladesh, dementia is perceived as an usual outcome of old age and not considered as an illness (Amin, 2017). Accessing appropriate healthcare and social support for people living with dementia is difficult in Bangladesh, and there are growing calls for a skilled and experienced dementia workforce. It is recognized that healthcare workers, nurses, practitioners, family members and caregivers all need appropriate education and training about dementia (Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh, 2018; Roy *et al.*, 2020). In addition to this, because of the rapid socio-economic and demographic transitions, poverty, changing social patterns, the influence of globalization and other socio-economic factors related to

growth and development; the traditional extended family and community care, as well as the support systems, have been weakening day by day. It is estimated that by 2040, the increasing number of older populations will challenge the existing health care services by not only with the change in the conventional family structure but also with the rapid increase of the unmet need of the health care services. Therefore, a clear trajectory is needed to establish a complete and professional support system for the older people and people living with dementia in Bangladesh (Amin, 2017; Islam and Nath, 2012; Kabir *et al.*, 2016; Nath and Islam, 2009).

A recent study on the situation of Alzheimer's disease and facilities, expertise, and awareness among general people in Bangladesh conducted by Roy *et al.* (2020) revealed that the number of health care practitioners including neurologists, neuropsychologists, geriatricians, and geriatric psychiatrists working on Alzheimer's disease is not sufficient enough compared to a large number of the older population in Bangladesh (Roy *et al.*, 2020). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the number of neurologists available per 10,000 population in Bangladesh is only 0.09. Moreover, there is no long-term care facilities, adult day centers and outpatient social welfare centers for people living with dementia and their families in Bangladesh. Although, there is an existence of a dementia representative within the ministry. However, there is no stand-alone or integrated dementia plan and no available guidance for health and social care workers to manage dementia risk and to improve the quality of life for the people living with dementia, their families and carers in Bangladesh (World Health Organization, 2017b).

However, recently, some non-governmental organizations have been working to raise awareness of dementia at the community and family level. These include the Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh (ASB), Dementia Care Foundation, Sir William Beveridge Foundation, and Sajida Foundation. Those organizations also provide support for research on dementia along with training for caregivers and old home services (Roy *et al.*, 2020).

In addition, there are other government, non-government and international organizations including the Department of Social Services, the Ministry of Social Welfare, Bangladesh Association for the Aged and Institute of Geriatric Medicine, Help Age International Bangladesh, Resource Integration Centre, Dhaka Ahsania Mission, Old Rehabilitation Centre, Service Centre for Elderly People (SCEP), and Palli Karma Sahayak Foundation (PKSF) working for the wellbeing of older people, which are not directly related with dementia services. They are providing general health service, neurological support, social and emotional support, empowerment and improved lifestyles, counseling services, recreational facilities, and very limited old home services in urban areas to improve the quality of life for older people and people living with dementia, their families and carers in Bangladesh (Roy *et al.*, 2020).

In addition to this, some educational and research institutes, including medical universities, government and private medical colleges and nursing institutes, as well as specialized health care research and training institutes, are increasingly responding to the needs of the ageing population. Although these organizations are working in the field of geriatric and gerontology, emphasising dementia and Alzheimer's related issues in the context of Bangladesh, the provisions of those organizations about dementia are in their infancy (Rabbani and Mollah, 2021; Roy *et al.*, 2020).

Regarding health education, currently, 147 government and Non-government Medical Colleges, 28 post-graduate Medical Institutions, 14 nursing colleges, and 47 nursing institutes are working to develop a skilled workforce and improve the quality of health and social care services in Bangladesh. However, there is an absence of dementia-specific education programme and training facilities at any level of health education in Bangladesh (Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2021). Further, the Institute of Social welfare and Research (ISWR), University of Dhaka has been conducting a professional Master's Programme on Gerontology and Geriatric Welfare (GGW) since 2012 to develop the professional knowledge base and workforce for the wellbeing of older people in the context of Bangladesh which is relatively a new subject in Bangladesh and needs much scholarly intervention to develop it further (Rabbani and Mollah, 2021).

1.2.5 Policies and Legal Frameworks Related to Dementia Care and Workforce Development in Bangladesh

Although in Bangladesh there are some national policies and legislations indirectly related to the welfare of older people, including the National Disability Policy 1995, the National Social Welfare Policy 2005, the National Health Policy 2011, and the Bangladesh Population Policy 2012, there is currently an absence of dementia care and workforce development planning and policy. Dementia care is yet to be included and prioritised in the country's national healthcare policy (Rahman *et al.*, 2017; World Health Organization, 2017b). Encouragingly within the Seventh Five Year Plan (2016-2020) of the Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh (GoB), the government has committed to promoting mental health and wellbeing of the people living with dementia, including access to essential care (Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2015). Furthermore, the Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh has emphasised the rights and privileges of the older people, along with other citizens (Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2018a). In addition to this, the Bangladesh Government has formulated the National Policy on Older Persons (Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2013a) and the Parent's Maintenance

Act in 2013 (Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2013b). Moreover, Bangladesh Government has formulated a new Mental Health Act in 2018, which brings hope for people living with mental illnesses including dementia for protecting their rights and developing provisions for health and rehabilitative services (Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2018b; Hossain *et al.*, 2019).

It follows that the Government needs to find innovative ways to ensure comprehensive support and care system for its older people and people living with dementia by formulating new as well as strengthening the existing policies, institutions, and socio-economic structures. Policy planners and those who will work for implementation must understand the complex interrelationships of the health, socio-economic status, and available facilities of the people living with dementia to address the challenges of the increasing number of older populations with dementia.

Moreover, the government also needs to work on comprehensive and integrated workforce development approaches to conduct formal training and education for health and social care workers, practitioners, caregivers, and family members who provide care and support to people living with dementia. It is therefore time to review national strategies and policies related to dementia care and develop an evidence base to support policy actors and health and social care professionals and allied groups, to develop progressive strategies that recognise dementia and dementia care as a public health priority in Bangladesh (Rahman *et al.*, 2017).

1.2.6 Requiring National Dementia Strategies and Frameworks for Workforce Development

In May 2017, the global action plan on public health response to dementia, 2017-2025 was adopted by the Seventieth World Health Assembly in Geneva, Switzerland. The global dementia action plan is aligned with the Shanghai Declaration on Promoting Health in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, Sustainable Development Goal 3 (good health and well-being), and the United Nations (UN) Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) that apply to people living in any country with dementia (World Health Organization, 2017a). It is expected that by 2025, seventy-five per cent of countries will have national policies, strategies, plans or frameworks for dementia. A comprehensive, multisectoral public policy response aimed at addressing the needs of people with dementia, their families and carers; is needed to improve the quality of life, enhance equitable access to services and reduce stigma and social isolation (World Health Organization, 2018).

Dementia is a complex phenomenon which requires specific attention in national dementia plans and needs to be integrated into other overarching policies such as mental health, Non-communicable Diseases (NCDs) and ageing policies (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2019a). Dementia is one of the toughest challenges in health care which presents a looming threat to the financial and social systems across the developed and developing world (Pot and Petrea, 2013). There is an urgent need for policies to be agreed and implemented for dementia care, therefore, the World Health Organization (WHO), ADI, and BUPA recommended that every country needs to have a National Dementia Plan (Pot and Petrea, 2013). As the prevalence of dementia rises and countries around the world face the challenge of supporting people living with dementia, their families and carers to live well with dementia, the need for specialist knowledge grows. To promote the best quality of life for people living with dementia, their families and carers, health and social care professionals, nurses, practitioners, family members and caregivers all need appropriate dementia education and adequate training (McCabe and Comstock, 2021). Additionally, the global action plan on public health response to dementia proposes to build the knowledge and skills of general and specialised staff in the health workforce to deliver evidence-based, culturally appropriate and human rights-based health and social care services for people living with dementia, their families and carers (World Health Organization, 2017a).

At present, 39 member states of WHO have got their national dementia plans or other policies on dementia (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2023). Many countries in Europe and some other countries across the rest of the world have their National Dementia Plans which are often presented as National Dementia Strategies (Jackson and Tolson, 2019). France, England, Scotland, Northern Ireland, the Netherlands, Norway, and Australia are considered as world pioneers in developing dementia care policies (Cahill, O'Shea and Pierce, 2012). Lessons can be learned from their experiences by countries like Bangladesh, who lack the development of health and social policy on dementia. Bangladesh is committed to implementing the Sustainable Development Goals as a government and a global priority (Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2015). The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are the road map to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all. In 2015, the United Nations General Assembly adopted the SDG agenda which outlines 17 goals and 169 targets to address the global challenges including poverty, inequality, climate change, environment degradation, peace and justice to improve lives and prospects of everyone, everywhere by 2030 and to ensure that no one will be left behind (United Nations, 2015). To ensure a healthy life and promote well-being for all at all ages, the SDG goal 3 'good health and well-being' was established by the UN in 2015 (United Nations, 2015). Although Bangladesh has taken some initiatives to develop policies and programmes to support and

care for people living with dementia and their families, these initiatives are not directly related to dementia care (national health policy, national mental health policy, national policy on older people etc.) (Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2011; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2012; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2013a; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2013b; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2018b). Therefore, it is time for Bangladesh to develop robust dementia related policies to move toward achieving the SDG goal 3 (Health and Well Being). In addition, the SDG goal 10 also aims at reducing 'inequality within and among countries'. At present, twenty per cent member states of the WHO have already developed their national dementia policies and strategies (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2023), whereas it is expected that by 2025, seventy-five per cent of the countries will develop their national policies and strategies as well as frameworks for dementia (World Health Organization, 2018). Such measures worldwide also place further emphasis on countries like Bangladesh to develop national dementia care and workforce development policy to address the upcoming challenges of dementia and to provide comprehensive and diverse services for the growing number of older populations including people living with dementia, their families and carers. Policy makers of Bangladesh can learn lessons from other countries to develop dementia care policies of their own.

1.2.7 National Dementia Strategies and Frameworks for Workforce Development and Dementia Care in Scotland

Dementia is one of the significant public health issues for the people in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2010). In the domain of dementia care policy and delivery of services for dementia care, Scotland is one of the most advanced nations. For example, care management was established for people living with dementia in 1991. In 1999, the UK Parliament delegated powers to the Scottish Parliament and afterward, the former Scottish Executive focused on the issue of dementia by setting up dementia care within the policies and welfare of health, mental health, long-term care, older people, and incapacity. Moreover, Scotland developed national care standards in 2001 and provided free personal care in 2002. The Scottish government started paying for family caregivers who would care for people with dementia at home in 2006 (Lin, 2010).

Legislative framework and provisions play an important role in developing dementia care policies and delivering dementia care to ensure the rights and dignity of the people living with dementia and their families and carers in Scotland. To access services provisions and ensure their rights as citizens, people with dementia and their families need legal protection and

support. Considering their loss of capacity and being vulnerable at points in the illness, mistreatment and abuses of human rights, people living with dementia are entitled to get safeguarding from abuse and neglect and if abuse is experienced, immediate actions need to be taken to stop and prevent it. However, research has shown that older adults with dementia are more likely to experience abuse and neglect than those without a diagnosis. These include psychological, physical, financial or sexual abuse that can take place anywhere, including the community, care homes or hospitals (Department of Health and Social Care, 2021). The legal framework in Scotland which aims to protect the rights of vulnerable adults and their decision making, including people with dementia incorporates the Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000; the Mental Health (Care and Treatment) (Scotland) Act 2003; and the Adult Support and Protection (Scotland) Act 2007 (Alzheimer Scotland, 2020). For example, the Adults With Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000 provides a framework for safeguarding the welfare of those adults who lack capacity to take decision for themselves due to a mental disorder or inability to communicate (Scottish Government, 2000). The Mental Welfare Commission is working in collaboration with NHS Education for Scotland to improve understanding of the Adults with Incapacity Act 2000 by devising and delivering new learning for health and care staff across Scotland. In addition, the Commission play an important role in ensuring that care, treatment and support are lawful and promote the welfare and rights of individuals with mental illness, learning disability and related conditions (Mental Welfare Commission for Scotland, 2023). However, the Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000 (AWI), though it had a set of guiding principles to protect the rights of people lacking in capacity, much has changed since 2000 and significant court decisions have raised concerns about the way residential care for adults is authorised. For example, in 2005, the European Court issued its ruling which made it clear that persons who lack capacity to consent to deprivation of liberty must have the protection of Article 5 European Court of Human Rights (ECHR). Further since 2009, the Scottish Government is committed to fully implement the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD). In addition, the increase in the number of guardianships under the legislation has resulted in significant delays in processing applications, meaning persons in need of help under the legislation are sometimes adversely affected because of these delays. Therefore, in 2018, the Scottish Government carried out a consultation on the Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000 to seek views with a wide range of stakeholders and service users suggesting changes to the legislation and practice around the AWI act (Scottish Government, 2018). On the other hand, the Regulation of Care (Scotland) Act 2001 enabled the Scottish Government to establish a regulation system of care services and to set up an inspection to ensure that social services could fulfil national care standards (Scottish Government, 2001). Accordingly, the National Care Standards was developed to improve the quality of institutional care. Further, the National Care Standards empower people to know

and claim their rights and make people and organisations that are responsible for respecting, protecting, and fulfilling rights more accountable. The Care Inspectorate and Healthcare Improvement Scotland use the National Care Standards to inspect the quality of care and particular healthcare services. The Standards also underpin the Scottish Social Services Council's Codes of Practice for Social Service Workers and for Social Service Employers. The Scottish Social Services Council (SSSC) registers and regulates social work and social care services staff and their education and training (Scottish Government, 2014). In addition, the Community Care and Health (Scotland) Act 2002 provided free personal care for older people and ensured rights for informal or unpaid carers. The act enables the Minister to implement joint working where they consider services require (Scottish Government, 2002). Further, the Mental Health (Care and Treatment) (Scotland) Act 2003 ensures that every person with a mental disorder including people living with dementia shall have the right to an adequate standard of living and access to independent advocacy (Scottish Government, 2011c). Furthermore, the Carers (Scotland) Act 2016 aims to ensure that people who provide unpaid care are supported to look after their health and wellbeing, including reducing any negative impact of their caring role on their health and wellbeing (Scottish Government, 2017b). In addition, the Public Bodies (Joint Working) (Scotland) Act 2014 provided a legal framework for integrating health and social care provision and established national outcomes for health and wellbeing (Scottish Parliament, 2014). Although, the integration has provided an opportunity to create a structured, coordinated and strategic approach to community support for people living with dementia in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2017a), however, health and social care integration has been challenging in Scotland due to fundamental institutional and cultural issues (Connolly et al., 2020).

In Bangladesh, there are no direct laws and policies related to dementia care and workforce development. However, the Bangladesh Government has formulated a new Mental Health Act in 2018, which brings hope for people living with mental illnesses including dementia for protecting their rights and developing provisions for health and rehabilitative services (Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2018b; Hossain *et al.*, 2019). Further, the Bangladesh Government has ratified and is committed to implement the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in promoting and protecting the rights of persons with disabilities (PWD) (Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2020). Therefore, Bangladesh can potentially learn from the Scottish legal context and experience of human rights-based dementia care policies to develop a national dementia care policy and legislative framework to promote the rights and dignity of people living with dementia, their families, and carers.

In Scotland, the first national strategy for dementia was developed in 2010 after the production of a Charter of Rights for people with dementia in 2009 which have been followed by many other countries (Jackson and Tolson, 2019). This strategy aimed to deliver world-class dementia care and treatment in Scotland, ensuring that people with dementia and their families are supported in the best possible way to live well with dementia (Scottish Government, 2010). Scottish Government also developed the Promoting Excellence Framework, which included updating professional qualifications, enhancing existing workforce capability and developing leadership within the dementia workforce (Scottish Government, 2011a). Moreover, Standards of Care for Dementia was developed in 2011 to help people living with dementia and their carers understand their rights, and make sure that they receive the support they need to stay well, safe and protect their own rights (Scottish Government, 2011c).

Since 2010, the Scottish government has developed and implemented three national dementia strategies, and dementia services have been transformed, with excellent contributions from staff working across health and social care, the public, third and independent sectors. Scotland can feel proud of its work on dementia, which is considered world leading (Scottish Government, 2017b). Although, consultation on a fourth strategy was planned for the start of 2020, the strategy was delayed by the COVID-19 pandemic and as an interim measure a Dementia Transition and Resilience Plan (TRP) was created in 2021. The TRP was intended to respond to the ongoing challenges around the impact of the pandemic on people living with dementia and to continue to build on and extend national action in the 2017–2020 strategy (Scottish Government, 2021b). Finally, in 2023, the Scottish government published the fourth National Dementia Strategy for ten years based on learning developed from delivering the previous strategies and committed to upholding rights, civic participation, social inclusion, support, and care for people living with dementia in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2023a).

The Scottish Government has updated the Promoting Excellence Framework in 2021, which sets out the knowledge and skills needed for new ways of working for all health and social care staff to help people living with dementia, their families and carers to maximise their rights, choices, and health and wellbeing at all stages of their own dementia journey. It works alongside other standards and frameworks, such as the NHS Knowledge and Skills Framework, the Social Services Continuous Learning Framework, and the National Occupational Standards for Health and Social Care (Scottish Government, 2021b). In addition to this, while many countries have dementia plans or strategies, Scotland is now among the first countries in the world to develop a government-sponsored, standalone research strategy for brain health and dementia in 2021. This strategy provides the framework to launch a

coordinated and collegiate approach to brain health and dementia research in Scotland. This further enhances Scotland's status as an innovative producer of important research that leads to improvements in people's lives and enables a deeper understanding of the mechanisms behind dementia and other brain diseases (The Scottish Dementia Research Consortium and Brain Health Scotland, 2021).

On the contrary, there is no single study conducted on dementia care and workforce development policy in Bangladesh (World Health Organization, 2017b), although some dementia-related studies are being published. However, there is a paucity of country-specific dementia research and data on prevalence and diagnosis sparse (Haq *et al.*, 2015; Hossain *et al.*, 2021; ICDDR-B, 2021; Palmer *et al.*, 2014; Rahman, 2017; Rahman *et al.*, 2017; Uddin *et al.*, 2016; Uddin, 2017; Uddin *et al.*, 2018; Uddin *et al.*, 2019). As Scotland is known around the world for its progressive dementia care and workforce development policies, this study has focused on transferable policy lessons from Scotland to Bangladesh.

However, there are known differences between Scotland and Bangladesh that must be appreciated and considered in determining opportunities for policy learning and transfer. Moreover, each country has different social, economic, and demographic structures, cultural aspects, political systems, and government capacities. Furthermore, Scotland and Bangladesh have different health and social care structures for dementia care and workforce development. For example, in Bangladesh, there is a lack of understanding and awareness of dementia among the general people, and an absence of dementia care supportive health and social care infrastructure. Further, there is a lack of dementia education and training programs for the health and social care practitioners working in these settings to prepare them to be skilled enough to provide necessary dementia care and support services for the people living with dementia and their families and carers (Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh, 2018; Roy *et al.*, 2020). In addition, there is a lack of comprehensive provisions in the existing national policies and legislation to provide dementia care and support services and protect the rights of people living with dementia, their families, and carers (Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2011; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2012; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2013a; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2013b; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2018b). Whereas, Scotland's dementia care policy and workforce development approaches are comparatively mature and some argue world leading. Since 2010, Scotland has successfully developed and implemented national dementia care and workforce development policies and has made significant progress in recognising dementia as a public health priority. Therefore, it can be assumed that Scotland is more experienced in its policy towards dementia care and that

Bangladeshi policy makers may learn lessons from the Scottish experiences. Thus, an 'adopt and adapt' process could be more flexible for pragmatic change in Bangladesh (Goodman and Peng, 1996), in order to take into account, the social, economic, demographic, and cultural differences between Bangladesh and Scottish contexts.

1.3 Positionality

Awareness of the potential impact of positionality is an important consideration when designing a study (Wilson, Janes and Williams, 2022). This is because the researcher's values, beliefs, experiences, motivations and cultural background may influence design choices and interpretations of findings (Bourke, 2014; Letherby, Scott and Williams, 2013). I was born and educated in Bangladesh, a South-Eastern country where social awareness about dementia is minimal, and dementia is perceived as the usual outcome of old age and not considered an illness (Amin, 2017). There is an absence of dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Bangladesh for providing services and to improve the quality of life for the people living with dementia and their family members and carers. Such situation in my home country motivated me to conduct this study on dementia care and workforce development policy learning opportunities from Scotland as the Scottish dementia care policy is portrayed as progressive. Although there are differences between the cultural values of the East and that of the West, I appreciate the Western education and understand the need to investigate and analyse the strengths and challenges of moving between the two different cultures. Also, as a social work educator and researcher, I value the rights of people living with dementia and their family members and carers and believe that dementia care policy matters to improve their quality of life. Moreover, I adopted an exploratory sequential mixed methods approach underpinned by the pragmatism worldview to determine the most suitable method within the context for this study. The mixed methods approach considers both objective and subjective knowledge, and draws upon diverse methods, different worldviews, assumptions, and different data collection and analysis techniques (Creswell and Creswell, 2018; Pluye and Hong, 2014). Underpinned by philosophical pragmatism, mixed methods study design have the potential to embrace multiple perspectives and to do so with culturally sensitivity. Importantly the action orientation of pragmatism aligned with my desire to inform policy actions to influence and shape future dementia care services in Bangladesh (Creswell and Creswell, 2018).

As I reflect upon my own positionality in relation to the present research, I feel like my academic background and professional interests inspired me to undertake this study on

dementia care and workforce development policy learning opportunities from Scotland to Bangladesh. My educational background includes Social Work and Disaster Management. I completed my bachelor's and master's degree in Social Work from the Institute of Social Welfare and Research, University of Dhaka. I have also completed Post Graduate Diploma in Disaster Management jointly organised by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and the University of Dhaka.

In addition, I have been working as a faculty member of Social Work and in a Specialized master's degree on Gerontology and Geriatric Welfare in the Institute of Social Welfare and Research, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh, since 2010. The Institute of Social Welfare and Research is the oldest and largest Social Work School and research institute in Bangladesh. As a faculty member of Gerontology and Geriatric Welfare, I felt the necessity of having higher degree and research experiences in this area. As I received a PhD scholarship fund from my employer, the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh, and I got the PhD admission offer from the Alzheimer Scotland Centre from Policy and Practice (ASCPP) at the University of the West of Scotland, UK, my interest to know more about dementia increased. In Bangladesh, the number of people living with dementia is increasing due to the ever-increasing ageing population. In addition, there is no national dementia care policy or programme in Bangladesh to provide dementia care and to improve the quality of life for people living with dementia, their carers, and family members. Therefore, as I started my doctoral journey in ASCPP at UWS, I could realise that dementia education and practice in Bangladesh cannot be changed without policy and legal framework. Moreover, health and social care practitioners need appropriate dementia education and training to provide good quality care and services for people living with dementia in Bangladesh. As an educator and researcher, such situation of my home country encouraged me to undertake this study with a hope to improve dementia education and practice to make a difference in the life of people living with dementia and their carers in Bangladesh.

For these reasons, I came to Scotland to undertake a PhD to enhance my knowledge and research capacity on long-term care for older people including dementia care, dementia education, and workforce development policy. With a teaching background in Gerontology and Geriatric Welfare Specialized master's Programme as well as having research and working experience with older people in Bangladesh, I have focused to investigate and analyse Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches to determine the utility for application within Bangladesh.

Further, absence of studies on dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Bangladesh was another motivation to do this study and it influenced me to

choose the mixed methods approach underpinned by the pragmatism worldview. Pragmatism worldview opens the door for mixed methods researchers to use multiple methods, different worldviews, assumptions, and different data collection and analysis techniques to provide the best understanding of a research problem (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Therefore, pragmatism was considered as the philosophical worldview for this mixed methods study to underpin decisions at each stage of the research process. For a more in-depth understanding of the present research process/design, I have taken two different research positions—quantitative and qualitative methods under the mixed method study design. For the qualitative approach, this study has considered to evaluate the policy success of Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches using qualitative data collection technique of Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) alongside scrutiny of policy documents. Nominal Group Technique (NGT) was chosen to collect qualitative and quantitative data to identify dementia policy aspirations and priorities of multi-sectoral stakeholders' groups in Bangladesh. Both the NGT and KIIs were initially designed to be conducted face to face and in person with participants. However, due to the internationally evolving COVID-19 restrictions on face-to-face meetings during data collection, as a researcher I had to take pragmatic actions. Therefore, I had to move my position slightly from the original plan to collect NGT and KIIs data in person and the virtual key informant interview and NGT interview approach was considered right to collect data from the key policy stakeholders in Scotland and multi-sectoral stakeholders' groups in Bangladesh (discussed in detail in section 4.4 and 4.5).

1.4 Study Aim and Objectives

Aim of the Study

The aim of the study is to investigate and analyse Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches to determine the utility for application within Bangladesh.

Objectives of the Study

01. To critically review the evidence base shaping dementia care and dementia workforce development policy and policy implementation within Scotland and Bangladesh;
02. To determine Scottish dementia policy scope, indicators of success and lessons for possible policy transfer to Bangladesh;

03. To scope with multi-sectorial stakeholders in Bangladesh their aspirations and priorities for the development of dementia care policy; and
04. To make recommendations to inform future dementia policy development in Bangladesh.

1.5 Research Questions

01. What is known about shaping and implementation of dementia care and dementia workforce development policy within Scotland and Bangladesh?
02. What is the scope and what are success indicators of Scottish dementia policy, and what are the lessons for possible policy transfer to Bangladesh?
03. What are the aspirations and priorities of multi-sectorial stakeholders in Bangladesh for the development of dementia care policy? and
04. What elements could be considered in the future dementia policy development in Bangladesh?

1.6 Study Design and Methodology

The study design involves the use of mixed methods, including an integrative literature review, documentary policy analysis framework with key informant interviews, and Nominal Group Technique (NGT) group discussion. The study chronology followed the logical order of the research objectives, with the findings of successive research activities building the evidence base to inform the next set of data collection activities. Data collection has been undertaken in Scotland, Bangladesh and online. Details of the study design, methodology, and methods are discussed in Chapter Three and Four. This study has been underpinned by Marsh and McConnell's (2010) Policy Success and Dolowitz and Marsh's (2000) Policy Transfer Framework.

1.7 Outline of the Thesis

This thesis is organized into seven chapters, including this introductory chapter, which provides a brief background to this study and an overview of the thesis as a whole. The second

chapter discusses the literature review and identifies what is known and the evidence gap. The third and fourth chapter outline the methodology and theoretical perspectives, and research methods. Chapter five reports the findings of the Documentary policy analysis framework with Key Informant Interviews in Scotland. Chapter six reports the findings arising from the Nominal Group Technique-Group Discussions with multi-sectorial stakeholders in Bangladesh. Finally, chapter seven presents the final discussion, recommendations, and conclusion of this study.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1 Overview

This chapter reports an integrative literature review critically examining the development and implementation of national dementia care strategies, including the dementia workforce education approaches in Scotland and Bangladesh. The chapter begins with the rationale for undertaking an integrative review before detailing the review methods, including questions, search strategy, and quality appraisal. Findings from the literature review and key messages for the thesis are reported.

2.2 Introduction

Despite the increased number of people living with dementia in Bangladesh, dementia policy and dementia care are at an early stage (Kabir *et al.*, 2013; Rahman *et al.*, 2017; Sultana, 2019; World Health Organization, 2017b). Further, there is a paucity of research on dementia care in Bangladesh (World Health Organization, 2017b). Research is needed to accelerate policy progress and examine opportunities for policy learning and policy transfer from other countries. Scotland is known worldwide for its progressive dementia care and workforce development policies (Scottish Government, 2017b). Therefore, this integrative review critically examined the evidence base to identify gaps in knowledge and inform the research questions and approaches underpinning this thesis.

2.3 Rationale for Integrative Literature Review

Due to the apparent insufficiency of empirical evidence related to developing and implementing national dementia care policies and dementia workforce education approaches in Scotland and Bangladesh, this study used an integrative literature review method. Integrative literature review is the most comprehensive form of review method as it allows the researcher to review a diverse range of studies while maintaining a strict and focused research objective. An integrative literature review offers a comprehensive approach to reviewing the literature to inform practice and policy (Whittemore and Knaf, 2005). Through the inclusion of a diverse range of studies and theoretical perspectives, integrative reviews can generate a state-of-the-art understanding of what is known and not known about the phenomenon of interest (Souza, Silva and Carvalho, 2010). Integrative literature reviews discern the overarching theoretical and empirical directions and general assertions in the existing

literature (Spenceley and Williams, 2006). Moreover, this distinctive and intuitive review approach integrates the diverse forms of research evidence (qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods) with more conceptual elements (Torraco, 2016).

Although these are compelling arguments for selecting an integrative review policy-focused thesis, it is important to recognise and manage the potential known threats to rigour, particularly those associated with reviewer bias (Beck, 1999; O'Mathúna, 2000). Whitemore and Knafl's (2005) five-stage approach addresses rigour concerns by decreasing risks of reviewer bias. Furthermore, their staged and protocol-based approach mitigates inaccuracy and makes linkages between diverse sources of evidence visible and available for critical scrutiny (Jones-Devitt, Austen and Parkin, 2017).

The review protocol defines the review questions, search keywords, and details the search technique, criteria for including and excluding evidence, and standardised approaches to quality appraisal (Whitemore and Knafl, 2005). This was undertaken systematically following the five stages for a rigorous review set out by Whitemore and Knafl (2005), namely:

- problem identification,
- literature search,
- data evaluation,
- data analysis, and
- presentation.

2.4 Problem Identification

Whitemore and Knafl (2005) recommended that the review purpose and question should be clearly defined in the problem identification stage. This was completed and the review purpose and question are outlined below.

2.4.1 Review Purpose and Question

The purpose of this integrative literature review was to critically analyse the development and implementation of national dementia care strategies, including the dementia workforce education approaches in Scotland and Bangladesh.

Two review questions were considered: -

-what is known from research about dementia care and related workforce development policy and its implementation in Bangladesh?

-what is known from research about dementia care and related workforce development and related policy and it's implementation within Scotland?

The Population or Problem, Interest, and Context (PICo) approach was selected to frame this review and determine the inclusion and exclusion criteria, as detailed later and summarised in Table 2.2 (Murdoch University, 2020). PICo is a modified form of the PICO (Patient/Population, Intervention, Comparison/Control, and Outcome) framework (Richardson *et al.*, 1995). This integrative literature review aims to critically review the development and implementation of national dementia care strategies, including the dementia workforce education approaches in Scotland and Bangladesh. The research focus is well-aligned to the use of the PICo framework because it considers both the setting or distinct characteristics and a range of study designs (Murdoch University, 2020). Following the PICo framework, Figure 2.1 provides an overview of the Population (P), Phenomenon of Interest (I), and Context (Co) related to this review.

P= (Population or Problem = What is known about dementia care policy and related workforce development approaches)

I= (Interest = implementation in)

Co= (Context = Scotland and Bangladesh?)

Figure 2. 1: Overview of the Review Question Using the PICo Structure

2.5 Literature Search

2.5.1 Database Search

Fourteen databases were searched to identify relevant records for this review (see Appendix 2.1). Additionally, the reference list of each record was manually examined to find any relevant documents related to the review purpose.

2.5.2 Search Terms

Each database search was performed using the following Boolean search string and relevant search terms:

Table 2. 1: Keywords Groups and Search Terms

Keyword Groups	Search Terms
Dementia	Dementia OR Alzheimer OR "Alzheimer's disease"
AND	
Dementia care	"Care home" OR "care homes" OR "care facility" OR "care settings" OR "residential home" OR "residential care" OR "nursing home" OR "nursing homes" OR "nursing care" OR "long term care" OR "home care" OR "social care" OR "community care"
AND	
Workforce development	"Workforce development" OR "workforce education" OR "workforce planning" OR "workforce training" OR "professional training" OR "nursing training"
AND	
Policies	Policy OR guidelines OR plan OR "action plan" OR directions OR program OR legislations OR act OR law OR regulation OR circular OR "constitutional directions"
AND	
Approaches	Approaches OR strategies OR framework OR model OR intervention OR "quality improvement" OR "service planning" OR "human resource planning" OR "service reform" OR "strategic planning"
AND	
Development and Implementation	Development OR Implementation
AND	
Research	Research OR Study OR Studies OR Survey OR Investigation

2.5.3 Study Selection Reporting and Selection Criteria

To promote rigour, the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) Flow Diagram presents the searching and sourcing process. This process includes the identification, screening of title and abstract, full-text review and eligibility, and inclusion and exclusion (Moher et al., 2009). Moher et al. (2010) argue that using a PRISMA statement is useful for integrative reviews to promote transparency in the selection of items to be included or excluded in the review. For the purpose of this integrative review, inclusion criteria involve studies that report on the development and implementation of dementia care policies and related workforce development approaches published in the context of Scotland and Bangladesh. On the other hand, studies were excluded due to reporting on other health conditions for older people and not meeting the inclusion criteria for time and language. The inclusion and exclusion criteria is summarised in Table 2.2.

Table 2. 2: literature Review Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria Framed Using the PICO Structure

PICO Structure	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Population or Problem (What is the Problem, condition or disease you are interested in?)	Policies and approaches related to dementia care, and workforce development for people living with dementia, their carers, community people, practitioners, health and social care professionals.	Policies and approaches related to other health conditions for older people and their carers, community people, practitioners, health, and social care professionals.
Interest (Interest relates to a defined event, activity, experience, or process)	Development and implementation of health and social care policies and workforce development approaches for people with dementia and their families.	Development and implementation of care policies and workforce development approaches related to other health conditions for older people.
Context (Context is the setting or distinct characteristics)	Scotland and Bangladesh.	Except Scotland and Bangladesh.

Each record obtained through the integrative search was examined against the following inclusion and exclusion criteria:

- a. Studies published from 2010 to 2020 in English and Bengali;
- b. Studies published in scholarly journals, systematic reviews, and thesis;
- c. Studies using mixed-methods, qualitative, and quantitative research design; and
- d. Studies that report on the development and implementation of dementia care policies and related workforce development approaches in Scotland and Bangladesh.

2.5.4 Search Results

Nineteen journal papers and six PhD theses met the review criteria for inclusion, 1 quantitative study, twelve qualitative studies, ten mixed-method studies and two systematic reviews. The initial database search identified 4,390 records, including articles and PhD theses. Firstly, the topics of the records were examined, and duplicates were removed (n=632) using EndNote duplicate screening and hand search processes. The remaining records (n=3,758) were screened for relevance by title and abstract, and non-relevant records (n=3,659) were removed. Full texts (n =99) were examined for eligibility following the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and 18 studies were included in the database search. Manual searching of reference lists resulted in 07 papers relevant to the review. Using the PRISMA screening process, 25 studies were included for retrieval in the literature review. Three of these studies were found to be of low quality based on the process of quality grading and subsequently excluded. This decision making process is discussed later in section 2.6. Therefore, twenty-two studies were included in the final synthesis. In every stage of PRISMA screening process, two reviewers assessed records: the researcher and one supervisory team member. Next, Figure 2.2 outlines the search results and study selection process in line with the PRISMA guidelines (Moher et al., 2009).

Figure 2.2: Outlines of the study section process in line with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines

Figure 2. 2: Outlines of the Study Selection Process in Line with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) Guidelines

2.6 Data Evaluation

The data evaluation stage of integrative literature review focuses on the rigour, methodological quality, informative value and representation of the studies (Whittemore and Knafli, 2005). The quality of retrieved studies was assessed by the researcher and one supervisory team member using selected critical appraisal tools appropriate for the study design.

For qualitative studies and systematic reviews, Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) critical appraisal tools were chosen. The JBI has developed theories, methodologies and rigorous processes for the critical appraisal and synthesis of diverse forms of evidence to aid in clinical decision-making in health care (JBI, 2017). The JBI tools themselves have been peer reviewed, and their internal validity asserted by consensus (Buccheri and Sharifi, 2017). Further, JBI tools provide increased depth to critique and analysis and focus on congruity, that appears to be the most coherent (Hannes, Lockwood and Pearson, 2010; JBI, 2017). The CASP tools was discounted for the present review as it does not give a numerical score (Cameron *et al.*, 2011) and it appears to be less sensitive to aspects of validity than the JBI tools (Hannes, Lockwood and Pearson, 2010). The JBI tools have 6 to 11 questions with the response alternatives yes, no, unclear or not applicable depending on study design. The JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist for Qualitative Research and Systematic Reviews include 10 and 11 questions, respectively (JBI, 2020a; JBI, 2020b; JBI, 2021). The qualitative studies and systematic reviews were assessed using related JBI questions and were assigned 1 for one satisfactory 'yes' answer and 0 for a 'no' or 'unclear' answer. The final score was determined after combining the values assigned for each question. Examples of the quality appraisal process using JBI critical appraisal tools are presented in Appendix 2.2. Of the fourteen studies evaluated using the JBI critical appraisal tools, eight of them were rated between eight to ten (Dawson *et al.*, 2015; Górska, 2018; Kelly, 2010; Lee, 2011; Lillo-Crespo *et al.*, 2018; Mullan, 2012; Surr and Gates, 2017; Watson, 2015). Five of them were rated between six to seven (Astell *et al.*, 2014; Caine, 2014; Fox *et al.*, 2020; Górska *et al.*, 2013; Surr *et al.*, 2019), and the remaining one was rated between four to five (Brown, Standen and Khilji, 2013) (see Table 2.3).

Table 2. 3: Quality Assessment with JBI Critical Appraisal Tools for Qualitative Research and Systematic Reviews and Obtained Score

Paper Authors	Quality Appraisal Tool Used	Quality Checklist Score	Grade
Dawson et al., 2015	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Systematic Reviews and Research Syntheses	10 out of 11	High
Górska, 2018	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Qualitative Research	08 out of 10	High
Kelly, 2010		08 out of 10	High
Lee, 2011		09 out of 10	High
Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018		10 out of 10	High
Mullay, 2012		09 out of 10	High
Surr and Gates, 2017	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Systematic Reviews and Research Syntheses	09 out of 11	High
Watson, 2015	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Qualitative Research	08 out of 10	High
Astell et al., 2014		06 out of 10	Moderate
Caine, 2014		07 out of 10	Moderate
Fox et al., 2020		07 out of 10	Moderate
Górska et al., 2013		07 out of 10	Moderate
Surr et al., 2019		06 out of 10	Moderate
Brown, Standen and Khilji, 2013		05 out of 10	Low

Mixed methods and quantitative studies were evaluated using Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) (Pluye *et al.*, 2011). The MMAT is a unique appraisal tool that can assess the methodological quality of quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods elements of mixed methods studies (Pluye, 2013). The MMAT presents a quality scoring grade based on different indicators relevant to the study design. The MMAT (version 2011) consists of 2 scanning questions and 19 indicators with the response alternatives yes, no, or 'cannot tell' corresponding to five methodological domains. These include randomized controlled trials, quantitative, qualitative, mixed methods, and non-randomized studies. However, the MMAT cannot appraise the methodological quality of non-empirical studies and economic and diagnostic accuracy studies (Hong *et al.*, 2018). The mixed methods and quantitative study were assessed using related MMAT questions and were assigned 1 for one satisfactory 'yes' answer and 0 for a 'no' or 'cannot tell' answer. Studies were rated between 1 and 4 based on methodological quality, sample, findings validation and implementation. Examples of the

quality appraisal process using Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool are presented in Appendix 2.3. Of the eleven studies assessed using the MMAT, four studies achieved a score of 4 (highest quality) (Johnson, 2014; Lin, 2010; Surr *et al.*, 2020; Tolson *et al.*, 2016), five moderate studies scored 3 (Banks *et al.*, 2014; Cooper *et al.*, 2017; Kelly and Innes, 2016; Levin *et al.*, 2018; Waugh *et al.*, 2011) and two of the weakest studies scored 2 (Finucane *et al.*, 2013; Hockley *et al.*, 2010) (see Table 2.4).

Table 2. 4: Quality Assessment with Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) for Mixed Methods Research and Quantitative Research and Obtained Score

Paper Authors	Quality Appraisal Tool Used	Quality Checklist Score	Grade
Johnson, 2014	Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) for Mixed Methods Research	04 out of 04	High
Lin, 2010		04 out of 04	High
Surr <i>et al.</i> , 2020		04 out of 04	High
Tolson <i>et al.</i> , 2016		04 out of 04	High
Banks <i>et al.</i> , 2014	Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) for Quantitative Research	03 out of 04	Moderate
Cooper <i>et al.</i> , 2017		03 out of 04	Moderate
Kelly and Innes, 2016		03 out of 04	Moderate
Levin <i>et al.</i> , 2018		03 out of 04	Moderate
Waugh <i>et al.</i> , 2011		03 out of 04	Moderate
Finucane <i>et al.</i> , 2013		02 out of 04	Low
Hockley <i>et al.</i> , 2010	02 out of 04	Low	

It is recognised that the appraisal tools used within this review each used different numeric scoring systems. To generate a meaningful and succinct overview of the strength of the underpinning evidence, a unifying approach was sought. To this end the internationally accepted Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) approach was identified as a helpful approach familiar to stakeholders within the UK and Bangladesh (Guyatt *et al.*, 2008; JBI, 2016).

The GRADE approach provides an explicit, thorough, transparent, and effective system of rating the evidence quality and recommendations strength. The GRADE approach evaluates the quality of evidence on one of four levels to achieve transparency and clarity. These are high, moderate, low, and very low (Guyatt et al., 2008). The GRADE working group has developed this approach to offer a systematic way for assessing the quality of clinical evidence and rating the strength of recommendations in systematic reviews, healthcare technology assessments, and clinical practice guidelines. The GRADE approach can be applied more broadly (JBI, 2014). Importantly for this thesis, the GRADE approach focuses on the confidence of synthesized results including issues related to publication bias, and inconsistency of results (JBI, 2014; JBI, 2016; Schünemann *et al.*, 2013). The JBI recommends the four key factors to assign a grade of recommendation. These include the parity between expectable and non-expectable outcomes, evidence quality, utility and predilection, and costs (JBI, 2013; JBI, 2014). Further, this thesis is concerned with the transferability of dementia care policy and workforce development approaches that determine the quality of services and practices that shape dementia care on a national level. Therefore, the GRADE was considered to assess evidence of policy and practice impact from very low to high.

Of the twenty-five studies, twelve were high quality. Ten studies were moderate quality and the remaining three were low quality (see Table 2.3 and 2.4). In relation to the three low quality studies (Brown, Standen and Khilji, 2013; Finucane *et al.*, 2013; Hockley *et al.*, 2010), what they reported was challenging to include. For example, Hockley et al. (2010) and Finucane et al. (2013) evaluated the Liverpool Care Pathway (LCP), which is now not considered to be the best practice in Palliative care in the UK and excluded following an Independent Review in 2013 (Knights, Wood and Barclay, 2013). Moreover, it is a complex argument and not the focus of this present review. Therefore, the decision was made to exclude these two papers based on methodological quality and the controversy surrounding the use of the LCP. Whereas Brown, Standen and Khilji's (2013) study about dementia advocacy was excluded because of low appraisal score and discussing single theme which could not be synthesised like other studies. Therefore, three low-quality studies were not included in the final synthesis. Finally, twenty-two high and moderate quality studies were included in this review to answer review questions and make future research and policy recommendations.

2.7 Data Analysis

The integrative review data analysis stage aims to ensure a complete and objective interpretation of primary documents and a synthesis of the evidence (Whittemore and Knafl, 2005). Therefore, a comprehensive analytic approach was identified for carrying out the review. The integrative review data analysis approach is compatible with various data from diverse sources and methods. This approach consists of data reduction, presentation, contrast and conclusion (Whittemore and Knafl, 2005).

2.7.1 Data Extraction

An extraction table was developed to capture the relevant data from the finally selected and included studies. The extraction table (see Appendix 2.4) was divided into columns where each study's essential information including study details, study design and methods, primary aim(s) and question(s), themes related to review purpose, context, data collection techniques and analysis methods, key findings, strength and weaknesses, and quality score was entered.

2.8 Presentation of Findings

2.8.1 Study Characteristics

Each study was read to determine its key features. Of the twenty-two included studies, two of them were systematic reviews (Dawson *et al.*, 2015; Surr and Gates, 2017). Twenty were empirical research including eleven qualitative studies (Astell *et al.*, 2014; Caine, 2014; Fox *et al.*, 2020; Górska *et al.*, 2013; Górska, 2018; Kelly, 2010; Lee, 2011; Lillo-Crespo *et al.*, 2018; Mullay, 2012; Surr *et al.*, 2019; Watson, 2015). Eight were mixed-method studies (Banks *et al.*, 2014; Johnson, 2014; Kelly and Innes, 2016; Levin *et al.*, 2018; Lin, 2010; Surr *et al.*, 2020; Tolson *et al.*, 2016; Waugh *et al.*, 2011), and one quantitative investigation (Cooper *et al.*, 2017).

Although this review's primary aim was to critically analyse what is known about workforce development and dementia care policies in Scotland and Bangladesh, the reviewer identified no studies for the context of Bangladesh. The majority of the studies (12) were undertaken solely in Scotland, whereas 10 of the Scottish studies involved international collaborations with the rest of the UK and the other eleven countries. These include the Republic of Ireland, South

Korea, Taiwan, the USA, Canada, Portugal, Finland, Sweden, Spain, Slovenia, and the Czech Republic.

2.8.2 Findings

The review findings are presented under five major themes:

1. Dementia as a public health concern
2. Implementation of the principles of public health policy
3. Provision of post-diagnostic support
4. Development of service and care infrastructure
5. Preparation and development of the dementia workforce

Of the twenty-two reviewed studies, thirteen studies were found to discuss only one theme, whereas nine studies were found to discuss more than one of these themes. One study was found to discuss all five identified themes related to workforce development and dementia care policies in Scotland. If a study referred to more than one themes, it was listed under all the relevant themes. The evidence base is critically reviewed within each themed section, as are the implications for policy and practice.

2.8.2.1 Dementia as a Public Health Concern

Dementia as a public health concern is identified in seven out of the twenty-two studies. Authors and methodological quality are given below in Table 2.5.

Table 2. 5: Authors and Methodological Quality of the Reviewed Studies Related to Dementia as a Public Health Concern

Paper Authors	Quality Appraisal Tool Used	Quality Checklist Score	Grade
Dawson et al., 2015	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Systematic Reviews and Research Syntheses	10 out of 11	High
Górska, 2018	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Qualitative Research	08 out of 10	High
Lee, 2011		09 out of 10	High
Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018		10 out of 10	High
Mullay, 2012		09 out of 10	High
Tolson et al., 2016	Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) for Mixed Methods Research	04 out of 04	High
Górska et al., 2013	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Qualitative Research	07 out of 10	Moderate

This section of the chapter considers what is known and not known about dementia as a public health concern. This major theme is presented under the three sub-themes: awareness of service needs and early diagnosis ensure access to dementia care, the importance of early and timely diagnosis to improve the quality of life, and cultural and public health policy influences on awareness and attitudes of dementia diagnosis (see Figure 2.3).

Figure 2. 3: Sub-Themes Related to Dementia as a Public Health Concern

Awareness of Service Needs and Early Diagnosis Ensure Access to Dementia Care

In Scotland, a study by Górska et al. (2013) found that a greater awareness of people living with dementia and their families about service-related needs can identify gaps in service provision. Moreover, service-related awareness supported care sustainability and increased access to non-pharmacological services to develop social networks (Górska et al., 2013). Further, Górska (2018) explored the importance of integrated care delivery through well-coordinated and comprehensive diagnosis and post-diagnostic support services to fulfil the service needs of people living with dementia and their unpaid family carers within the Scottish context.

The study (Górska et al., 2013) suggests that primary health care practitioners should emphasise awareness and early recognition of risk factors for developing dementia. In addition, access to dementia-specific nurses and consultants can support early diagnosis (Górska et al., 2013). However, the study identified numerous obstacles to obtaining early diagnosis services. These include disregarding the early health risk factors of a person by the primary health care practitioners, a lack of coordination in services provided by the primary health care practitioners and expert dementia nurses and consultants, the inappropriate use of diagnostic tools, lengthy diagnosis procedures, and difficulties in recognising the importance of diagnoses (Górska et al., 2013). The study claimed that due to lengthy diagnosis procedure, people living with dementia missed the opportunities to retain good health and well-being and reduce the condition's progression. However, the findings of this study emphasise a comprehensive assessment package to deliver timely diagnosis services for people living with dementia (Górska et al., 2013).

The Importance of Early and Timely Diagnosis to Improve the Quality of Life

Recent studies have highlighted the importance of early and timely diagnosis to improve the quality of life for people living with dementia and their carers (Dawson et al., 2015; Górska et al., 2013; Lee, 2011; Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018; Tolson et al., 2016). A study by Lillo-Crespo et al. (2018) conducted in Scotland and six European countries reported that the absence of proper detection and lack of early diagnoses reduce access to proper support strategies for people with dementia to live longer and healthier lives. The study found that lack of coordination between dementia care providers and the people living with advanced dementia and family carers had a negative impact on their care experiences and care quality.

Furthermore, fragmentation of care reduced opportunities to draw upon the expertise of family carers and undermined partnership approaches. Family carers considered that this impacted on care provider's ability to plan and deliver continuity of care to the person tailored to their preferences and home situation (Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018). In another study, Lee (2011) found that early diagnosis, positive family relationships, and adequate community services helped Scottish informal and family carers provide care for people living with dementia. Family networks and accessibility of community care reduces family perception of care burden and delays consideration of moving an older relative to a residential care facility (Lee, 2011).

Cultural and Public Health Policy Influences on Awareness and Attitudes of Dementia Diagnosis

Dementia is considered by some researchers and policy analysts an essential parameter for interpreting and analysing a country's policy related to health, care, and culture (Lee, 2011). Lee (2011) conducted a comparative qualitative study between two groups of family carers living in Scotland and South Korea to understand the Scottish and Korean family carers' perceptions regarding dementia diagnosis and dementia care in the family, community, and residential settings. The study found that dementia diagnosis is intently connected to health and social care policy and access to dementia care. Lee (2011) argues that health and social care policy is more important than culture in influencing carers' awareness and viewpoint regarding dementia diagnosis. However, Lee's claim can be disputed. For example, Mullay (2012) argues that socio-cultural diversity often impacted people with dementia in a different way than people with no cognitive impairment. Mullay (2012) conducted a qualitative study in Scotland to determine the relationships between cultural aspects and residential dementia care. The study emphasised that dementia is a condition that affects people living with dementia differently and needs to be considered the individual experiences and the culture. The study also focused on how service providers consider this in constituting "person-centred" care processes which is the bedrock of the national dementia strategy (Mullay, 2012). In addition, a systematic review by Dawson et al. (2015) suggests that different groups have varied experiences with diagnosis and emphasises the importance of acknowledging and addressing the range of experience and needs. Therefore, the socio-cultural aspects and public health policy have influenced awareness and attitudes toward dementia diagnosis.

In summary, from the reviewed studies, early and timely diagnosis is a key driver for public health policy to ensure access to better health care and treatment for people living with

dementia, their family, and carers (Dawson et al., 2015; Górska et al., 2013; Lee, 2011; Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018; Tolson et al., 2016). However, there are several challenges, including lack of coordination and inappropriate use of assessment tools in diagnosis services (Górska et al., 2013; Górska, 2018). The implementation of the principles of public health policy related to dementia care and workforce development approaches is discussed next.

2.8.2.2 Implementation of the Principles of Public Health Policy

The importance of the underpinning principles of public health policy related to dementia care and workforce development is identified in six out of the twenty-two studies. Authors and methodological quality are given below in Table 2.6.

Table 2. 6: Authors and Methodological Quality of the Reviewed Studies Related to the Implementation of Principles of Public Health Policy

Paper Authors	Quality Appraisal Tool Used	Quality Checklist Score	Grade
Dawson et al., 2015	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Systematic Reviews and Research Syntheses	10 out of 11	High
Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Qualitative Research	10 out of 10	High
Watson, 2015		08 out of 10	High
Tolson et al., 2016	Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) for Mixed Methods Research	04 out of 04	High
Fox et al., 2020	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Qualitative Research	07 out of 10	Moderate
Cooper et al., 2017	Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) for Quantitative Research	03 out of 04	Moderate

The evidence regarding the implementation of the principles of public health policy is discussed next. This major theme is presented under the following four sub-themes: dementia-specific palliative approach to care, challenges and positive care experiences in advanced dementia palliative care, community-based service-delivery model for dementia palliative care, and relationship-centred palliative dementia care in care homes (see Figure 2.4).

Figure 2. 4: Sub-Themes Related to Implementation of the Principles of Public Health Policy

Dementia-Specific Palliative Approach to Care

In the advanced stage of dementia, people have complex needs and are highly dependent but are not necessarily requiring end of their life care (Tolson et al., 2016). Dementia-specific palliative approaches to care are designed to support people with advanced dementia achieve the best possible living for years. Evidence suggests that policy innovations aligned with integrated palliative care practice models and the dementia workforce education improve both the quality of service provision and the experience of advanced dementia care (Tolson et al., 2016). The study by Tolson et al. (2016) found that palliative care practice models should focus on a coordinated effort and interactions with individuals, groups, and organisations. The study also underscored the significance of palliative care education for practitioners caring for people living with advanced dementia and long-term conditions (Tolson et al., 2016). Similarly, a recent systematic review proposes a multi-dimensional strategy for addressing multifaceted dementia-related needs, including co-morbidities and palliative care (Dawson et al., 2015). Furthermore, Fox et al. (2020) mentioned that numerous countries deliver dementia palliative care, although the effectiveness differs significantly. However, little is documented about what care practitioners deem the critical elements of a dementia palliative care model (Fox et al., 2020).

Challenges and Positive Care Experiences in Advanced Dementia Palliative Care

A study by Tolson et al. (2016) conducted in Scotland and six European countries examined the provision of integrated advanced dementia care. The study reviewed the different elements of advanced dementia care and recognised that what was deemed good reflected the prudent health care model across the different participating countries. The study findings revealed that all seven European countries have some national action plans for general palliative care. It is

evident that Finland and Scotland have some of the most well-established and integrated national plans to provide dementia related palliative care. The study also identified challenges related to palliative care, including segmentation of care and limited options for supporting people living with advanced dementia and their carers (Tolson et al., 2016). However, early diagnosis, strong collaboration between care providers, a proper plan, education, and support for family carers ensure the best possible life for people living with advanced dementia (Palliare), which lead to access to effective palliative care at the end of life (Tolson et al., 2016). Moreover, advanced dementia education for health and social care practitioners and family carers is essential for better advanced dementia care and palliative care experiences (Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018; Tolson et al., 2016).

Community-Based Service-Delivery Model for Dementia Palliative Care

Palliative care approaches can improve the outcomes for people living with dementia and their carers especially when a person living with dementia's illness progresses to advanced dementia (Fox et al., 2020). A qualitative study by Fox et al (2020) conducted in the Republic of Ireland, England, Wales, Scotland, and Northern Ireland has developed a community-based service-delivery model for palliative dementia care. The study identified potential core components for developing a community-based service-delivery model. These include accessible care, timely care, comprehensive care, integrated care, person-centred care, and care for the carer (Fox et al., 2020).

Relationship-Centred Palliative Dementia Care in Care Homes

Residential care workers are involved in the provision of palliative and end-of-life care to improve the personhood and well-being of care home residents with advanced dementia (Cooper et al., 2017). However, there is a greater need for attention to the emotional labour of care in palliative dementia care because of the increased interconnectedness between the emotions of the staff and the people living with dementia and their families (Watson, 2015). A qualitative study by Watson (2015) investigated the theoretical basis of relationship-centred palliative dementia care in a specialist dementia care home without nursing. The study's purpose was to gain a better insight from the perspective of people living with dementia and the social care practitioners. However, this was rooted in the local perspective but examined how this can influence comprehensive health and social care in Scotland. The study findings provide new insight into the care providers and care receivers relationship to inform practice

and national policy and improve health and social care provisions in the residential care for people living with advanced dementia (Watson, 2015). The study explored three important factors which influence the caring relationship. These are direct hands-on bodily care, recognising and supporting selfhood, and witnessing and responding to suffering. These factors were investigated and revealed how people living with advanced dementia continue to comprehend and interact with the environment until death. However, it is unclear from Watson's study how the wider multi-professional healthcare team were contributing, and this oversight is an omission (Watson, 2015).

Overall, from the reviewed studies, there is promising evidence that the community-based service-delivery model, and relationship-centred palliative dementia care approach ensure the access to better advanced dementia care and palliative care experiences (Fox *et al.*, 2020; Watson, 2015). However, there is a lack of coordination and limited options for supporting people living with advanced dementia to implement the palliative care approach (Lillo-Crespo *et al.*, 2018; Tolson *et al.*, 2016). The provision of post-diagnostic support is discussed next.

2.8.2.3 Provision of Post-Diagnostic Support

Six out of the twenty-two studies identified the provision of post-diagnostic support. Authors and methodological quality are given below in Table 2.7.

Table 2. 7: Authors and Methodological Quality of the Reviewed Studies Related to the Post-Diagnostic Support

Paper Authors	Quality Appraisal Tool Used	Quality Checklist Score	Grade
Dawson <i>et al.</i> , 2015	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Systematic Reviews and Research Syntheses	10 out of 11	High
Górska, 2018	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Qualitative Research	08 out of 10	High
Astell <i>et al.</i> , 2014		06 out of 10	Moderate
Górska <i>et al.</i> , 2013		07 out of 10	Moderate
Kelly and Innes, 2016	Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) for Mixed Methods Research	03 out of 04	Moderate
Levin <i>et al.</i> , 2018		03 out of 04	Moderate

The evidence concerning the provision of post-diagnostic support is discussed next. This major theme is presented under the following four sub-themes: satisfaction and unmet needs related to post-diagnostic support, the needs and benefits of post-diagnostic support service, the experiences of learning technology for people diagnosed with dementia, and effectiveness of post-diagnostic support services (see Figure 2.5).

Figure 2. 5: Sub-Themes Related to the Provision of Post-Diagnostic Support

Satisfaction and Unmet Needs Related to Post-Diagnostic Support

Górska et al. (2013) found that people living with dementia and their unpaid family carers are usually satisfied with the post-diagnostic support services following a diagnosis of dementia, particularly positive, respectful, and caring relationships with practitioners working throughout the service. However, the study identified several gaps in post-diagnostic support to improve self-identity and community connections. These include a lack of coordination in service delivery, discontinuity of health care practitioners, and limited non-pharmacological interventions (Górska et al., 2013). Further, Levin et al. (2018) conducted a study on the post-diagnostic support (PDS) model in Scotland to explore the best way to provide post-diagnostic support for people newly diagnosed with dementia. This study explored the most important elements of post-diagnostic support service delivery. These include understanding and perceptions of service guidelines and recording process, service development and accessibility, service variability in different sectors, decision-making, model selection and determinants of person-centred outcomes, and challenges and opportunities in service delivery and management (Levin *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, the study claimed that Link Workers in the Five Pillar Model support newly diagnosed people living with dementia, their family, and carers (Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b). The Five Pillars Model, integral to Scotland's post-diagnostic approach offers strategies, connections, and resources to plan to live as well as possible with dementia and to prepare for the future (Levin *et al.*, 2018; Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b). The study also

suggests that a supporting guidance framework should include the job description of Link Workers and have a person-centred ethos based on Alzheimer's Scotland's post-diagnostic support model (Levin *et al.*, 2018).

The Needs and Benefits of Post-Diagnostic Support Service

In terms of support services, Kelly and Innes (2016) conducted a comparative study to ascertain the benefits of post-diagnostic support service over time for people living with dementia and their family members in Scotland regarding government policy commitment to addressing community service needs. The study found that post-diagnostic support services can address various local service delivery gaps, including poor community networks and low-level clinical support, by providing continuous and comprehensive support. These supports include information, counselling and guidelines, accessibility to services and participation in community activities (Kelly and Innes, 2016). Furthermore, Kelly and Innes's (2016) findings revealed that the post-diagnostic support service increases independence, motivation, and self-confidence in people recently diagnosed with dementia and their family carers. In addition, a systematic review conducted by Dawson *et al.* (2015) revealed the significance of providing post-diagnostic support for people with dementia and their formal and informal carers (Dawson *et al.*, 2015). However, the study found limited success in facilitating and promoting advanced care planning due to the reluctance of people living with dementia and their family carers (Kelly and Innes, 2016).

The Experiences of Learning Technology for People Diagnosed with Dementia

The use of technology is a newly developing area in dementia care to support people living with dementia (Dawson *et al.*, 2015). Dawson *et al.* (2015) conducted a systematic review and found that non-pharmacological interventions are more cost-effective and useful than technological interventions to enable people diagnosed with dementia to stay in the community (Dawson *et al.*, 2015). However, Astell *et al.* (2014) claimed that technology learning improves the quality of life of people diagnosed with dementia. Moreover, Astell *et al.* (2014) found that technology can assist people living with dementia in participating in meaningful community activities and maintaining a social life to fulfil their needs for independence, happiness, and enjoyment. However, the study found that only a few technological devices were explicitly designed to meet the needs of people living with dementia (Astell *et al.*, 2014). The study's (Astell *et al.*, 2014) findings suggest that integrating recent and upcoming digital technology with an understanding of the cognitive profiles and needs can enable people to maintain a

quality life with dementia. Furthermore, the study revealed that the experience of learning technology added to a holistic perspective on life (Astell et al., 2014).

Effectiveness of Post-Diagnostic Support Services

The study by Górska, (2018) supports the Scottish National Dementia Strategies' commitment to delivering integrated dementia care through coordinated and comprehensive post-diagnostic support. The study also found that integrated dementia care ensures people living with dementia stay in the community for longer (Górska, 2018). Further, a systematic review by Dawson et al. (2015) on the effectiveness of post-diagnostic support services in Scotland suggests that locally based, multi-component interventions are helpful for family members and carers to assist people with dementia staying at home. Multi-component interventions include education, cognitive training, cognitive stimulation, and cognitive rehabilitation (Dawson et al., 2015). The systematic review also suggests that many interventions have only local and limited positive influences. Nonetheless, compelling evidence suggests that multi-component interventions are more likely to succeed (Dawson et al., 2015).

From reviewing studies, there is evidence that information, advice, emotional support, access to services, multi-component and non-pharmacological interventions, learning technology, community networks and participation in social activities can support people living with dementia to stay in communities for longer and support independence (Astell *et al.*, 2014; Dawson *et al.*, 2015; Górska, 2018; Kelly and Innes, 2016). However, there are several unmet needs, including discontinuation of support workers and limited non-pharmacological services (Dawson et al., 2015; Górska et al., 2013). Development of service and care infrastructure for dementia care and the dementia workforce is discussed next.

2.8.2.4 Development of Service and Care Infrastructure

Development of service and care infrastructure is identified in twelve out of the twenty-two studies. Authors and methodological quality are given below in Table 2.8.

Table 2. 8: Authors and Methodological Quality of the Reviewed Studies Related to the Development of Service and Care Infrastructure

Paper Authors	Quality Appraisal Tool Used	Quality Checklist Score	Grade
Dawson et al., 2015	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Systematic Reviews and Research Syntheses	10 out of 11	High
Górska, 2018	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Qualitative Research	08 out of 10	High
Kelly, 2010		08 out of 10	High
Lee, 2011		09 out of 10	High
Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018		10 out of 10	High
Johnson, 2014	Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) for Mixed Methods Research	04 out of 04	High
Lin, 2010		04 out of 04	High
Tolson et al., 2016		04 out of 04	High
Astell et al., 2014	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Qualitative Research	06 out of 10	Moderate
Caine, 2014		07 out of 10	Moderate
Górska et al., 2013		07 out of 10	Moderate
Cooper et al., 2017	Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) for Quantitative Research	03 out of 04	Moderate

The evidence related to service and care infrastructure development is discussed next. This major theme is discussed under the following five sub-themes: health and social care integration, participation of people living with dementia and their carers in research and service design, the role of the dementia workforce and person-centred care, family and community-based care, and non-pharmacological interventions (see Figure 2.6).

Figure 2. 6: Sub-Themes Related to the Development of Service and Care Infrastructure

Health and Social Care Integration

Health and social care integration is one of Scotland's significant reforms in programmes to provide sufficient health and social care support throughout their care journey (Tolson et al., 2016). Górska et al. (2013) and Górska (2018) also highlighted integrated and well-coordinated health and social care support is required for providing diagnostic and post-diagnostic services and ensuring high-quality care for people living with dementia and their family carers (Górska et al., 2013; Górska, 2018). However, Lillo-Crespo et al. (2018) explored several health and social care integration challenges. These include a lack of collaboration between service sectors and a lack of effective dementia care plans. These challenges directly influence the quality and continuity of health and social care support for the people living with dementia and family care providers.

Participation of People Living with Dementia and their Carers in Research and Service Design

The literature considers people living with dementia and their family carer's participation in research and health and social care service design (Astell et al., 2014; Caine, 2014; Dawson et al., 2015). Caine (2014) examined the barriers and facilitators of participation of people living with dementia and their carers in research to investigate the significance of music in improving the quality of life. This study revealed that music increased the well-being of the people living with dementia and their carers. The study found that a person-centred approach to service receivers' involvement in the study provides opportunities for them to contribute to health and social care planning and distribution (Caine, 2014). However, the participation of people living with dementia and their carers in the research process needs detailed planning and rigorous thinking (Caine, 2014). On the other hand, Astell et al. (2014) presented the experiences of a person living with dementia as a co-researcher on learning technology. This study examined the influence of learning and using technology on the quality of life for people living with dementia and the feasibility of translating positive experiences to other people living with dementia (Astell et al., 2014). However, the generalisation of this study's findings based on a single case study is limited because different people have varied experiences and needs in their different types and stages of dementia (Astell et al., 2014).

The Role of the Dementia Workforce and Person-Centred Care

Residential care homes and care providers contribute to addressing the care needs of residents living with dementia (Cooper et al., 2017). These include enhancing dignity, assuring security, and improving the quality of life (Cooper et al., 2017). However, care standards and

good working environment for residential care providers are the foundation for providing quality care for the residents (Johnson, 2014; Lin, 2010). A comparative study conducted by Lin (2010) between Scotland and Taiwan identified quality indicators related to the environment, health, and social care. The study developed a dementia care model focused on institutional care and explored an evidence-based care standard to assess the quality of residential dementia care (Lin, 2010). Moreover, the study found (Lin, 2010) that quality indicators assist in improving residential dementia care quality and support policymakers in identifying appropriate care standards to meet the residents' needs.

In addition, Johnson (2014) conducted a cross-national comparative study in Canada, Scotland, and the United States to examine the relationship between the good working environment for residential care providers and quality care for the residents (Johnson, 2014). This study underscored the significance of a suitable working environment that provides residential care staff with adequate resources and sufficient time to perform their roles properly. The study found that the absence of these essential elements creates a challenging work environment for the residential care providers to perform their appropriate roles and provide basic physical and social care needs for the residents. The study also found that inability to provide appropriate care for the residents based on government-approved care standards often violates the human rights of the residential care providers and residents (Johnson, 2014).

Further, Kelly (2010) conducted a multi-method observational study on identifying and promoting self in dementia. The study found that care providers' interactions with the residents were often limited and sometimes unpleasant. In addition, residents experienced illbeing in the care home. However, interactions were generally facilitative and joyful during creative sessions, and the residents experienced well-being (Kelly, 2010). Kelly (2010) argued that identifying and promoting selfhood in creative interaction sessions markedly distinguish care providers' attitudes toward residents' resulting in consequences for residents' well or ill-being experiences.

Family and Community-Based Care

Family carer perceptions of family and community-based dementia care findings are discussed in this section. Lee (2011) conducted a comparative study between Scotland and Korea to identify five important factors related to family and community-based support for people living with dementia. These included living conditions, family relationships, financial support, motivations, and the burden of care. The study (Lee, 2011) found that Scottish family carers maintained stronger family relationships than Korean ones. In addition, Korean family

carers experienced a heavier burden than Scottish family carers due to limited family support and a lack of community-based services (Lee, 2011).

Furthermore, good community care and support are considered a prerequisite for the social inclusion of people living with dementia. The study found that inadequate community care services result in early institutionalisation (Lee, 2011). Further, a recent study by Lillo-Crespo et al.(2018) conducted in European countries, including Scotland, found that people living with advanced dementia prefer to live in a familiar environment and be connected to and maintain social interactions and familiar living patterns. This familiar environment assists people living with dementia in managing their symptoms and improve their quality of life (Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018).

Non-Pharmacological Interventions

Non-pharmacological interventions are considered here because the development and implementation of evidence-based non-pharmacologic interventions are highlighted in the Scottish dementia strategies, standards of dementia care, and workforce development approaches to ameliorate the impact of cognitive and non-cognitive symptoms. Further, non-pharmacological interventions support independence and engagement in meaningful activities, and address the psychological and emotional needs of people living with dementia and their carers (Scottish Government, 2010; Scottish Government, 2011a; Scottish Government, 2011c; Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b). Research has shown that non-pharmacological interventions are frequently utilised as an alternative treatment and support services for people living with dementia (Dawson et al., 2015). The study by Gorska (2013) also explored that access to non-pharmacological interventions promotes and facilitates social networks for people living with dementia and their family members. These include emotional support, occupational therapy, speech and language therapy, physiotherapy, and access to daycare services. However, there are significant barriers, including inadequate resources and long waiting periods, to access non-pharmacological interventions (Górska et al., 2013).

From reviewing the studies, it is clear that there is a growing need to integrate health and social care services and ensure the participation of people with dementia and carers in the policy planning and distribution of health and social care services (Astell *et al.*, 2014; Caine, 2014; Dawson *et al.*, 2015; Tolson *et al.*, 2016). However, there are several drawbacks, including a lack of coordination between different service providers and a lack of effective dementia care plans (Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018). The final theme, the preparation and development of the dementia workforce, is discussed next.

2.8.2.5 Preparation and Development of the Dementia Workforce

Preparation and development of the dementia workforce is identified in ten out of the twenty-two studies. Authors and methodological quality are given below in Table 2.9.

Table 2. 9: Authors and Methodological Quality of the Reviewed Studies Related to the Preparation and Development of the Dementia Workforce

Paper Authors	Quality Appraisal Tool Used	Quality Checklist Score	Grade
Dawson et al., 2015	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Systematic Reviews and Research Syntheses	10 out of 11	High
Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Qualitative Research	10 out of 10	High
Surr and Gates, 2017	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Systematic Reviews and Research Syntheses	09 out of 11	High
Johnson, 2014	Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) for Mixed Methods Research	04 out of 04	High
Surr et al., 2020		04 out of 04	High
Tolson et al., 2016		04 out of 04	High
Surr et al., 2019	JBI Critical Appraisal Tool for Qualitative Research	06 out of 10	Moderate
Banks et al., 2014	Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) for Mixed Methods Research	03 out of 04	Moderate
Cooper et al., 2017	Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) for Quantitative Research	03 out of 04	Moderate
Waugh et al., 2011	Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) for Mixed Methods Research	03 out of 04	Moderate

The evidence regarding the preparation and development of the dementia workforce is discussed next. This major theme is presented under the following three sub-themes: professional development of dementia care workforce, need for dementia education and training and barriers and facilitators, and Dementia Champions Programme to improve the experiences of people living with dementia (see Figure 2.7).

Figure 2. 7: Sub-Themes Related to the Preparation and Development of the Dementia Workforce

Professional Development of Dementia Care Workforce

There is worldwide concern about delivering quality care to people with dementia in the health and social care sector. However, the study (Surr and Gates, 2017) found a lack of specialised knowledge and competence in the dementia care workforce to provide quality care for people with dementia. Johnson (2014) conducted a cross-national comparative study to understand the experiences of the dementia care staff working in the residential care sectors in Canada, Scotland, and the USA. The study identified care workers' training requirements for workforce development to provide a high level of physical and mental health needs for people living with dementia. The study found that Scotland comprises two options for conducting a professional training programme for the workforce development of care home nurses. These are classroom-based training and nursing home-based training (Johnson, 2014). In addition, a recent Delphi study (Cooper et al., 2017) conducted in four localities across the UK, including Scotland focussed on priorities for the professional development of registered nurses working in the nursing homes. The study revealed that most significant areas for Continued Professional Development for residential care home nurses are dementia care, personal care and addressing long-term health challenges (Cooper *et al.*, 2017). However, the study identified the challenges nurses face in accessing Continuing Professional Development opportunities due to limited workforce and lack of institutional support. The study also highlighted that specialised external support from primary and community health care workforce, and specialist gerontological qualifications can assist care home nurses in their professional development (Cooper *et al.*, 2017).

Need for Dementia Education and Training and Barriers and Facilitators

Health and social care workers require the necessary education and training to provide quality dementia care (Surr et al., 2020). A systematic review conducted by Surr and Gates (2017) evaluated the success of dementia education and training approaches for dementia care workers. The review illustrated that proper training directly correlates with the health care workforce and their operational instruments and treatment practices (Surr and Gates, 2017). However, the effectiveness of a dementia training programme depends on the health and social care workers' capability to apply their understanding into practice through behaviour modification (Surr et al., 2020). The study conducted by Surr et al. (2020) identified essential facilitators for the effectiveness of the dementia training programme. These include training relevant to the roles of the health and social care workforce, competent supervision of training, trainees' motivation to learn, and training benefits (Surr et al., 2020). Further, Surr et al. (2019) identified several components of successful training design, delivery and management that apply not only to dementia training but to more comprehensive professional training programmes within the health and social care sectors. These include participatory in-person training, interactive and collaborative training, and tailored training (Surr et al., 2019). Moreover, Surr et al. (2019) recommended involving expert facilitators to deliver and effectively implement dementia training. However, the study identified significant barriers to implementing a dementia care training programme. These include a lack of time and funds, shortage of health and social care workforce and lack of favourable working environment (Cooper et al., 2017; Surr et al., 2020).

Further, a qualitative study by Lillo-Crespo et al. (2018) identified a lack of experienced practitioners in dementia care (Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018). Moreover, the study found a lack of evidence-informed education on advanced dementia care among the professional and non-professional workforce in European countries, including Scotland (Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018).

Dementia Champions Programme to Improve the Experiences of People Living with Dementia

People living with dementia and their family members have found negative experiences during hospital admission in acute healthcare settings. Evidence shows that the Dementia Champions Programme educates and prepares the health and social care workers in acute healthcare settings and promotes workforce development (Banks et al., 2014; Waugh et al., 2011). The study by Waugh et al. (2011) found that the Dementia Champions Programme prepared the health and social care workers with the necessary skills and knowledge to develop their competence. Moreover, the study also found that the Dementia Champions

Programme promoted commitment among health and social care workers to deliver quality dementia care in hospital settings (Waugh *et al.*, 2011). However, the study (Banks *et al.*, 2014) identified significant challenges related to implementing the Dementia Champions Programme. These include a lack of adequate resources and a lack of flexible planning. However, the study found that the framework of the Dementia Champions Programme offered a cost-effective approach to educating and training National Health Service and Social Service Dementia Champions as change agents within the shortest time (Banks *et al.*, 2014). Additionally, the Dementia Champions Programme outcomes were asserted to be transferrable to other professionals and different health and social care settings in other countries (Banks *et al.*, 2014).

To summarise, the reviewed studies show that health and social care workers need access to appropriate dementia education and dementia training for their professional development to ensure quality dementia care (Surr and Gates, 2017; Surr *et al.*, 2020). However, there are several barriers, including insufficient resources and a lack of evidence-informed education on advanced dementia care to prepare and develop the dementia workforce (Lillo-Crespo *et al.*, 2018; Surr *et al.*, 2019; Surr *et al.*, 2020). Implications and knowledge gaps, and future research prospects are discussed next.

2.9 Discussion of Literature Review Key Findings

This integrative literature review critically explored the development and implementation of national dementia care strategies and related the dementia workforce development strategies in Scotland and Bangladesh.

The review key findings are framed around five major themes, dementia as a public health concern, implementation of the principles of public health policy, provision of post-diagnostic support, development of service and care infrastructure, and preparation and development of the dementia workforce. The search strategy yielded a small amount of research literature pertaining to dementia policy in Scotland and an absence of research regarding dementia policy within Bangladesh.

Critical appraisal of the included 22 studies reporting dementia policy development and implementation within Scotland and UK, demonstrated that the existing evidence base was of mixed quality in terms of strength of the evidence. Of the twenty-two reviewed studies, the

majority, namely 54.55 % (twelve), were high quality, and 45.45 % (ten) studies were moderate quality. A further challenge within the evidence base is that the studies were relatively narrow in their focus, with none offering a comprehensive scrutiny of Scottish national strategies. It is therefore important to acknowledge that while useful insights can be discerned from the available research in terms of the policy evidence that there are also considerable gaps in knowledge and number of untested assumptions.

This integrative review employed a rigorous methodology following Wittemore and Knaff's (2005) five stages to synthesise research evidence to enhance understanding, identify gaps in current policy research evidence, and inform policy and practice. Of the twenty-two included studies, two were systematic reviews, and twenty were empirical research. These include eleven qualitative, eight mixed-method, and one quantitative investigation. Due to the limited research evidence on the implementation of dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Scotland and Bangladesh, both systematic reviews and empirical research was considered in this integrative review. Based on their study design, the selected studies were critically examined using JBI and MMAT appraisal tools for strengths, weaknesses, and reliability of study findings. The review only considered the studies published 2010 to 2020 in English and Bengali (although no published studies in Bengali fulfilled the inclusion criteria). This may have excluded other sources of literatures including the networking of official websites of different dementia organisations and government relevant departments, print journal hand search and grey literature that might have contributed further understanding of workforce development and dementia care policies in Scotland and Bangladesh.

Review Question 1- Key Findings

-what is known from research about dementia care and related workforce development policy and its implementation in Bangladesh?

This integrative review found that no studies discussed the dementia care policy implementation and related workforce development approaches in the context of Bangladesh. There is a dearth of research-based literature in Bangladesh due to insufficient dementia care infrastructure (as explained in Context and Background Chapter One).

Review Question 2- Key Findings

-what is known from research about dementia care and related workforce development and related policy and it's implementation within Scotland?

This integrative review found that Scottish public health policy concerning early and timely diagnosis were introduced to promote timely access to dementia care and improve the quality of life for people living with dementia, their family, and carers (Dawson et al., 2015; Górska et al., 2013; Lee, 2011; Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018; Tolson et al., 2016). However, significant challenges were identified within several of the reviewed studies. These included challenges in obtaining early and timely diagnostic services and a lack of coordination and lengthy diagnosis procedures (Górska et al., 2013; Górska, 2018). There is, however, evidence to suggest that early access to primary health care services, specialist nurses and physicians contribute to early diagnostic services and better outcomes for people with dementia (Górska et al., 2013). Surprisingly the search strategy failed to identify studies focussed on dementia prevention although this has been implicit within national dementia strategies over the last decade.

Scottish dementia policy is underpinned by human rights which is a philosophical and values decision. It seems reasonable and generally believed to be a positive approach through moral reasoning. However, none of the reviewed studies discussed challenges or endorsed this rights-based dementia care approach. Moreover, the utility and practice impact of rights-based dementia care policy has not been interrogated through research, but is generally assumed to be desirable and helpful. There is a paucity of policy research evidence on the contributions of the human rights-based dementia care approach to making a difference in the care and support people living with dementia, their family, and carers receive in Scotland.

Further, this integrative review found that policy innovations aligned with integrated palliative care practice models and multi-dimensional strategies addressing palliative care can support people with advanced dementia to live the best possible (Dawson et al., 2015; Tolson et al., 2016). However, there are limited options for supporting people living with advanced dementia and their carers in European countries, including Scotland (Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018; Tolson et al., 2016). Additionally, there are limited opportunities to facilitate and promote advanced care planning due to the disinclination of recently diagnosed people living with dementia and their family to imagine and plan for their future care (Kelly and Innes, 2016).

This integrative review explored that the multi-component interventions and comprehensive support, are effective and useful in providing post-diagnostic support services for people living with dementia, their family, and carers (Dawson et al., 2015; Kelly and Innes, 2016). Locally based, multi-component interventions are helpful for family members and carers to assist people with dementia staying at home for extended (Dawson et al., 2015). Moreover, comprehensive support increases the independence, motivation and self-confidence of people diagnosed with dementia and their family carers (Kelly and Innes, 2016). Additionally, the experience of re-learning and re-connecting with technology can improve the quality of life of people diagnosed with dementia (Astell et al., 2014; Dawson et al., 2015). However, this review identified several unmet needs related to diagnostic procedures and post-diagnostic service provision in Scotland, which is a key policy priority in national dementia strategies. These included poor coordination of available services, lack of continuity of the support workers, and limited access to non-pharmacological services (Górska et al., 2013). In addition, the review found that the Link Workers can play a positive and useful role for newly diagnosed people living with dementia and family carers. However, there was a variation in the approach and role of Link Workers in the Alzheimer's Scotland Post-Diagnostic Support (PDS) Model (Levin *et al.*, 2018).

The findings of this review illuminated that quality indicators can improve institutional dementia care and the quality of life for people living with dementia in care homes. Moreover, quality indicators support in regulating services and care improvement (Lee, 2011; Lin, 2010). However, the absence of a good working environment and the lack of adequate resources and sufficient time create stressful work conditions for dementia care workers to deliver quality care for people living with dementia in residential dementia care settings (Johnson, 2014). Further, this review identified that the integration of health and social care can ensure the participation of people with dementia and carers in the planning and distribution of dementia care services and provide appropriate care and support throughout the journey of care for people living with dementia and their family and carers (Astell *et al.*, 2014; Caine, 2014; Dawson *et al.*, 2015; Tolson *et al.*, 2016). However, there is a lack of coordination among the care providers and insufficient effective dementia care plans to integrate health and social services (Lillo-Crespo et al., 2018).

Further, this integrative review found that health and social care workers require access to the specialised knowledge, necessary skills, and effective approaches to dementia training for their professional development to deliver quality care for people living with dementia (Surr and Gates, 2017; Surr et al., 2019; Surr et al., 2020). However, due to limited staff, and lack of funding and organisational support, health care workers face challenges being able to access

Continuing Professional Development opportunities and prepare them with up-to-date specialised knowledge, necessary skills, and competence to deliver high-quality care for residents (Cooper *et al.*, 2017; Surr and Gates, 2017). Additionally, no studies identified the knowledge and skill needs of informal and unpaid family carers to support them in their caring role in the Scottish context. Moreover, this review identified a lack of competent or experienced qualified practitioners involved in dementia care and a lack of evidence-informed education on advanced dementia care among the dementia workforce in European countries, including Scotland (Lillo-Crespo *et al.*, 2018). This further highlights the need for future research on advance dementia care education and training for professional and non-professional caregivers to provide quality care for people living with dementia and their family carers.

Additionally, this integrative review found that the Dementia Champions Programme prepared the health and social care workers with the required knowledge and skills to promote the quality of care for people living with dementia in acute health care sectors (Banks *et al.*, 2014; Waugh *et al.*, 2011). However, research needs to be conducted to highlight and document how Dementia Champions Programme could be transferrable in different groups and organisational structures in other countries. Moreover, developing leadership within the dementia workforce can contribute to successfully implementing national dementia care strategies. However, no studies discussed the importance of leadership structure to deliver good quality care for people living with dementia, their families, and carers. Further, dementia policy success depends on continuous monitoring and evaluation of the achievements of significant policy goals. However, no studies evaluated the success or failure of dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Scotland with the involvement of key dementia policy stakeholders, health and social care practitioners, care providers, people living with dementia and their carers.

2.10 Summary

Although this review's primary aim is to critically analyse what is known and not known about workforce development and dementia care policies in Scotland and Bangladesh, the majority of the studies included in the present review were conducted in Scotland and the rest of the UK and Europe. This integrative review provides a comprehensive finding on the significant aspects of developing and implementing national dementia care strategies and the dementia workforce education approaches in Scotland. There is however a significant gap in the literature on the development, implementation and effective evaluation of dementia care policies. Moreover, there is a need for further robust and transparent research on dementia

prevention and diagnosis, integrated dementia Pallaire, human rights-based dementia care approach, challenges and unmet needs related to post-diagnostic service provision, and advanced dementia care planning. Further research is required on the challenges and prospects of integration of service and care infrastructure, necessary knowledge, skills and training for informal and unpaid family carers, and the prospects of transferability of the Dementia Champions Programme in different groups in other countries. Research is needed to examine the transferability of dementia care policies and workforce development approaches to develop an effective, feasible and acceptable dementia care approaches in the context of Bangladesh. Therefore, the relevance of this policy learning from Scotland to Bangladesh was explored through interviews and group discussions with the policy stakeholders both in Scotland and Bangladesh.

The integrative review informed the research questions and direction of the subsequent stages of the study: a documentary policy analysis of Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches, key informant interviews with dementia policy stakeholders in Scotland, and Nominal Group discussions with family members and informal carers of people living with dementia, health and social care practitioners, academics (educators and researchers), dementia care providers, and policy planners in Bangladesh. The methodology, theoretical perspectives, and ethical considerations are discussed in the next chapter.

Chapter Three: Methodology and Theoretical Perspectives

3.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses methodology, theoretical perspectives, and ethical considerations. It begins with an exploration of philosophical pragmatism which underpins the mixed methods research design, including the reasons for this choice. This leads to a discussion of how rigour is conceptualized and can be promoted within mixed methods studies. Importantly it also discusses and frames the conceptual approach to exploring policy including the underpinning policy learning, policy success, and policy transfer theoretical perspectives. Discussion of ethical considerations, principles and cultural perspectives complete the chapter.

3.2 The Pragmatic Paradigm or Worldview and Mixed Methods Research

A paradigm or worldview is a basic set of beliefs and general philosophical orientation about the world and the nature of research that a researcher brings to a study to guide action. Although there is an ongoing debate about what worldviews or paradigms researchers bring to inquiry, four paradigms or worldviews are widely discussed in the literature: post-positivism, constructivism, transformative, and pragmatism (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). The major elements of each paradigm or worldview are presented in Table-3.1.

Table 3. 1: The Major Elements of Paradigms or Worldviews (Creswell and Creswell, 2018, p. 6).

Post-positivism <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Determination• Reductionism• Empirical observation and measurement• Theory verification	Constructivism <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Understanding• Multiple participant meanings• Social and historical construction• Theory generation
Transformative <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Political• Power and justice oriented• Collaborative• Change-oriented	Pragmatism <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Consequences of actions• Problem-centered• Pluralistic• Real-world practice oriented

There are associations between worldview and research design. For example, the post-positivist paradigm is associated with quantitative research, whereas the constructivism paradigm is related to qualitative research. Further, the transformative paradigm is linked with transformative research that contains an action agenda and changes the lives of marginalised groups and individuals. On the other hand, the pragmatism paradigm is related to mixed methods research (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). However, these are not fixed and are very much dependent upon the researcher and the project.

Pragmatism as a philosophy originated in the United States in the late nineteenth century. The first detailed summary was psychologist William James's 1907 book, *Pragmatism* (1995). In addition to James, other major pragmatists include Charles S. Peirce in philosophy; John Dewey in education and philosophy; and George Herbert Mead, whose work served as the basis for symbolic interactionism (for general overviews of pragmatism) (Morgan, 2017).

Pragmatism as a worldview arises out of actions, situations, and consequences rather than antecedent conditions (as in post-positivism). Instead of focusing on methods, researchers emphasise the research problem and question and use all approaches available to understand the problem (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). From a pragmatic point of view, research is a form of inquiry, and all inquiry is a form of action to meet goals that are framed in terms of research questions. Among several forms of pragmatism, John Dewey's emphasis on inquiry is especially useful because it directly links research design issues. For Dewey, inquiry in everyday life and research begins with a problematic situation that must be addressed through action. The process of addressing a problem requires careful reflection on both the nature of the problem and the range of possible solutions (Morgan, 2017).

The present mixed methods study investigates policy development and focuses on contextual knowledge instead of absolute or relative knowledge. This study does not aim to generate new theories through inductive empiricism or to verify a theory in a deductive manner. Moreover, this study does not link with political and social change to confront social inequalities and oppressions that result in asymmetric power relationships (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Therefore, post-positivism, constructivism, and transformative were not assumed appropriate to fulfil the aims of this mixed methods study. The pragmatism worldview underpins this mixed methods study because pragmatism is associated with mixed methods research and focuses on the consequences of the research evidence in real-world life and practice associated with this.

Pragmatism has gained considerable support amongst mixed-methods researchers and has likely become the most widely supported paradigm. For example, several mixed methods researchers, including, Biesta (2010), Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004), Maxcy (2003), and

Morgan (2007), have argued in favour of pragmatism as a paradigm for mixed methods research (Hall, 2020; Morgan, 2017).

Pragmatism is a philosophy of knowledge (epistemology) in its own right. It emphasises the importance of context in determining the truthfulness of knowledge. The priority is not to ascertain what is objectively true (post-positivism) or subjectively true (interpretivism) but rather what helps to guide action (contextually true). Individual researchers have the freedom to choose the research methods, techniques, and procedures that best meet their needs and purposes. Thus, pragmatism opens the door for mixed methods researchers to use multiple methods, different worldviews, assumptions, and different data collection and analysis techniques to provide the best understanding of a research problem (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Therefore, pragmatism was considered as the philosophical worldview for this mixed methods study to underpin decisions at each stage of the research process.

3.3 Research Design/Methodology

The exploratory sequential mixed methods design (Creswell and Creswell, 2018) has been selected combining, an integrative literature review, documentary policy analysis framework with Scottish key informant interviews, and Nominal Group Technique (NGT) group discussions with different groups of stakeholders in Bangladesh. The exploratory sequential mixed methods design is underpinned by the pragmatic paradigm or worldview and policy learning, policy success and policy transfer theoretical and conceptual perspectives. The overall study design and choice of methods (detailed in Chapter 4) were influenced by the practicalities of data collections during the height of the COVID-19 Pandemic. The merits and limitations of these research design choices are deliberated in the final discussion chapter Seven.

3.3.1 Mixed Methods

As the name implies mixed method research involves collecting, analysing, and mixing both qualitative and quantitative data in a single study (Creswell and Clark, 2017). Even though the explicit term 'mixed methods research' is relatively new, Maxwell (2016) contends that it has been used in the natural as well as social sciences for centuries (Maxwell, 2016). In recent years, mixed methods research designs have gained popularity in public administration, public policy research, and social, behavioural and health sciences (Bryman, 2016; Creswell, 2015; Tzagkarakis, Ioannis and Kritas, 2022).

Mixed method studies integrate the two sources of data by combining or merging them, connecting them (e.g., qualitative follows quantitative), or embedding them (e.g., qualitative data flows into an experimental trail). It incorporates these procedures into a design or plan for conducting the study, where philosophical assumptions or theories often frame the study (Creswell, 2015).

Although much progress has been made in mixed methods design typologies and several designs exist in the mixed methods field, the researcher needs to be critically considered the research aims and questions to develop an appropriate mixed methods research design (Schoonenboom and Johnson, 2017). Schoonenboom and Johnson (2017) outlined six major mixed methods designs. These include convergent parallel design, explanatory sequential design, exploratory sequential design, embedded design, transformative design, and Multiphase design. Moreover, Creswell and Creswell (2018) identified three core mixed methods designs: the convergent design, the explanatory sequential design, and the exploratory sequential design.

In a convergent mixed methods design, the researcher collects quantitative and qualitative data simultaneously and then integrates the information in interpreting the overall results to comprehensively analyse the research problem. Whereas the explanatory sequential design involves a two-phase data collection project in which the researcher collects quantitative data in the first phase, analyses the results, and then uses the results to plan or build on to the second qualitative phase to explain the initial quantitative results in more detail. On the other hand, the exploratory sequential design is the reverse sequence of the explanatory sequential design. In this design, the researcher begins with a qualitative research phase to explore participants' views. The data are then analysed, and information is used to plan or build into a second quantitative phase of the study to test or generalise the first phase qualitative results. Moreover, multiphase mixed methods design includes more than two phases, or the researcher combines sequential and concurrent strands within a study to address the overall study objective (Creswell and Creswell, 2018; Schoonenboom and Johnson, 2017). However, it is noteworthy that mixed-methods research is distinguished from multimethod research because it combines either multiple qualitative or multiple quantitative approaches within the same study (Schoonenboom and Johnson, 2017).

This research adopted the exploratory sequential mixed methods design based on philosophical pragmatism. As this study intended to investigate and analyse Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches to determine policy learning opportunities for Bangladesh, the exploratory sequential mixed methods research design was adopted. To achieve the research objective of determining Scottish dementia policy scope,

indicators of success and lessons for possible policy transfer to Bangladesh, the research needed to generate qualitative data. On the other hand, to identify the aspirations and priorities of multi-sectorial stakeholders for the development of dementia care policy in Bangladesh, it was essential to collect both quantitative and qualitative data accordingly. The study chronology follows the logical order of the research objectives, with the findings of successive research activities building the evidence base to inform the next set of data collection activities. These include an integrative literature review, documentary policy analysis with Scottish key informant interviews, and Nominal Group Technique (NGT) group discussions with multi-sectorial stakeholders in Bangladesh.

The documentary policy analysis is a stepwise process for interpreting qualitative data used in this study in combination with key informant interviews with policy stakeholders to provide an informed and in-depth view of dementia policy success in Scotland, as discussed later in Chapter Four and Five. Nominal Group Technique (NGT) is a democratic and consensus-building approach used in this study to collect both quantitative and qualitative data accordingly with multi-sectorial stakeholders to identify the issues and priorities for dementia care policy and workforce development in Bangladesh, as discussed later in Chapter Four and Six. The study collected qualitative data in the first phase from the documentary policy analysis framework with Scottish key informant interviews in Scotland. Then, it interrogated this data to evaluate the dementia policy success and identify tentative dementia policy learning for countries like Bangladesh. In the second phase both quantitative and qualitative data was generated from a series of Nominal Group Technique group discussions with different groups of stakeholders in Bangladesh. This was undertaken to identify the issues and priorities for dementia care policy and workforce development in Bangladesh from the perspectives of different professionals and lived experience stakeholders.

The Nominal Group Technique (NGT) was used to generate the quantitative element of the mixed methods approach of this study. The NGTs facilitated decision-making following the ranking approach. Such technique allows a rich generation of original ideas, balanced participation of all group members, and a rank-ordered set of decisions based on a mathematical voting method. The NGTs combined both qualitative and quantitative data collection in small groups of participants and involved a process to stimulate individual generation of ideas by group members through discussion and recording of those themes and finally, ranking them in order of priority (Harrison Denning, 2014). As such, the NGT is often described as a semi-quantitative/qualitative approach (Potter, Gordon and Hamer, 2004). The flexibility of the technique enables the researchers to modify and suit the needs of participants and researchers within a mixed methods study design (Manera *et al.*, 2019). The generation

of items and group discussion are closer to the qualitative approach, but quantitative analysis of data contributes to the ranking process (Steward, 2004). NGT data can be analysed quantitatively or qualitatively (Keatinge *et al.*, 2000). The qualitative data can be compared to the priority scores (quantitative data) and used to contextualise and justify group priorities (McMillan *et al.*, 2014). Although quantitative analysis of NGT data is usually limited to simple descriptive statistics, the quantitative data (ranking) that emerges from the NGT process provides an opportunity to evaluate the strength of the statement (Lloyd-Jones, Fowell and Bligh, 1999; MacPhail, 2001). In this study, the quantitative element generated from the NGT identified the priorities of multi-sectoral stakeholder groups for future dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Bangladesh. The quantitative approach to scoring is detailed in section 4.5 of Chapter Four.

There are specific purposes for combining qualitative and quantitative methods in the mixed methods research. Several analysts argue that using mixed methods research reduces bias, providing context, increasing the reliability of the outcomes, and validating measures and illuminating constructs (Ammenwerth and Rigby, 2016; Bryman, 2016; Hendren, Luo and Pandey, 2018; Palinkas *et al.*, 2015; Tzagkarakis, Ioannis and Kritas, 2022). The choice of conducting mixed methods research contributes to a better understanding of research problems and provides strengths that compensate for the potential shortcomings of employing either quantitative or qualitative research alone (Tzagkarakis, Ioannis and Kritas, 2022; Creswell, 2015). Mixed methods researchers combine qualitative and quantitative methods within the same study to examine different aspects of a single research question or use separate but related qualitative and quantitative research questions to obtain fuller and richer information (Schoonenboom and Johnson, 2017).

3.3.2 Promoting Rigour in Mixed Methods Studies

The promotion of rigour ensures the quality and scientific integrity of research. It requires understanding at both a conceptual and practical level during the planning, completion and reporting of a study. Rigour is primarily concerned with the researcher's actions, the steps taken in the scientific process, and the reporting mechanisms used to describe those steps to the reader to understand better precisely what the researchers did during their study (Harrison, Reilly and Creswell, 2020). Although the empirical and methodological literature about mixed methods research is increasing, there are limited discussions in relation to how rigour is established. There are known tensions and differences in how rigour is understood and promoted within qualitative and quantitative approaches, which maybe combined within a single mixed method study (Younas, Rasheed and Zeb, 2020). Although challenging, failing

to maintain rigour in mixed-method designs can compromise the quality and credibility of findings (Bazeley, 2018). Accordingly, this section outlines how rigour was considered within this mixed method study.

Underpinned by the pragmatic paradigm, the present study adopted an exploratory sequential mixed methods design (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Arguably using such sequential approaches supports rigour due to the opportunity afforded for cumulative understanding, building upon and between each data collection activity (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). Some authors contend that rigour in mixed methods research can be assessed through the quality and strengths of the discrete qualitative and quantitative data collection methods (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018; Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2008; Younas, Rasheed and Zeb, 2020). For example, quantitative strand needs to ensure validity and reliability criteria whereas qualitative part should ensure the trustworthiness criteria which includes credibility, confirmability, transferability, and dependability (O’Cathain, 2010; Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2008).

Planning and operationalizing rigour in mixed-method design is a multifaceted process that requires careful consideration at every stage of the research journey. The present exploratory sequential mixed methods design drew selectively upon the legitimisation framework (Younas, Rasheed and Zeb, 2020). This framework includes 11 legitimisation criteria: commensurability approximation legitimisation, conversion legitimisation, inside-outside legitimisation, integration legitimisation, multiple validities legitimisation, paradigmatic/philosophical legitimisation, pragmatic legitimisation, sample integration legitimisation, sequential legitimisation, socio-political legitimisation, and weakness minimisation legitimisation (Younas, Rasheed and Zeb, 2020). Although the authors claim that using all eleven criteria supports mixed method rigour, this felt somewhat cumbersome and difficult to fully operationalise, particularly in absence of an empirical evidence base to substantiate the authors claim. Nonetheless it was considered helpful to embrace the idea of pragmatic legitimisation as an overarching concept in addition to embracing the more established approaches to rigour within either qualitative or quantitative methods (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). In addition, sample legitimisation highlighted the need to ensure that key informants had authentic understanding of the making of and implementation of Scottish dementia policies, and that appropriate participants were assembled for each of the stakeholder Nominal Groups for the NGT. Although inside-outside legitimisation is not clearly differentiated it did bring to the fore the usefulness of consulting with key national agencies in the planning of the project both in terms of potential participants and how their contributions might be considered ‘trustworthy’ and culturally appropriate.

In addition to drawing upon some of the legitimisation criteria the more established work of Greene, Caracelli and Graham (1989) was embraced. They identified five purposes and rationale for a mixed methods research design, relevant to understanding research quality and opportunities to promote rigour (see detailed in Table 3.2). These include triangulation, complementarity, development, initiation, and expansion (Greene, Caracelli and Graham, 1989).

The present study considered triangulation and complementarity for choosing an exploratory sequential mixed methods design (Schoonenboom and Johnson, 2017; Tzagkarakis, Ioannis and Kritas, 2022). Four types of triangulations are used in the research to promote rigour. These include method triangulation, investigator triangulation, theory triangulation, and data source triangulation (Tzagkarakis, Ioannis and Kritas, 2022). For example, this study intended to generate qualitative data through documentary policy analysis framework and key informant interviews in Scotland. Whereas Nominal Group Technique discussions were considered to collect qualitative and quantitative data from multi-sectoral stakeholder groups in Bangladesh.

Further, complementarity assists in the interpretation of different aspects of social phenomena through the synthesis of the results of each method and increases the meaningfulness and validity of the findings (Schoonenboom and Johnson, 2017; Tzagkarakis, Ioannis and Kritas, 2022). In this study, key informant interviews findings in Scotland have complimented the information gathering through the documentary policy analysis framework to analyse the process, programme, and political level success in Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches. In addition, the NGT discussions findings in Bangladesh have complimented the tentative recommendations and dementia policy learning from Scotland to Bangladesh derived from the synthesised findings of documentary policy analysis and key informant interviews in Scotland.

**Table 3. 2: Purposes and Rationale for Choosing Mixed Methods Research Design
(Greene, Caracelli and Graham, 1989, p. 259)**

Purpose	Rationale
<p>Triangulation seeks convergence, corroboration, correspondence of results from different methods.</p>	<p>To increase the validity of constructs and inquiry results by counteracting or maximizing the heterogeneity of irrelevant sources of variance attributable especially to inherent method bias but also to inquirer bias, bias of substantive theory, biases of inquiry context.</p>
<p>Complementarity seeks elaboration, enhancement, illustration, clarification of the results from one method with the results from the other method.</p>	<p>To increase the interpretability, meaningfulness, and validity of constructs and inquiry results by both capitalizing on inherent method strengths and counteracting inherent biases in methods and other sources.</p>
<p>Development seeks to use the results from one method to help develop or inform the other method, where development is broadly construed to include sampling and implementation, as well as measurement decisions.</p>	<p>To increase the validity of constructs and inquiry results by capitalizing on inherent method strengths.</p>
<p>Initiation seeks the discovery of paradox and contradiction, new perspectives of frameworks, the recasting of questions or results from one method with questions or results from the other method.</p>	<p>To increase the breadth and depth of inquiry results and interpretations by analysing them from the different perspectives of different methods and paradigms.</p>
<p>Expansion seeks to extend the breadth and range of inquiry by using different methods for different inquiry components.</p>	<p>To increase the scope of inquiry by selecting the methods most appropriate for multiple inquiry components.</p>

The pragmatism worldview informs the use of policy learning theoretical frameworks in this study to investigate and analyse the development and implementation of Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches and determine the lessons for possible

policy transfer to Bangladesh. Next the specific theoretical and conceptual perspective in which the study is framed are discussed.

3.4 Theoretical and Conceptual Perspectives

Theoretical and conceptual perspectives offer insight into research activity. The present study is underpinned by the policy learning, policy transfer and policy success theoretical and conceptual perspectives, which helped to ask research questions.

3.4.1 Policy Learning Theory

Policy learning is an ongoing process whereby individual policymakers continually learn from each other through literature, attending conferences, informal visits to services in other countries, and formal exchange programmes. Lesson-drawing and policy transfer are mechanisms by which learning and transfer take place. These concepts are generally described as policy learning (Freeman, 2003). Deutsch (1963) first introduced policy learning in the study of politics and policy in his relatively rationalist theory of government. Following Deutsch, among others, Heclo (1974), Walker (1974), Friedmann (1984), Haas (1992), Hall (1993), Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith (1993), and Parsons (1995) contributed to developing the policy learning frameworks (Moynon, Scholten and Weible, 2017).

Governments and associated bodies 'imitate' policies from other sectors or nations, particularly if those are seen as more successful, without necessarily involving 'learning' (Weyland, 2004). Innovation and influence can be measures of policy success, irrespective of the particular policy outputs and outcomes. A policy process may produce new and innovative ways of tackling a problem (Lundberg, 2007). Innovation refers to new ideas or policy instruments, which involves the adoption of policy from elsewhere (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a). Innovation can also be based on policy transfer from another political jurisdiction (Dolowitz, Greenwold and Marsh, 1999; Dolowitz and Marsh, 2000). If policy instruments or even broad frameworks, are imported from elsewhere, the assumption is that there is some value in doing so. In effect, a policy transferred from elsewhere can bring with it not only particular policy instruments but also the idea, sometimes erroneous, that it was successful in the original jurisdiction (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a).

3.4.2 Policy Transfer Framework

Policy transfer can be understood as a process by which 'knowledge about how policies, administrative arrangements, institutions and ideas in one political setting (past or present) is used in the development of policies, administrative arrangements, institutions and ideas in another political setting' (Dolowitz and Marsh, 2000, p. 5). Policy transfer analysis is a theory of policy development and change that seeks to make sense of a process or set of processes in which knowledge about institutions, policies or delivery systems at one sector or level of governance is used in the development of institutions, policies or delivery systems at another sector or level of governance (Evans, 2009).

Different forms of policy transfer such as band wagoning (Ikenberry, 2019), convergence (Bennett, 1991), diffusion (Majone, 1991), emulation (Howlett, 2000), policy learning (May, 1992), social learning (Hall, 1993) and lesson-drawing (Rose, 2005) have been identified in a wide range of literature which has attracted significant academic attention from domestic, comparative and international political scientists. However, these conceptual variations share a reasoning which is about the fact that there are benefits for policy leaders to look beyond their immediate sphere of control and to look to other contexts to examine whether what they do control can be improved.

Dolowitz and Marsh (2000) have led efforts to develop a comprehensive theory of policy transfer. In essence, they have drawn together a general framework of heterogeneous concepts, including policy diffusion, policy convergence, policy learning and lesson-drawing, under the umbrella heading of policy transfer (see Table 3.3). Dolowitz and Marsh suggest that all these phenomena can be organized into one framework as 'dimensions of policy transfer'. They invite policy-researchers to use and refine their framework within empirical studies as this will then help to assess the utility of it and whether it needs to be developed as a framework. The framework developed by Dolowitz and Marsh poses a series of questions (i.e., why transfer? who is involved in transfer? what is transferred? from where? degrees of transfer, constraints of transfer, how to demonstrate policy transfer? and how transfer leads to policy failure?) which can be used both to organize our current knowledge of the process and to guide future work (Dolowitz and Marsh, 2000).

Table 3. 3: A Policy Transfer Framework (Dolowitz and Marsh, 2000, p. 9)

Why Transfer? Continuum			Who Is Involved in Transfer?	What Is Transferred?	From Where			Degrees of Transfer	Constraints on Transfer	How to Demonstrate Policy Transfer	How Transfer leads to Policy Failure
Want To..	Have To			Past	Within-a Nation	Cross-national				
Voluntary	Mixtures	Coercive									
Lesson Drawing (Perfect Rationality)	Lesson Drawing (Bounded Rationality)	Direct Imposition	Elected Officials	Policies (Goals) (Content) (Instruments)	Internal	State Governments	International Organizations	Copying	Policy Complexity (Newspaper) (Magazine) (TV) (Radio)	Media	Uniformed Transfer
	International Pressures (Image) (Consensus) (Perceptions)	Conditionality (Loans) (Conditions Attached to Business Activity)	Bureaucrats Civil Servants	Programs	Global	City Governments	Regional	Emulation		Reports (Commissioned) (uncommissioned)	Incomplete Transfer
	Externalities	Obligations	Pressure Groups	Institutions		Local Authorities	State	Mixtures	Past Policies	Conferences	Inappropriate Transfer
			Political Parties	Ideologies			Local Governments	Inspiration	Meetings/ Visits		
			Policy Entrepreneurs/ Experts	Attitudes/ Cultural Values			Past Relations		Structural	Statements (written) (verbal)	
			Consultants	Negative Lessons					Institutional		
			Think Tanks						Feasibility		
			Transnational Corporations						(Ideology) (Cultural proximity) (Technology) (Economic) (Bureaucratic)		
			Supranational Institutions						Language		

3.4.3 Policy Success Framework

Policy success resides in meeting targets and achieving outcomes. A successful policy redresses power imbalances, reduces inequalities and involves stakeholders in formulating policy goals and evaluating results (McConnell, 2010). However, defining policy 'success' is difficult. Policy success can vary and be disputed. There are also some critical choices involved in evaluating policy success. These include the form of policy success, timeframe, interests, reference points, information, policy isolation, conflict and ambiguity (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a). In this context, the synthesised framework provides a robust and transparent set of indicators for exploring success. The present study has used an original modified and synthesised framework (see Table 3.4) to undertake a documentary analysis based on McConnell's (2010) and Marsh and McConnell's (2010) existing three-level frameworks for evaluating policy success to analyse the process, programme, and political level success in Scottish dementia care and workforce development policies. The synthesised documentary analysis framework identifies the indicators of success in policy to contextualise these indicators to dementia care and workforce development policies.

Table 3. 4: Synthesised Documentary Analysis Framework for Evaluating Policy Success (McConnell, 2010; Marsh and McConnell, 2010a)

Dimensions of Policy Success	Indicators of Success	Types of Evidence/Sources
Process Success	Preserving government policy goals and instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legislative records • Executive minutes • Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders
	Legitimacy in the formation of choices and passage of legislation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legislative records • Executive minutes • Analysis of legislative voting patterns
	Building a sustainable coalition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of support from ministers • Analysis of support from stakeholders
	Innovation and influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legislative records • Executive minutes • Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders • Academic and practitioner reports
	Opposition to process is virtually non-existent and/or support is virtually universal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legislative records • Executive minutes • Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders
Programme Success	Operational: Implementation in line with objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programme/policy evaluation • Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders
	Outcome: Achievement of desired outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programme/policy evaluation • Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders
	Resource: Efficient use of resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programme/policy evaluation • Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders
	Actor/interest: Creating benefit for a target group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative and quantitative studies with policy beneficiaries
	Opposition to program aims, values, and means of achieving them is virtually non-existent, and/or support is virtually universal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programme/policy evaluation • Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders
Political Success	Government popularity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opinion polls • Election results
	Sustaining the broad values and direction of government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of manifestoes • Policy strategy documents
	Opposition to political benefits for government is virtually non-existent and/or support is virtually universal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manifestos of opposition political parties

This synthesised framework is a conceptual innovation, achieved by connecting Marsh and McConnell's (2010) success indicators with Dolowitz and Marsh's (2000) Policy Transfer Framework. Moreover, such conceptual innovations will add the value of corresponding the policy transfer literature with the policy success literature in dementia policy research while undertaking multi-level comparative policy implementation studies. One of the main concerns of Dolowitz and Marsh's Policy Transfer Framework is to examine the relationship between policy transfer and policy success/failure and they suggest that policy transfer is likely to be unsuccessful or failure if it is unformed, incomplete or inappropriate (Dolowitz and Marsh, 2000). Through the policy success and policy transfer frameworks within a spirit of philosophical pragmatism, Scottish dementia care policy documents have been scrutinised and interpreted with added insights from key informant interviews and Nominal group stakeholder discussions to understand 'what' could be transferred from Scotland to make recommendations and inform future dementia policy development in Bangladesh.

The present study used policy success and policy transfer frameworks because these frameworks provide a robust and transparent set of indicators and dimensions to define and operationalise dementia policy success in Scotland and identify the transferable dementia policy lessons from Scotland to Bangladesh. However, there are some limitations involved in Marsh and McConnell's policy success framework in assessing and distinguishing process, programme and political success of dementia care policies from the perspective of different stakeholders due to overlaps and tensions within and between these three dimensions (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a; Marsh and McConnell, 2010b). Further, policy success frameworks were designed to explore single policy interventions, not an evolving set of policies developed over several years (McConnell, Grealy and Lea, 2020).

3.5 Ethical Considerations

Ethics is the branch of philosophy that deals with morality. Further, ethics is more commonly understood as the practical application of moral philosophy through the introduction of principles and rules designed to regulate human behaviour. This discipline contains a set of propositions for the intellectual analysis of morality. The problems of ethics relate to obligation, rights, duty, right and wrong, conscience, justice, choice, intention, and responsibility (Grove, Burns and Gray, 2012). Ethics play an important role in scientific inquiry (Morin, Olsson and Atikcan, 2021). Ethical conduct in research is also associated with the promotion of values that protect the interests of all concerned, such as accountability, trust, mutual respect, and fairness (Robson, 2011). Ethical issues arise in the qualitative, quantitative, and mixed

methods research and all stages of research (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). A number of general and specific ethical issues are related to research involving with human subjects (Wisker, 2012). Organisations and researchers should make sure that any research involving human participants, human material or personal data complies with all legal and ethical requirements and other applicable guidelines (UKRIO, 2009). When the research involves human subjects, ethical considerations may often be complex and centre on areas such as: respecting privacy; human dignity; protecting rights of self-determination; maximising benefits and minimising any risks of harm, and obtaining informed consent (Resnik, 2015; Robson, 2011). Ethical integrity refers to the mechanisms and principles which a researcher builds into the planning of a study to safeguard research participants and study sites (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2018; Flick, 2018). The most widely used set of basic principles for research ethics (review), has been those first formulated as the 'Belmont Principles', and widely disseminated by Beauchamp and Childress (2001). These principles are typically given as respect for persons (and their autonomy), beneficence, non-maleficence, and distributive justice (ensuring benefits and burdens are shared equitably) (Morin, Olsson and Atikcan, 2021; UKRIO and ARMA, 2020). Research ethics in the social sciences initially drew on the 'patient protection' model of medical research but has more recently broadened in scope to include consideration of benefits, risks and harms to all persons connected with and affected by the research and to the social responsibilities of researchers (ESRC, 2016). Though educational or social research does not appear to have the potential for inflicting a similar degree of physical or psychological harm to its research participants (Islam, 2017), sometime psychological, reputational and physical harm can occur in educational and social research, the most famous example of this is the Stanley Milgram's 'obedience experiments' (Herrera, 2001). Moreover, social research is within the remit of research in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and social care research is, therefore, subject to the same requirements as medical research in areas of data protection and storage (Morin, Olsson and Atikcan, 2021; NHS, 2018).

Ethical scrutiny and approval by a properly constituted ethics committee- is a key process that promotes and supports researchers to design research with ethical integrity. Researchers need to have their research plans reviewed by an institutional review board (IRB) on their college and university campuses (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Research ethics and governance are often assumed to be the same. However, there are differences between research ethics and research governance. Research ethics refers to the ethical considerations and principles that guide researchers to work with research participants, collected data, other researchers, research users, and others involved with research from inception to completion. Research governance, conversely, is a code of practice and an administrative process which

sets standards in research, defines mechanisms to deliver standards, and oversees those who enforce the standards to ensure the quality of research is consistent with the high standards (Manchester Metropolitan University, 2023; The Royal Children's Hospital, 2016; Tolich, 2012; University of the West of Scotland, 2019). For example, research governance in the University of the West of Scotland is guided by four principles: independence, competence, facilitation and openness (University of the West of Scotland, 2019). In practice, research needs to receive an ethical review to ensure the rights, safety and welfare of participants, and a governance review to ensure institutional accountability and acceptability (The Royal Children's Hospital, 2016). There are ethical scrutiny processes in place at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). University of the West of Scotland (UWS) guidelines for ethical practice in research and scholarship UWS (2019) have outlined the ethical principles guiding research with human participants. These include autonomy, veracity and informed consent, privacy and confidentiality, justice and inclusiveness and benefits and harms (University of the West of Scotland, 2019).

Different ethical approaches shape research practice, including duty-based, outcomes-based, and relational ethics. A duty-based ethics is technically known as deontology. 'Deontology' derives from the Greek 'dean' translated as 'duty'. Deontology is an umbrella term for ethical theories emphasising that duty is at the heart of morality. Immanuel Kant's deontology is the most prominent and influential form of duty-based ethics. Central concepts of Kant's deontology include good will, duty, and autonomy. Deontology is a non-consequentialist way of doing ethics, i.e., for deontology, an action is deemed right or wrong not because of its consequences or effects on the world but because it conforms to a moral law or principle (Kearns, 2017). Duty-based ethics provides a set of rules or duties which ought to follow, and which help guide our actions (Oberai, 2023).

On the other hand, outcome-based ethics is known as consequentialism. In contrast to duty-based ethics, outcome-based ethics judge actions in terms of their positive or negative consequences. For example, an activity or policy, including the distribution of social resources, is viewed as morally right if it maximizes utility among people in the society or world (Gustafson, 2018; Peterson, 2013; Sabbagh, 2009; Spall, 2023).

Further, relational ethics is a process that emerges through re-examining the nature of existence, knowledge, oppression, and injustice. Relational ethics provides the framework to rethink the nature of data science through a relational understanding of being and knowing. (Birhane, 2021). Philosophy of relational ethics emphasizes the contextual features of relationships and the experience of relationships in influencing moral choices (MacDonald, 2007). Through the lens of relational ethics, the researchers explore data science's wider

social, political, and historical nature and the need to rethink ethics in broader terms. Relational ethics asks that for any solution sought, the starting point be the individuals and groups impacted the most. This means we seek to centre the needs and welfare of those disproportionately impacted, not solutions that benefit the majority. Adopting relational ethics means we view our understandings, proposed solutions, and definitions of bias, fairness, and ethics as partially open (Birhane, 2021).

Underpinned by philosophical pragmatism, the present study investigates dementia care policy development in Scotland and focuses on the context in determining lessons for possible policy transfer to inform future dementia policy development in Bangladesh. Therefore, relational ethics appears to be relevant to shape the design of this study of the different ethical approaches. For example, as data was collected from both Scotland and Bangladesh through key informant interviews and nominal group discussions, the researcher acknowledged the socio-economic, political, cultural, and linguistic differences between Scotland and Bangladesh. The researcher used culturally sensitive and language-appropriate materials and approaches. For example, the researcher translated the personal information sheet, NGT protocol, and consent form into Bengali to ensure all participants could participate actively in the NGT discussions. Further, to obtain informed consent from the participants, the researcher provided a clear and understandable personal information sheet and consent form explaining the purpose of the study and the methods involved. In addition, the researcher ensured that the participants understood potential risks and benefits, their rights and the option to decline participation.

Among the ethical principles of UWS to guide research with human participants, as outlined above, the most important underlying ethical considerations for this study are informed consent, anonymity, confidentiality, inclusiveness, and no harm (University of the West of Scotland, 2019). Informed consent ensures that a participant has complete information and understanding of the research project and the risk involved before, during, and after participation (Morin, Olsson and Atikcan, 2021; Palys and Atchison, 2021). Autonomy allows participants to make informed choices without coercion or fear after understanding the purpose of the research study. The principle of autonomy acknowledges the right of all individuals to determine their course of action. It underlies the need for free and informed consent (University of the West of Scotland, 2019). Several components must be present in informed consent, including disclosure, understanding, voluntariness, competence, consent, authorisation, and exculpation (Iphofen, 2020; Morin, Olsson and Atikcan, 2021).

Further, confidentiality is another important ethical principle in this present study. Confidentiality permits the protection of all the data collected from the participants by not divulging the information without the consent of the participants. The researchers must take every precaution to ensure the confidentiality of the participants identifiable information (Palys and Atchison, 2021). Furthermore, research ethics usually requires not to disclose the identity of individuals, groups or organisations who have participated in research. Moreover, ensuring anonymity is a legal requirement as per the Data Protection Act 2018 to protect the rights of research participants (Iphofen, 2020; University of the West of Scotland, 2019). Therefore, to ensure anonymity, the researcher needs to use pseudonyms or codes in place of the participants' real names. Moreover, the researcher must ensure that the participant's name, location, job title or any identifiable data will not be used in any publication or report from the study. In addition, the researcher should make necessary efforts to secure the participants' well-being, maximise benefits, and minimise any unforeseen harm. The interests and integrity of the participants need to be protected from physical, psychological and cultural harm (University of the West of Scotland, 2019). It is worth noting that anonymity could not be assured in the NGT groups as the participants all see each other, but anonymity and confidentiality could be assured outside of those groups. In this study, the researcher prepared an NGT protocol with an introduction and ground rules to conduct Nominal group discussions. Further, participants were asked to keep confidential what was discussed within the groups.

Both these principles and UWS processes have guided preparation for ethical research conduct before entering the research field and adhered to throughout the project. For example, concerning autonomy and informed consent, the researcher provided the potential participants with a Personal Information Sheet to inform them about the aim of the research, what they were required to do and when to participate, and the extent of their participation. Moreover, the researcher assured them that their participation would be voluntary and that they could withdraw without explanation or consequence. Further, to ensure privacy and confidentiality, participants were assured anonymity and the use of pseudonyms in the thesis while analysing and presenting data. Moreover, participants were informed that all personal data collected would be deleted after completion of the research. In addition, the researcher assured and took the necessary initiatives to ensure equal participation and avoid the risk of coercion of research participants. The detailed application of ethical guidelines and principles in data collection and analysis is discussed in Methods Chapter Four.

3.6 Summary

This chapter presents the study's research design/methodology and ethical considerations. In addition, this chapter discusses the conceptual and theoretical perspectives that underpin the study. In the following chapter the study methods, including sampling strategy, participant recruitment, data collection techniques and analysis plan are detailed.

Chapter Four: Methods

4.1 Introduction

This chapter begins with an overview of the study design. This overview shows the research chronology, timelines and different inquiry methods used. The integrative literature review is included in this overview, but is not elaborated within this chapter having been described and reported in Chapter 2. Following, the study overview the practical application of the ethical principles (discussed in Chapter 3) is explained, including the process of securing ethical approval. This is followed by the detailed discussion of the methods used to complete the documentary policy analysis, illuminated by key informant interviews, and the subsequent nominal group interviews. The sampling strategy, participant recruitment, data collection methods and analytical approaches are explained for each component. Although the study is reported in English, as explained later, data collection activities in Bangladesh were undertaken in the local language (Bengali) with translation into English for reporting, with back translation to promote accuracy for analytical purposes.

4.2 Study Overview

The study chronology followed the logical order of the research objectives, with the findings of successive research activities building the evidence base to inform the next set of data collection activities. This sequential approach, as explained in section 3.3 (Chapter 3), was selected to add rigour and augment confidence in the interpretation of the study findings. Data collection was undertaken in Scotland, Bangladesh and online. Desk-based research activities, including the integrative literature review and documentary policy analysis, were mainly undertaken within Scotland. Key informant interviews were carried out in Scotland with selected key policy stakeholders at the national level to complement the information gathering through the documentary policy analysis framework. Then the final step of the research, the Nominal Group Technique group discussions, took place on-site in Bangladesh. Table 4.1 presents the overview of research objectives and research questions, research steps and data collection methods.

Table 4. 1: The Overview of Research Objectives and Research Questions, Research Steps and Data Collection Methods

SL	Research Objectives	Research Questions	Research Steps	Place of Data Collection	Time	Method/Data/Evidence Source
1	To critically review the evidence base shaping dementia care and dementia workforce development policy and policy implementation within Scotland and Bangladesh.	What is known about shaping and implementation of dementia care and dementia workforce development policy within Scotland and Bangladesh?	Research Step-01	Scotland	December 2019-September 2023	Integrative literature review
2	To determine Scottish dementia policy scope, indicators of success and lessons for possible policy transfer to Bangladesh.	What is the scope and what are success indicators of Scottish dementia policy, and what are the lessons for possible policy transfer to Bangladesh?	Research Step-02(A)	Scotland	July 2020-May 2023	Documentary Policy Framework Analysis
			Research Step-02(B)	Scotland	October 2020-February 2021	Key informant interviews
3	To scope with multi-sectorial stakeholders in Bangladesh their aspirations and priorities for the development of dementia care policy.	What are the aspirations and priorities of multi-sectorial stakeholders in Bangladesh for the development of dementia care policy?	Research Step-03	Bangladesh	July-November 2021	Nominal Group Technique discussion
4	To make recommendations to inform future dementia policy development in Bangladesh.	What elements could be considered in the future dementia policy development in Bangladesh?	Research Step-01, 02, and 03	Scotland and Bangladesh	-	Integrative literature review Documentary Policy Framework Analysis Key informant interviews Nominal Group Technique discussion

Research Step-01: Integrative Literature Review

The purpose of the integrative literature review was to critically analyse the development and implementation of national dementia care strategies, including the dementia workforce education approaches in Scotland and Bangladesh. The integrative review followed the established methods developed by Whitemore and Knafl (2005) as described in Chapter 2 (section 2.3). The process is designed to examine a broad range of literature on a particular topic. It typically employs a wide sampling frame that includes experimental and non-experimental research, theoretical and empirical literature, as well as grey literature relevant to the topic at hand (Whitemore and Knafl, 2005). The findings of the literature review influenced the design of the subsequent research activities described below. For example, it was clear from the literature review that the introduction of dementia policy within Scotland occurred after 2010 and this information was useful to set the initial date parameters to commence searching Scottish policy publications.

Research Step-02: Documentary Policy Framework Analysis with Key Informant Interviews

Research Step-02 (A) Documentary Policy Framework Analysis

The documentary policy framework analysis was planned in combination with key informant interviews with policy stakeholders to provide an informed and in-depth view of dementia policy success in Scotland. The present study used a modified and synthesised framework (see Table 4.2) based on McConnell's (2010) and Marsh and McConnell's (2010) existing three-level frameworks for evaluating policy success to analyse the process, programme, and political level success in Scottish dementia care and workforce development policies. The synthesised framework identified the indicators of success in policy to contextualise these indicators to dementia care and workforce development policies.

Research Step-02 (B) Key Informant Interviews with Policy Stakeholders in Scotland

Key informant interviews had been carried out in Scotland with key policy stakeholders at the national level to build an understanding of the influences, background stories, challenges, and lessons on dementia care policy development within Scotland and to complement the information gathering through the documentary policy analysis framework. Such contextual understanding was essential in terms of building both practical and theoretical understanding of the enablers and barriers that were not exposed through the documentary analysis alone.

It was also important in understanding the motivations behind policy documents as well as to explore the major influencers who made significant contributions for the development and implementation of Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches. The synthesised findings of the Documentary Policy Analysis and Key Informant Interviews are presented and discussed in Chapter 5.

Research Step-03: Nominal Group Technique Discussions

The Nominal Group Technique (NGT) interviews had been conducted in Bangladesh with multi-sectorial stakeholders involved in dementia care, workforce development and policymaking in Bangladesh to identify the issues and priorities of dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Bangladesh. Due to COVID-19-related lockdown restrictions in Bangladesh during data collection, an adapted virtual NGT interview approach was used based on the classical form of the Nominal Group Technique (discussed in detail in section 4.5). The classic form of the NGT includes four structured stages: silent generation of individual ideas; round-robin recording of those ideas; clarification/discussion; and priority voting or ranking (Delbecq, Van de Ven and Gustafson, 1975). The aim of this democratic and consensus-building approach was to enable each group, to critically consider and generate a comprehensive list of the factors, that were important to them, in relation to future dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Bangladesh. NGT data provided a local (Bangladesh) perspective and complemented the information derived from the documentary policy analysis and Scottish Key Informant interviews of senior policy influencers and national leads. Chapter 6 presents and discusses the findings of Nominal Group Technique (NGT) discussions.

4.3 Ethical Approval and Application of Ethical Principles and Guidelines in this Study

The study received ethical approval from the Health and Life Sciences School Ethics Committee (SEC) at the University of the West of Scotland (Reference Number: 11822) (see Appendix 4.1). A systematic procedure had been followed to obtain ethical approval for this study. University of the West of Scotland (UWS) guidelines for ethical practice in research and scholarship UWS (2019) have outlined the ethical principles guiding research with human participants. These include autonomy, veracity and informed consent, privacy and

confidentiality, justice and inclusiveness and benefits and harms (University of the West of Scotland, 2019). Both these principles and UWS processes guided the preparation for ethical research conduct before entering the research field and adhered to throughout the project. The detailed application of ethical principles and guidelines is discussed below.

Autonomy, Veracity and Informed Consent

The researcher took the necessary initiatives to apply the ethical principles of autonomy, veracity and informed consent in this study. For example, the participants' information sheets (see Appendix 4.4 and 4.14) were sufficiently detailed, relevant, and accurate. Furthermore, the researcher included all relevant aspects clearly and honestly of this study that was relevant to decide to give informed consent (see Appendix 4.5 and 4.15). Participants in the Key Informant Interviews and Nominal group Discussions were recruited voluntarily, and participants were free to withdraw from this study without giving any reason for withdrawing. However, the participants were allowed to withdraw from the study after three months of interviews and Nominal Group Discussions. Anonymised data could not be withdrawn after three months as it was included in the analysis and design of the next stage of the study. Although, none withdrew their participation from the study. There was no undue influence or coercion, e.g., by offering disproportionate rewards or disincentives for not consenting. The researcher informed the potential participants about the nature and procedures of Key Informant Interviews and the Nominal Group Technique in this study. Further, participants were given sufficient time to consider the information and decide on participation in the key informant interview and group discussion (University of the West of Scotland, 2019).

Privacy and Confidentiality

The next ethical principles followed in this study were privacy and confidentiality. To promote anonymity, the researcher used pseudonyms or codes in place of the real name of the participants. Therefore, this could not be linked to the participants of Key Informant Interviews and stakeholders of the Nominal Group Discussions in any way. Furthermore, the researcher assured that the participant's name, location, job title or any identifiable data would not be used in any publication or report from this study.

According to Data Protection Act (1998), all electronic data were stored and saved in a secure protected location and a password-protected computer within the premises of the University of the West of Scotland (UK Parliament, 1998). Moreover, Personal data were treated

following the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the UK Data Protection Act 2018 (Mourby *et al.*, 2019). The researcher assured that collected data would be accessible only by the researcher and supervisory team for at least 36 months to allow for analysis, thesis completion and publication dissemination according to the UKRIO Code of Practice for Research (UKRIO, 2009) and UWS privacy and confidentiality policy (University of the West of Scotland, 2019). After 36 months, the researcher deleted all electronic data. All hardcopy information was saved in a locked cabinet in the researcher's office for 36 months. At the end of this period, the researcher shredded and trashed all hard copies. Data access, control and dissemination were also protected under the Data Protection Act (UK Parliament, 1998).

Justice and Inclusiveness

Fairness and equity principles were followed for all research participants (key policy and NGT stakeholders) in the study during data collection from the Key Informant Interviews and Nominal Group Discussions (University of the West of Scotland, 2019). For example, Nominal Group Discussion assured the participants an equal opportunity to contribute to the study (McCance *et al.*, 2007; Søndergaard *et al.*, 2018). Further, Nominal Group Discussion minimised opportunities for a few individuals to dominate the process and was identified as an appropriate democratic approach to facilitate the involvement of all NGT stakeholders in the discussion and decision-making processes (McCance *et al.*, 2007). Moreover, Nominal Group discussions involved family members and informal carers of people living with dementia to know their views and experiences and in setting research priorities to inform decisions on future dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Bangladesh. The participation of family members and informal carers of people living with dementia in the NGT helped to identify an appropriate approach to generate and prioritise preferences for good quality care throughout the illness (Dening, Jones and Sampson, 2013; Mulqueen and Coffey, 2017).

Benefits and Harms

Furthermore, benefits and harms ethical principles were followed in this study. The researcher made necessary efforts to secure the participants' well-being, maximise benefit, and minimise any unforeseen harm during the Key Informant Interviews and Nominal Group Discussions. The interests and integrity of the participants were protected from physical, psychological and cultural harm (University of the West of Scotland, 2019). For example, the researcher was concerned about the potentially embarrassing or upsetting situation related to the difficult personal experiences of family members and informal carers of people living with dementia

while discussing barriers to care in the Nominal Group Discussion. Moreover, the researcher provided reasonable breaks during group discussion and offered counselling or emotional support to encourage the participation of the family members and informal carers of people living with dementia throughout the NGT consensus-generating process (SDWG, 2013).

Moreover, potential risk factors of the 'participants' in the Key Informant Interviews and Nominal Group Technique were considered based on the prescribed procedure and guidelines of the University of the West of Scotland (University of the West of Scotland, 2018). The researcher assured the participants that there was no harm to any volunteered participants. However, the researcher was concerned about the potential benefits and harms to the participants during the Key Informant Interviews and Nominal Group Discussions and clarified it in participant information sheets and consent forms (University of the West of Scotland, 2019) (see Appendix 4.4, 4.5, 4.14, and 4.15).

4.4 Documentary Policy Analysis Framework with Key Informant Interviews

The documentary policy analysis framework was used in combination with key informant interviews with policy stakeholders/actors to provide an informed and in-depth view of dementia policy development in Scotland. The purpose of the documentary policy analysis was to:

- a) understand the dementia policy landscape and policy developments (including agendas), and
- b) to pursue questions raised by the documents in interviews with relevant key policy actors in Scotland.

Key informant interviews had been carried out in Scotland with key policy stakeholders at the national level to build an understanding of the influences, background stories, challenges, and lessons on dementia policy development within Scotland and to complement the information gathering through the documentary policy analysis framework. Such contextual understanding was essential in terms of building both a practical and theoretical understanding of the enablers and barriers that were not exposed through the documentary analysis alone. It was also important to understand the motivations behind documents as well as to explore the major influencers who made significant contributions to the development and implementation of Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches.

4.4.1 Documentary Analysis Framework of Policy Success

Policy success resides in meeting targets and achieving outcomes. A successful policy redresses power imbalances, reduces inequalities and involves stakeholders in formulating policy goals and evaluating results (McConnell, 2010). However, defining policy 'success' is difficult. Policy success can vary and be disputed. There are also some critical choices involved in evaluating policy success. These include the form of policy success, timeframe, interests, reference points, information, policy isolation, conflict and ambiguity (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a).

A framework is generally a stepwise process for interpreting qualitative data. The present study used a modified and synthesised framework (see Table 4.2) based on McConnell's (2010) and Marsh and McConnell's (2010) existing three-level frameworks for evaluating policy success to analyse the process, programme, and political level success in Scottish dementia care and workforce development policies. In this context, the synthesised framework provided a robust and transparent set of indicators for exploring success. The synthesised documentary analysis framework identified thirteen indicators of success in policy to contextualise these indicators to dementia care and workforce development policies. Key policy documents were used in combination with key informant interviews with policy stakeholders to provide an informed and in-depth view of dementia policy 'success' in Scotland. Framework analysis process was used to analyse policy documents and key informant interview data (detailed in section 4.4.5).

Table 4. 2: Synthesised Documentary Analysis Framework for Evaluating Policy Success (McConnell, 2010; Marsh and McConnell, 2010a)

Dimensions of Policy Success	Indicators of Success	Types of Evidence/Sources
Process Success	Preserving government policy goals and instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legislative records • Executive minutes • Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders
	Legitimacy in the formation of choices and passage of legislation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legislative records • Executive minutes • Analysis of legislative voting patterns
	Building a sustainable coalition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of support from ministers • Analysis of support from stakeholders
	Innovation and influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legislative records • Executive minutes • Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders • Academic and practitioner reports
	Opposition to process is virtually non-existent and/or support is virtually universal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legislative records • Executive minutes • Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders
Programme Success	Operational: Implementation in line with objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programme/policy evaluation • Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders
	Outcome: Achievement of desired outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programme/policy evaluation • Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders
	Resource: Efficient use of resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programme/policy evaluation • Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders
	Actor/interest: Creating benefit for a target group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative and quantitative studies with policy beneficiaries
	Opposition to program aims, values, and means of achieving them is virtually non-existent, and/or support is virtually universal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programme/policy evaluation • Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders
Political Success	Government popularity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opinion polls • Election results
	Sustaining the broad values and direction of government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of manifestoes • Policy strategy documents
	Opposition to political benefits for government is virtually non-existent and/or support is virtually universal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manifestos of opposition political parties

4.4.2 Selection of Policy Items

The Scottish Government's relevant ministries and departments, including the Ministry for Mental Wellbeing and Social Care, and Public Health Scotland, national agencies, including Health Improvement Scotland, and NHS Education for Scotland, and the Scottish Parliament and the different political party's websites were searched to identify relevant dementia care policies and workforce development approaches to evaluate the dementia policy success in Scotland. Further, the websites of relevant national and international dementia care organisations were also searched, such as Alzheimer Scotland, Scottish Dementia Working Group, National Dementia Carers Action Network, Alzheimer Europe, Alzheimer Disease International (ADI), and WHO. The use of a variety of international sources and agencies helped to look deeper to understand the global agenda and international drivers that shaped and influenced national policy in Scotland. In terms of rigour, this assisted to generate a comprehensive sampling frame and contextual understanding along with the interpretation of the framework analysis to see individual policies and build a picture of policy connectivity and maturity. Moreover, a Google search was conducted to locate similar organisations' reports, working papers and policy documents. Furthermore, key Informant Interviews helped to identify policy documents related to developing and implementing Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches. Additionally, the reference list of each policy item was manually examined to find any relevant documents related to the documentary policy analysis purpose.

Finding relevant policy documents for this research had some challenges because the search was limited to electronic sources and informed by the key dementia policy stakeholder interviewees. It was difficult to get documents such as confidential reports, evaluation reports, and meeting minutes from the Scottish Government's concerned ministries and departments and national and international dementia care organisations working on developing and implementing the dementia care policy and workforce development approaches. However, these issues did not undermine the use of the available policy documents to accomplish the study objectives.

Total 22 policy items including dementia national action plans, strategies, frameworks, policy documents, evaluation reports and relevant program options were included for evaluating policy success, to analyse the process, programme, and political level success in Scottish dementia care and workforce development policies. The time duration of the selected policy items was from 2007 to 2021 (Click on [Timeline Dementia Care Policy in Scotland - Google Slides](#) to see the selected dementia policy items / see Appendix 4.2).

4.4.3 Sampling Strategy and Recruitment Process of Key Informant Interviews

This study used the purposeful sampling technique and aimed to recruit a minimum of five (05) key policy stakeholders who, in different ways, were involved in the development or implementation of Scottish dementia policies. These include senior personnel from various national agencies, charities representing people affected by dementia, and Scottish Government officials. Because of the seniority of the people who aimed to recruit, the supervisory team made initial contact with five (05) potential key policy stakeholders to determine their willingness, in principle, to receive a more formal request to consider participation from the doctoral researcher. Following receipt of an expression of possible interest, the doctoral researcher contacted the potential key policy stakeholders by their professional emails, which were available in the public domain, with a request to consider participation in a virtual (Webex, Teams or Zoom) or telephone audio-recorded interview (see Appendix 4.3). An advantage of online/telephone interviewing is that they allow researchers to access participants across distance and time barriers (Mann, 2016). Potential key policy stakeholders were requested to consider the invitation and respond as soon as possible, indicating whether they wished to participate in the study. A reminder email was sent to those potential key policy stakeholders who did not reply to the initial invitation email two weeks later. It was decided that if the minimum sample size were not reached following the initial invitation, more potential key policy stakeholders would be identified and contacted. All five (05) potential key policy stakeholders agreed to participate in the study. Those who indicated potential interest were sent further information by email, including the researcher provided an information sheet detailing the purpose of the interview and estimated duration, a consent form, and an opportunity to ask further questions about the study (see Appendix 4.4 and 4.5). Key policy stakeholders were given an opportunity to withdraw from the Key Informant Interview without explanation or redress. However, the participants were allowed to withdraw from the study after three months of the interviews. Anonymised data could not be withdrawn after three months as it was included in the analysis and design of the next stage of the study. Although, none withdrew their participation from the study. Appointments were scheduled at a time and date convenient to those who agreed to participate.

4.4.4 Data Collection Approach and Instrument of Key Informant Interviews

This study used semi-structured interviews to collect relevant data from the key policy stakeholders in Scotland. Semi-structured interviews with key policy stakeholders are considered the most appropriate communication medium to generate insights and insider perspectives on national policy development and decision-making (Samarasinghe, 2017).

Semi-structured interviews enable a guided conversation between researcher and informant to elicit information on particular topics systematically and allow for some prompting and reordering during the interview to ensure the flow of the conversation (Berg and Lune, 2007; Bryman, 2012). Moreover, semi-structured interviews allow for negotiation, discussion, and expansion of the interviewee's responses (Mann, 2016), and are considered a useful technique to generate rich, descriptive data that cannot be easily captured through survey questionnaires or fully structured/standardised interviews (Arksey and Knight, 1999).

The semi-structured interview guidelines included open-ended questions for gathering qualitative data. The interview guidelines were prepared based on the findings of the integrative literature review, documentary policy analysis, and the conceptual frameworks of Policy Transfer (Dolowitz and Marsh, 2000) and Policy Success (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a; McConnell, 2010) for assessing policy success in Scottish dementia care policies and investigating the policy transferability from Scotland to Bangladesh. The researcher made necessary amendments to the initial draft interview schedule, following the guidelines of the supervisory team.

Initial pilot interviews were conducted with two academics in the ASCPP at the University of the West of Scotland to ensure that the English questions were clearly expressed, and the key dementia policy stakeholders could understand the questionnaire. These academics were asked to modify these questions and give recommendations to improve and refine the draft interview. Finally, following the pilot interviews, the researcher updated and revised the draft interview schedule according to the suggestions of academics and the guidelines of the supervisory team (see Appendix 4.6).

The pilot and final interviews were conducted between October 2020 and February 2021. All the interviews were conducted through MS Teams. Due to internationally evolving COVID-19 and restrictions on face-to-face meetings, the virtual interview was considered an appropriate approach to collect data from the key policy stakeholders in Scotland. Further, the selection of the virtual programme was guided by the accessibility needs of the participant and used in line with UWS data management policies (University of the West of Scotland, 2019).

One member of the supervisory team was present with the researcher for each interview during both in pilot and final data collection to make an additional audio/online recording as backup and also in case of connectivity problems. In addition to this, the presence of a native English speaker not only contributed to the quality of the interviews but also helped in terms of analysing meaning recognising that points could be lost in translation. Again, such English language support added in promoting quality and accuracy of interpretation. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with prior verbal and written consent from the key policy

stakeholders, and all the interviews were audio-recorded with permission. The researcher asked for verbal consent to be recorded at the start of the actual interview and offered an opportunity for the participants to ask any questions about the interview or study before starting the recording (see Appendix 4.5).

Main study interviews lasted from 40 to 65 minutes. At the end of each interview, the researcher invited the key policy stakeholders to list or make suggestions on which policy documents they considered relevant to the purpose of this study. This was to assist in the verification of the completeness of the policy document data set used in the documentary analysis.

The researcher prepared the verbatim transcription using MS Teams and made necessary corrections based on interview recordings. The accuracy of the transcript was checked in two ways- the researcher listened to the full audio recording and re-checked the transcript, as did the supervisor who was present at the interview. The corrected transcript was then sent to the participants for them to check their answers and ask further questions for clarification. Following member checking, transcripts were anonymised in terms of person and place in preparation for analysis.

4.4.5 Data Analysis Plan of Policy Documents and Key Informant Interviews

Framework analysis was used to analyse policy documents and key informant interviews data of this study (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994). Framework analysis is a systematic and flexible approach to managing and analysing qualitative data in medical and health research (Gale et al., 2013). Further, framework analysis provides an excellent tool to assess policies and procedures and is suitable for applied policy research (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003; Srivastava and Thomson, 2009). This approach is better adapted to research with specific questions, a limited time frame, a pre-designed sample (e.g., professional participants) and a priori issues (e.g., organizational and integration issues). Although framework analysis may generate theories, the prime concern is to describe and interpret what is happening in a particular setting (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994). Moreover, framework analysis is not aligned with a particular epistemological, philosophical, or theoretical approach. Therefore can be adapted for use in inductive or deductive analysis or a combination of the two (e.g. using pre-existing theoretical constructs deductively, then revising the theory with inductive aspects, or using an inductive approach to identify themes in the data before returning to the literature and using theories deductively to help further explain specific themes) (Gale et al., 2013). For this study, framework analysis for the policy documents and Key Informant Interviews data in Scotland

was guided by a deductive technique based on the conceptual framework of Policy Success (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a; McConnell, 2010).

Framework analysis was adopted to analyse policy documents and Key Informant Interviews data because framework analysis is most commonly used for the thematic analysis of semi-structured interview transcripts to generate themes by comparing within and between cases. It can also be used to analyse policy documents (Gale et al., 2013). Its defining feature is the matrix output: rows (cases), columns (codes) and 'cells' of summarised data, providing a structure into which the researcher can systematically reduce the data to analyse it by the case (individual interviewee) and by code (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003).

Framework analysis provides clear steps to follow and produces highly structured outputs of summarised data (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003). In the analysis stage, policy documents and interview data of this study were shifted, charted and sorted following the five stages: familiarisation, construction of initial thematic framework, indexing, charting, and mapping and interpretation (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994).

Stage-01: Familiarisation

Familiarisation with the data provided a contextual understanding and initial thoughts and impressions about the content of the policy documents and interview transcripts (Furber, 2010; Gale et al., 2013). Immersion in the raw data was achieved through data collection from the key policy stakeholders, listening to interview recordings, preparing verbatim transcripts, and repetitive reading of interview transcripts and policy documents to identify key ideas and notes.

Stage-02: Construction of Initial Thematic Framework

An initial thematic framework (see Appendix 4.7) was developed based on Key Informant Interview guidelines (see Appendix 4.6) and the dimensions and indicators (see Table 4.2) in the Policy Success Framework (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a; McConnell, 2010).

One interview transcript and policy document were selected purposively and coded against the initial coding framework by the researcher and two supervisory team members. The researcher updated and revised the initial thematic framework, following the feedback and guidelines of the supervisory team. The thematic framework included a detailed code aligned with themes and subthemes (see Appendix 4.8).

Stage-03: Indexing

The researcher used NVivo qualitative data analysis software (NVivo-12) to assist in coding the interview transcripts and policy documents. The NVivo qualitative data analysis software helps record and organise data, allowing coded data to maintain links with the original transcripts (Jackson and Bazeley, 2019). Firstly, all the interview transcripts and policy documents were imported into NVivo qualitative data analysis software (NVivo-12). Then, the revised and updated thematic framework was entered into NVivo (NVivo-12) to manage data and support analysis.

The thematic framework was applied, and all the relevant data from the policy documents and the key informant interviews were indexed against the codes. Facilitating the identification of data corresponded to a particular theme and subtheme or code in the framework. Examples of data indexing processes using the coding framework are presented in Appendix 4.9 and 4.11.

Stage-04: Charting

The indexed data was then arranged to form charts/ framework matrices of key themes and subthemes with data entries linked to individual participants and policy documents. Examples of data charting tables are presented in Appendix 4.10 and 4.12.

Stage-05: Mapping and Interpretation

In the final stage, the framework matrices were used to arrive at a final, synthesised interpretation of how successful dementia policy in Scotland was since 2007. Any discrepancies in the data analysis process were resolved with the discussions of supervisors until a consensus was reached.

Following these five stages promoted consistency, supported data triangulation and was intended to optimise the use of the conceptual framework.

4.5 Nominal Group Technique Interviews

The Nominal Group Technique (NGT) is a well-established structured cross-sectional mixed methods approach for establishing consensus (Mason *et al.*, 2021). The NGT entails face-to-face discussion in small groups and provides a prompt result for researchers (McMillan, King and Tully, 2016). Moreover, structured and face-to-face group interaction empowers NGT participants by allowing them to have their voices heard and opinions considered by other members (Tully and Cantrill, 1997). The classical Nominal Group Technique (NGT) interviews were planned to conduct face-to-face group discussions to identify the issues and priorities of

dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Bangladesh. The classic form of the Nominal Group Technique includes four structured stages: silent generation of individual ideas; round-robin recording of those ideas; clarification/discussion; and priority voting or ranking (Delbecq, Van de Ven and Gustafson, 1975). However, due to COVID-19 pandemic related restrictions and challenges, the researcher had to make some adaptations of the classical NGT and moved to an online approach. The aim of this democratic and consensus-building approach was to enable each group, to critically consider and generate a comprehensive list of the factors, that were important to them, in relation to future dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Bangladesh. Following idea generation, the group democratically generated a prioritised list of actions. The NGT data provided a local (Bangladesh) perspective and complemented the information derived from the documentary policy analysis and Scottish Key Informant interviews of senior policy influencers and national leads.

Although the researcher had plan to conduct Policy Delphi to generate consensus (Patterson, Newman and Doona, 2016) among the policy makers about future dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Bangladesh, due to COVID-19 pandemic restrictions, the study used virtual adapted NGT. The study used NGT ideally to identify the issues related to the priorities and expectations of multi-sectoral stakeholder groups for future dementia care policy and workforce development approaches in Bangladesh. Several practical considerations informed the decision to use NGT in this study like NGT is a time-efficient data collection approach that allows for gathering a substantial amount of information within a single-occasion process (Potter, Gordon and Hamer, 2004). Such choice of using online NGT was a significant consideration for the study since, the NGT required multi-sectoral stakeholder groups involvement during the COVID-19 pandemic and limited availability of family members and informal carers of people living with dementia, health and social care practitioners, academics (educators and researchers), dementia care providers, and policy planners. Further, in bringing together a diverse group of individuals from different stakeholder groups in Bangladesh, the NGT provided a unique and valuable opportunity to identify the issues and priorities that are important to all groups, irrespective of the level of consensus. In addition, NGT allowed for in-session completion and immediate dissemination of results to the group, promoting satisfaction with participation (Harvey and Holmes, 2012). Further, NGT ensured the gathering of a comprehensive and range of ideas raised by multi-sectoral stakeholder groups, in a democratic style by offering all participants a chance to speak and ensuring that every suggestion is treated equally. Therefore, it helped to avoid the risk of the group being dominated by specific individuals (French, 2001; Gallagher *et al.*, 1993; Krueger and Casey, 2000).

4.5.1 Sampling Strategy

The suggested size of a nominal group is 5-9 participants (Potter, Gordon and Hamer, 2004). The NGT used the purposive sampling technique to assemble five stakeholder groups in Bangladesh, each with 5-9 participants. These included (a) family members and informal carers of people living with dementia; (b) health and social care practitioners; (c) academics (educators and researchers); (d) dementia care providers; and (e) policy planners.

4.5.2 Participant Recruitment

The list of names for the potential stakeholders of Nominal group discussions was generated and identified through recommendations made by the Secretary-General of the Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh (ASB), the external supervisor in Bangladesh and the academics of the Gerontology and Geriatric Welfare Masters Programme of the Institute of Social Welfare and Research (ISWR) at the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. The researcher is a full-time faculty member of the Institute of Social Welfare and Research (ISWR), University of Dhaka, Bangladesh, and has been involved with the Gerontology and Geriatric Welfare Masters Programme. Moreover, the Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh (ASB) worked as a gatekeeper to identify and develop initial links with the potential NGT stakeholders in Bangladesh.

The NGT recruited five (05) different stakeholder groups involved in dementia care, workforce development and policymaking, including family members and informal carers of people living with dementia, health and social care practitioners, academics (educators and researchers), care providers, and policy planners in Bangladesh. Among the list of names for the five (05) potential NGT stakeholder groups, health and social care practitioners, academics (educators and researchers), care providers, and policy planners were contacted by their professional emails, which were available in the public domain, with a request to consider participation in a virtual (Webex, Teams or Zoom) audio-recorded Nominal Group Discussion (see Appendix 4.13). The selection of the virtual programme was guided by the accessibility needs of the participant and used in line with UWS data management policies. Due to internationally evolving COVID-19 and restrictions on face-to-face meetings, the virtual Nominal Group Discussion was considered an appropriate approach to collect data from the stakeholders in Bangladesh. Potential stakeholders were requested to consider the invitation and respond as soon as possible, indicating whether they wished to participate in the study. A reminder email was sent to those potential NGT stakeholders who did not reply to the initial invitation email two weeks later. No further communication was made for non-respondents. It was decided

that if the minimum sample size was not reached for each group following the initial invitation, more potential NGT stakeholders would be identified and contacted. Those who indicated potential interest were sent further information by email, including the researcher provided an information sheet detailing the purpose of the Nominal Group Technique and the estimated duration of group discussion, a consent form, and an opportunity to ask further questions about the study (see Appendix 4.14 and 4.15). The NGT stakeholders were given an opportunity to withdraw from the Nominal Group Discussion without explanation or redress. However, the participants were allowed to withdraw from the study after three months of the Nominal Group Discussions. Anonymised data could not be withdrawn after three months as it was included in the analysis and design of the next stage of the study. Although, none withdrew their participation from the study. Appointments were scheduled at a time and date convenient to those who agreed to participate.

On the other hand, potential family members and informal carers of people living with dementia did not have professional email. They were identified and contacted with the support of the Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh (ASB). The purposive sampling technique was used to identify potential family members and informal carers of people living with dementia. The potential family members and informal carers of people living with dementia who were literate and had the capacity to communicate their own language (Bengali) and were able to fully participate in a group discussion were invited by the Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh to consider their interest to join in NGT group discussions (see Appendix 4.13). Those who indicated potential interest were sent further information to their postal address or by email with the support of the Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh (ASB), including the researcher provided an information sheet detailing the purpose of the Nominal Group Technique and the estimated duration of group discussion, and a consent form and an opportunity to ask further questions about the study (see Appendix 4.14 and 4.15). Family members and informal carers of people living with dementia were given an opportunity to withdraw from the Nominal Group Discussion without explanation or redress. However, the participants were allowed to withdraw from the study after three months of the Nominal Group Discussions. Anonymised data could not be withdrawn after three months as it was included in the analysis and design of the next stage of the study. Although, none withdrew their participation from the study. Appointments were scheduled at a time and date convenient to those who agreed to participate.

The primary aim of involving family members and informal carers of people living with dementia in NGT was to know their views and experiences and to set research priorities to inform decisions on future dementia care policy and workforce development approaches in Bangladesh. The participation of family members and informal carers of people living with

dementia in the NGT identified as an appropriate approach to generate and prioritise preferences for good quality care throughout the illness (Denning, Jones and Sampson, 2013; Mulqueen and Coffey, 2017).

4.5.3 Data Collection Approach and NGT Protocol

The background/context of the study and the findings of the integrative literature and documentary policy analysis with key informant interviews informed Nominal group discussions with stakeholders involved in dementia care, workforce development and policymaking in Bangladesh. The NGT protocol was prepared to promote efficient management of the NGT process. The NGT protocol was designed based on the classical form of Nominal Group Technique proposed by Delbecq, Van de Ven and Gustafson (1975) and are comprised of four key stages: silent generation; round-robin; clarification; and voting (ranking or rating) (Delbecq, Van de Ven and Gustafson, 1975) to identify the issues and priorities of dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Bangladesh (see Appendix 4.16).

An initial draft of the NGT protocol was provided to the supervisory team to ensure that the English questions were clearly expressed and stakeholders could understand the guidelines. As for the Bangla version of the NGT protocol, the researcher invited two academics from the Institute of Social Welfare and Research (ISWR), University of Dhaka, Bangladesh, to provide their opinions. These academics were asked to modify this protocol and give recommendations to improve the NGT protocol. The researcher made necessary amendments to the initial draft of the NGT protocol, following the suggestions of academics and the guidelines of the supervisory team.

Further, one pilot NGT was conducted with five participants, including two academics and three postgraduate research students from the Institute of Social Welfare and Research (ISWR), University of Dhaka, Bangladesh, to ensure the NGT protocol was clearly expressed, and the NGT stakeholders could understand the guidelines clearly. In addition, these academics and students were asked to modify this protocol and give recommendations to improve and refine the draft NGT protocol.

Following the NGT pilot, the researcher corrected and revised the NGT protocol according to the suggestions of pilot NGT participants and the guidelines of the supervisory team. The information sheet, informed consent form, and NGT protocol were translated into Bangla for

Bangladeshi stakeholders to avoid problems with foreign language expression and to enable them to answer the questionnaire easily. The researcher's first language is Bangla; therefore, the researcher handled the translation. The wording of the information sheet, informed consent form, and NGT protocol stated clearly that the responses would be dealt with confidentially and reported anonymously.

The pilot and final NGT discussions were conducted between July 2021 and November 2021. All the NGT discussions were conducted through Zoom. One member of the supervisory team was present with the researcher as a Co-facilitator for each NGT discussion during both pilot and final data collection to make an additional audio/online recording as a backup but also to be there just in case of connectivity problems or if there was a point where additional support was helpful. Nominal Group discussions were conducted with prior verbal and written consent from the stakeholders, and all the discussions were audio-recorded with permission. The researcher asked for verbal consent to be recorded at the start of the actual discussions and offered an opportunity for the participants to ask any questions about the discussions or study before starting the recording (see Appendix 4.15).

Main NGT discussions lasted from 90 to 140 minutes. The researcher prepared the verbatim transcription and translation of the selected discussions of the NGT and made necessary corrections based on the NGT discussion recordings. The accuracy of the group priority lists, and transcript was checked in two ways-the researcher listened to the full audio recording and re-checked the priority lists and transcript, as did the supervisor who was present at the discussion. The corrected group priority lists were then sent to the participants for them to check their answers and ask further questions for clarification. Following member checking, group priority lists and transcripts were anonymised in terms of person and place in preparation for analysis.

4.5.4 The Nominal Group Process for Generating Consensus

The main aim of NGT was to generate themes and issues, which were discussed to create a list of key issues and then ranked in order of importance by the group (Søndergaard et al., 2018). The Nominal Group discussions were conducted in an online format (Zoom) using the following four key stages: silent generation; round-robin; clarification; and voting (ranking or rating) (Delbecq, Van de Ven and Gustafson, 1975).

Stage One-Silent Generation

A nominal group generally involves one to two questions initially considered by participants who are asked to silently reflect on and list key issues in response to a question (Claxton, Ritchie and Zaichkowsky, 1980). This stage is called the silent generation of ideas. In this study, the Nominal group discussion started by introducing the purpose of the study, the NGT aim (in a manner appropriate to each Stakeholder Group), and the process for generating consensus in the NGT discussions through a brief PowerPoint presentation (see Appendix 4.17). Following a brief context-setting introduction by the Researcher and Co-facilitator, participants were asked to individually consider only one question appropriate to each Stakeholder Group and read it aloud.

Although the overall purpose of NGT was to identify the issues and priorities of dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Bangladesh, questions were adapted to be meaningful for the particular stakeholder group as shown in Table 4.3. The researcher encouraged participants to seek clarification if they were unclear about the terms in the question. Having read the question appropriate to each Stakeholder Group, participants were invited to identify the issues and priorities of dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Bangladesh. Participants were asked to write down the things that they considered important in response to the question. Participants wrote their answers or ideas on individual notepads individually and silently. An individual's list can be as long or as short as they like. The researcher and Co-facilitator supported participants needing more explanation to prepare a written list.

Table 4. 3: Questions Used for Five NGT Groups

	Group 1: Family Members and Informal Carers of People Living with Dementia	Group 2: Health and Social Care Practitioners	Group 3: Academics (Educators and Researchers)	Group 4: Care Providers	Group 5: Policy Planners
Questions used	What do family members and informal carers need to improve the dementia care and living standards for people living with dementia in Bangladesh?	What are the most important aspects need to consider to improve dementia care in health and social care settings in Bangladesh?	What do academics (educators and researchers) consider important to improve the dementia care and workforce development in Bangladesh?	What do care providers need to improve the dementia care for the people living with dementia and their family carers in Bangladesh?	What are the most important aspects need to consider in dementia policy to improve the dementia care and workforce development in Bangladesh?

Stage Two- Round-Robin

In the second stage, participants were then asked to share one idea with the group, taking it in turns to share a single idea from their list. In the initial round, participants shared their first idea; after everyone in the group had shared an idea, the person who started the round shared their second idea and so on, until all ideas had been shared. Participants were able to think of new ideas during this process but must waited for their turn before they could share with the group. There were no discussions at this stage. Instead, ideas were recorded verbatim on a Word file and shared on the computer screen accessible to all the participants during the online NGT discussion session. This stage continued until no new ideas were forthcoming.

Stage Three-Clarification

The third stage was to group similar ideas to create a shorter list. The researcher discussed all ideas to clarify statements' meaning and wording to ensure participant understanding. Similar ideas were grouped with agreement from all participants. Participants also had the opportunity to exclude, include, or alter ideas. Participants did not have to agree with all ideas listed. Ideally, the group processes generated a short list of the key points. All ideas/key points were discussed to ensure participant understanding (Delbecq, Van de Ven and Gustafson, 1975), thus enabling them to make an informed decision when they came to vote on ideas.

Stage Four- Voting (Ranking or Rating)

After initial discussion, clarification and idea sharing, each participant was asked to select and then rank their top ideas. There are two common approaches which are used to facilitate NGT priority voting or ranking exercises. The simplest is to provide each participant with a sticky coloured star, which they place against the most important issues on the list. The item with the highest number of stickers is ranked 1 as top priority, and the least stars is the lowest or least important item. The number of stars provided will be less than the full number of items on the list so, forcing participants to make choices. In the more traditional, and arguably more complex technique, participants will be provided with a ranking sheet, where they will be asked to select their top five ideas from the entire set of generated ideas and then rank those five ideas. The facilitator will specify that a number will be allocated to each selected item, with larger numbers reflecting greater importance (Delbecq, Van de Ven and Gustafson, 1975; McMillan *et al.*, 2014). For example, for five selected ideas, five points will be allocated to their top priority and one point to their lowest priority. Although there is no anonymity for participants during nominal group discussions, individual scoring on a ranking sheet is confidential (McMillan, King and Tully, 2016). Both approaches were considered during the pilot NGT and compared on-site in Bangladesh to determine viability in practice prior selection of the method to be used. Arguably the true ranking approach is considered the most robust. However, this is not precision science, and it is essential to find a way that is feasible in practice. This study used a ranking approach which was considered the most feasible and manageable to conduct NGT data collection using the virtual platform Zoom due to the COVID-19 restrictions in Bangladesh.

The researcher recorded and collated all the ideas in a Word file generated from the NGT meetings and shared them on the computer screen accessible to all the participants during

the online NGT discussions. This process enabled the NGT participants to see and review the data during the NGT discussions.

Following the ranking approach, the researcher asked the participants to select their top five ideas from the entire set of generated ideas and then rank those five ideas. NGT participants used the Zoom “Chat” function to share their scoring on top five priority confidentially. The researcher specified that a number would be allocated to each selected item, with larger numbers reflecting greater importance. For example, for five selected ideas, five points were allocated to their top priority and one point to their lowest priority. Next, the scores for each idea were summed, and ideas were listed in order by total scores. Finally, the five ideas with the highest scores were identified as the most important for the group.

4.5.5 Data Analysis Plan

The Nominal Group Technique results in qualitative data (recordings of discussions) and quantitative data (numerical rankings of ideas) (Mason *et al.*, 2021). The analysis of data from the Nominal Group Technique and reporting results was carried out using qualitative and quantitative methods (Potter, Gordon and Hamer, 2004). The data generated from the Nominal Group discussions were analysed using qualitative and quantitative content analysis. The content analysis uses a descriptive approach to coding the data and its interpretation of quantitative counts of the codes (Farrow *et al.*, 2020). Quantitative content analysis provides frequency counts of the type of instance of interest, while qualitative content analysis describes and illustrates findings through the integration of quotations into text (Robson, 2011). Using qualitative analysis, quotes from NGT participants were extracted from the transcripts to help explain individual and group thinking on the priorities of dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Bangladesh. This qualitative analysis also provided improved clarity and depth in the explanation of results. On the other hand, quantitative analysis of data results from the scoring and ranking methods was used to conclude the meeting process and identify group priorities of different stakeholders regarding the issues and priorities of dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Bangladesh.

4.6 Summary

This chapter presents the methods used to pursue the study plan, and ongoing decisions about the ethical application, promotion of rigour, data generation and data analysis have been justified. In the following two chapters, the findings from the study are presented, including synthesised findings of documentary policy analysis and key informant interviews and Nominal Group discussions highlighting dementia care policy success in Scotland and the transferability of dementia care policy learning from Scotland to Bangladesh.

Chapter Five: Findings of the Documentary Policy Analysis and Key Informant Interviews

5.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to critically evaluate dementia policy 'success' in Scotland. Key policy documents have been used in combination with key informant interviews with policy stakeholders to provide an informed and in-depth view of dementia policy 'success' in Scotland. The policy documents and key informant interviews data were analysed using Ritchie and Spencer's (1994) five steps framework analysis (discussed in Chapter 4). To operationalise 'success', the present study has used a modified and synthesised framework based on McConnell's (2010) and Marsh and McConnell's (2010) existing three-level frameworks for evaluating policy success to analyse the process, programme, and political level success in Scottish dementia care and workforce development policies. The synthesised framework has identified thirteen indicators of success in policy. In accordance with the synthesised framework, findings are presented under the following three major themes based: *Process Success*; *Programme Success*; and *Political Success*.

5.1.1 Evaluating Process Success

The policy-making process refers to the stages in which issues emerge and are framed, options are explored, interests are consulted, and decisions are made (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a). This is a significant aspect of evaluating the success or failure of a specific policy. Nevertheless, processes are essential in both practical and symbolic terms. Indeed, a policy which is produced through constitutional and quasi-constitutional procedures will confer a significant degree of legitimacy on policy outcomes, even when those policies are contested (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a). A key concern of policymakers is to get decisions taken, and legislation passed, using executive powers to steer the policymaking process towards such goals. These are *process* successes because the government gets the policy it wants in a legitimate manner and with the support of a coalition of interests (McConnell, 2010). This section considers process success in dementia care and workforce development policies in Scotland. The analysis is informed by five key indicators for process success, as outlined by Marsh and McConnell, namely: *preserving government policy goals and instruments*; *legitimacy in the formation of choices and passage of legislation*; *building a sustainable coalition*; *innovation and influence*; and, *opposition to process is virtually non-existent and/or*

support is virtually universal. These indicators are used within the synthesised framework to evaluate the process success.

According to Marsh and McConnell (2010), process success rests on the preservation of government's policy goals and instruments. For example, amendments to a government bill may facilitate the achievement of its goals rather than acting as a barrier (McConnell, 2010). The Scottish government has made dementia a national priority in 2007 (Scottish Government, 2010). Since 2007, dementia care has occupied a prominent position in policy rhetoric and action over a decade, with significant progress in policy documents, including national dementia strategies, Promoting Excellence Frameworks, Standards for Dementia Care and Charter of Rights for People living with Dementia and their Carers in Scotland (Alzheimer Scotland, 2009; Scottish Government, 2010; Scottish Government, 2011a; Scottish Government, 2011c; Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2015; Scottish Government, 2017b; Scottish Government, 2021b) (also discussed in Integrative Literature Review Chapter Two). In Scotland, the first national strategy for dementia was developed in 2010 after the production of the Charter of Rights for People with Dementia in 2009 'to deliver world-class dementia care and treatment in Scotland, ensuring that people living with dementia and their families are supported in the best possible way to live well with dementia' (Scottish Government, 2010, p. 11). Several factors have successfully influenced the Scottish Government and policymakers to develop the first National Dementia Care Strategy in 2010. These include the involvement of key stakeholders in the policy development process and emphasis placed on collaborative working, commitment from across political parties and public support to establish dementia as a national public health priority, and creating pressure from national dementia charities on the Scottish Government to focus on the needs of people living with dementia and their carers. Further, the formation of the Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer's and development of the Charters of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers and the Human Rights-Based Approach to Dementia-PANEL developed a foundation stone of Scottish national dementia strategies and workforce development approaches. It was a perfect storm for change in terms of important elements coming together at the same time, for example, the politics, the evidence of the problem and the influence of key stakeholders.

According to Marsh and McConnell (2010) 'programmatic' success is more likely to be achieved if the policy process involves, and reflects the interests of, a sufficiently powerful coalition of interests. From the perspective of policy-makers, putting together a strong alliance supportive of a particular policy can be construed as successful policy (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a). The documentary policy analysis and key dementia policy stakeholder interview

findings revealed that the development of the Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer's, the Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers, the Technology Charter for People Living with Dementia, national dementia strategies, the Standards of Dementia Care, and the Promoting Excellence Frameworks are based on strong collaboration and direct involvement of key stakeholders in a coordinated way to improve outcomes (Alzheimer Scotland, 2009; Scottish Government, 2010; Scottish Government, 2011a; Scottish Government, 2011c; Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2015; Scottish Government, 2017b; Scottish Government, 2021b). In this context, key dementia policy stakeholder 05 mentioned that:

'One of the keys, very early on, was to.. involve every single potential stakeholder developing and implementing strategies, in particular, directly involving people with dementia and carers...which we've done consistently, and we've actually managed to do it' (P 5, Line 213-217).

Further, key dementia policy stakeholder 02 also noted that:

'We engaged with a whole cross-sector...from individual members of the public living with dementia, carers, carers organisations...academics were involved in the consultation,..That happened every time that we've had a National Dementia Strategy' (P 2, Line 259-263).

Additionally, key dementia policy stakeholder 04 mentioned that '...another key driver in Scotland in terms of the...strategy was the involvement of partners' (P 4, Line 112-113). The Scottish Government and Alzheimer Scotland hosted a series of national dementia dialogues and consultation events since 2009 to provide an opportunity for a wide range of stakeholders to share their views and experiences in developing a national dementia strategy. A wide range of stakeholders, including health and social care workers, professional experts, representatives from the statutory and voluntary sectors and organisations working to improve dementia care, people living with dementia, their families and carers, have participated in national and local level dialogues and consultations. For example, the Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers states that:

'The Charter reflects the views of over 500 people (including people with dementia, their carers, and professionals) who took part in the widespread consultation carried out on behalf of the Cross-Party Group by Alzheimer Scotland between May-July 2009' (Alzheimer Scotland, 2009, p. 3).

Further, Alzheimer Scotland has facilitated 30 public engagement sessions across the country to gather the views and opinions of 127 people living with dementia and 171 carers to

encourage a broad discussion of individuals' experiences of dementia and their views and opinions regarding the development of the fourth National Dementia Strategy in 2023 (Alzheimer Scotland, 2022).

These national and local level dementia dialogues, consultation events, and public engagement sessions since 2009 have positively influenced the development of Scottish dementia strategies and contributed to improving liaison among the stakeholders and developing dementia-friendly and dementia-enabled communities, organisations, institutions and initiatives to improve the quality of dementia care and services (Scottish Government, 2009; Scottish Government, 2010; Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b; Scottish Government, 2021b; Scottish Government, 2023a).

The national dementia dialogues and consultation events identified a number of priorities in discussions with a wide range of key stakeholders for developing national dementia strategies. For example, the second National Dementia Strategy states that:

'The key outcomes for this Strategy, which emerged from the National Dementia Dialogue as priorities were: more people with dementia living a good quality life at home for longer, dementia-enabled and dementia-friendly local communities, that contribute to greater awareness of dementia and reduce stigma, timely, accurate diagnosis of dementia, better post-diagnostic support for people with dementia and their families, more people with dementia and their families and carers being involved as equal partners in care throughout the journey of the illness, better respect and promotion of rights in all settings, together with improved compliance with the legal requirements in respect of treatment, people with dementia in hospitals or other institutional settings always being treated with dignity and respect' (Scottish Government, 2013, p. 5).

Further, the third National Dementia Strategy states that:

'This strategy is the product of collaboration between colleagues from across health, social care and the third sector and includes direct input at every stage from people with dementia, their families and carers' (Scottish Government, 2017b, p. 5).

In addition to this, the development of Promoting Excellence Frameworks published in 2011 and 2021 have involved experts, including people living with dementia, their families and carers (Scottish Government, 2011a; Scottish Government, 2021b). The Promoting Excellence frameworks have developed based on the values and principles that people living with dementia, their families and carers have identified as most important to them (Scottish

Government, 2011a; Scottish Government, 2021b). Further, in a review of a consultation process that took place alongside the implementation of a local dementia strategy in Scotland (McCabe and Bradley, 2012) found that people with dementia were able to meaningfully contribute to the development of strategy. Including the views of people with dementia gained support for the strategy and aided its implementation (McCabe and Bradley, 2012). In this context, Alzheimer's Disease International also acknowledged that 'the [Scottish Government] is actively including people with dementia and carers in the development of policies' (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2012, p. 7). For example, the preparation of the first National Dementia Strategy document was undertaken by the Scottish Government, working with the support and engagement of a Dementia Strategy Management Group drawn from the chairs of the five workstreams and other key dementia stakeholders. Professional expertise, dementia services users and carers were represented on each of the five workstreams (Scottish Government, 2009; Scottish Government, 2010). Moreover, the Scottish Dementia Forum, chaired by the Minister for Public Health and Sport has brought together representatives from the statutory and voluntary sectors as well as people living with dementia and the people who care for them, has been created and has met regularly (Scottish Government, 2010). These findings indicate that close collaboration with a wide range of stakeholders was sought throughout the process to listen to the voices of people living with dementia, their carers and families while developing the new dementia plan and workforce development approaches. The evidence from wider literature also suggests that 'bottom-up' processes that engage stakeholders, including people living with dementia, as well as a broad range of professionals and practitioners, in meaningful dialogue about policy objectives and priorities, can result in more effective policy formation (Hare, 2020; McCabe and Bradley, 2012). For example, in relation to the development of the Fourth National Dementia Strategy, the Scottish Government has also taken a co-operative approach with the National Dementia Lived Experience Panel to collect responses received from national conversations with a wide range of professionals and practitioners, along with people living with dementia and their carers (Scottish Government, 2022). It also helped shape a shared vision between the Scottish Government and national dementia organisations where people living with dementia and their carers to have access to timely, skilled and well-coordinated support from diagnosis to end of life, which helps achieve the outcomes that matter to them (Scottish Government, 2017b; World Health Organization, 2018).

Political commitment across the political parties and public support to establish dementia care as a national public health priority reinforced the development of dementia policy in Scotland.

The development of the Charter of Rights reflected the views of people living with dementia, their carers, political parties and professionals. For example, to develop the Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers, the Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer's has brought together Members of the Scottish Parliament representing the different political parties (Alzheimer Scotland, 2009). In this context, key dementia policy stakeholder 01 noted that, 'we [the Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer's] managed to get to be...parliament group about the Procedures Committee agreed to it' (P 1, Line 104-106). Further, the Cross-Party Group has worked with organisations representing the interests of people with dementia and their carers. For example, the Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers states that:

'The group works towards ensuring high quality support, services and treatment are in place to assist people with dementia and their carers throughout Scotland. As part of this work the group has considered how to ensure that the rights of people living with dementia and their carers are fully recognised at all levels of government and by individuals and non-governmental organisations, regardless of where they are and in every part of their daily lives' (Alzheimer Scotland, 2009, p. 2).

Additionally, key dementia policy stakeholder 01 also mentioned that:

'... we [the Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer's] worked with...Scottish Human Rights Commissioner to take all these challenges that people have brought to us and barriers and said what would,...a document look like that could empower people and give them rights, and the Scottish Human Rights Commissioner, Alzheimer Scotland and myself [ALLIANCE] put together all...and it distilled all the information that we've collected from...over 1000 people from the Roadshows and turned it into a Charter of Rights' (P 1, Line 185-192).

Support from Members of the Scottish Parliament representing the different political parties has significantly contributed to forming the Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer's and approving the Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers. In this context, the Scottish Parliament notes that in 2009 the Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers was supported and signed by all political parties in the Parliament (Scottish Parliament, 2009a; Scottish Parliament, 2019). The key dementia policy stakeholder interview findings also acknowledged that all the political parties in the Scottish Parliament have worked collaboratively and expressed their support to approve the Charter of Rights. Key dementia policy stakeholder 02 stated that, 'in the Parliament,... the whole of the political spectrum in Scotland supported the Charter of Rights' (P 2, Line 192-194). Further, key dementia policy

stakeholder 01 also mentioned that 'every single political party in Parliament signed up to the Charter of Rights and that was very powerful' (P 1, Line 272-274).

However, key dementia policy stakeholders identified the lack of motivation and complexity in developing the Cross-Party Group and approving the Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers in the Scottish parliament. On this point, key dementia policy stakeholder 02 noted that:

'at that time...that was quite a difficult thing, because...the Scottish Government were planning their own Charter for Patients' Rights and they...weren't quite so supportive of the Charter of Rights [for People with Dementia and their Carers]' (P 2, Line 187-190).

However, lobbying was as an effective way to get support for the approval of the Charters of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers from the parliament members representing different political parties in the Scottish Parliament. For example, key dementia policy stakeholder 01 mentioned that 'but the thing was, we've [the Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer's] done a lot of lobbying behind the scenes...and picked all the political parties...to support...it [the Charter of Rights]' (P 1, Line 237-258).

Further, creating pressure from the different national dementia charities on the political parties and the Scottish Government to focus on the needs of people living with dementia and their carers contributed to developing a national dementia strategy. In Scotland, campaigning was orchestrated through different national dementia charity organisations to put dementia on the political manifesto into the media and public attention, fuelling impetus and then commitment to the first National Dementia Strategy.

In this context, Alzheimer Scotland has worked as a policy entrepreneur to galvanise networks among different elements to introduce the first National Dementia Strategy in Scotland. Key dementia policy stakeholders mentioned that recognising dementia care as a political priority in Scotland allowed the national charity organisations in campaigning to introduce dementia care commitment in the political party's national election manifestos. For example, key dementia policy stakeholder 02 mentioned that:

'...we [Alzheimer Scotland] as an organization had been campaigning for a National Dementia Strategy...At the same time, we [Alzheimer Scotland] had developed an election manifesto calling for a Scottish National Dementia Strategy' (P 2, 132-157).

In addition, this political recognition supports the charities constantly reminding the Scottish Government about their priorities and commitments to develop a national dementia care policy. For example, key dementia policy stakeholder also 02 pointed out that:

‘...having dementia recognizes as a political priority...is important. It allows us as a campaigning organization to continually remind the Scottish Government that this is one of their own priorities’ (P 2, Line 556-559).

Further, key dementia policy stakeholder 03 also acknowledged that:

‘the Alzheimer Scotland then took on the mantle of trying to develop an overall strategy...for Scotland and,...that coupled with the voice of the Scottish Dementia Working Group,...sort of recaptured...the minds of the Scottish Government...So, there was a lot of government support...And there's a lot of initiatives...from Alzheimer Scotland ...That then became the basis of that first strategy’ (P 3, Line 114-124)

These findings indicate that leading national dementia charity organisations have played a pivotal role in developing the foundation of the Scottish National Dementia Strategy in 2010.

In addition, the evidence shows that legislative framework and relevant provisions can play a significant role in successful policy development and implementation. The Charter of Rights has provided a legislative framework in Scotland ‘to empower people with dementia and their carers to assert their rights in every parts of their daily lives and...ensure the highest quality of service provision to people with dementia and their carers’ (Alzheimer Scotland, 2009, p. 2). Additionally, key dementia policy stakeholder 01 acknowledged that:

‘...then we [the Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer’s] wanted to make sure it [the Charter of Rights] wasn't a document that sat on a shelf. That was something...that followed on the National Dementia Strategy and then the workforce plan and then...the Standards’ (P 1, Line 259-262).

In this context, Alzheimer’s Disease International states that the Scottish national initiatives ‘treating people with dignity and respect, especially in care and health services’ (Alzheimer’s Disease International, 2012, p. 7) and ‘made distinctive recommendations to conquer negative stigma associated with dementia through research and publications’ (Alzheimer’s Disease International, 2012, p. 20). However, whilst a landmark document, there has been a gulf between the language of rights and the reality for many people living with dementia in

Scotland. For example, people living with dementia, their families, and carers are not always treated with dignity and respect and identified challenges in offering care and support to people with dementia and their families and carers to promote well-being and quality of life, protect their rights and respects their humanity. Further, there is a lack of continuity and consistency in offering timely, person-centred, coordinated and flexible dementia support services for people living with dementia, their families, and carers across various settings, including hospitals and communities (Scottish Government, 2010; Scottish Government, 2017b). Moreover, key dementia policy stakeholders mentioned that people with dementia, their family members, and carers living in the community have been facing challenges accessing different support services to ensure their rights and maintain quality of life. For example, key dementia policy stakeholder 01 noted that:

‘There are too many people who are not able to access services who have needs, just because their needs relatively speaking are not as bad as other peoples needs, so they need to access rest by, you know they need to access day care while we're in the middle of a pandemic just now [2021]. But, even when we're not in a pandemic, not everyone can access day care services, not everyone can access respite services. And, yet people are in...desperate need’ (P 1, Line 424-429).

However, the analysis found that the Charter of Rights has worked as a basis and foundation stone for developing and implementing the Scottish national dementia strategies, the Standards of Dementia Care, the Technology Charter for People Living with Dementia, and workforce development approaches since 2009 (Alzheimer Scotland, 2009; Scottish Government, 2010; Scottish Government, 2011a; Scottish Government, 2011c; Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2015; Scottish Government, 2017b; Scottish Government, 2021b). Further, the key dementia policy stakeholders mentioned that the Charter of Rights facilitated raising voices for developing a national dementia strategy in Scotland. For example, Key dementia policy stakeholder 01 pointed that:

‘...having that Charter of Rights,...I think that was quite powerful...and... it just gives ammunition to groups like Alzheimer Scotland to just really take up the fight and to argue for national dementia strategies’ (P 1, Line 270-275).

In addition, key dementia policy stakeholder 02 also acknowledged that, ‘the Charter of Rights, then became the very foundation stone of the first Dementia Strategy’ (P 2, Line 194-195). Further, key dementia policy stakeholder 04 mentioned that:

'A key driver, for Scotland's dementia strategy and then the subsequent workforce, development...was the Charter of Rights for people with dementia, families and carers...So, people living with dementia found...their voice and...identifying issues that were going wrong for them...and their aspirations, and that's really what the Charter kind of...' (P 4, Line 100-112).

Further, the documentary policy analysis found that:

'The Charter places their [people living with dementia and their carers] human and other legal rights at the centre of Scotland's National Dementia Strategies. It underpins both the Standards of Care for Dementia in Scotland and Promoting Excellence. Both are key commitments of Scotland's National Dementia Strategies to deliver the highest quality of care, treatment and support for all people with dementia in Scotland' (Ferguson, 2020, p. 20).

Therefore, the legislative framework and relevant provisions have contributed to the development of the key policy documents in Scotland in achieving policy goals related to dementia care and workforce development. For example, the Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and the Standards of Care for Dementia support to monitor and evaluate hospitals, nursing facilities, and dementia-related services and prepare a guideline for dementia treatment standards for people with dementia and their families to help them recognize and ensure their rights (Lee, 2019).

Moreover, the Scottish Parliament adopted the Human Rights-Based Approach to dementia, PANEL, in 2009 and innovative practice models and dementia services developed based on the Human Rights-Based Approach and Person-Centred Care. This PANEL approach was endorsed by the United Nations and provided a framework of Participation, Accountability, Non-discrimination, Empowerment, and Legal aspects which underpin the respect for the rights of people living with dementia and their carers (Alzheimer Scotland, 2009). The first National Dementia Strategy has emphasized a Human Rights-Based Approach to ensure high-quality, person-centred care from diagnosis to end of life (Hare, 2020). The documentary policy analysis found that the Human Rights-Based Approach guaranteed that people with dementia, their families, and caregivers have the right not to be discriminated against, and rights should be enjoyed equally (Kelly and Innes, 2016). Further, key dementia policy stakeholder 02 mentioned that:

'Human Rights-based Approach...recognizing...the rights of people living with dementia and their carers. It's about their rights as citizens and the recognition that

they have the same human and other legal rights, as everybody else' (P 2, Line 452-456).

Further, key dementia policy stakeholder 04 identified Human Rights-Based Approach and PANEL principles to create a larger movement and guide structures for meaningful stakeholder engagement in implementing dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Scotland:

'So, stakeholder partnerships pushing absolutely inclusive and meaningfully involve people with lived experience of dementia and families, and carers a Human Rights-Based Approach,...was absolutely kind of underpinning things and then. The use of PANEL principles to guide structures for meaningful stakeholders engagement,...So,...what happened with dementia strategy in Scotland a... movement was created to large extend' (P 4, Line 433-444)).

Moreover, the Scottish Parliament acknowledges that:

'...for the first time in Scotland, the PANEL approach allowed people with dementia and their carers to participate in decisions, have accountability in their care and be empowered to access their rights without stigma;...ensured that public and private bodies, voluntary organisations and individuals are held responsible for the care and treatment of people with dementia and accountable for the respect, protection and fulfilment of human rights;...the Charter in underpinning three national dementia strategies and resulting initiatives working to improve people's lives;...ensuring that the voice of lived experience sets the agenda for the next 10 years; values the efforts made by organisations across Scotland, especially the Scottish Public Services Ombudsman, to use the Charter as a tool for empowerment, raising awareness of rights and improving quality of services' (Scottish Parliament, 2019, pp. SSM-18709).

However, the importance of a Human-Rights-Based Approach appears to have dropped out in the third National Dementia Strategy. For example:

'The third Strategy is much lighter on human rights, only mentioning them in connection to inappropriate prescribing of antipsychotic medication...the strong human rights focus of the first Strategy is now being watered down. Scotland's Rights-Based Approach is justly feted, and it seems that each success fuels determination to keep moving forwards' (Hare, 2020, p. 56).

In summary, there is promising evidence that the development process of dementia care policies and workforce development was overall successful. Evidence suggests that a collaborative and Rights-Based Approach can be successful in the dementia policymaking process. Since 2009, the dementia strategies have had significant success, including the development of the Charters of the Rights and the Human Rights-Based Approach to dementia-PANEL, the Promoting Excellence Frameworks, and the Standards for Dementia Care based on direct involvement and strong collaboration with different stakeholders, including the Scottish Government, different political parties, Alzheimer Scotland, and the Scottish Dementia Working Group (SDWG) to improve the quality of life for people living with dementia and their carers. For example, consultation events have continually contributed to developing dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Scotland by emphasising the voice of lived experience. Direct involvement and active participation of a wide range of stakeholders in consultation events enabled a broad discussion of individuals' experiences of dementia and their views and opinions on the future of dementia care policy and workforce development approach since the first National Dementia Strategy in Scotland. In addition, consultation events enabled quieter and hidden voices to be heard in the conversation as opinions and views were also sought in the way the participants choose, either in written or in the form of audio and video clips. Online participation was also encouraged (Scottish Government, 2022). Although, the National Dementia Lived Experience Panel is formed to develop and implement the fourth National Dementia Strategy, voices of people living with advanced dementia may not be heard (Scottish Government, 2023a; Scottish Government, 2023b). Further, these consultation events have created opportunities for the stakeholder groups, i.e., SDWG and National Dementia Carers Action Network (NDCAN), to let the Scottish Government know what has worked well in dementia care policy and workforce development approach for people living with dementia and their families and carers and, perhaps more importantly, what needs to be improved in future dementia care policy and services. Based on the analysis of the policy development process in Scotland, other countries like Bangladesh, who are yet to establish dementia policies and service infrastructure, can potentially learn from the Scottish experience. These include rooting dementia reforms in the language of human rights, establishing rights-based charters to grant legitimacy and build support for policy reform, establishing political and public support and building sustainable collaboration and involving different stakeholders in developing and implementing national dementia strategies and workforce development approaches. The programme success of dementia care policies and workforce development is discussed next.

5.1.2 Evaluating Programme Success

Programmatic success is often seen as synonymous with policy success because programmes of actions are often the instruments of policy implementation (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a). Programmatic success relates to the effectiveness, efficiency and resilience of implementing policy goals. These are the standard reference points to assess the programme success of a policy (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a). Program success occurs if the measure that government adopts, including a stance of doing nothing, produces the results desired by government (McConnell, 2010). For example, effectiveness in the delivery of services and efficient use of resources is considered a programme success of public policies (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a). This section considers programme success in dementia care and workforce development policies in Scotland. The analysis is informed by five primary indicators of programme success, as outlined by Marsh and McConnell, namely: *implementation policies in line with objectives; achievement of desired outcomes; efficient use of resources; creating benefit for a target group; and, opposition to program aims, values, and means of achieving them is virtually non-existent, and/or support is virtually universal*. These indicators are used within the synthesised framework to evaluate the programme success.

Operational success occurs if a policy is implemented according to objectives laid down when it was approved. Successful programme implementation can be considered policy success, even (and perhaps especially) in complex systems of governance (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a). The major objectives of the Scottish national dementia strategies and workforce development approaches can be summarised as follows: more timely diagnosis and better care and treatment, improved post-diagnostic support, more integrated and person-centred support, improved end-of-life and palliative care and increased workforce development and capability (Alzheimer Scotland, 2009; Scottish Government, 2010; Scottish Government, 2011a; Scottish Government, 2011c; Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2015; Scottish Government, 2017b; Scottish Government, 2021b).

The documentary policy analysis and key policy stakeholder interviews suggest that although progress was made in diagnosis rates, post-diagnostic support, and improving the experience of people living with dementia and their families and carers in hospitals and other settings since 2010, there are gaps in the implementation of dementia care policies, and workforce development approaches in line with the objectives of Scottish dementia policies (Scottish

Government, 2017b; Scottish Government, 2021b). In this context, the third National Dementia Strategy noted that:

‘...despite this progress much more remains to be done. The gap between the policy commitments found in all three strategies and the real life experience of many people is far too wide’ (Scottish Government, 2017b, p. 2).

Further, key dementia policy stakeholder 02 also acknowledged that:

‘... there is a big difference between the policy intention and the commitments of the National Dementia Strategy and how they are delivered locally for people living with dementia and carers. So, for example,...the First National Dementia Strategy had two priorities. One was around improving the experience of people with dementia and acute hospital care. The workaround...still not fully achieved though’ (P 2, Line 333-340).

Similarly, key dementia policy stakeholder 01 highlighted the inconsistencies in policy goals and implementation and mentioned that ‘the problem has always been that gap between policy and implementation, and that’s always a challenge’ (P 1, Line 264-265). Additionally, key dementia policy stakeholder 04 noted that:

‘so,...the barriers are often quite systematic and complex...to transform an entire health and social care system...to improve experiences and outcomes for people with dementia, when... the system...don’t work smoothly’ (P 4, Line 235-239).

These findings indicate that the implementation of dementia care programmes was not as good as the policy intentions. In this context, this section critically discusses the major programme successes along with gaps in developing and implementing the Promoting Excellence Frameworks for workforce development in health and social care sectors, innovative practices of the Five Pillar Model, Eight Pillar Model and Advanced Dementia Practice Model, and delivering major services including dementia diagnosis, post-diagnosis support guarantee, and end-of-life and palliative care.

The documentary policy analysis and key policy stakeholder interviews suggest that the Promoting Excellence Framework enabled the attainment of dementia policy success in terms of developing the necessary skills and knowledge of health and social care workers and creating a significant positive impact on the life of people living with dementia, their families and carers. However, comprehensive research-based evidence and evaluation are absent about the role of the Promoting Excellence Framework in dementia workforce development. The Promoting Excellence Framework 2011 was seen as ground-breaking as Scotland’s first

national workforce development framework. It set high aims for the care and support of people living with dementia, their families and carers. The Framework reflects the actions, priorities and commitments of the national dementia strategies and ongoing national activity on dementia (Scottish Government, 2011a). The Framework is set out in four different levels of skill and knowledge, including dementia-informed practice level, dementia skilled practice level, enhanced dementia practice level, and expertise in dementia practice level. Each level sets the specific knowledge and skills specific staff need based on their role rather than their position in the organisation or their profession (Scottish Government, 2011b; Scottish Government, 2021b). The documentary analysis found that the NHS Education for Scotland (NES) and the Scottish Social Services Council (SSSC) have been active since 2011 in supporting the four framework levels in practice, including developing core educational resources and training programmes; and developing leaders and infrastructures to support implementation (Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b). For example, since 2011, the Promoting Excellence workforce skills and development programme has provided training programmes for health and social services workers in psychological interventions for people with dementia and their families and carers in cognitive stimulation therapy, managing stress and distress and acceptance and commitment therapy. Further, training for trainers in palliative care for people with dementia and a post-diagnostic support training programme has been developed and delivered for the Link Workers. In addition, Promoting Excellence has also been embedded in pre-registration nursing programmes (Scottish Government, 2011b; Scottish Government, 2012; Scottish Government, 2017b). Moreover, third National Dementia Strategy mentioned that a large suite of accessible educational resources has developed, 'which has been used by tens of thousands of staff across health and social services' (Scottish Government, 2017b, p. 7). These initiatives have made significant positive changes in the health and social care settings to respond to the needs of people with dementia, their families, and carers in different health and social care settings and communities. These include providing post-diagnostic support, advanced dementia care and end-of-life care (Scottish Government, 2011b; Scottish Government, 2012; Scottish Government, 2017b).

Moreover, dementia friendly communities have designed Dementia Care Training Programme based on the Promoting Excellence Framework for key staff, junior leaders and school volunteers to develop a good understanding about dementia and emphasise the importance and privilege of caregiving. Dementia Friendly Communities provides learning about positive relationships, mentoring and training for workforce development to improve dementia friendly practice across Scotland, and similar initiatives that support the empowerment of those affected by dementia (Life Changes Trust, 2015). Additionally, Alzheimer Scotland Dementia

Nurse Consultants and Dementia Champions have participated in training to improve their capacity and capability in line with the skills framework set out in Promoting Excellence Framework (Scottish Government, 2011a; Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b). An evaluation report on the impact of the Alzheimer Scotland Dementia Nurse Consultants/Specialists and Dementia Champions found that Dementia Champions have been effective and active in taking forward a wide range of changes and improvements within their own services and the wider Social Services. For example, implementing Promoting Excellence; influencing staff attitudes and practices towards people with dementia; improving the environment; delivery of person-centred care and involvement (Ellison, Watt and Christie, 2014). Further, the Framework contributed to improve the Standards of Care for Dementia in Scotland. As this, key dementia policy stakeholder 05 noted that:

‘Our national...dementia skills programme...was designed specifically to implement the standard...to help improve the standards...that was...something in the first strategy around developing a national framework around standards and workforce’ (P 5, Line 227-230).

Moreover, in Scotland, the Scottish Government and national charities collaboratively developed evidence-based, innovative practice models to improve the quality of life of people living with dementia and their carers and enable more people to live safely and comfortably in their communities and homes with their families for longer. These include Alzheimer Scotland’s Five Pillars Model, Eight Pillars Model, and Advanced Dementia Practice Model (Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b). In Scotland, everyone newly diagnosed with dementia is entitled to be offered, at minimum, a year’s worth of post-diagnostic support coordinated by an appropriately trained Link Worker. Link Workers are trained based on Promoting Excellence Framework and work with health and social care partnerships to deliver high-quality post-diagnostic support using Alzheimer Scotland’s Five Pillars Model (Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b) (Please see Figure 5.1).

Figure 5. 1: Alzheimer Scotland's 5 Pillars Model of Post-Diagnostic Support

This model has been suggested as a useful model for post-diagnostic support for people living with dementia, their families and carers (Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b). For example, key dementia policy stakeholder 03 mentioned that:

'The one of the key facilitators...was the fact that...the message was really fairly simple. The key message about the Five Pillars Framework enabled staff across the disciplines that would involve focussing the mind on those Five headings...and recognise that the like how you might plan for the future? how you would support social connections? how you would teach people about managing their underlying illness and peer support? that sort of thing...these were messages which were commonly...echoed across the country so that everyone focused on these particular things and...that...was a great strength of the strategy' (P 3, Line 335-343).

The documentary policy analysis also found that the post-Diagnostic support guarantee by the Scottish Government is considered world-leading and, to date, is the only national Post-Diagnostic guarantee of its kind. The Five Pillar Model uses person-centred planning to put the person, not the illness, at the centre of the support. This model supports people living with

dementia to understand their illness, build resilience and develop their abilities and strengths to live well with dementia and maintain independence for as long as possible. Moreover, this high-quality post-diagnostic support can delay admission to residential care, hospital, and other costly health and social care services (Alzheimer’s Disease International, 2022).

On the other hand, the analysis found that Alzheimer Scotland’s Eight Pillars Model of Integrated Community Support provides a useful platform for coordinated care to support people with dementia living at home during the moderate to severe stages of the illness (Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b) (Please see Figure 5.2 below).

Figure 5. 2: Alzheimer Scotland’s 8 Pillars Model of Integrated Community Support

The approach centres around a Dementia Practice Coordinator who provides tailored post-diagnostic support while simultaneously increasing the level and focus of integrated care coordination. The primary responsibility of the Dementia Practice Coordinator is the direction and management of care based on Alzheimer Scotland’s Advanced Dementia Practice Model (Blake Stevenson Ltd., 2017; Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b). Moreover, Alzheimer Scotland’s Advanced Dementia Practice Model combines the skill and understanding of the existing Eight Pillars team, particularly the Dementia Practice

Coordinator, to provide optimum care to support the person with dementia to die in their place of choice and to support those closest to the person through the bereavement process (Alzheimer Scotland, 2015; Scottish Government, 2017b) (Please see Figure 5.3 below).

Figure 5. 3: Alzheimer Scotland’s Advanced Dementia Practice Model

The Advanced Dementia Practice Model provides Health and Social Care Partnerships with a blueprint for delivering integrated dementia care and honours the right to personhood, full citizenship, and optimum participation in society for people living with advanced illness and at the end of life with dementia (Alzheimer Scotland, 2015). However, the analysis found that support for people living with advanced dementia is currently inconsistent in quality and availability. Because the Advanced Dementia Practice Model is often based on a poor understanding of what people living with advanced dementia actually experience and need (Alzheimer Scotland, 2015). Further, an independent evaluation report highlighted the need to develop skills and competencies for the Dementia Practice Coordinator around therapeutic

interventions to provide better-integrated care and support. In addition, the evaluation report identified challenges in ensuring continuity of care and adopting preventative approaches. Also, the report recognised limitations in embedding interdisciplinary approaches and co-location of service (Blake Stevenson Ltd., 2017; Scottish Government, 2017b).

Although, the analysis found that the Scottish Government has developed a transformational approach to diagnosis, post-diagnostic support, palliative and end-of-life care, integrated care, general health care and dementia-friendly communities, recognised internationally as an example of best practice. However, there are significant gaps in delivering dementia care services, including a lack of harmonised ways of dementia diagnosis, gaps in practice and commitment to post-diagnostic support guarantee, insufficient end-of-life care for people living with dementia, an absence of a robust evaluation, a lack of coordination and integration in health boards and local authority, an absence of direct funding and staff for programme implementation, and lack of accountability in integrating the health and social care system for providing dementia care services and treatment.

The National Dementia Strategy recognises that diagnosis is important as it is a gateway to effective care and support. Since 2007 the NHS in Scotland has worked to increase the number of people who have a diagnosis of dementia (Fortinsky and Downs, 2014; Scottish Government, 2011b). However, the documentary policy analysis identified challenges related to the delivery of early and timely diagnosis. For example, the third National Dementia Strategy notes that:

‘We [The Scottish Government]...accept that there are still challenges around earlier diagnoses, especially in those cases where a definitive diagnosis is harder for a clinician to make in the earlier stages of the illness’ (Scottish Government, 2017b, p. 11).

Further, there was an underestimation of the rate of diagnosis of dementia in Scotland. It was thought that the initial dementia diagnosis rate was likely to have been underestimated by approximately 50% (Scottish Government, 2016). Although, currently sufficient centres are working to make a diagnosis of dementia in Scotland. However, key dementia policy stakeholders opined that due to the lack of harmonised ways of dementia diagnosis, different approaches had been used in memory assessment around the country. Key dementia policy stakeholder 03 mentioned that:

‘...at the moment...82 centres...are doing memory assessments with a view to making a diagnosis. Now my anticipation is that each of those 82 are probably doing something different to come to the diagnosis’ (P 3, Line 386-389).

These findings indicate that the diagnosis process still needs to be more consistent and needs further initiatives to improve the early and timely diagnosis.

Further, improving post-diagnostic information and support has been a key service delivery area of the Scottish Government's National Dementia Strategies since 2010 (Fortinsky and Downs, 2014; Scottish Government, 2010; Scottish Government, 2016). Although, the Scottish government has emphasised strengthening integrated and person-centred support and established National Local Delivery Plan (LDP) standard to monitor the delivery of post-diagnostic support guarantee effectively (Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b). However, in 2019-20, only 42.9 % of newly diagnosed with dementia were referred for post-diagnostic support, and 81.3% received a minimum of one year's support (Public Health Scotland, 2022). Moreover, key dementia policy stakeholders also mentioned that this post-diagnostic support has failed to provide the needed service for all people diagnosed with dementia in line with the government's commitments. On this point, key dementia policy stakeholder 02 mentioned that,

'the Scottish Government introduced a national post-diagnosis support guarantee... in 2012 and...the commitment began...in 2013...even eight years later, along we've got that national guarantee, fewer than half of the people who should be offered that are being offered it' (P 2, Line 371-377).

The study findings indicate that the government's political commitment to improve post-diagnostic support has experienced a significant variation between policy and practice. The analysis found that targets of post-diagnostic support were too ambitious, and there was not enough support and coordination in place to fully realise them. For example, the lack of coordination between Health Boards and local authorities and the lack of accountability in integrating the health and social care system created challenges to providing post-diagnostic support for all people diagnosed with dementia and achieving government targets. Further, there was an absence of dedicated funding and direct staff for implementing the national dementia care policy (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2022; Public Health Scotland, 2022).

In addition, the Scottish Dementia Strategies and the Standards of Care for Dementia emphasised to ensure good quality palliative and end-of-life care for people with dementia regardless of setting or diagnosis and strengthening community care (Scottish Government,

2013; Scottish Government, 2017b). Further, the Standards of Care for Dementia in Scotland set out requirements on NHS Boards, local authorities and other care providers to ensure that palliative and specialist palliative care is provided in a variety of settings (Scottish Government, 2011c). However, just 20% of those with frailty or dementia had been formally identified as requiring palliative care, compared to 75% of those with cancer (Zheng *et al.*, 2013). Although the Standards of Care for Dementia in Scotland and accompanying framework outline the right to end-of-life care and the need for necessary skills and knowledge of health and social care staff for supporting people with dementia nearing the end of life, however, there has been little assessment or audit carried out against some of these standards. This has made it difficult to understand what progress is being made in Scotland in end-of-life care for people living with dementia; beyond that, the vast majority of dementia patients are not accessing palliative care (Marie Curie Cancer Care, 2015).

The analysis found that the Scottish Government is committed to establishing a national policy governance structure with a broad-based group including service users and carers as well as Integration Authorities for monitoring and implementing the national dementia strategy and improving major dementia services, including post-diagnostic support (Scottish Government, 2017b; Scottish Government, 2021a). However, key dementia policy stakeholders identified lack of robust evaluation and complexity to assess the overall progress and effectiveness of Scottish dementia strategies. As this, key dementia policy stakeholder 04 pointed out,

'I think,...there hasn't been any robust evaluation...taken forward,...So, I'm certainly not seeing they are taking any evaluation, I think, the point I was trying to make was evaluation is complex' (P 4, Line 342-349).

Further, there is a lack of appropriate reporting on delivering intensive social care packages and dementia support services provided by the local partnership. Although the local government has been offering a whole range of different services for people with dementia and other health conditions, it is not adequately reported, which has created challenges in evaluating the actual performance of dementia services. On this point, key dementia policy stakeholder 05 explained that:

'...a lot of local services are delivering intensive social care packages to people who haven't had dementia and other health conditions. They are getting diagnosed with dementia after they already have the social care package in place. So, the dementia support is being offered, but it's not getting reported. Because. I think,...that people get a whole range of different services...and, dementia is just part of that obviously. So, I

think that's difficult to untangle that when we...try to manage performance. So that's a big challenge' (P-5, Line 311-318).

Moreover, key dementia policy stakeholders identified a lack of integration in health and social care partnerships and the absence of direct funding and staff for dementia care as the significant barrier to ensuring the post-diagnostic support guarantee and implementing the dementia strategy on the ground level to deliver quality services for people living with dementia and their carers. Key dementia policy stakeholder 02 explained:

'Although the Scottish Government...have a national guarantee around post diagnostic support, the delivery of that guarantee is not the Scottish Government, but the health and social care partnerships. And that's the barriers that we exist, so, although we have a national guarantee that decisions are taken locally, if they're not prioritised, then they're not putting funding towards those areas, and that often is the barrier. They.. don't have sufficient funding from the National Government to implement this...so we have a patchwork cloak...of delivery. And I think, post-diagnosis was a good example because...that is the biggest barrier for implementation' (P 2, Line 391-399).

Similarly, key dementia policy stakeholder 05 acknowledged that,

'Our budget on dementia is relatively small because we're not actually funding any, we're not directly funding the frontline services that they come out of overall allocations to health and social care partnerships. Our budget is relatively small and has been for a number of years' (P 5, Line 157-159).

Further, key dementia policy stakeholder 05 also pointed out that although, 'there are lots of other people who work on dementia, they are not part of dementia team as well' (P 5, Line 154-155). Additionally, key dementia policy stakeholder 04 mentioned that ' so there's always going to be an hidden barriers, and translate from policy to practice in a system that's pressured...and faces financial challenges and stuff like that' (P 4, Line 216-219).

In addition, there appears to be gaps and a lack of accountability in integrating health and social care systems for providing dementia care services and treatment. The integration of health and social care has been a priority for the government since the second term of the Scottish National Party (Sturgeon, 2011). The Public Bodies (Joint Working) (Scotland) Act

2014 provided a legal framework for integrating health and social care provision (Scottish Parliament, 2014) The integration of health and social care in Scotland is designed to enable more older people with multiple conditions, including people living with dementia, to stay living well in their own homes for longer and retain an active part in their communities as far as possible (Scottish Government, 2019). Further, the integration has provided an opportunity to create a structured, coordinated and strategic approach to community support for people living with dementia in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2017a). However, health and social care integration has been challenging in Scotland due to fundamental institutional and cultural issues that need to be addressed locally within Health and Social Care Partnership (HSCP) areas (Connolly et al., 2020). Further, Key dementia policy stakeholders noted that there is no cohesion between national dementia strategy and local priority. As this, key dementia policy stakeholder 02 noted that:

‘So, you have a National Dementia Strategy, and then you have some Health and Social Care Partnerships who developed their own local strategy, and it has no resemblance,...no cohesion between...them’ (P 2, Line 678-680).

Further, key dementia policy stakeholder 04 mentioned that ‘multiple policy and initiatives...aren't often joined together’ (P 4, Line 231). Moreover, key dementia policy stakeholder 05 identified a lack of accountability and legal requirements for the local authorities to implement a national dementia strategy. ‘There's no legal requirement for Local partnerships to report back on what they're doing to Ministers...that means there's no obligation for local areas to adopt a national strategy locally’ (P-5, Line 201-204).

These findings indicate that local strategies do not always align with national policy. Therefore, local authorities need to learn about compelling local implementation and compliance with national policy. Although this may seem odd, it shows the unintentional consequences of the integration agenda in Scotland.

Overall, it appears that the implementation of the dementia programme has met with some success, but has not been entirely successful. The Scottish Government has developed and implemented various evidence-based policies and seemingly world-leading practice models of dementia care. The study found that significant progress has been made with the diagnosis, Post-Diagnostic Support, Integrated Health and Social Care, Standards of Dementia Care, and Promoting Excellence Frameworks. However, there are several barriers, including lack of timely and appropriate diagnosis, lack of timely access to good quality post-diagnostic support, poor access to palliative care, insufficient funding, lack of end-of-life care services for people

with dementia responsive to individual needs, and inconsistency in providing available support to every person living with dementia and their careers. The analysis identified a number of policy learning for dementia policymakers, health and social care practitioners, and other countries to develop a successful programme in national dementia care and workforce development policy and reform existing dementia policy. These include ensuring dedicated funding and developing skilled and competent health and social care professionals to follow ambitious and innovative practice models and new service provisions. Further, there is a need to develop clear lines of responsibility and accountability among the health and social care sectors and local and national authorities to implement these ambitious new programmes.

5.1.3 Evaluating Political Success

Political success is the 'holy grail of political elites' (McConnell, 2010, p. 353). Political success is the final benchmark for policy success (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a). Policy can be framed as successful because of an assumption that it has positive political impact. These include enhancing the government's reputation and the popularity of political leaders amongst voters, which translates into direct support during elections. Therefore, opinion polls, election results and media commentary, can all be marshalled as evidence that a particular policy initiative was successful in boosting the fortunes of government, governing parties and their programmes (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a; McConnell, 2010). Dementia and dementia care have historically occupied a low position on the political agenda, and there has been little government policy on caring for people living with dementia (Sassi and McDaid, 1999). However, dementia care as a political agenda can contribute for the future welfare and benefit of people living with dementia and their carers (Innes, 2002). Scotland's population is ageing, and higher proportions of older people tend to participate in political elections compared with younger adults (e.g. 18-21-year-olds) (Scottish Parliament, 2007; Scottish Parliament, 2011; Scottish Parliament, 2016; Scottish Parliament, 2021). This section considers political success in the Scottish Government's advancement of dementia care and workforce development policies in Scotland. The analysis is informed by three key indicators for political success, as outlined by Marsh and McConnell, namely: *government popularity; sustaining the broad values and direction of government;* and, *opposition to political benefits for government is virtually non-existent and/or support is virtually universal.* These indicators are used within the synthesised framework to evaluate the political success.

Several factors have influenced the political success of developing and implementing national dementia strategies and workforce development approaches in Scotland. These include a lack of political opposition to the Scottish National Party's national priority on dementia at the outset, dementia care policies gained popularity among the general public and people living with dementia, their families and carers, and recognition of the world-leading dementia practice approaches. However, the analysis identified gaps in the Scottish Government's delivery of dementia health and social care services, growing criticisms and disagreement with the SNP's government plan to reform social care services.

Care for older people and people living with dementia has been established as an issue high on the public and political agenda for the Scottish Government and major political parties in Scotland since 2007. The Scottish Government's commitment and political recognition of dementia as a national public health priority in 2007 contributed to developing a National Dementia Strategy in Scotland in 2010. For example, the Scottish National Party's 2007 election Manifesto committed that 'an SNP government will ensure dementia is a national priority... to increase public understanding and help people reduce their risk of dementia' (The Scottish National Party, 2007, p. 40). Further, the Scottish Green Party's 2007 Manifesto notes that 'we [the Scottish Green Party] will provide appropriate care and support for those with dementia and their carers' (The Scottish Green Party, 2007, p. 11). In addition, the key dementia policy stakeholder interviews also found that all the political parties were committed to improving dementia care in Scotland. In this context, key dementia policy stakeholder 03 stated that, 'I think that...none of the political parties was against the thought that...people with dementia needed better services' (P 3, Line 152-154). However, the Scottish National Party's political commitment to making dementia 'a national priority' has played a significant role in developing a National Dementia Strategy and improving dementia care services for the people living with dementia, their families, and carers in Scotland. Key dementia policy stakeholder 02 mentioned that:

'in 2007, the current...Scottish National Party [SNP]...was elected to government...and one of their first actions was to make dementia a national public health priority. That again was an enabling factor because they had committed to recognising dementia...as a health priority within Scotland' (P 2, Line 134-138) and 'they [SNP] created some of the conditions which enabled that first Dementia Strategy to come' (P 2. Line 199-200).

Moreover, key dementia policy stakeholder 05 acknowledged that, 'for as long as the SNP is in power there has been a lot of consensus around dementia politically' (P 5, Line 122-123). However, a proposed amendment to Scotland's first National Dementia Strategy, from

Scottish Labour, that sought 'to ensure that sufficient resources are made available to support the Scottish strategy' was narrowly voted down in the Scottish Parliament (Scottish Parliament, 2009b). This shows that the lack of consensus among the different political parties in relation to the allocation of funding for the dementia strategy has negatively impacted on implementing and delivering health and social care services for the people living with dementia and their carers in Scotland.

The analysis found that the SNP government has gained popularity among the general public, older people, people living with dementia, their families and carers in developing and implementing dementia care policies in Scotland. In particular, from the perspective of government and the governing party, a policy may be successful if it assists their electoral prospects, reputation or overall governance project (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a). A 'successful' policy may also help rescue the party or government from low popularity or help consolidate a lead in opinion polls. It may also apply to a policy which helps pave the way for a national election campaign (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a). In 2007, the first time any political party in Scotland highlighted the dementia care issue appropriately in an election manifesto (The Scottish National Party, 2007). Since 2007, the Scottish National Party (SNP) has continuously been elected in the Scottish Government and gained significant public support (Scottish Parliament, 2007; Scottish Parliament, 2011; Scottish Parliament, 2016; Scottish Parliament, 2021). The Scottish Government has made significant progress in implementing National Dementia Care Strategies since 2010 and has contributed to the early detection, improved care pathways and awareness of dementia (Lee, 2019; Scottish Government, 2011b; Scottish Government, 2017b). Further, key dementia policy stakeholder 03 mentioned that:

'at that time [First SNP Government] ...Health Secretary...certainly was very aware that people with dementia were disadvantaged and made it her mission to try to improve the lot of people with dementia' (P 3, Line 118-122).

As a result, the SNP Government established positive and impactful consequences among the Scottish people for providing health and social care services for older people and developing and implementing national dementia strategies for people living with dementia, their families, and carers in Scotland. For example, the SNP 2021 Manifesto acknowledged that:

'The SNP has a proud record of supporting Scotland's older people while in government. From providing record health spending to free personal care, supporting

older people to work and tackling loneliness we've worked hard to make Scotland the best place to grow old' (The Scottish National Party, 2021, p. 58).

Therefore, it can be assumed that the continuity of policy-making in dementia care has boosted SNP legitimacy and has been a factor for the SNP's remaining in power continuously since 2007 (Scottish Parliament, 2007; Scottish Parliament, 2011; Scottish Parliament, 2016; Scottish Parliament, 2021). Further, the continuity of policy-making in dementia care may have helped to secure 'the grey vote' for the SNP in Scotland. Moreover, this consistency with dementia care policy may have also convinced the Scottish public that the NHS is safe in the SNP's hands.

Following the continuous political success of the SNP government related to prioritising dementia care in the national public health policy since 2007, other political parties also started to include the commitment to improve dementia care services for people living with dementia, their families, and carers in different national election manifestos to access the political benefit. For example, the Scottish Labour Party's included the dementia care in their 2011 election Manifesto and committed that:

'We [the Scottish Labour Party]...aim to expand the provision of services for those with dementia and Alzheimer's, to improve the management of these patients in acute hospital settings and to ensure that every area of the country has access to improved services' (The Scottish Labour Party, 2011, p. 43).

On the other hand, the Scottish Conservative and Unionist Party's 2021 election Manifesto states that:

'We [the Scottish Conservative and Unionist Party] would review the expansion of post-diagnostic support and ensure everyone with advanced dementia receives an individual assessment of their health and care needs. We [the Scottish Conservative and Unionist Party] would also review what changes are required to ensure personal and nursing care payments sufficiently cover the cost of care. We [the Scottish Conservative and Unionist Party] would increase investment in dementia research and work to raise awareness. We [the Scottish Conservative and Unionist Party] would develop a new national plan for palliative care to ensure everyone can access the support they need whether they die in hospital, a hospice, a care home or at home' (The Scottish Conservative and Unionist Party, 2021, p. 36).

Such political commitment from the Scottish Conservative and Unionist Party's national election manifesto in 2021 suggests that though dementia care has always been at the heart of the political agenda for the Scottish Government since 2007, Scottish Policy and Strategy remained weak on research and evaluation both as methods to support policy and to drive actions towards the success of policy.

Further, Scotland has been recognised for developing and implementing 'world-leading' innovative dementia practice approaches to improve the quality of life for people living with dementia and their carers. Since the development of the first National Dementia Strategy in Scotland, the wider dementia care and workforce development approaches have shifted and progressed. In this context, the third National Dementia Strategy states that:

'Over the last decade [2007-2017], dementia services have been transformed, with excellent contributions from staff working across health and social care, the public, third and independent sectors. Scotland can feel proud of its work on dementia, which is considered leading in the world' (Scottish Government, 2017b, p. 1).

Further, the 2021 Promoting Excellence Framework also acknowledged that:

'the wider national policy context has changed and progressed since 2011, including the integration of health and social care, the roll out of self-directed support and the legislation which expands support and entitlements for carers' (Scottish Government, 2021b, p. 2).

The key dementia policy stakeholders also identified significant progress, including progressive dementia policy landscape, moving away from primarily medical model care and improved post-diagnostic support in developing and implementing national dementia care policies and workforce development approaches. At this point, key dementia policy stakeholder 05 claimed, 'Scotland is recognised as being quite progressive, cause we've moved away from a primarily medical model care' (P 5, Line 332-334). Further, another key dementia policy stakeholder also acknowledged that 'there's a lot of progress in that. Post Diagnosis Support is a really good example' (P 2, Line 346-347). This global recognition for developing and implementing progressive and innovative dementia care policy has contributed to the SNP's aim of being an independent and competent government. For example, the SNP's 2021 Manifesto noted that:

'Scotland is a welcoming, outward-looking and inclusive nation. Our relationships with international community benefit trade, investment, travel, education, and knowledge

exchange. They and help promote our values, such as human rights, and are crucial in the fight against global challenges...We believe we have a strong role to play, through both action and leadership- on the world stage now, and as a full independent country soon' (The Scottish National Party, 2021, p. 71).

Although, the progressive development of dementia care services and world-leading achievement of developing innovative approaches to the Scottish dementia policies has made political success for the SNP Government. However, the documentary analysis found growing criticisms of the SNP government in delivering health and social care services for older people and people living with dementia and their carers in Scotland. For example, the Scottish Liberal Democrat Party's 2011 election Manifesto noted that:

'the health service faces enormous challenges for the future, most of all from the growing population of elderly people and the extra health care they need...Scotland has a growing, ageing population and it is in everyone's interest to make sure that resources are used to the maximum and new ways are found to help people who need care' (The Scottish Liberal Democrats Party, 2011, pp. 60-64).

Further, the Scottish Labour Party identified challenges related to the accessibility of social care services for people living with advanced dementia and proposed to provide social care services free and address the disparity between health and social care services. The Labour Manifesto 2021 also notes that:

'in recent years the eligibility for social care has reduced and many individuals, particularly those living with care needs linked to deteriorating health conditions such as advanced dementia, have either had to pay to get all the care they need, or gone without because they cannot afford it' (The Scottish Labour Party, 2021, p. 57).

Further, the Scottish Conservative and Unionist Party criticised the SNP government existing public health services. The Scottish Conservative and Unionist Party's 2021 election Manifesto notes that 'under the SNP, Scotland has become the 'sick man of Europe' with poor public health outcomes and stark health inequalities which have left too many people vulnerable to COVID-19' (The Scottish Conservative and Unionist Party, 2021, p. 35).

Further, the analysis identified opposition to the SNP government reform plan in Social Care Services in Scotland. For example, in the 2021 election manifesto, the Scottish National Party acknowledged that the importance of social care services has never been more evident in Scotland and committed to establishing the National Care Services in Scotland based on the recommendations of the independent Feeley review-2021 in the next parliamentary term

(Scottish Government, 2021a; The Scottish National Party, 2021). However, other major political parties have expressed a different opinion regarding the SNP's proposal to establish the National Care Services in Scotland. Evidence suggests that the dominance of dementia care and the care of older people, which the SNP has enjoyed since 2007, is starting to fade. For example, the Scottish Labour Party states that:

'We [the Scottish labour Party] do not believe that huge structural change is necessary or desirable; we [the Scottish labour Party] want to devolve power to local people, not centralise. Instead, we [the Scottish labour Party] will create National Care Contracts to set the framework for social care services-promoting greater consistency and raising minimum standards' (The Scottish Labour Party, 2021, p. 57).

Further, the Scottish Liberal Democrats Party's 2021 election Manifesto states that:

'We [the Scottish Liberal Democrats Party] do not support the creation of a National Care Service...because we [the Scottish Liberal Democrats Party] are concerned that this risks losing local innovation and skills' (The Scottish Liberal Democrates Party, 2021, p. 15).

Moreover, the Scottish Conservative and Unionist Party also disagreed with the unnecessary structural reforms in social care services and mentioned that:

'Action is required to address the historic underfunding of the sector and ensure it is prepared to care for Scotland's ageing population...However,..We [the Scottish Conservative and Unionist Party] would maintain local democratic accountability of the social care system and avoid any unnecessary structural reforms' (The Scottish Conservative and Unionist Party, 2021, p. 36).

To summarise, the analysis of political success shows that recognised dementia as a national public health priority supports the SNP government to gain political success and increased popularity among the voters to remain in power. However, the other political parties also highlighted their contributions and commitment to older people and dementia care in Scotland. In addition, they identified the SNP government's overall drawbacks related to the well-being of older people and dementia care. The analysis explored significant political success factors as a policy learning for the other government, political parties, and policy makers based on the analysis of Scottish dementia care and workforce development policy. For example, developing and implementing ambitious and innovative reform programmes in dementia care policy and workforce development approaches increase popularity among the voters in ageing counties, like the UK, and enhances re-election prospects. Further, innovative, and bold

reforms can boost the standing or status of countries on the international stage in dementia care policy. Moreover, other political parties encourage likely to follow suit and want to build on, rather than scrap, the reforms the party in power has put in place. A critical evaluation of the overall success of dementia care policy is discussed next.

5.2 Summary of Dementia Care Policy Success in Scotland, and Tentative Recommendations to Policy Development in Bangladesh

This section summarises the overall success and limitations of Scotland's National dementia care strategies and workforce development approaches based on the findings and analysis of the documentary policy analysis and key dementia policy stakeholder interviews. These are significant findings in learning about what has yet to work so well for addressing the gaps between policy and actions. For example, a specific policy may have a process and political success, but programmatic success might not be quite rosy. Finally, this section offers some tentative recommendations and policy learning about dementia care policy development in Bangladesh.

5.2.1 Summary of Dementia Care Policy Success in Scotland

The summary of dementia care policy success is structured under three major themes based: Process Success; Programme Success; and Political Success based on the synthesised Policy Success Framework.

5.2.1.1 Process Success

National-level dementia consultation events and dialogues with a wide range of stakeholders contributed to generating input and support from 'the bottom-up' in developing, updating, and improving dementia policy in Scotland. Additionally, human connection and direct involvement of people living with dementia and their carers create a larger movement supporting to development and implementation of dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Scotland. The analysis found that there was an investment and an effort in talking with an inclusive range of stakeholders to galvanise stakeholder engagement and develop a sense of shared ownership and build a diverse coalition of support. Moreover, the

Scottish Government's political commitment and consensus among the different political parties to making dementia a national priority supported the development and implementation of Scotland's National Dementia Care Strategy. Further, a combination of political and public support, the centrality of people with lived experience, and the involvement of health and social care practitioners and allied health professionals in dementia care supported the achievement of significant progress in dementia care policy in Scotland.

In addition, the Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers and related legal provisions ensured ownership by the Scottish Government and supporting stakeholders. The Charter established the rights and dignity of those living with dementia and their family carers in Scotland. Further, the Charter of Rights developed a foundation to develop a national dementia care policy in Scotland. Framing dementia care through the human rights lens provided Lego-ethical leverage and created compelling reasons for change. The analysis found that the particular language and rhetoric of 'Rights' was a key success factor in the process because it provided a rationale to develop dementia care services and policy that was very difficult to argue against. Moreover, the analysis found that the recognition of the rights of people living with dementia and their carers and the development of a legislative framework in the health and social care sectors support the implementation of dementia care policy in Scotland. However, the analysis found a significant difference between the language of rights and accessing different dementia support services to ensure rights and maintain quality of life for people living with dementia, their families and carers. Moreover, the Rights-Based Approach has received less importance in the third National Dementia Strategy than in the first and second strategies.

5.2.1.2 Programme Success

Development of innovative practice models (Five Pillars Model, Eight Pillars Model, and Advanced Dementia Practice Model) and bold commitments of the Scottish Government supported to provide diagnosis and post-diagnostic support service, integrated community support, and optimum care for people living with dementia, their families and carers in Scotland. However, the analysis found that there is a lack of similar assessments and harmonised ways of diagnosis around the country to reduce the problems relating to the diagnosis of dementia in Scotland. Further, the post-diagnostic support service has experienced a significant variation between commitment and actual performance. There is a lack of integration in health and social care partnerships to ensure the post-diagnostic support

guarantee and implement the dementia strategy. Moreover, there is a systematic and complex challenge in implementing dementia policy due to the lack of connectivity among the different national policies and initiatives of the Scottish Government. The analysis found that dementia care is not reasonably as connected as others across health and social care in Scotland. Moreover, the local strategies do not always align with the national policy because local partnerships have no legal requirement to adopt National Dementia Strategy locally. Therefore, people living with dementia and their carers living in the community have been facing challenges accessing different support services to maintain their quality of life. Additionally, the analysis found a lack of dedicated and specific funding to support the implementation of national dementia care policies in Scotland. Further, there is a lack of direct staff working in the health and social care sectors to implement dementia care strategy and workforce development approaches in Scotland.

Although, developing the Standards of Dementia Care supported people living with dementia, their families and carers in understanding common expectations and entitlement to dementia services. However, the analysis found that no comprehensive assessment has been carried out against Standards of Care for Dementia to understand the progress in dementia care services for people with dementia, their families and carers in Scotland. Further, there is a complexity and lack of robust evaluation to assess the overall progress and effectiveness of Scottish dementia strategies. Additionally, the analysis found a lack of coordination and appropriate reporting on delivering dementia support services by the local partnership.

Further, Promoting Excellence Frameworks supported the development of the necessary skills, knowledge, and competencies of health and social care workers to implement Scotland's national dementia care policy and workforce development approaches. The development of a national framework setting out dementia knowledge and skills provided a tool upon which to plan workforce development. The framework supports determining what health and social care practitioners need to know and the skills they need to provide the appropriate level of dementia care services for their particular job and role. It is an educational benchmark tool-which gives the basis for planning and commissioning workforce development at the national and local levels. It also informs educators about the learning outcomes needed to achieve the different dementia care expertise and practice levels. The analysis found that Promoting Excellence Framework has contributed to developing core educational resources and providing training programmes for health and social services workers and developing leaders and infrastructures to support the implementation of dementia care policy and

workforce development approaches and respond to the needs of people with dementia, their families, and carers in different health and social care settings and communities.

5.2.1.3 Political Success

The Scottish Government has shown their commitment in caring for older people and people living with dementia. The analysis found that the SNP Government has established trust and confidence among the Scottish people by continuously developing and implementing national dementia care strategies and providing health and social care services for older people and people living with dementia, their families, and carers in Scotland since 2007. Further, the Scottish dementia care policy and workforce development approach is recognised as a progressive and world-leading innovator in dementia care to improve the quality of life for people living with dementia, their families and carers. This finding supports the present PhD study framing; for example, Scotland is the place to learn and transfer dementia care policy and workforce development approaches to other countries like Bangladesh. However, there is growing criticism from other political parties on the delivery and management of SNP's dementia care services and initiatives. Moreover, alternative visions for service delivery in dementia care are increasingly being offered by the political opposition of the SNP.

5.2.2 Tentative Recommendations to Policy Development in Bangladesh

The analysis identified a list of key policy learning for other countries like Bangladesh, who are yet to develop a national dementia care policy and workforce development approach based on the evaluation of dementia care policy success in Scotland. However, these tentative suggestions need to consider that there is a very different national, economic, social, and historical context between Scotland and Bangladesh.

Using a 'bottom-up' approach with the direct involvement of people living with dementia, their families, and carers, voluntary sector, and cross-party support can be a learning for countries like Bangladesh to develop a national dementia care policy and workforce development approach based on the process success of the Scottish dementia care policy. Further, human rights universally compel compliance irrespective of topic or jurisdiction. Therefore, Bangladesh can learn from the Scottish experience of a Rights-based dementia care approach to develop a national dementia care policy to ensure rights for the people living with dementia, their families, and carers.

In addition, Bangladesh can learn from the programme success of Scottish dementia care policies to set ambitious targets for dementia service improvement based on innovative practice models (Five Pillars Model, Eight Pillars Model, and Advanced Dementia Practice Model) in developing a national dementia care policy. However, based on the Scottish experiences, other countries like Bangladesh need to ensure dedicated funding to deliver ambitious targets in dementia care services. Further, national dementia care policy development needs to emphasise dedicated and specific staff and ensure key lines of responsibility and accountability for the health and social care sectors and local and national authorities to achieve innovative and ambitious goals. Moreover, there is a need to develop a national policy governance structure and mechanism to continuously monitor the implementation of dementia care services and robust evaluation to assess the success of dementia care policy for people living with dementia, their families, and carers. Additionally, other countries like Bangladesh can learn from the workforce development initiatives in Scotland, including National Education Service for Scotland, Dementia Champions Programme and Promoting Excellence Frameworks for developing a dementia care workforce to improve the necessary knowledge and skills base for the health and social care providers working with people living with dementia and their carers.

Moreover, in developing a national dementia care policy, Bangladesh can learn from the political success of Scottish dementia care experiences to establish political consensus among the different political parties early on. Further, Bangladesh can learn from Scotland about demonstrating competency and awareness of the needs of older sections of the population. The analysis also found that there have been good opportunities to influence national dementia care strategy within parliamentary settings in Scotland. Therefore, the policy learning for Bangladesh is that the legislature needs to be engaging with wider civil society and facilitate knowledge exchange.

5.3 Summary

These summary findings are important for discussing the levels of transferability of dementia care policy and workforce development approaches from Scotland to Bangladesh. The present study is about learning from the experience of Scotland and understanding the conditions that would need to be in place to maximize success in Bangladesh. For example,

some innovative practice models of Scotland's National Dementia Strategies, including post-diagnostic support, Dementia Champions Programme, palliative and end-of-life care, and advanced dementia care, could tentatively be transferred to Bangladesh, and there may be many challenges. These findings will help to understand what could tentatively be transferred from Scotland to Bangladesh. Bangladesh can learn what approaches should be learned and what should be avoided to transfer dementia care and workforce development policies based on the Scottish experience. Because specific dementia care and workforce development approaches may have been successfully implemented in Scotland, the transferability of these approaches in other countries like Bangladesh may not be easy and smooth. Further, there are differences in health and social care structure, people's perceptions and expectations and the capacity of government between Scotland and Bangladesh. Policy transfer is a process in which knowledge about how policies, administrative arrangements, institutions and ideas in one national context is used in the development of policies in another (Dolowitz and Marsh, 2000). However, in the context of public policy making, transfer does not equate with 'doing the same as' another country. Rather, it is a dialogical process in which elements of public policy developed in one national context are distilled, considered and critically applied in another national context. Therefore, the feasibility of transferability of dementia care policy and workforce development approaches from Scotland to Bangladesh and their potential application within Bangladesh will be explored and determined based on responses of the key dementia policy stakeholder interviews in Scotland and Nominal Group Discussions with (a) family members and informal carers of people living with dementia; (b) health and social care practitioners; (c) academics (educators and researchers); (d) dementia care providers; and (e) policy planners in Bangladesh (discussed in the following chapters).

Chapter Six: Findings of the Nominal Group Discussions in Bangladesh

6.1 Brief Outline of the Chapter

Nominal Group Technique interviews were conducted with five stakeholder groups in Bangladesh. This chapter commences with an update to the original plan for methods described in Chapter Four, as pandemic public health restrictions necessitated online data collection rather than the original plan for face to face data collection. An overview of the five stakeholder groups and facilitators is included. Findings are presented for each of the stakeholder groups, detailing the characteristics of participants and the key findings from each stage of the NGT interviews. These include reporting of the ideas generation stage, creation of a thematic ideas list, voting and ranking of the thematic list. The NGT data were analysed using content analysis (Farrow *et al.*, 2020). The chapter ends with a comparison of the highest ranked items across the different stakeholder groups to distil similarities and differences. The chapter concludes with an overview of findings and reflections.

6.1.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to identify the issues and priorities of dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Bangladesh. The Nominal Group Technique (NGT) interviews have been conducted with stakeholders in Bangladesh to critically consider and generate a comprehensive list of the factors that are important to them in relation to future dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Bangladesh. Due to COVID-19 related lock down restrictions in Bangladesh at the time of data collection an adapted virtual NGT interview approach was used. This was based on classical form of Nominal Group Technique (Delbecq, Van de Ven and Gustafson, 1975) comprising four structured stages: silent generation; round-robin; clarification; and priority voting (ranking or rating) (discussed detailed in section 4.5 of Methods Chapter 4). The revised online NGT protocol was pretested with two academics and three postgraduate research students from the Institute of Social Welfare and Research (ISWR), University of Dhaka, Bangladesh (see section 4.5.3 of Methods Chapter 4). This exercise explored communications with participants to help them to prepare for the NGT session. During the test session ideas were recorded in a Word file generated from the NGT discussions and shared them on the computer screen

accessible to all the participants to enable discussion and idea refinement. Participants used the Zoom “Chat” function to share their scoring on the top five priority confidentially, and all sessions were recorded. Feedback from participants endorsed the online approach as straightforward, although some felt more time was required as the discussions were undertaken at pace. Accordingly in the main NGT sessions timings were extended and breaks were introduced. No other adjustments were felt necessary to the online protocol.

6.2 An Overview of the Findings of the Nominal Group Discussions in Bangladesh

Due to internationally evolving COVID-19 and restrictions on face-to-face meetings both in Bangladesh and Scotland during the data collection (from July 2021 to November 2021), virtual (Zoom) Nominal Group Discussions were conducted to collect data from the stakeholders in Bangladesh. The option of online NGT was approved by the UWS Health and Life Sciences, School Ethics Committee. Although it was challenging to communicate with potential NGT participants due to COVID-19 restrictions in Bangladesh, participant recruitment was facilitated by the Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh, Dementia Care Foundation, and the local academic supervisor. Moreover, the Bangladesh academic supervisor Professor Golam Rabbani, supported the researcher in the completion of virtual NGT discussions, acting as a co-facilitator.

Twenty-five stakeholders took part in five virtual Nominal group discussions, including (a) family members and informal carers of people living with dementia (n=5); (b) health and social care practitioners (n=4); (c) academics (educators and researchers) (n=7); (d) dementia care providers (n=4); and (e) policy planners (n=5). The group sizes were smaller than anticipated as discussed in the following sections.

The overall NGT process took 90 to 140 minutes with different stakeholder groups. At the start of each Nominal Group Discussion, the researcher introduced the study's overall aim and the NGT's purpose and outlined the process for generating consensus within NGT discussions and what was expected of participants during each stage of the process. This was achieved through a virtual brief PowerPoint presentation (see Appendix 4.17). Although the overall purpose of NGT was to identify the issues and priorities of dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Bangladesh, questions were adapted to be meaningful for the particular stakeholder group as shown in Table 6.1. The NGT interviews were carried out in the local language (Bengali) and translated into English. The five NGT discussions generated between 12 and 26 ideas. The academics (educators and researchers) NGT group

generated the highest of 26 ideas, whereas the health and social care practitioners NGT group generated least-12 (see Table 6.1).

Table 6. 1: Summary of Five NGT Groups

	Group 1: Family Members and Informal Carers of People Living with Dementia	Group 2: Health and Social Care Practitioners	Group 3: Academics (Educators and Researchers)	Group 4: Care Providers	Group 5: Policy Planners
Participants	05	04	07	04	05
Duration (Minutes)	105	95	120	90	140
When/where	21 st August 2021/Online Zoom (Bangladesh)	7 th September 2021/Online Zoom (Bangladesh)	16 th August 2021/Online Zoom (Bangladesh)	11 th November 2021/Online Zoom (Bangladesh)	5 th September 2021/Online Zoom (Bangladesh)
Questions used	What do family members and informal carers need to improve the dementia care and living standards for people living with dementia in Bangladesh?	What are the most important aspects need to consider to improve dementia care in health and social care settings in Bangladesh?	What do academics (educators and researchers) consider important to improve the dementia care and workforce development in Bangladesh?	What do care providers need to improve the dementia care for the people living with dementia and their family carers in Bangladesh?	What are the most important aspects need to consider in dementia policy to improve the dementia care and workforce development in Bangladesh?
Number of ideas generated in the Round-robin stage	18	12	26	18	24
Thematic list created in the discussions and clarification stage	16	11	21	17	22

The NGT findings are presented and discussed in two forms. Firstly, group-wise generated ideas, thematic lists, voting and ranking of the thematic list and the top five priorities list of five NGT interviews are presented and discussed separately to identify their needs and priorities in the national dementia care policy in Bangladesh. Then the top three priorities of the five NGT groups are compared and discussed to identify similarities and differences between different stakeholders' priorities for future dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Bangladesh.

6.2.1 Findings of Family Members and Informal Carers of People Living with Dementia in Bangladesh

This section presents the findings of the NGT group discussions with the family members and informal carers of people living with dementia. These include the characteristics of participants, detailing the reporting of the ideas generation stage, creation of a thematic list, voting and ranking of the thematic list, and top five priorities of dementia care policies and workforce development approaches to improve the dementia care and living standards for people living with dementia in Bangladesh.

6.2.1.1 The Characteristics of Participants of Family Members and Informal Carers

With the cordial support of the Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh, 11 family members and informal carers of people living with dementia were invited to participate. Finally, five family members and informal carers participated in the virtual NGT-group discussions. Table 6.2 outlines the characteristics of participants, including professional backgrounds, relationships with the people living with dementia, and duration of providing care. Interestingly, all participants were the adult children of a parent living with dementia, and no spousal carers attended the meeting. The reasons for the lack of spousal carers is not known but might be linked to the cultural obligations on adult children.

Table 6. 2: The Characteristics of Participants of Family Members and Informal Carers

Participants Code	Profession	Relation with People Living with Dementia	Providing Caring for	Duration of care
FMIC 01	Teacher	Son	Both father and mother	1 year
FMIC 02	Advocate	Daughter	Mother	4 years
FMIC 03	Teacher	Son	Father	1 year
FMIC 04	Journalist	Son	Mother	1 year
FMIC 05	Banker	Daughter	Father	5 years

* *FMIC=Family Members and Informal Carers*

6.2.1.2 Generated Ideas of Family Members and Informal Carers

All participants silently generated ideas in response to the NGT question and shared these in turn during the round-robin stage. Four round robins were performed before all participants exhausted their ideas. Delbecq et al. (1975) indicated that discussion statements normally generated a range of between 18 and 25 items. The family members and informal carers of people living with dementia group generated 18 ideas. This part of the NGT process took approximately 35 minutes. All priorities/ideas are presented using the participants' own words. The responses from each of the five participants are presented in Table 6.3.

Table 6. 3: List of Generated Ideas of Family Members and Informal Carers of People Living with Dementia

Round -Robin	Participants and Generated Ideas				
	FMIC 01	FMIC 02	FMIC 03	FMIC 04	FMIC 05
1	Trained up care givers for the people living with dementia	Specialised hospitals for the people living with dementia in centrally, locally and community level	Training course for the family carers/care givers	Support to identify proper/appropriate physician to avoid mistreatment	To acknowledge dementia as a disease from the part of family members and society
2	Need specialised dementia experts/doctors in the field of medical/treatment	Providing psychological support to boost up the care givers (monthly/quarterly)	Develop training for proper referral system in treatment for doctors after identifying primary symptoms of dementia	To develop understanding/awareness regarding potential factors of dementia about among the family members (pre-post)	To develop understanding and expertise among the doctors
3	Make dementia as a disease /Treat dementia as a disease	To identify and be aware of potentially challenging times/issues of people living with dementia by the family members	To make affordable and access of medicine for people living with dementia in Bangladesh	Make a social movement to take a commitment from the government to develop care and treatment for people living with dementia	Good and well-trained caregiver for people living with dementia
4	-	Social awareness to develop the dignity of people living with dementia	Prioritise mental well-being and develop infrastructure to ensure mental health	To ensure proper treatment from the part of doctors	-

Family members and informal carers of people living with dementia NGT group generated different ideas/priorities to improve the dementia care and living standards for people living with dementia in Bangladesh. For example, ‘need specialised dementia experts/doctors in the field of medical/treatment’, ‘social awareness to develop the dignity of people living with dementia’, ‘prioritise mental well-being and develop infrastructure to ensure mental health’, and ‘make a social movement to take a commitment from the government to develop care and treatment for people living with dementia’. These ideas are illustrated in the following quotes of family members and informal carers of people living with dementia:

'Bangladesh has no dedicated doctors for dementia...we have heart specialists, nose, and throat specialists....like them, we need specialist doctors for people living with dementia in Bangladesh' (FMIC 01, NGT 01).

'I want to say another thing, and that is...recognition of the social dignity of patients...The patient must have social dignity...Because they don't have that level... so that it can ensure their social dignity by other persons...So that their dignity is not ignored...Such an issue needs to include in the policy' (FMIC 02, NGT 01).

'So far, we have talked about dementia cure or management... But I think the ones that are needed to prevent dementia, or the kind of infrastructure support needed to ensure mental health, I think it should be seriously considered...I mean, prioritise mental well-being and then...develop infrastructure to ensure better well-being...for mental health... For example. Recreational Park, where they can get the entertainment facilities' (FMIC 03, NGT 01)

'Dementia care and workforce development initiatives in Bangladesh are currently private initiatives...The government should take such an initiative or have management for those patients...But we don't see any such initiatives...There should be a comprehensive effort to attract the attention of the government in this regard...So, the government is forced to take the initiative in this regard...An initiative should be taken by the management of the government for this huge population' (FMIC 04, NGT 01).

However, some of these ideas generated in this stage were very similar. For example, both FMIC 01 and FMIC 05 opined to recognise dementia as a disease like other diseases on the part of family members and society. For this reason, in the third stage of the NGT, a thematic list of ideas was created, grouping similar ideas.

'My other point is the recognition of dementia as a disease... such as...other traditional diseases...because many people don't know that dementia is a disease...Many consider it madness...In fact, it's not like that...The way we prioritise diseases such as heart disease and diabetes...are given a lot of priority, but dementia is not prioritised like that...Many people have dementia, but it is not recognised as a disease like other diseases' (FMIC 01, NGT 01).

'What is most needed...for example, within our family...My father has been suffering from dementia for five years...but...No one wants to admit dementia as a disease... even my brother... my relatives don't admit that my father is living with dementia...Many say that he has gone mad...If only everyone in society understood that dementia is a disease...If the treatment is good for these people from the beginning...So, it [recognising dementia as a disease] is very much necessary first' (FMIC 05, NGT 01).

6.2.1.3 Thematic Ideas List of Family Members and Informal Carers

In the third stage, the researcher discussed all ideas generated in the round-robin stage to clarify the statements' meaning and wording to ensure participant understanding (Delbecq, Van de Ven and Gustafson, 1975). This part of the NGT process took approximately 15 minutes to create the thematic ideas list with changes in the original list of generated ideas. Specifically, similar ideas were grouped with agreement from all participants. Further, participants also excluded, included, or altered ideas. For example, the ideas generated in the second stage of NGT about 'to develop understanding and expertise among the doctors and nurses' and 'to develop the national policy for the development of expertise among doctors and nurses' was discussed by participants FMIC 05 and FMIC 02 and finally, the group agreed that these two ideas could be listed one theme as 'develop national policy for the development of understanding and expertise among doctors and nurses'.

'One thing I have to say is that...The matter should be brought to the national level... Dementia disease should be included under the National Policy...We must publicise this matter at the national level...otherwise, the public will not understand...it [dementia] should be recognised at the national level...to develop...a national policy for the development of expertise among the doctors and nurses in dementia' (FMIC 05, NGT 01).

'There may be...a policy to develop expert doctors and nurses in dementia treatment' (FMIC 02, NGT 01).

Further, the idea generated about 'to make affordable and access of medicine for people living with dementia in Bangladesh' was discussed by FMIC 04 and mentioned that along with affordable and access to medicine, there should be initiatives to ensure up-to-date medicine and treatment for people living with dementia in Bangladesh.

'There are many good medicines outside the country which have not yet come to our country...In that case, whatever the latest medicine developed in the treatment of dementia...There should be given importance in this regard so that...medicine...can be brought to Bangladesh quickly...Whatever the latest discovery of science [in dementia treatment], whether in medicine or therapy... Be it in any country...should be available in our country' (FMIC 04, NGT 01).

The participants agreed with the opinion and decided to re-write the theme as 'ensure access and affordable to up-to-date medicine and treatment for people living with dementia in Bangladesh'. Finally, a thematic list of 16 ideas was agreed (see Table 6.4). This thematic list enabled the participants to make an informed decision to vote on ideas.

Table 6. 4: Thematic Ideas List of Family Members and Informal Carers of People Living with Dementia

SL No	Thematic List of Ideas
1	Trained up care givers for the people living with dementia
2	Specialised hospitals for people living with dementia at central, local, and community levels
3	Training course for the family carers
4	Support to identify proper/appropriate physician to avoid mistreatment
5	Need specialised dementia experts/doctors in the field of medical/treatment
6	Providing psychological support to boost up the care givers
7	Develop training for a proper referral system in treatment for doctors after identifying primary symptoms of dementia
8	Develop understanding and awareness regarding potential factors of dementia among the family members
9	Identify and be aware of potentially challenging times/ issues of people living with dementia by the family members
10	Ensure access and affordable to up-to-date medicine and treatment for people living with dementia in Bangladesh
11	Make a social movement to take a commitment from the government to develop care and treatment for of people living with dementia
12	Acknowledge dementia as a disease
13	Social awareness to develop the dignity of people living with dementia
14	Prioritise mental wellbeing and develop infrastructure to ensure mental health
15	Ensure proper treatment from the part of doctors
16	Develop national policy for the development of understanding and expertise among doctors and nurses

6.2.1.4 Voting and Ranking of the Thematic Ideas List of Family Members and Informal Carers

Stage Four of NGT discussions was for voting and ranking the thematic list of ideas. This stage took approximately 15 minutes. Participants were invited to vote on the five ideas most important to them, awarding 5 votes to their top priority and one vote to the fifth priority. Scores for each thematic item were totalled and the list re-ordered starting the item with the highest score. Where items scored equally the idea with the highest frequency of votes was prioritised first, in this way ranking table was produced as shown in Table 6.5.

Family members and informal carers of people living with dementia NGT group emphasised developing a national policy for improving expertise among doctors and nurses about dementia. Other important ideas were ensuring access to up-to-date medicine and treatment, providing training for the family carers, and developing social awareness to ensure the dignity of people living with dementia. Items which no votes scored zero included recognising dementia as a disease, a system of referral and medical training to recognise dementia symptoms.

Table 6. 5: Voting and Ranking of the Thematic Ideas List of Family Members and Informal Carers of People Living with Dementia

List of Ideas	Priorities (scores from each participant)					Sum of scores (for each idea)	Ranked priority (via scores)	Frequency of voting (for each idea)	Ranked priority (via scores & frequency)
	FMIC 01	FMIC 02	FMIC 03	FMIC 04	FMIC 05				
Specialised hospitals for people living with dementia at central, local, and community levels	0	5	5	5	2	17	1 st	4	1 st
Develop national policy for the development of understanding and expertise among doctors and nurses	4	1	0	4	5	14	2 nd	4	2 nd
Trained up care givers for the people living with dementia	5		4		4	13	3 rd	3	3 rd
Need specialised dementia experts/doctors in the field of medical/ treatment	0	4	0	1	0	5	4 th	2	4 th
Develop understanding and awareness regarding potential factors of dementia among the family members	0	0	2	2	0	4	5 th	2	5 th
Ensure access and affordable to up-to-date medicine and treatment for people living with dementia in Bangladesh	0	0	1	0	3	4	5 th	2	5 th
Training course for the family carers	0	0	3	0	0	3	6 th	1	6 th
Support to identify proper/appropriate physician to avoid mistreatment	0	0	0	3	0	3	6 th	1	6 th
Providing psychological support to boost up the care givers	0	3	0	0	0	3	6 th	1	6 th
Ensure proper treatment from the part of doctors	3	0	0	0	0	3	6 th	1	6 th
Make a social movement to take a commitment from the government to develop care and treatment for people living with dementia	0	2	0		0	2	7 th	1	7 th
Social awareness to develop the dignity of people living with dementia	2	0	0	0	0	2	7 th	1	7 th
Identify and be aware of potentially challenging times/issues of people living with dementia by the family members	0	0	0	0	1	1	8 th	1	8 th
Prioritise mental wellbeing and develop infrastructure to ensure mental health	1	0	0	0	0	1	8 th	1	8 th
Develop training for a proper referral system in treatment for doctors after identifying primary symptoms of dementia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Acknowledge dementia as a disease	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

6.2.1.5 Top Five Priorities of Family Members and Informal Carers

Table 6.6 presents the top five priorities of family members and informal carers NGT group in Bangladesh.

Table 6. 6: Top Five (05) Priorities of Family Members and Informal Carers

Top 05 Priorities	Priorities of Family Members and Informal Carers	Number of votes	Collective total for each idea
Priority 1	Specialised hospitals for people living with dementia at central, local, and community levels	4	17
Priority 2	Develop national policy for the development of understanding and expertise among doctors and nurses	4	14
Priority 3	Trained up care givers for the people living with dementia	3	13
Priority 4	Need specialised dementia experts/doctors in the field of medical/treatment	2	5
Priority 5	a). Develop understanding and awareness regarding potential factors of dementia among the family members	2	4
	b). Ensure access and affordable to up-to-date medicine and treatment for people living with dementia in Bangladesh	2	4

The participants of the family members and informal carers NGT group prioritised establishing dementia-specific health care infrastructure and developing trained-up professional caregivers to ensure proper treatment and care for people living with dementia in Bangladesh. For example, FMIC 02 mentioned that:

'I want to say...what we [family carers] feel now...It is...a specialised hospital for dementia...hospital or may be dementia care centre...maybe at the community level...for those living with dementia...it is not only central level but also at the local level... We have dementia patients everywhere...I mean...centre...and can be like care centre...So that we [family carers] can get the support from there... And we can send people living with dementia to these centres...Such a specialised hospital...I would say....that maybe a care centre or dementia hospital' (FMIC 02, NGT 01).

Further, FMIC 05 pointed that:

‘Another issue is that good caregivers....well-trained caregivers...Because now, I want to pay a lot of money, but I am not getting any well-trained caregiver...for my father... for people living with dementia...normally people are already available...but they are not trained in dementia care’ (FMIC 05, NGT 01).

6.2.2 Findings of Health and Social Care Practitioners Group in Bangladesh

6.2.2.1 The Characteristics of Participants of Health and Social Care Practitioners

With the cordial support of the local supervisor, 11 health and social care practitioners involved in dementia care in Bangladesh were recruited, four of whom participated in the NGT-group discussion. Table 6.7 outlines the characteristics of participants, including professional backgrounds and duration of working in the health and social care sectors.

Table 6. 7: The Characteristics of Participants of Health and Social Care Practitioners

Participants Code	Profession	Working Areas	Duration
HSCP 01	Health Care Practitioner	Neurologist	11 years
HSCP 02	Social Care Practitioner	Social Service Officer	12 years
HSCP 03	Health Care Practitioner	Neurologist	13 years
HSCP 04	Social Care Practitioner	Social Service Officer	8 years

** HSCP= Health and Social Care Practitioners*

6.2.2.2 Generated Ideas of Health and Social Care Practitioners

Following silent generation of ideas three round robins were performed giving rise to 12 ideas. This part of the NGT process took approximately 35 minutes. Table 6.8 presents the ideas using the participants’ own words.

Table 6. 8: List of Generated Ideas of Health and Social Care Practitioners

Round -Robin	Participants and Generated Ideas			
	HSCP 01	HSCP 02	HSCP 03	HSCP 04
1	Develop awareness and recognise dementia as disease among the doctors, nurses, mass people etc.	Publication and awareness about the causes of dementia among the mass people	Increase awareness about the dementia as a condition among the health care workers and mass people to avoid the misdiagnosis and mistreatment	Take necessary/ effective initiatives from the part of government about dementia among the mass people to introduce dementia as a health condition
2	Introduce training to identify the causes of dementia for the health care and social care practitioners (nurse, doctors, social workers) to ensure proper diagnosis, and treatment of dementia in the right time	To ensure food security for the grass root level dementia patients through social safety networks of government.	Introduce online platform/service to provide daily life challenge and emergency management for the people living with dementia to ensure required service, information, and guidelines in the grassroots level	Provide social treatment/ care for the people living with dementia in the community and group level and develop proper policy and planning
3	Develop a common platform for dementia support group with the involvement of different level stakeholders including doctors, nurses, social workers, policy planners, carers, dementia people, etc.	To conduct a nationwide survey to identify the actual number of dementia people in Bangladesh	Develop a support group for the carers of the people living with dementia to ensure their needed service and care	Include dementia affected people within the umbrella of social safety net

At the start of the round-robin stage, ideas generated by the health and social care practitioners' NGT group were related to developing an understanding and awareness about dementia and recognising dementia as a health condition and disease among health and social care professionals and mass people. Such as: 'publication and awareness about the causes of dementia among the mass people', 'increase awareness about the dementia as a

condition among the health care workers and mass people to avoid the misdiagnosis and mistreatment', and 'take necessary/effective initiatives from the part of government about dementia among the mass people to introduce dementia as a health condition'.

'There is definitely a reason for this disease [dementia]... If the campaign can be done through billboards about the causes of the disease [dementia]...Then...awareness can be increased among people...That is, first of all, awareness should be raised among the mass people about the cause of the disease [dementia]' (HSCP 02, NGT 02).

'Awareness must be raised, and that is among the common people, of course... as well as among the doctors...so that...we [doctors] can take preventive measures for dementia...can make the diagnosis of dementia with proper attention...and we can provide proper guidelines [to patients and the family] in the right direction...We need to build up awareness about this...And this is the first task...Because of a lack of awareness, we often neglect this matter... We think of it as something else...or we can think of this as any other mental disease... So, awareness is very much important...to avoid misdiagnosis and mistreatment' (HSCP 03, NGT 02).

'Many people are affected by this disease, more or less in old age... In this case, the most alarming thing is that people often cannot properly understand this condition... that the person actually has dementia...I think... the most important thing needed in that case...effective initiatives should be taken from the government level to make people aware about dementia...I think that in many cases most people...educated people...or even many people who work in this field, are not aware of this disease...So, as the first step, it is most important to introduce the word dementia to mass people' (HSCP 04, NGT 02).

However, in the later rounds, health and social care practitioners started to generate different ideas. For example, HSCP 01 emphasised introducing training to identify the causes of dementia for the health care and social care practitioners (nurses, doctors, social workers) to ensure proper diagnosis and treatment of dementia at the right time.

'I think, in dementia care, the first thing we need to diagnose dementia...We must first begin the process of diagnosis and treatment...Then comes the issue of dementia care...That's why training is so important...Because of our traditional education system, even like health sciences...in our country, the issue of dementia has not been included in the sector with due importance...Due to this, even our doctors are not aware of it [dementia]... That's why...there should be a training program overall...for doctors,

social workers, and stakeholders who are working there...So that this disease can be diagnosed and treated at the right time' (HSCP 01, NGT 02).

On the other hand, HSCP 02 recommend conducting a nationwide survey to identify the actual number of dementia people in Bangladesh.

'In Bangladesh...We do not know the actual number of dementia patients in Bangladesh... I think there is a need for a survey on this...A survey could be an easy way to provide treatment' (HSCP 02, NGT 02).

6.2.2.3 Thematic Ideas List of Health and Social Care Practitioners

This part of the NGT process took approximately 15 minutes to create the thematic ideas list with changes in the original list of generated ideas by grouping similar ideas with agreement from all participants. Participants also excluded, included, or altered ideas. For example, HSCP 01 opined to exclude the idea generated in the second stage of NGT about 'develop a support group for the carers of the people living with dementia to ensure their needed service and care' because this idea is almost covered by the 'develop a common platform for dementia support group with the involvement of different level stakeholders including doctors, nurses, social workers, policy planners, carers, dementia people, etc.'

'I think the first one is almost included in the second point... which also emphasises on developing a support group, including family carers...So we can exclude the first idea.... In addition, in my opinion...here it is nice to use the term caregivers instead of carers' (HSCP 01, NGT 02).

The NGT participants came to a consensus that the thematic list about 'develop a common platform for a dementia support group with the involvement of different level stakeholders including doctors, nurses, social workers, policy planners, caregivers, dementia people, etc.' would cover both ideas.

Moreover, there were divergence opinions between HSCP 01 and HSCP 02 about the ideas of 'develop awareness and recognise dementia as disease among the doctors, nurses, mass people etc.' and 'introduce training to identify the causes of dementia for the health care and social care practitioners (nurse, doctors, social workers) to ensure proper diagnosis, and treatment of dementia in the right time' to make them separate or combine in the third stage of NGT.

'These two ideas...can be done together...as there are some similarities...related to awareness of dementia' (HSCP 02, NGT 02).

'In my opinion, the first one is related to the publication... but [the second one] the issue of training will be different...because the second point is associated with training' (HSCP 01, NGT 02).

After some discussion within the group, the participants agreed that these two ideas should be listed as separate themes. Finally, a thematic list of 11 ideas was agreed (see Table 6.9).

Table 6. 9: Thematic Ideas List of Health and Social Care Practitioners

SL No	Thematic List of Ideas
1	Develop awareness and recognise dementia as a disease among the doctors, nurses, mass people etc.
2	Publication and awareness (use of mass media) about the causes of dementia among the mass people
3	Increase awareness about the dementia as a condition among the health care workers and mass people to avoid the misdiagnosis and mistreatment
4	Take necessary and effective initiatives from the part of government to introduce dementia as a health condition among the mass people
5	Introduce training to identify the causes of dementia for the health care and social care practitioners (nurses, doctors, social workers) to ensure proper diagnosis and treatment of dementia in the right time
6	Ensure food security for the grass root level dementia patients through the Social Safety Net by the government
7	Introduce online platform/ service to provide daily life challenge and emergency management for the people living with dementia to ensure required service, information, and guidelines in the grassroots level
8	Provide social treatment/care for the people living with dementia in the community and group level and develop proper policy and planning
9	Conduct a nationwide survey to identify the actual number of dementia people in Bangladesh
10	Develop a common platform for a dementia support group with the involvement of different level stakeholders including doctors, nurses, social workers, policy planners, caregivers, dementia people, etc.
11	Include dementia affected people within the umbrella of the Social Safety Net to provide monetary support

6.2.2.4 Voting and Ranking of the Thematic Ideas List of Health and Social Care Practitioners

Stage Four of NGT discussions was for voting and ranking the thematic list of ideas. This stage took approximately 15 minutes. Table 6.10 presents the voting and ranking of the thematic ideas list of health and social care practitioners. The health and social care practitioners focused on recognising dementia as a disease, ensuring early diagnosis and treatment, and establishing dementia support groups and organisations to improve dementia care in health and social care settings in Bangladesh. Moreover, participants emphasised conducting dementia research and avoiding the misdiagnosis and mistreatment of dementia. Further, items which no votes scored zero included using mass media to raise awareness of dementia and developing policy and planning for dementia care.

Table 6. 10: Voting and Ranking of the Thematic Ideas List of Health and Social Care Practitioners

List of Ideas	Priorities (scores from each participant)				Sum of scores (for each idea)	Ranked priority (via scores)	Frequency of voting (for each idea)	Ranked priority (via scores & frequency)
	HSCP 01	HSCP 02	HSCP 03	HSCP 04				
Develop awareness and recognise dementia as a disease among the doctors, nurses, mass people etc.	5	5	5	5	20	1 st	4	1 st
Introduce training to identify the causes of dementia for the health care and social care practitioners (nurses, doctors, social workers) to ensure proper diagnosis, and treatment of dementia in the right time	3	2	3	4	12	2 nd	4	2 nd
Develop a common platform for a dementia support group with the involvement of different level stakeholders including doctors, nurses, social workers, policy planners, caregivers, dementia people, etc.	0	4	1	2	7	3 rd	3	3 rd
Conduct a nationwide survey to identify the actual number of dementia people in Bangladesh	1	1	0	3	5	4 th	3	4 th
Introduce online platform/service to provide daily life challenge and emergency management for the people living with dementia to ensure required service, information and guidelines in the grassroot level	2	0	2	0	4	5 th	2	5 th
Include dementia affected people within the umbrella of the Social Safety Net to provide monetary support	0	3	0	1	4	5 th	2	5 th
Increase awareness about the dementia as a condition among the health care workers and mass people to avoid the misdiagnosis and mistreatment	0	0	4	0	4	5 th	1	6 th
Take necessary and effective initiatives from the part of government to introduce dementia as a health condition among the mass people	4	0	0	0	4	5 th	1	6 th
Publication and awareness (use of mass media) about the causes of dementia among the mass people	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ensure food security for the grass root level dementia patients through the Social Safety Net by the government	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Provide social treatment/care for the people living with dementia in the community and group level and develop proper policy and planning	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

6.2.2.5 Top Five Priorities of Health and Social Care Practitioners

Table 6.11 presents the top five priorities of health and social care practitioners NGT group in Bangladesh.

Table 6. 11: Top Five (05) Priorities of Health and Social Care Practitioners

Top 05 Priorities	Priorities of Health and Social Care Practitioners	Number of votes	Collective total for each idea
Priority 1	Develop awareness and recognise dementia as a disease among the doctors, nurses, mass people etc.	4	20
Priority 2	Introduce training to identify the causes of dementia for the health care and social care practitioners (nurses, doctors, social workers) to ensure proper diagnosis, and treatment of dementia in the right time	4	12
Priority 3	Develop a common platform for a dementia support group with the involvement of different level stakeholders including doctors, nurses, social workers, policy planners, caregivers, dementia people, etc.	3	7
Priority 4	Conduct a nationwide survey to identify the actual number of dementia people in Bangladesh	3	5
Priority 5	a). Introduce online platform/service to provide daily life challenge and emergency management for the people living with dementia to ensure required service, information and guidelines in the grassroot level	2	4
	b). Include dementia affected people within the umbrella of the Social Safety Net to provide monetary support	2	4

The health and social care practitioners' NGT group prioritised developing dementia awareness among the health care practitioners and mass people and providing financial support for people living with dementia. For example, HSCP 01 mentioned that:

'Awareness is greatly lacking...there is a lack of awareness about the word dementia in our country... And this lack of awareness is not only among patients but also among doctors...For example, even...many of us doctors...doctors lack awareness of dementia... For example, most people have the idea that people's memory decreases with age, and they forget...There is such a tendency among the people in our society to accept these things...But it [dementia] is a disease, or it has care... And it is very necessary...to emphasise on developing awareness and recognise dementia as a disease among doctors, nurses, mass people etc.' (HSCP 01, NGT 02).

Moreover, HSCP 04 opined that:

'If we think that...we will bring people living with dementia under direct financial support... as currently, the Social Safety Net Program at the government level in our country is very strong... and the government has allocated a huge amount of budget in this field... For example, we currently provide financial assistance...or financial benefits are provided to people from different sectors...In that case, people living with dementia can be included directly in the government's Social Safety Net program to provide financial assistance at the marginal level... that can be a big undertaking' (HSCP 04, NGT 02).

6.2.3 Findings of Academics (Educators and Researchers) Group in Bangladesh

6.2.3.1 The Characteristics of Participants of Academics (Educators and Researchers)

With the cordial support of the local supervisor 10 academics (educators and researchers) involved in higher education and research institutes and working in dementia-related education and research activities in Bangladesh were recruited. Seven of these participated in the NGT-group discussions. Table 6.12 outlines the characteristics of participants, including professional backgrounds and duration of working in the academic sectors.

Table 6. 12: The Characteristics of Participants of Academics (Educators and Researchers)

Participants Code	Profession	Working Areas	Duration
A-ER 01	Professor	Social Work	20 years
A-ER 02	Associate Professor	Health Economics	14 years
A-ER 03	Associate Professor	Clinical Psychology	15 years
A-ER 04	Associate Professor	Food and Nutrition Science	15 years
A-ER 05	Associate Professor	Educational and Counselling Psychology	12 Years
A-ER 06	Assistant Professor	Clinical Pharmacy and Pharmacology	10 Years
A-ER 07	Associate Professor	Gerontology and Geriatric Welfare	9 years

** A-ER= Academics-Educators and Researcher*

6.2.3.2 Generated Ideas of Academics (Educators and Researchers)

Five round robins were performed before all participants exhausted their ideas. The academics group generated 26 ideas. This part of the NGT process took approximately 45 minutes. These ideas are presented using the participants' own words in Table 6.13.

Table 6. 13: List of Generated Ideas of Academics (Educators and Researchers)

Round -Robin	Participants and Generated Ideas						
	A-ER 01	A-ER 02	A-ER 03	A-ER 04	A-ER 05	A-ER 06	A-ER 07
1	Provide a thorough orientation and training programme for health care professionals and primary care providers	Steering the existing health and social workforce towards better service provisions of dementia care with minor changes in existing services	Role of multi-disciplinary (teamwork/ collaboration) among the professionals for rehabilitation of the people living with dementia	Need a research-based approach to identify core facilities already developed in Bangladesh for the people living with dementia and carers	Explore the current situation and building data base about dementia in Bangladesh	Developing Food based approach and dietary guidelines (role of natural diet) to prevent the developing of dementia	Course development and training for family carers for unmet needs
2	Emphasis of therapeutic interventions (pharmacological and non-pharmacological) for the people living with dementia	Integrating the care from the begging the lower tier of health system in Bangladesh	Emphasis on bio-psychosocial model rather than medical model for the people living with dementia	Identification of risk factors for developing dementia	Mass campaign to raise awareness about dementia	More steps require to improve the understanding between the workforce and dementia patients	Convince funding agencies and Government to provide more research in dementia estimation
3	Investment in health and community care system and promote well-equipped care for the people living with dementia	Taking awareness campaign regarding dimension of dementia among care providers and community people	Distance PGD certificate course on dementia care	Figuring out gaps for improving the present conditions for dementia	-	Giving support to the dementia patients to become engaged with hobbies or favourite tasks	Awareness raising program/campaign focusing social tabu
4	Promote and encourage relationship between professional staff and family care providers	-	Improve Mental health services for the elderly people	Developing diagnosis facilities to identify the prevalence and brain health of dementia	-	-	Training of healthcare professionals to identify difference between dementia, delirium and depression
5	-	-	-	Setting cut-off points to classify the level of severity of dementia patients in Bangladesh	-	-	Dementia Day care centres and Home care packages

Most of the 26 ideas emphasised education and training for health and social care professionals and family carers to improve dementia care and workforce development in Bangladesh. For example, A-ER 01 and A-ER 07 mentioned that:

'In the context of Bangladesh...right now...I think the most important thing is...provide a thorough orientation and training programme for health care professionals....as well as other stakeholders' (A-ER 01, NHT 03).

'My first opinion is...Course development and training for family carers to address their unmet needs' (A-ER 07, NGT 03)

Other ideas focussed on developing understanding and awareness about dementia. For example: 'mass campaign to raise awareness about dementia', 'awareness raising program/campaign focusing on social tabu', and 'taking awareness campaign regarding the dimension of dementia among care providers and community people'.

'I have another point that I want to include here, and that is mass campaign...to raise...awareness on dementia' (A-ER 05, NGT 03).

'My third opinion...is...awareness raising program/campaign focusing on social tabu... Although it is related to an awareness-raising program, however, it is a little different...I am referring here to raise awareness about... the social tabu related to dementia' (A-ER 07, NGT 03).

6.2.3.3 Thematic Ideas List of Academics (Educators and Researchers)

This part of the NGT process took approximately 25 minutes to create the thematic ideas list with changes in the original list of generated ideas by grouping similar ideas, excluding, including, and altering ideas with agreement from all participants. Finally, a thematic list of 21 ideas was agreed (see Table 6.14). For example, the ideas generated in the second stage of NGT about 'convince funding agencies and Government to provide more research in dementia estimation' and 'investment in health and community care system and promote well-equipped care for the people living with dementia' was discussed by participants A-ER 01 and A-ER 03 and finally, the group agreed that these two ideas could be listed one theme as 'provide more funding and investment in dementia research and health and community care systems to improve care for people living with dementia'.

'As...the previous point is almost similar...I mean here...whether investment and funding can be combined...because, by investment, we are talking about improving this system here...Everything will come here...Again, the word of funding has also come up, so whether the two can be marched together... if it's possible' (A-ER 01, NGT 03).

'Yes, these two can be merged... together' (A-ER-03, NGT 03)

Further, the ideas generated about 'provide a thorough orientation and training programme for health care professionals and primary care providers', 'course development and training for family carers for unmet needs', and 'training of healthcare professionals to identify difference between dementia, delirium and depression' was discussed by the participants. For example, A-ER-07 opined that:

'In our country, all care is family centred and family-based...that is number one...and my second point is...People don't even know about dementia...Doctors don't know, and most doctors can't identify... if we can give this training to family care providers about the unmet needs of the patients...then dementia patients will get the most services in the context of Bangladesh' (A-ER-07, NGT 03).

Finally, the group agreed to make a single theme integrating these three ideas: 'provide a thorough orientation and training programme for health and social care professionals and family carers'. For example, A-ER-01 argued that:

'I have seen the word training with several points...I think it would be good if all points related to training could be brought under one umbrella point...Because the training has been discussed based on each issue...So, if they can be brought under one point as training...Then if we just say the training program, it will include all the points in it' (A-ER 01, NGT 03).

Table 6. 14: Thematic Ideas List of Academics (Educators and Researchers)

SL NO	Thematic List of Ideas
1	Provide a thorough orientation and training programme for health and social care professionals and family carers
2	Steering the existing health and social workforce towards better service provisions of dementia care with minor changes in existing services
3	Role of multi-disciplinary teamwork/collaboration among the professionals for rehabilitation of the people living with dementia
4	Need a research-based approach to identify core facilities already developed in Bangladesh for the people living with dementia and carers
5	Explore the current situation and build a database about dementia in Bangladesh
6	Developing food-based approach and dietary guidelines (role of natural diet) to prevent the developing of dementia
7	Emphasis of therapeutic interventions (pharmacological and non-pharmacological) for the people living with dementia
8	Integrating the care from the begging the lower tier of health system in Bangladesh
9	Emphasis on the bio-psychosocial model rather than the medical model for the people living with dementia
10	Identification of risk factors for developing dementia
11	Mass campaign and awareness raising program to develop understanding and awareness about dementia
12	More steps require to improve the understanding between the workforce and dementia patients
13	Provide more funding and investment in dementia research and health and community care systems to improve care for people living with dementia
14	Distance Post-Graduate Diploma (PGD) certificate course on dementia care
15	Figuring out gaps for improving the present conditions of dementia care
16	Giving support to the dementia patients to become engaged with hobbies or favourite tasks
17	Promote and encourage relationship between professional staff and family care providers
18	Improve mental health services for the elderly people
19	Developing diagnosis facilities to identify the prevalence of dementia and brain health
20	Dementia Day care centres and Home care packages
21	Setting cut-off points classified (level of severity) dementia patients in Bangladesh

6.2.3.4 Voting and Ranking of the Thematic Ideas List of Academics (Educators and Researchers)

This stage of the NGT process took approximately 20 minutes. Following the voting and ranking, the thematic ideas list of academics (educators and researchers) NGT group is presented in Table 6.15.

Academics (educators and researchers) NGT groups focused on dementia education and training programmes for health and social care professionals and family carers, improving the health care system for people living with dementia and awareness-raising programs to develop understanding about dementia. Other important priorities were therapeutic interventions, improving mental health services, and establishing dementia day care centres. Moreover, ideas that participants offered, but did not prioritise, are presented in Table 6.15. For example, emphasising the bio-psycho-social model rather than the medical model, providing recreational facilities, and promoting relationships between professional dementia carers and family members of people living with dementia.

Table 6. 15: Voting and Ranking of the Thematic Ideas List of Academics (Educators and Research)

List of ideas	Priorities (scores from each participant)							Sum of scores (for each idea)	Ranked priority (via scores)	Frequency of voting (for each idea)	Ranked priority (via scores & frequency)
	AER 01	AER 02	AER 03	AER 04	AER 05	AER 06	AER 07				
Provide a thorough orientation and training programme for health and social care professionals and family carers	3	0	5	4	4	0	5	21	1 st	5	1 st
Need a research-based approach to identify core facilities already developed in Bangladesh for the people living with dementia and carers	4	3	0	5	0	0	0	12	2 nd	3	2 nd
Explore the current situation and build a database about dementia in Bangladesh	0	5	0	2	5		0	12	2 nd	3	2 nd
Provide more funding and investment in dementia research and health and community care systems to improve care for people living with dementia	5	0	0	0	2	3	0	10	3 rd	3	3 rd
Role of multi-disciplinary teamwork/collaboration among the professionals for rehabilitation of the people living with dementia	0	0	4	1	3	0	0	08	4 th	3	4 th
Mass campaign and awareness raising program to develop understanding and awareness about dementia	2	1	0	0	1	0	3	07	5 th	4	5 th
Identification of risk factors for developing dementia	0	2	0	3	0	0	0	05	6 th	2	6 th
Emphasis of therapeutic interventions (pharmacological and non-pharmacological) for the people living with dementia	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	05	6 th	1	7 th
Steering the existing health and social workforce towards better service provisions of dementia care with minor changes in existing services	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	04	7 th	1	8 th
Developing food-based approach and dietary guidelines (role of natural diet) to prevent the developing of dementia	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	04	7 th	1	8 th

List of ideas	Priorities (scores from each participant)							Sum of scores (for each idea)	Ranked priority (via scores)	Frequency of voting (for each idea)	Ranked priority (via scores & frequency)
	AER	AER	AER	AER	AER	AER	AER				
	01	02	03	04	05	06	07				
More steps require to improve the understanding between the workforce and dementia patients	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	04	7 th	1	8 th
Improve mental health services for the elderly people	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	03	8 th	2	9 th
Dementia Day care centres and Home care packages	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	03	8 th	2	9 th
Distance Post-Graduate Diploma (PGD) certificate course on dementia care	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	03	8 th	1	10 th
Figuring out gaps for improving the present conditions of dementia care	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	02	9 th	1	11 th
Integrating the care from the begging the lower tier of health system in Bangladesh	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	01	10 th	1	12 th
Developing diagnosis facilities to identify the prevalence of dementia and brain health	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	01	10 th	1	12 th
Emphasis on the bio-psychosocial model rather than the medical model for the people living with dementia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Giving support to the dementia patients to become engaged with hobbies or favourite tasks	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Promote and encourage relationship between professional staff and family care providers	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Setting cut-off points classified (level of severity) dementia patients in Bangladesh	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

6.2.3.5 Top Five Priorities of Academics (Educators and Researchers)

Table 6.16 presents the top five priorities of academics (educators and researchers) NGT group to improve dementia care and workforce development in Bangladesh.

Table 6. 16: Top Five (05) Priorities of Academics (Educators and Researchers)

Top 05 Priorities	Priorities of Academics (Educators and Researchers)	Number of votes	Collective total for each idea
Priority 1	Provide a thorough orientation and training programme for health and social care professionals and family carers	5	21
Priority 2	a). Need a research-based approach to identify core facilities already developed in Bangladesh for the people living with dementia and carers	3	12
	b). Explore the current situation and build a database about dementia in Bangladesh	3	12
Priority 3	Provide more funding and investment in dementia research and health and community care systems to improve care for people living with dementia	3	10
Priority 4	Role of multi-disciplinary teamwork/collaboration among the professionals for rehabilitation of the people living with dementia	3	8
Priority 5	Mass campaign and awareness raising programme to develop understanding and awareness about dementia	4	7

Academics (educators and researchers) NGT groups prioritised research initiatives to explore the existing dementia care facilities and the current dementia situation in Bangladesh. For example, A-ER 04 mentioned that:

‘We need a research-based approach to identify core facilities already developed in Bangladesh...for the people living with dementia and carers’ (A-ER 04, NGT 03).

In addition, A-ER 07 noted that:

‘Convince funding agencies and Government to provide more research support in dementia...basically dementia estimation is the first phase...Actually, we don't know how many dementia patients there are in Bangladesh...There are three different studies, and none of their estimations are close to each other...these estimations are

different... Therefore, if research is done in this regard from the beginning, it is possible to move forward based on that... So, we should know that first' (A-ER 07, NGT 03).

6.2.4 Findings of Dementia Care Providers Group in Bangladesh

6.2.4.1 The Characteristics of Participants of Dementia Care Providers

With the cordial support of the Dementia Care Foundation, 06 dementia care providers working in dementia care in Bangladesh were recruited and four participated. Table 6.17 outlines the characteristics of participants, including professional backgrounds and duration of working as dementia care providers.

Table 6. 17: The Characteristics of Participants of Dementia Care Providers

Participants Code	Profession	Working Areas	Duration
DCP 01	Doctor	Dementia Care	10 years
DCP 02	Founder of Care organisation	Dementia Care	10 years
DCP 03	Counsellor- Clinical Psychology	Dementia Care	7 years
DCP 04	Founder of Care organisation	Dementia Care	9 years

* *DCP= Dementia Care Providers*

6.2.4.2 Generated Ideas of Dementia Care Providers

This part of the NGT process took approximately 25 minutes. Seven round robins were performed before all participants exhausted their list of 18 ideas. Table 6.18 presents these in the words of the participants.

Table 6. 18: List of Generated Ideas of Dementia Care Providers

Round -Robin	Participants and Generated Ideas			
	DCP 01	DCP 02	DCP 03	DCP 04
1	Proper assessment and screening of the disease condition	Understanding Dementia	Early detection and diagnosis	Information about diagnosis, treatment, and care
2	categorization of the dementia disease risk	Capacity Building	Awareness and education about dementia	Find support in care
3	Educate the family members regarding the dementia process, comprehensive care and to do things in case of any emergency situation	palliative care/end-of-life care	Culture-specific coordinated and comprehensive intervention	-
4	To find out any other co-morbidities to avoid misdiagnosis or maltreatment regarding dementia	-	Community mobilisation	-
5	Strengthening the support system and proper steps for community mobilisation	-	Develop an appropriate referral system for multidisciplinary and coordinated interventions for dementia care	-
6	Improvement of quality of life of the demented people	-	Ensure quality of life for the informal family dementia carers	-
7	Cost effective management policy at primary health care level	-	-	-

Dementia care providers' NGT group generated several ideas to ensure early detection, proper diagnosis, and treatment of dementia, including 'proper assessment and screening of the disease condition', 'early detection and diagnosis', and 'information about diagnosis, treatment, and care'. For example, DCP 01, DCP 03, and DCP 04 noted that:

'My first priority...I will say...proper assessment and screening of the disease condition'
(DCP 01, NGT 04)

'What I will say... that is... early detection and diagnosis' (DCP 03, NGT 04)

'We need to provide...information about diagnosis, treatment, and care...for people living with dementia and their family members...carers' (DCP 04, NGT 04).

Moreover, dementia care providers emphasise improving and ensuring the quality of life for the people living with dementia and their informal family dementia carers in Bangladesh. For example, DCP 01 and DCP 04 mentioned that:

'My priority six-which is... improvement of the quality of life of dementated people' (DCP 01, NGT 04).

'...along with...improving their [people living with dementia] quality of life...in the context of Bangladesh...family members...who are providing 24 hours care in the family...improvement of their [informal family care givers] quality of life...I want to add this' (DCP 03, NGT 04).

6.2.4.3 Thematic Ideas List of Dementia Care Providers

This stage of the NGT process took approximately 15 minutes to create the thematic ideas list with changes in the original list of generated ideas with agreement from all participants. For example, in the second stage of NGT, the ideas generated about 'community mobilisation' and 'strengthening the support system and proper steps for community mobilisation' were combined as 'strengthening the support system and proper steps for community mobilisation to improve dementia care'. Further, participants also excluded, included, or altered ideas. For example, the ideas generated about 'awareness and education about dementia', 'educate the family members regarding the dementia process, comprehensive care and to do things in case of any emergency situation', and 'capacity building' discussed between DCP 01, DCP 02, and DCP 03. There were agreement and disagreement about these ideas among the participants:

'... 'Awareness and education about dementia' idea can be merged with... 'capacity building'.... however, I think...awareness and capacity building can be two separate points...because... education should come with capacity building, but two points can be put separately here...I want to emphasise two points separately... Moreover, 'educate the family members regarding the dementia process, comprehensive care,

and to do things in case of any emergency situation' point is connected with capacity building' (DCP 02, NGT 04).

'Yes, It [Educate the family members regarding the dementia process, comprehensive care, and to do things in case of any emergency situation] comes with capacity building...just a little bit elaborated here' (DCP 01, NGT 04).

'Also, this point [Educate the family members regarding the dementia process, comprehensive care, and to do things in case of any emergency situation] is related to education...where we are talking about education... It seems to me... this point...is related to both awareness and education about dementia...and capacity building' (DCP 03, NGT 04)

'I mean...education can be brought together with capacity building, and awareness can be a separate one...This means giving importance to awareness separately...For example, awareness raising of dementia can be a point...and... And education can connect capacity building' (DCP 02, NGT 04).

After discussions among the group members, participants agreed to revise these ideas as 'awareness raising about dementia', 'educate the family members regarding the dementia process, comprehensive care, and to do things in case of any emergency', and 'education about dementia and Capacity Building'. Finally, a thematic list of 17 ideas was agreed (see Table 6.19).

Table 6. 19: Thematic Ideas List of Dementia Care Providers

SL No	Thematic List of Ideas
1	Proper assessment and screening of the disease (dementia) condition
2	Understanding dementia
3	Early detection and diagnosis of dementia
4	Categorization of the dementia disease risk
5	Information about diagnosis, treatment, and care
6	Awareness raising about dementia
7	Educate the family members regarding the dementia process, comprehensive care, and to do things in case of any emergency
8	Find support in dementia care
9	Culture-specific coordinated and comprehensive intervention
10	To find out any other co-morbidities to avoid misdiagnosis or maltreatment regarding dementia
11	Education about dementia and capacity building
12	Strengthening the support system and proper steps for community mobilisation to improve dementia care
13	Prepare about the stage and needs of palliative care/end-of-life care for the family members
14	Develop an appropriate referral system for multidisciplinary and coordinated interventions for dementia care
15	Improvement of quality of life of the demented people
16	Ensure quality of life for the informal family dementia carers
17	Cost-effective management policy at the primary health care level (in the grass root level)

6.2.4.4 Voting and Ranking of the Thematic Ideas List of Dementia Care Providers

This part of the NGT process took approximately 15 minutes. Table 6.20 presents the voting and ranking of the thematic ideas list of dementia care providers. Dementia care providers' NGT group focused on ensuring early diagnosis, proper treatment, and comprehensive care for people living with dementia in Bangladesh. Other highlighted areas were dementia education, strengthening the community healthcare and support system and ensuring the quality of life for the family carers. Further, responses that participants offered, but did not prioritise, are also presented in Table 6.20. For example, emphasising culture-specific intervention and avoiding misdiagnosis and maltreatment.

Table 6. 20: Voting and Ranking of the Thematic Ideas List of Dementia Care Providers

List of Ideas	Priorities (scores from each participant)				Sum of scores (for each idea)	Ranked priority (via scores)	Frequency of voting (for each idea)	Ranked priority (via scores & frequency)
	DCP 01	DCP 02	DCP 03	DCP 04				
Early detection and diagnosis of dementia	0	4	4	2	10	1 st	3	1 st
Education about dementia and capacity building	3		3	4	10	1 st	3	1 st
Prepare about the stage and needs of palliative care/end-of-life care for the family members	0	1	1	5	07	2 nd	3	2 nd
Educate the family members regarding the dementia process, comprehensive care, and to do things in case of any emergency	4	3	0	0	07	2 nd	2	3 rd
Proper assessment and screening of the disease (dementia) condition	5	0	0	1	06	3 rd	2	4 th
Understanding dementia	0	5	0	0	05	4 th	1	5 th
Awareness raising about dementia	0		5	0	05	4 th	1	5 th
Cost-effective management policy at the primary health care level (in the grass root level)	1	2	0	0	03	5 th	2	6 th
Information about diagnosis, treatment and care	0	0	0	3	03	5 th	1	7 th
Strengthening the support system and proper steps for community mobilisation to improve dementia care	0	0	2	0	02	6 th	1	8 th
Ensure quality of life for the informal family dementia carers	2	0	0	0	02	6 th	1	8 th
Categorization of the dementia disease risk	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Find support in dementia care	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Culture-specific coordinated and comprehensive intervention	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
To find out any other co-morbidities to avoid misdiagnosis or maltreatment regarding dementia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Develop an appropriate referral system for multidisciplinary and coordinated interventions for dementia care	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Improvement of quality of life of the demented people	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

6.2.4.5 Top Five Priorities of Dementia Care Providers

Table 6.21 presents the top five priorities of dementia care providers NGT group to improve dementia care for the people living with dementia and their family carers in Bangladesh.

Table 6. 21: Top Five (05) Priorities of Dementia Care Providers

Top 05 Priorities	Priorities of Dementia Care Providers	Number of votes	Collective total for each idea
Priority 1	a). Early detection and diagnosis of dementia	3	10
	b). Education about dementia and capacity building	3	10
Priority 2	Prepare about the stage and needs of palliative care/end-of-life care for the family members	3	7
Priority 3	Educate the family members regarding the dementia process, comprehensive care, and to do things in case of any emergency	2	7
Priority 4	Proper assessment and screening of the disease (dementia) condition	2	6
Priority 5	a). Understanding dementia	1	5
	b). Awareness raising about dementia	1	5

Dementia care providers' NGT group emphasised preparing and planning the stage and needs of end-of-life care for people living with dementia and their family members. For example, DCP 02 mentioned that:

'What I'm really trying to convey is that people living with dementia will have a time when they are nearing the end of life... And people living with dementia will need some specialised care when they progress through the severe stages...for example, at that time one will become bedbound...gradually she/he will start to forget everything... And gradually, her/his eating and drinking will start to stop...Given that period, they need specialized care...Understanding that matter...I mean...people living with dementia and family members must be prepared for this [severity stage of dementia]' (DCP 02, NGT 04).

Moreover, DCP 03 opined that:

'It seems to me that...Sometimes families may need a plan....For example, there should be a future plan of what stage the person's severity may progress to and what kind of assistive support the person may need in the future., there is a need to be prepared

and understand the severity stages...that is a very important aspect...I think' (DCP 03, NGT 04).

6.2.5 Findings of Policy Planners Group in Bangladesh

6.2.5.1 The Characteristics of Participants of Policy Planners

With the cordial support of the local supervisor, 05 policy planners involved in the planning and implementation of national policies related to older people and dementia care in Bangladesh were recruited and all five participated. Table 6.22 outlines the characteristics of participants.

Table 6. 22: The Characteristics of Participants of Policy Planners

Participants Code	Profession	Working Areas	Duration
PP 01	Professor and Policy Adviser	Older People and Dementia Care	35 years
PP 02	Former Member of Parliament	Adviser of the Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh	12 years
PP 03	Former Civil Surgeon	Adviser of the Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh	30 years
PP 04	Associate Professor and Policy Adviser	Social Statistics and Dementia Care	16 years
PP 04	Senior Social Service Officer	Social Policy	25 years

* *PP= Policy Planners*

6.2.5.2 Generated Ideas of Policy Planners

This part of the NGT process took approximately 50 minutes. Six round robins were performed before all participants exhausted their ideas. The policy planners' group generated 24 priorities/ideas, which are presented in the original words in Table 6.23.

Table 6. 23: List of Generated Ideas of Policy Planners

Round -Robin	Participants and Generated Ideas				
	PP 01	PP 02	PP 03	PP 04	PP 05
1	Continues Research process for the development of a data base to formulate dementia policy	Develop understanding and awareness and introduce training about dementia among the doctors, nurses, etc.	Conduct a Baseline survey by field level workers	Develop a suitable dementia diagnosis scale	Identification of dementia patients
2	Sensitise and communicate with political parties and political leaders to introduce dementia policy in the national political election manifesto	Mass awareness among the general people, political leaders, concerned authorities etc	Include dementia as a NCD-(Non-Communicable Disease) in the health priority	Dementia support centre both GOs and NGOs initiatives	Determination the minimum standard of care for the people living with dementia
3	Prevent and control all source of mistreatment and wrongful treatment (eradicate faith-based malpractice/treatment)	Liaison and lobbying with the member of parliament and other political leaders and parties and sensitise them about dementia	Organise, train and orientation of domestic care workers, family members as a care givers, professional care givers of the people living dementia	Develop collaborative research initiatives between government and academic institutions	Include dementia issues in others relevant health and social policies
4	Use the media positively (electric and printed) to focus dementia issues	Better use of existing health infrastructure (grassroot level community health care, Upazila health care centre etc) for the benefit of dementia people	Attention to dementia comorbidity conditions	-	Introduce rehabilitation for the people living with dementia
5	Develop volunteerism for the dementia people	-	-	-	To encourage and motivate NGOs and COS to establish organisation on dementia management
6	a). Include the dementia issues in technical, general and academic course curriculum b). Use the community and religious leaders (Imam) to facilitate dementia issues c). Setup a separate council for mental health, including Autism, dementia etc	-	-	-	-

In the second stage of the NGT, the policy planners group generated a list of ideas related to research initiatives to build a database and explore the current situation of dementia to improve dementia care and workforce development in Bangladesh. These include 'continues research process for the development of a data base to formulate dementia policy', 'conduct a Baseline survey by field level workers', and 'develop collaborative research initiatives between government and academic institutions'. For example, PP 01, PP 03, and PP 04 opined that:

'We need research first...research to develop a database and continuous research... It will be fast... Because we have no information [about dementia]...That is why I think research should be given importance in policy...continues research process for the development of a database to formulate dementia policy' (PP 01, NGT 05).

'My idea is that...to conduct a base survey... Since we have a structure in place...in that case, if a survey can be conducted by field-level workers, then we will get accurate data [about dementia] ...This is my first point' (PP 03, NGT 05).

'Many of my points have already been covered, but one thing I want to emphasise here is that...Whether research can be conducted through coordination of academic institutes with the government on dementia...Because it is not possible to conduct such research only at the individual level or in academic institutes alone' (PP 04, NGT 05).

Further, the policy planners' NGT group generated ideas that emphasised the role of the government, parliamentary members, political parties, and political leaders in introducing dementia policy in Bangladesh. For example, 'sensitise and communicate with political parties and political leaders to introduce dementia policy in the national political election manifesto', 'mass awareness among the general people, political leaders, concerned authorities etc.', and 'liaison and lobbying with the member of parliament and other political leaders and parties and sensitise them about dementia'.

'So, what we have to do is...to sensitise and...communicate with the political parties...and political leaders to include dementia management issues in their...election manifestos... because we have no policy [on dementia] so far...this policy is absolutely a government matter... the government is often obliged if it is mentioned in their election manifesto... We see...that...the biggest programme in the Ministry of Social Welfare for

the elderly in Bangladesh is the Old Age Allowance Programme which came from the election manifesto of the political party' (PP 01, NGT 05).

'I also agree with everyone's opinion...Our policy is very necessary...Dementia should be included in all relevant ministries' activities... and it is true that the focus should be done through the government... because if we do it separately through various NGOs and private initiatives or organisations, it will not get that much importance...But these private and non-governmental initiatives can act as a medium to tell the government what can be included in the dementia policy...that might be important...By that, I mean we need a medium through which we can inform the government...The medium here is Parliament, and we have to reach the Parliament... I spoke on this issue when I was a Member of the National Parliament... Maybe if I stayed in the Parliament for a few more days, then I could take this matter to the last place...Now again, we have to take the matter to the Parliament through some such policymakers...In other words, we have to take steps to make it attention to the government' (PP 02, NGT 05).

In addition, PP 05 and PP 01 opined that dementia issues need to include in other relevant health and social policies in Bangladesh:

'The opinion... which can be recorded here...that is...among the policies we have in place, such as National Health Policy, Women's Policy, Elderly Policy, Social Welfare Policy, Disability Development Policy, etc... inclusion of dementia aspects...concepts in relevant national policies...relevant...others health and social policies... Because...we have nothing on this [dementia] in the health policy' (PP 05, NGT 05).

'After 11 years of effort...We formulated the National Older Policy in 2013... Now reviewing this policy, I feel very ashamed...because there is only one thing mentioned in the entire policy, and that is 'to expand and strengthen elderly-friendly mental health services'... But dementia is not mentioned here... But dementia is really an older people's problem' (PP 01, NGT 05).

6.2.5.3 Thematic Ideas List of Policy Planners

This part of the NGT process took approximately 35 minutes to create the thematic ideas with agreement from all participants. For example, there were divergence opinions between PP 01 and PP 05 about the ideas of 'continues Research process for the development of a data base to formulate dementia policy' and 'conduct a Baseline survey by field level worker' to make them separate or combine in the third stage of NGT.

'Research can be called research activity rather than process...I think 'continues Research process for the development of a data base to formulate dementia policy' and 'conduct a Baseline survey by field level worker' are almost the same... Because we will create a database based on the field survey...That's why these two things go together... But the term field workers can be left out because the policy does not specify who will conduct the research... who will collect the data... Because the first research that will be done is called the baseline research, and based on that, the database will be created, and then continuous research will be done' (PP 01, NGT 05).

'I wanted to talk a little bit about combining 'continues Research process for the development of a data base to formulate dementia policy' and 'conduct a Baseline survey by field level workers' together... PP 01 is right about combining the two...But my opinion is...There are two issues here: One is to determine the statistics or information on how many people in Bangladesh are suffering from dementia...This is one... Another is to conduct continuous research to understand their situation and to explore what steps can be taken to improve their quality of life and develop their livelihood... That is why it is better if these two issues are separated' (PP 05, NGT 05).

'Yes, I think it can be....one is nationwide...to conduct a nationwide survey to develop a database...another one is specific studies for...to address dementia situations... It's okay...we can separate these two points' (PP 01, NGT 05).

After some discussion within the group, the participants agreed that these two ideas should be listed as separate themes: 'continuous research activities for the development of a database to formulate dementia policy' and 'conduct a nationwide survey on dementia'. Finally, a thematic list of 22 ideas was agreed (see Table 6.24).

Table 6. 24: Thematic Ideas List of Policy Planners

SL No	Thematic List of Ideas
1	Continuous research activities for the development of a database to formulate dementia policy
2	Conduct a nationwide survey on dementia
3	Develop a suitable dementia diagnosis scale
4	Identification and recognition of dementia
5	Develop understanding, and awareness on dementia among the health care professionals and other health care providers, including doctors, nurses, etc.
6	Communicate and lobbying with political parties and political leaders to formulate dementia policy
7	Mass awareness using media among the general mass, political leaders, concerned authorities etc
8	Include dementia issues in Non-Communicable Disease (NCD) prevention documents
9	Determination the minimum standard of care for the people living with dementia
10	Include dementia issues in others relevant national health and social policies
11	Prevent and control all source of mistreatment and wrongful treatment (eradicate faith-based malpractice / treatment)
12	Liaison and lobbying with the Member of Parliament and other political leaders and parties to make them interested about dementia care
13	Organise, train and orientation of domestic care workers, family (members as a) care givers, professional care givers for the people living dementia
14	Develop collaborative research between government and academic institutions on dementia
15	Develop volunteerism among younger generations for assisting dementia patients
16	Include the dementia issues in technical, general and professional academic course curricula
17	Use the community and religious leaders to disseminate and facilitate dementia issues
18	Better Use of existing health infrastructure (grassroot level community health care, Upazila health care centre etc) for the benefit of dementia people
19	Put sufficient attention to comorbid conditions of people living with dementia
20	Setup a separate council for mental health, including autism, dementia etc
21	Introduce rehabilitation arrangements for the people living with dementia
22	Encourage and motivate philanthropic persons, Non-Government Organisations (NGOs) and Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) to establish organisation on dementia management

6.2.5.4 Voting and Ranking of the Thematic Ideas List of Policy Planners

This stage took approximately 20 minutes. The voting and ranking of the thematic ideas list of policy planners NGT group is presented in Table 6.25. Policy planners NGT group focused on dementia research and lobbying with political parties and government to formulate a national dementia care policy. Further, policy planners emphasised providing dementia training for family carers, ensuring a minimum living standard, and introducing rehabilitation services for people living with dementia. Moreover, ideas that policy planners offered, but did not prioritise, are also included in Table 6.25. For example, including dementia issues in relevant national health and social policies and professional and academic course curricula and ensuring proper use of existing health care services for people living with dementia.

Table 6. 25: Voting and Ranking of the Thematic Ideas List of Policy Planners

List of Ideas	Priorities (scores from each participant)					Sum of scores (for each idea)	Ranked priority (via scores)	Frequency of voting (for each idea)	Ranked priority (via scores & frequency)
	PP 01	PP 02	PP 03	PP 04	PP 05				
Continuous research activities for the development of a database to formulate dementia policy	5	3	3	5	0	16	1 st	4	1 st
Conduct a nationwide survey on dementia	0	0	5	4	4	13	2 nd	3	2 nd
Develop understanding, and awareness on dementia among the health care professionals and other health care providers, including doctors, nurses, etc.	4	2	1	1	3	11	3 rd	5	3 rd
Mass awareness using media among the general mass, political leaders, concerned authorities etc	1	4	0	2	0	07	4 th	3	4 th
Develop a suitable dementia diagnosis scale	0	0	4	3	0	07	4 th	2	5 th
Identification and recognition of dementia	0	0	0	0	5	05	5 th	1	6 th
Encourage and motivate philanthropic persons, Non-Government Organisations (NGOs) and Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) to establish organisation on dementia management	5	0	0	0	0	05	5 th	1	6 th
Organise, train and orientation of domestic care workers, family (members as a) care givers, professional care givers for the people living dementia	2	1	0	0	0	03	6 th	2	7 th
Communicate and lobbying with political parties and political leaders to formulate dementia policy	3	0	0	0	0	3	6 th	1	8 th
Include dementia issues in Non-Communicable Disease (NCD) prevention documents	0	0	2	0	0	2	7 th	1	9 th
Determination the minimum standard of care for the people living with dementia	0	0	0	0	2	2	7 th	1	9 th
Introduce rehabilitation arrangements for the people living with dementia	0	0	0	0	1	01	8 th	1	10 th

List of Ideas	Priorities (scores from each participant)					Sum of scores (for each idea)	Ranked priority (via scores)	Frequency of voting (for each idea)	Ranked priority (via scores & frequency)
	PP 01	PP 02	PP 03	PP 04	PP 05				
Include dementia issues in others relevant national health and social policies	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Prevent and control all source of mistreatment and wrongful treatment (eradicate faith-based malpractice/ treatment)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Liaison and lobbying with the Member of Parliament and other political leaders and parties to make them interested about dementia care	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Develop collaborative research between government and academic institutions on dementia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Develop volunteerism among younger generations for assisting dementia patients	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Include the dementia issues in technical, general and professional academic course curricula	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Use the community and religious leaders to disseminate and facilitate dementia issues	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Better Use of existing health infrastructure (grassroot level community health care, Upazila health care centre etc) for the benefit of dementia people	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Put sufficient attention to comorbid conditions of people living with dementia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Setup a separate council for mental health, including autism, dementia etc	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

6.2.5.5 Top Five Priorities of Policy Planners

The top five priorities of policy planners NGT group are presented in Table 6.26.

Table 6. 26: Top Five (05) Priorities of Policy Planners

Top 05 Priorities	Priorities of Policy Planners	Number of votes	Collective total for each idea
Priority 1	Continuous research activities for the development of a database to formulate dementia policy	4	16
Priority 2	Conduct a nationwide survey on dementia	3	13
Priority 3	Develop understanding, and awareness on dementia among the health care professionals and other health care providers, including doctors, nurses, etc.	5	11
Priority 4	Mass awareness using media among the general mass, political leaders, concerned authorities etc	3	7
Priority 5	Develop a suitable dementia diagnosis scale	2	7

Policy planners NGT group prioritised developing understanding and building awareness about dementia among health and social care practitioners, general mass, political leaders, and relevant authorities. For example, PP 02 mentioned that:

‘The biggest thing is...First of all, our doctors and nurses need to have training...We need to prioritise this first... After that, those who are health workers must have ideas [about dementia] ...so that they can separate these types of patients when patients visit to them...I mean....Awareness of dementia among doctors, nurses and health workers... so that they can find out who has dementia...and they can differentiate them’ (PP 02, NGT 05).

PP 02 further added that:

‘Creating massive awareness is important...because many educated and aware people do not know about this [dementia]...For example, when we [Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh] first started working on this issue, we went to the former Health Minister of Bangladesh together with the Secretary General of Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh...but Minister didn't understand what the matter was...Later when we tried to explain it to him, he said...I will look into it...As many people still do not understand the matter, in that case, we have to develop an understanding of this matter first...Our politicians need to understand’ (PP 02, NGT 05).

6.3 Comparative Discussions of the Highest-Ranks 1 to 3 Items Across the Different Groups

In this section, the top three priorities of the five NGT groups are compared and discussed to identify similarities and differences between different stakeholders' priorities for future dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Bangladesh (see Table 6.27).

Table 6. 27: Top Three (03) Priorities of the Five NGT Groups

Top 03 Priorities	NGT=01: Family Members and Informal Carers	NGT=02: Health and Social Care Practitioners	NGT=03: Academics (Educators and Researchers)	NGT=04: Dementia Care Providers	NGT=05: Policy Planners
Priority 1	Specialised hospitals for people living with dementia at central, local, and community levels	Develop awareness and recognise dementia as a disease among the doctors, nurses, mass people etc.	Provide a thorough orientation and training programme for health and social care professionals and family carers	a). Early detection and diagnosis of dementia b). Education about dementia and capacity building	Continuous research activities for the development of a database to formulate dementia policy
Priority 2	Develop national policy for the development of understanding and expertise among doctors and nurses	Introduce training to identify the causes of dementia for the health care and social care practitioners (nurses, doctors, social workers) to ensure proper diagnosis, and treatment of dementia in the right time	a). Need a research-based approach to identify core facilities already developed in Bangladesh for the people living with dementia and carers b). Explore the current situation and build a database about dementia in Bangladesh	Prepare about the stage and needs of palliative care/end-of-life care for the family members	Conduct a nationwide survey on dementia
Priority 3	Trained up care givers for the people living with dementia	Develop a common platform for a dementia support group with the involvement of different level stakeholders including doctors, nurses, social workers, policy planners, caregivers, dementia people, etc.	Provide more funding and investment in dementia research and health and community care systems to improve care for people living with dementia	Educate the family members regarding the dementia process, comprehensive care, and to do things in case of any emergency	Develop understanding, and awareness on dementia among the health care professionals and other health care providers, including doctors, nurses, etc.

Among the top three priorities of the five NGT groups, most of the items emphasised providing education and training for health and social care professionals and family carers. For example, all the top three ideas identified by the dementia care providers NGT group related to education and training for health and social care professionals and family carers: 'education about dementia and capacity building', 'prepare about the stage and needs of palliative care/end-of-life care for the family members', and 'educate the family members regarding the dementia process, comprehensive care, and to do things in case of any emergency'. Moreover, family members and informal carers NGT group also selected their 2 and 3 priorities as 'develop national policy for the development of understanding and expertise among doctors and nurses' and 'trained up care givers for the people living with dementia'.

On the other hand, both policy planners and academics (educators and researchers) NGT groups emphasised research initiatives to build a database and explore the current situation of dementia in the context of Bangladesh. For example, the top 1 and 2 priorities identified by the policy planners NGT group were: 'continuous research activities for the development of a database to formulate dementia policy', and 'conduct a nationwide survey on dementia' to develop a database on dementia and explore the current situation of dementia care. On the other hand, the academics (educators and researchers) NGT group identified the 'need a research-based approach to identify core facilities already developed in Bangladesh for the people living with dementia and carers', 'explore the current situation and build a database about dementia in Bangladesh' and 'provide more funding and investment in dementia research' as their top 2 and 3 priorities.

Further, developing understanding and awareness about dementia was emphasised by both health and social care practitioners and policy planners NGT groups. For example, 'develop awareness and recognise dementia as a disease among the doctors, nurses, mass people etc.' was selected as the top 1 priority of health and social care practitioners NGT group, whereas 'develop understanding, and awareness on dementia among the health care professionals and other health care providers, including doctors, nurses, etc.' was top 3 for policy planners NGT group.

In addition, dementia care providers and health and social care practitioners NGT groups emphasised early detection, proper diagnosis, and treatment of dementia care. For example, the dementia care providers' NGT group ranked their top 1 as 'early detection and diagnosis of dementia'. On the other hand, health and social care practitioners' NGT group's top 2 priority was 'ensure proper diagnosis, and treatment of dementia in the right time'.

Moreover, both family members and informal carers and academics (educators and researchers) NGT groups prioritised developing and promoting health and social care

systems/infrastructure for people living with dementia. For example, the top 1 priority of family members and informal carers NGT group was to establish 'specialised hospitals for people living with dementia at central, local, and community levels' whereas 'provide more funding and investment in health and community care systems to improve care for people living with dementia' was the top 3 priority of academics (educators and researchers) NGT group.

Additionally, the health and social care practitioners' NGT group emphasised 'develop a common platform for a dementia support group with the involvement of different level stakeholders including doctors, nurses, social workers, policy planners, caregivers, dementia people, etc.' as their top 3 priority.

6.4 An Overview of NGT Findings and Reflection

The purpose of the NGT group discussions was to identify multi-sectoral stakeholders' priorities for dementia care policy and workforce development in Bangladesh. Overall, there are six main priorities and aspects reflected across the five (05) NGT groups discussions. These included: developing understanding and dementia awareness, education and training for health and social care professionals and family carers, early detection, proper diagnosis, and treatment, developing and promoting health and social care systems/infrastructure for people living with dementia, research initiatives to build a database and explore the current situation of dementia, and developing and promoting dementia support organisations/groups to provide support and needed services for people living with dementia and family carers.

All five NGT groups agreed on developing understanding and building awareness about dementia among the health and social care practitioners, family members and informal carers, and community people to recognise dementia as a disease. Further, providing dementia education and training for health and social care professionals, care providers, and family carers was also emphasised by most of the stakeholder groups. However, there were divergences and different views between groups on achieving these priorities. For instance, family members and informal carers NGT group prioritised formulating a national dementia care policy to develop understanding and awareness and improve expertise among doctors, nurses, and caregivers to ensure proper treatment and care for people living with dementia. In contrast, the policy planners NGT group advocated including dementia issues in current relevant national health and social policies. Although, the policy planners noted that strong commitment from the political parties and the government is needed to formulate a separate national dementia care policy in Bangladesh.

Further, the participants of the academics (educators and researchers), health and social care practitioners, and policy planners NGT group highlighted continuous research initiatives to explore the dementia situation and build a database to develop a national dementia care policy. Additionally, ensuring early diagnosis, up-to-date medicine, proper treatment, and comprehensive care was emphasised by the health and social care practitioners, dementia care providers, and family members and informal carers NGT group than other groups.

Virtual NGT interview was a good alternative during the COVID-19-related lockdown restrictions in Bangladesh to recruit and collect data from a wide range of stakeholders. Further, the researcher and co-facilitator found the online NGT protocol appropriate to make sense of NGT participants to conduct virtual NGT interviews. Moreover, most participants felt comfortable with the online NGT interview for sharing their ideas. However, there were a few technical challenges related to uninterrupted internet connection during the NGT process for all the participants. For example, two participants in the dementia care providers and academics (educators and researchers) NGT groups were disconnected after the round-robin idea generation stage due to a loss of internet connection and could not participate in the discussion and clarification stage. Although, the participants managed to reconnect in the voting and ranking stage, agreed with the created thematic ideas list, and finally contributed to identifying their group priorities. However, this has impacted the equal contribution of each participant in all stages of the NGT process.

In addition, the number of participants in the health and social care practitioners and dementia care providers NGT groups was four, respectively, less than intended. This low participation was likely because recruitment and commencement for NGT interviews were during the COVID-19 pandemic and with extreme pressure on health and social care services. More participants would have generated further ideas during the round-robin stage and contributed more discussions during the clarification and discussion stage. In addition, due to the COVID-19 restrictions, the NGT interviews were carried out online, and face-to-face discussions may have overcome the issues related to uninterrupted Internet access.

Noteworthy, every possible step has been taken to overcome the challenges of online NGT interviews. For example, all the processes of NGT interviews were open and transparent in front of the participants. Further, during the online NGT discussion session, the co-facilitator supported the researcher in recording and sharing the generated ideas, thematic ideas list and priority voting on a Word file on the computer screen accessible to all the participants. Additionally, the co-facilitator checked this data recording process to ensure it correctly reflected participants' views.

The next chapter will discuss the overall findings of this thesis and explore dementia policy learning and transferability from Scotland to Bangladesh based on synthesised findings of the Documentary Policy Analysis and Key Informant Interviews in Scotland and NGT stakeholders' responses in Bangladesh (discussed in the Final Discussion, recommendations, and conclusion Chapter 7).

Chapter Seven: Final Discussion, Recommendations, and Conclusion

7.1 Introduction

This study investigated and analysed Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches to determine the utility for application within Bangladesh. This research is the first systematic attempt to critically interrogate the transferable policy lessons from Scotland and identify multiple stakeholder policy aspirations and priorities within Bangladesh. This final discussion, recommendations, and conclusion chapter begins with the merits and limitations of the study, considers the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on study design and methods. The discussions of key findings is presented aligned with each of the four research questions, and interpreted in light of contemporary literature and policy developments that occurred following data collection. The chapter concludes with recommendations for future dementia care policy and workforce development, research, education and practice in Scotland and Bangladesh.

7.2 Merits and Limitations of the Study

In discussing and interpreting study findings it is important to recognise the research merits and limitations.

A strength of this study is the underpinning conceptual framework, a fusion and modification of the policy success framework based on McConnell's (2010) and Marsh and McConnell's (2010) existing three-level frameworks for evaluating the process, programme, and political level success in Scottish dementia care and workforce development policy. The synthesised policy success framework identified a list of key policy learning attributes and created a conceptual lens to scrutinise the evidence underpinning the development of a future national dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Bangladesh. This synthesised framework is a conceptual innovation by connecting Marsh and McConnell's (2010) success indicators with Dolowitz and Marsh's (2000) Policy Transfer Framework. Moreover, such conceptual innovations will add the value of corresponding the policy transfer literature with the policy success literature in dementia policy research while undertaking multi-level comparative policy implementation studies.

Although, the policy success framework (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a) was developed more than a decade ago and some argue that the policy success framework is more suitable to assess single policy initiative (McConnell, Greal and Lea, 2020), the present study has used a modified and synthesised policy success framework based on McConnell's (2010) and Marsh and McConnell's (2010) existing three-level frameworks to evaluate a broad and evolving set of policies. This has created a new possibility in the field of policy analysis by providing a robust and transparent set of indicators and dimensions to evaluate dementia policy success in Scotland. However, there were some challenges in assessing and distinguishing the process, programme and political success due to overlaps within and between these three dimensions (Marsh and McConnell, 2010a; Marsh and McConnell, 2010b). Therefore, to distinguish these dimensions and to minimise the issue of overlapping any discrepancies raised were resolved in consultation with the supervisors until a consensus decision was reached.

The integrative literature review reported in chapter 2, followed the established Five stage approach developed by Wittemore and Knafelz (2005). Although rigorously followed only a small evidence base was identified, with a paucity of policy implementation research from Scotland. No relevant dementia policy studies or other evidence was found for Bangladesh. While not unsurprising in terms of the known immaturity of dementia policy and infrastructure in Bangladesh, the lack of accessible evidence on the impact of Scottish policy was disappointing. Key informants hinted that evaluations of Scottish policy had been undertaken but it was not possible to determine if such evaluation reports exist or if these had been embargoed.

This study employed the exploratory sequential mixed methods design underpinned by philosophical pragmatism and policy learning, policy success and policy transfer theoretical and conceptual perspectives to collect both qualitative and quantitative data to provide a context and better understanding of research problems (Ammenwerth and Rigby, 2016; Bryman, 2016; Creswell, 2015; Hendren, Luo and Pandey, 2018; Palinkas *et al.*, 2015; Tzagkarakis and Kritas, 2022). This study conducted the documentary policy analysis framework with Scottish key informant interviews to collect qualitative data to evaluate the dementia policy success and identify tentative dementia policy learning for countries like Bangladesh. In the final stage, this study collected quantitative and qualitative data from the Nominal Group Technique group discussions with different stakeholders in Bangladesh to identify the issues and priorities of dementia care policy and workforce development in Bangladesh.

As explained earlier in the thesis, research planning and design coincided with the emergence of COVID-19. Methods had to be adapted recognising that health and social care policy stakeholders would have reduced availability. Furthermore, lockdown restrictions meant that data collection had to be undertaken at a distance from the key dementia policy stakeholders in Scotland and stakeholder groups in Bangladesh rather than the original plan for face-to-face data collection. Although it was challenging to communicate with potential participants due to COVID-19 restrictions, participant recruitment and completion of virtual data collection were supported by the supervisory team and national dementia organisations in Scotland and Bangladesh. Moreover, an adapted virtual NGT protocol was prepared and piloted to promote efficient management of the virtual NGT process for generating consensus within NGT discussions. This democratic and consensus-building approach provided each participant with an equal opportunity to share their ideas and contribute to identifying the group priorities of dementia care policy and workforce development in Bangladesh. The number of participants in key informant and Nominal group technique interviews was small. Although only five key policy stakeholders were recruited in key informant interviews in Scotland, recruitment of senior personnel from a range of national agencies, charities representing people affected by dementia including Scottish Government officials who were directly involved in the development or implementation of Scottish dementia policies helped to gather in-depth information and build an understanding of the influences, background stories, challenges, and lessons on dementia care policy development within Scotland. Moreover, this study used the documentary analysis framework in combination with key informant interviews to complement the information gathering through the key informant interviews and understand the dementia policy landscape and policy developments. Although, some of the policy documents, including confidential reports, evaluation reports, and meeting minutes, were not accessible as they were not in the public domain. Nonetheless a sufficient set of influential dementia care policy, and workforce development approaches were retrieved to evaluate evidence of dementia policy success and satisfy the study objectives.

In addition, twenty-five stakeholders took part in five virtual Nominal group discussions in Bangladesh, including (a) family members and informal carers of people living with dementia (n=5); (b) health and social care practitioners (n=4); (c) academics (educators and researchers) (n=7); (d) dementia care providers (n=4); and (e) policy planners (n=5). Although, the group sizes were smaller than anticipated (5-9 participants) (Potter, Gordon and Hamer, 2004), the involvement of multi-level stakeholder groups provided diverse perspectives to generate what appeared to be comprehensive lists of the key factors and considerations for future dementia care policy and workforce development approaches in Bangladesh.

Additionally, triangulation and complementarity are considered in this study to promote rigour within the exploratory sequential mixed methods design (Schoonenboom and Johnson, 2017; Tzagkarakis and Kritas, 2022). For example, the NGT findings have complimented the tentative recommendations and dementia policy learning from Scotland to Bangladesh derived from the synthesised findings of the documentary policy analysis and key informant interviews in Scotland.

7.3 Overview of Key Findings

The overview of key findings is structured around the four research objectives/questions by integrating the findings from the Integrative literature review, Documentary Policy Analysis with Key Informant Interviews and Nominal Group Technique Discussions. Marsh and McConnell's (2010) Policy Success and Dolowitz and Marsh's (2000) Policy Transfer Framework are underpinned to discuss the significant findings. Table 7.1 presents the overview of research objectives, research questions and methods of data collection.

Table 7. 1: Overview of Research Objectives, Research Questions and Methods of Data Collection

SL	Research Objectives	Research Questions	Method/Data/Evidence Source
1	To critically review the evidence base shaping dementia care and dementia workforce development policy and policy implementation within Scotland and Bangladesh.	What is known about shaping and implementation of dementia care and dementia workforce development policy within Scotland and Bangladesh?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrative literature review
2	To determine Scottish dementia policy scope, indicators of success and lessons for possible policy transfer to Bangladesh.	What is the scope and what are success indicators of Scottish dementia policy, and what are the lessons for possible policy transfer to Bangladesh?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentary policy analysis with Key informant interviews
3	To scope with multi-sectorial stakeholders in Bangladesh their aspirations and priorities for the development of dementia care policy.	What are the aspirations and priorities of multi-sectorial stakeholders in Bangladesh for the development of dementia care policy?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nominal Group Technique discussion
4	To make recommendations to inform future dementia policy development in Bangladesh.	What elements could be considered in the future dementia policy development in Bangladesh?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrative literature review • Documentary policy analysis with Key informant interviews • Nominal Group Technique discussion

7.3.1 Research Question One: What is known about shaping and implementation of dementia care and dementia workforce development policy within Scotland and Bangladesh?

From the literature review there is agreement across a number of studies suggesting Scottish dementia policy is considered to be progressive when compared to other European countries. However, there is only a limited research literature investigating Scottish dementia policy implementation and impact. The studies which do exist are often small with a tendency to focus on either a specific aspect of dementia policy or indirectly evaluate policy usefulness through scrutiny of specific services. For example, this might be a broad examination of post diagnostic support, or a study focussed on a particular stage of illness such as advanced dementia. Overall, there is a limited research base of variable quality investigating and reporting on Scottish dementia care policy and workforce development policy implementation and outcomes. Within the reviewed literature is an underlying assumption that one of the strengths of Scottish policy is that it is underpinned by rights-based approaches. Although intuitively appealing this assumption about the merits of rights-based approaches has not been empirically tested within the reviewed papers and is now so enshrined it would be difficult to determine. There is as expected absence of literature focussed on dementia care and related policies within Bangladesh.

Dementia is a global public health challenge (Naheed *et al.*, 2023). Due to population ageing both Scotland and Bangladesh face social problems and health challenges associated with increasing numbers of people living with dementia. Moreover, both family members and informal carers provided most of the care for older people with dementia living at home. However, each country has developed dementia national action plans, legislative frameworks and provisions, policies, approaches and program options for older people and addresses dementia care and workforce development differently. Further, each country has a different social, economic, and cultural orientation and perception and expectations of people living with dementia and their carers about dementia care and workforce development. Furthermore, Scotland and Bangladesh have distinct health and social care systems, political structures, and government capacities.

Developing and implementing the dementia care policy and related workforce development approach is in an early stage in Bangladesh, despite the increasing numbers of people diagnosed with dementia in Bangladesh (ICDDR-B, 2021). Bangladesh has no direct policies on dementia care and workforce development. The experience of dementia care in Bangladesh is challenging due to a lack of understanding and awareness of dementia among

the general people and healthcare workers, stigma and discrimination, limited resources and insufficient health and social care infrastructures, the lack of dementia education and training programs and shortage of trained healthcare professionals, which makes it difficult for people living with dementia, their families, and carers to access the information and support services they need. However, dementia care policy and workforce development planning are not prioritised in the country's national healthcare policy (Rahman *et al.*, 2017; World Health Organization, 2017b). Moreover, there is a paucity of research on dementia care and workforce development policy in Bangladesh (World Health Organization, 2017b). In addition, there is an absence of dementia care supportive health and social care infrastructure and professionals working in these settings are not yet prepared and skilled enough to provide necessary dementia care and support services for the people living with dementia and their families and carers in Bangladesh. Further, the integrative review findings of this study also found no studies discussing the dementia care policy implementation and related workforce development approaches in the context of Bangladesh. In addition, the findings of a recent cross-sectional study on the prevalence of dementia among older people and variation across different socio-demographic characteristics in Bangladesh also found an absence of research evidence and national-level strategies focused on dementia care for the increasing number of current and future dementia cases (Naheed *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, the ADI's recent report on From Plan to Impact mentioned that although in Bangladesh, dementia is referred to in existing grouped health plans and some development towards a plan, it is not considered as a separate health condition, and progress stalled (Alzheimer's Disease International, 2023). Despite these challenges, as a member of the World Health Organisation, development member of Alzheimer Disease International and government commitment to implement the Sustainable Development Goals, there are growing initiatives and recognition of developing policies and programs to provide appropriate dementia care and support services and improve the quality of life for people living with dementia, their families and carers in Bangladesh. For example, the Bangladesh government has developed some indirect policies related to dementia care, including the national older policy, the national health policy, the national mental health policy, and the population policy. In addition, some non-government sectors have recently taken a few initiatives to develop a dementia workforce to provide dementia care and support for people living with dementia and carers and family members in Bangladesh (Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh, 2018; Amin, 2017; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2013a; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2015; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2018b; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2021; Kabir *et al.*, 2013; Rahman *et al.*, 2017; Roy *et al.*, 2020; Sultana, 2019; Uddin *et al.*, 2019; World Health Organization, 2017b).

On the contrary, dementia is one of the significant public health priorities in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2010). Since 2010, the Scottish Government has developed and implemented national strategies and workforce development approaches based on the Charter of Rights for people with dementia to deliver world-class dementia care and treatment for people with dementia and their families to live well with dementia (Scottish Government, 2010; Scottish Government, 2017b). Further, the integrative review of this study identified research evidence related to dementia care policy development and implementation and related workforce development approaches in Scotland. For example, the dementia care policy concerning multi-component interventions, collaborative approach and comprehensive support is helpful in providing early and timely diagnosis and post-diagnostic support services and improving the quality of life for people living with dementia, their family, and carers (Dawson *et al.*, 2015; Górska *et al.*, 2013; Kelly and Innes, 2016; Lee, 2011; Lillo-Crespo *et al.*, 2018; Tolson *et al.*, 2016). In addition, the Scottish dementia care policy emphasises integrating health and social to provide appropriate care and support for people living with dementia and their family and carers (Astell *et al.*, 2014; Caine, 2014; Dawson *et al.*, 2015; Tolson *et al.*, 2016). Further, the dementia care policy in Scotland recognises specialised knowledge, necessary skills, and training for health and social care professionals to deliver quality care for people living with dementia (Surr and Gates, 2017; Surr *et al.*, 2019; Surr *et al.*, 2020).

However, this review found considerable gaps in dementia care policy development and implementation and related workforce development approaches in Scotland. For example, there is a lack of coordination of available services and continuity of the support workers to ensure early and timely diagnosis and post-diagnostic support guarantee of the national dementia care policy in Scotland (Górska *et al.*, 2013). Further, there are limited options for supporting people living with advanced dementia and their carers in Scotland (Lillo-Crespo *et al.*, 2018; Tolson *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, there is a lack of qualified health and social care practitioners involved in dementia care and a lack of evidence-informed education on advanced dementia care in Scotland (Lillo-Crespo *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, this integrative review identified no comprehensive policy research evidence to evaluate the role of national dementia care policy and workforce development approaches for people living with dementia, their family, and carers in Scotland. Further, there is no policy research evidence on monitoring and implementing national dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Scotland.

7.3.2 Research Question Two: What is the scope and what are success indicators of Scottish dementia policy, and what are the lessons for possible policy transfer to Bangladesh?

Scotland's dementia care policy and workforce development approach is much more mature, progressive and some argue world leading. Since 2010, Scotland has successfully developed and implemented national dementia care and workforce development policies and making significant progress in improving the quality of life for the people living with dementia and their carers and family members. The documentary policy analysis with key informant interviews identified scope and a list of success indicators of Scottish dementia care policy and workforce development approaches. For example, Scottish dementia care policy emphasises direct involvement and strong collaboration with different stakeholders to generate input and support from 'the bottom-up' in developing, updating, and improving dementia policy in Scotland (Alzheimer Scotland, 2009; Scottish Government, 2010; Scottish Government, 2011a; Scottish Government, 2011c; Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2015; Scottish Government, 2017b; Scottish Government, 2021b). Moreover, Scottish dementia care policy is based on a Rights-Based Approach to ensure the rights and dignity of those living with dementia and their family carers in Scotland (Alzheimer Scotland, 2009). Further, the Scottish Government has developed and implemented innovative service models of dementia care to provide diagnosis and post-diagnostic support service, integrated community support, and optimum care for people living with dementia, their families and carers in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b). Furthermore, the analysis found that the Promoting Excellence Framework supported the development of the necessary skills, knowledge, and competencies of health and social care workers to develop a dementia workforce and implement Scotland's national dementia care policy (Scottish Government, 2011a; Scottish Government, 2021b). In addition, dementia care is recognised as a national public health priority (Scottish Government, 2010), and there is a consensus among the different political parties in Scotland to develop and implement dementia care policy and workforce development framework to improve the quality of life for people living with dementia and their family and carers (Alzheimer Scotland, 2009). However, this study identified a lack of timely access to good quality post-diagnostic support, poor access to palliative care, insufficient funding, lack of end-of-life care services, and a lack of coordination between national and local partnership as barriers to the successful implementation of dementia care policy.

The documentary policy analysis with key informant interviews also identified a list of key lessons for possible policy transfer to Bangladesh. In Bangladesh, there is a lack of

comprehensive provisions in the existing national policies and legislation to provide dementia care and support services and protect the rights of people living with dementia, their families, and carers (Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2011; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2012; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2013a; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2013b; Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2018b). Therefore, this study found that Bangladesh can learn from the Scottish human rights-based dementia care approach to develop a national dementia care policy and legislative framework for ensuring the rights and dignity of people living with dementia, their families, and carers. Further, Bangladesh can consider ensuring specific funding and staff and developing competent health and social care workers to implement ambitious and innovative dementia service models. In addition, this study found that there is need to develop a collaboration and consensus among the political parties to develop and implement of national dementia care policy. However, these lessons for possible policy transfer to Bangladesh need to be considered tentative because Scotland and Bangladesh have very different national, economic, social, and historical contexts.

7.3.3 Research Question Three: What are the aspirations and priorities of multi-sectorial stakeholders in Bangladesh for the development of dementia care policy?

Nominal Group technique discussions identified a list of the aspirations and priorities of the multi-sectorial stakeholders in Bangladesh for the development of dementia care policy. These include developing understanding and dementia awareness, education and training for health and social care professionals and family carers, early detection, proper diagnosis, and treatment, developing and promoting health and social care systems/infrastructure for people living with dementia, research initiatives to build a database and explore the current situation of dementia, and developing and promoting dementia support organisations/groups to provide support and needed services for people living with dementia and family carers.

All five NGT groups prioritised on developing understanding and building awareness about dementia among the health and social care practitioners, family members and informal carers, and community people to recognise dementia as a disease. Further, providing dementia education and training for health and social care professionals, care providers, and family carers was also emphasised by most of the stakeholder groups. Additionally, NGT findings of this study emphasised to develop a common platform with the involvement of different level stakeholders including doctors, nurses, social workers, policy planners, caregivers, dementia

people, etc.' to provide information, advise and support for dementia care and promote dementia workforce development in Bangladesh.

However, there were divergences and different views between groups on achieving these priorities. For instance, family members and informal carers NGT group prioritised formulating a national dementia care policy to develop understanding and awareness and improve expertise among doctors, nurses, and caregivers to ensure proper treatment and care for people living with dementia. In contrast, the policy planners NGT group advocated including dementia issues in current relevant national health and social policies. Although, the policy planners noted that strong commitment from the political parties and the government is needed to formulate a separate national dementia care policy in Bangladesh.

Further, the participation of the academics (educators and researchers), health and social care practitioners, and policy planners NGT group highlighted continuous research initiatives to explore the dementia situation and build a database to develop a national dementia care policy. Additionally, ensuring early diagnosis, up-to-date medicine, proper treatment, and comprehensive care was emphasised by the health and social care practitioners, dementia care providers, and family members and informal carers NGT group than other groups.

7.3.4 Research Question Four: What elements could be considered in the future dementia policy development in Bangladesh?

This study identified a list of elements to make recommendations to inform future dementia policy development in Bangladesh based on the integrative literature review, the documentary policy analysis framework with key informant interviews in Scotland and Nominal Group Technique discussions in Bangladesh.

Documentary policy analysis with key informant interviews in Scotland identified successful elements of Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches using a synthesised policy success framework based on McConnell's (2010) and Marsh and McConnell's (2010) existing three-level frameworks. On the other hand, Nominal Group Technique discussions in Bangladesh identified the priorities of the multi-sectorial stakeholders in Bangladesh that are important to them regarding future dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Bangladesh. These group priorities supported identifying the transferable and useful policy elements of Scottish dementia care policies and

workforce development approaches in Bangladesh based on Dolowitz and Marsh's (2000) Policy Transfer Framework.

For example, findings of the documentary policy analysis framework with key informant interviews in Scotland found that stakeholder direct involvement in developing national dementia care policies and workforce development approaches is one of the process successes of Scottish dementia care policy (Alzheimer Scotland, 2009; Scottish Government, 2010; Scottish Government, 2011a; Scottish Government, 2011c; Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2015; Scottish Government, 2017b; Scottish Government, 2021b). This successful policy element was also identified as the top three priority of the health and social care practitioners' NGT group for future dementia care policy in Bangladesh. This study found that Bangladesh can develop a future national dementia care policy and workforce development approach with the direct involvement of people living with dementia, their families, and carers, the voluntary sector, and cross-party support.

Further, the documentary policy analysis framework with key informant interviews demonstrated that a Right-based dementia care approach based on the Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers developed a foundation to develop a national dementia care policy in Scotland (Alzheimer Scotland, 2009). On the other hand, recognising human rights and ensuring the dignity of people living with dementia and their carers identified as one of the important priorities of family members and informal carers of people living with dementia NGT group in Bangladesh. Therefore, this study found the Right-based dementia care approach a potentially useful element in developing future national dementia care policy in Bangladesh.

In addition, findings of the documentary policy analysis framework with key informant interviews found that developing and implementing innovative dementia service models is another significant success in Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches to provide diagnosis and post-diagnostic support, integrated community support, and optimum care for people living with dementia, their families, and carers (Scottish Government, 2013; Scottish Government, 2017b). The findings of NGT discussions also emphasised improving early detection, proper diagnosis, and treatment of dementia in Bangladesh. This study's findings show that developing innovative dementia service models is a potentially useful element of the Scottish dementia care policy in developing a successful national dementia care policy in Bangladesh.

Moreover, the documentary policy analysis with key informant interview findings identified Promoting Excellence Frameworks as another programme success of Scottish dementia care

policy and workforce development approaches to develop health and social care workers' necessary skills, knowledge, and competencies (Scottish Government, 2011a; Scottish Government, 2021b). Further, integrative literature review findings of this study also found that Scottish dementia care policy recognises specialised knowledge, necessary skills, and training for health and social care professionals to deliver quality care for people living with dementia (Surr and Gates, 2017; Surr et al., 2019; Surr et al., 2020). On the other hand, the NGT findings found that most of the top three priorities of the five NGT groups emphasised providing education and training for health and social care professionals and family carers. Thus, this study identified Promoting Excellence Framework as useful for Bangladesh to develop competent and skilled health and social care workers to improve dementia care services and quality of life for people living with dementia, their family, and carers.

Furthermore, the documentary policy analysis with key informant interview findings of this study found that recognising dementia as a national public health priority (Scottish Government, 2010), and agreement among the different national political parties to develop a national dementia care policy is a significant political success of Scottish dementia care policy (Alzheimer Scotland, 2009). The NGT findings of this study also acknowledge this successful element. For example, the policy planners NGT group emphasised strong commitment from the political parties and the government to formulate a national dementia care policy in Bangladesh. Therefore, this study's findings identified political parties' support, consensus, and government recognition of dementia as a national public health priority as potentially useful elements of Scottish dementia care policy to develop future dementia care policy in Bangladesh.

7.3.5 Critical/ Reflective Discussion of what this Study Adds to what is Already Known

Integrating the policy success and policy transfer frameworks has not been done in previous studies about dementia care policy and workforce development approaches. Underpinned by a modified and synthesised framework based on McConnell's (2010) and Marsh and McConnell's (2010) policy success frameworks so far, this study has taken the first step in evaluating the process, programme, and political success of Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches to determine the utility for application within Bangladesh. That is, this study developed new knowledge and a new way of evaluating the success of dementia care policies and workforce development approaches and learning and transferring the dementia care policy to other countries like Bangladesh based on research evidence, who are yet to develop a national dementia care policy and workforce development approach.

7.3.6 Interpretation of the Study Findings in Light of New Literature

This study conducted an integrative literature review to critically examine the development and implementation of national dementia care strategies and related dementia workforce development approaches in Scotland and Bangladesh. The review included 22 research evidence published from 2010 to 2020 to address the review purpose and questions. However, the review found a small amount of research literature about dementia policy in Scotland and an absence of research regarding dementia policy within Bangladesh. This review's key findings are discussed around five major themes, dementia as a public health concern, implementation of the principles of public health policy, provision of post-diagnostic support, development of service and care infrastructure, and preparation and development of the dementia workforce.

It is mentionable that, in 2023, the Dementia Service Development Centre (DSDC), University of Stirling, prepared an umbrella review focussed on Dementia Policy in Scotland (Dementia Service Development Centre, 2023). The review aim was to understand what is known and not known on a series of specific issues identified by the Scottish Government to inform a new Dementia Strategy in Scotland. The review has included 289 research works published from 2017 to 2023 and provided a broad overview of the experiences of people with dementia and their care partners and their engagement with care and support services available to them. This review identified eleven key themes to address the review questions. These include prevention of dementia, living well with dementia, remaining living at home and connected to the community, dementia support models, experience of NHS community, specialist and hospital-based services, experience of care homes and end-of-life services, stigma and stereotypes in dementia, inequality in dementia, support for people with protected characteristics, support for care partners, and impact of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Although, the umbrella review identified a wide range of care models and interventions to support people with dementia and their care partners to live well with dementia. However, the review identified significant gaps in dementia care policy in Scotland. For example, there is a need to improve the education of primary and acute health care staff and the provision of care in hospitals. This finding is in line with the integrative review of this thesis. For example, like umbrella review findings, the integrative review of this study also found that health and social care workers need specialised knowledge, necessary skills, and dementia training for their professional development to deliver quality care in healthcare settings in Scotland (Surr and Gates, 2017; Surr et al., 2019; Surr et al., 2020). Moreover, key themes identified and discussed in the umbrella review are similar to the findings of the integrative review of this

study, including the development of service and care infrastructure and preparation and development of the dementia workforce. In addition, this umbrella review's findings align with the present study findings. For example, potentially useful elements of Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches are supported by this umbrella review's findings.

Further, Muirhead (2023) conducted a convergent parallel mixed methods study on the role of technology-enabled dementia education (TEDE) and training needs for health and social care practitioners (HSCP) in rural Scotland, which also aligns with the findings of this present integrative review. The study (Muirhead, 2023) findings suggested that rural HSCP are accepting of technology for dementia education with training needs greatest among acute care practitioners. Further, the findings resulted in practical recommendations for policy change and for the design and delivery of TEDE for rural HSCP (Muirhead, 2023). The present integrative review findings also suggest dementia education and training needs for the professional development of health and social care practitioners in Scotland (Surr and Gates, 2017; Surr et al., 2020).

In addition, Phenwan (2023) conducted a multimethod qualitative study in Scotland to improve understanding of the initiation and revision of Advance Care Planning (ACP) with and for people with dementia by ensuring that their future plans can be put into practice at the appropriate time with the appropriate people. The study found that people with dementia relationally co-created their ACP with key persons who had an established, trusting relationship with them. They initiated or revised their ACP prior to the diagnosis and throughout the disease trajectory, emphasising the iterative nature of the ACP. However, the findings suggested insufficient support for Health Care Practitioners (HCPs) for the ACP process (Phenwan, 2023). This finding is consistent with the integrative review findings of this thesis. For example, the integrative review of this study found that although advanced dementia education for health and social care practitioners and family carers is essential for better advanced dementia care and palliative care experiences (Lillo-Crespo *et al.*, 2018; Tolson *et al.*, 2016), there is a lack of evidence-informed education on advanced dementia care among the professional and non-professional workforce in European countries, including Scotland (Lillo-Crespo *et al.*, 2018).

7.3.7 Interpretation of Findings in Light of Recent Dementia Policy Developments

This study critically evaluates the process, programme, and political level success of Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches developed and implemented from 2007 to 2021 in combination with key informant interviews with policy stakeholders in Scotland. The analysis identified a list of factors that support to develop and implement dementia care policy and workforce development approach in Scotland. These include a rights-based approach, involvement of multi-level stakeholders, development of innovative practice models and government commitment and agreement among the political parties.

In 2023, the Scottish Government published the fourth national Dementia Strategy for the next ten years with a commitment to upholding rights, civic participation, social inclusion, support, and care for people living with dementia in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2023a). This study found that like previous dementia strategies developed and implemented since 2010, the new dementia strategy also emphasised on rights-based dementia care approach to upholding the human rights of people living with dementia and their care partners throughout their dementia journey. In addition, this strategy prioritised specialised education and training needs of health and social care workers to develop a skilled and knowledgeable dementia workforce to provide quality dementia care. In addition, this new strategy also acknowledged some challenges to the successful implementation of dementia care policies in Scotland, including significant waiting times for assessment and the absence of a seamless diagnostic pathway and treatments, inconsistent approaches to commissioning and delivery of post-diagnostic support (PDS) and absence dedicated and specific funding (Scottish Government, 2023a). Further, national charities have expressed disappointment that a new Scottish government dementia strategy did not come with priorities and spending plans (BBC, 2023). These findings are aligned with the present study findings of the documentary policy analysis with the key informant interviews in Scotland.

However, this study identified some significant changes in the new dementia strategy. For example, this is a long-term basis strategy compared to the earlier three dementia strategies with an ambitious long-term commitment to those living with dementia and their unpaid carers. Further, this strategy proposed to develop a two-year delivery plan to implement the strategy and to ensure delivery and accountability (Age Scotland, 2023). In addition, the new strategy took a co-productive approach and developed based on national-level consultations with a wide range of professions and practitioners, including members from equality organisations (Scottish Government, 2022). Although, this strategy was said to be informed by an umbrella review focussed on what is known and not known about Scottish dementia policy (Dementia

Service Development Centre, 2023). Some analysts contend that the absence of robust impact evaluations of the previous National Dementia Strategies, suggests a short-sighted approach to developing the fourth National Dementia Strategy (Alzheimer Scotland, 2022).

7.4 COVID-19 Pandemic Impact on Study Design and Methods

This research was designed during the COVID-19 pandemic, and pandemic-related public health restrictions enforced by the government of Scotland and Bangladesh impacted the Participant recruitment and data collection process. The researcher conducted virtual Key informant interviews and NGT discussions with the key policy stakeholders and different stakeholder groups in Scotland and Bangladesh due to the ongoing COVID-19 restrictions. This virtual data collection process has limited the researcher to observe the participants' non-verbal communication. Moreover, technology difficulties and uninterrupted internet connection were possible sources of challenge during the virtual data collection process and caused some initial interruptions to Key informant interviews and NGT discussions. Therefore, the researcher had to adapt the data collection and participant recruitment process throughout the study. However, recruiting participants and virtual data collection was not a significant challenge because of the supervisory team support, the researcher's doctoral training experiences and academic involvement in the Gerontology and Geriatric Welfare programme at the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. Further, this continuous adaptation helps the researcher to learn and develop experiences to cope with an extreme situation and balance between what is possible and good strong science.

7.5 Recommendations

Based on the findings, this study proposed several recommendations on dementia care and workforce development policy, future research, practice, and education. However, as the findings are shared and recommendations are proposed, the researcher believes that it will be important that such suggestions are made in a way that is culturally competent and through the decolonised lens. Cultural competence is understood as a collection of congruent behaviours, attitudes and policies that enables individuals, systems, or agencies to work effectively in cross-cultural situations and contexts (Cross, 1989; Frawley, Russell and Sherwood, 2020). In the introductory discussion of positionality (Section 1.3), it was acknowledged that there exists a tension between the Western colonial perspective and what is appropriate to do in Bangladesh, since these two are very alternative. The researcher is

from Bangladesh and has chosen to study in a Western way of understanding of what research is, has interpreted the findings through that Westernised lens, therefore, the researcher recognises that the findings and recommendations of this study need to be decolonised to optimise usefulness within the context of Bangladesh. Decolonisation is the process of undoing of colonialism and becoming independent of the imperial nations. Decolonization of research is a dynamic process, focussed on redefinition of the meaning of research from and within the community and local stakeholders (Datta, 2018). Applying a decolonised lens will allow the researcher to approach Western policies with a critically conscientized mindset so that the Western-centric policies are not blindly promoted for adoption in the global South. Accordingly, considerations of cultural competence will be important when the findings from this study are disseminated and shared with different audiences in Bangladesh. To help achieve this I have established relationships with a number of key organisations including the Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh and Dementia Care Foundation. The process of achieving a decolonised set of recommendations will take time and collaborative conversations, nonetheless a few illustrative examples are now considered.

For example, attitudes and beliefs towards ageing, dementia and caregiving are different between the two countries and can impact on the transfer of successful indicators of Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches directly to Bangladesh. Further, cultural differences may impact on the acceptance and implementation of the successful elements of Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Bangladesh. For example, although the synthesised Policy Success Framework (McConnell, 2010; Marsh and McConnell, 2010a) used in this study did not include cultural aspects as success indicators to evaluate Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches, the Policy Transfer Framework (Dolowitz and Marsh, 2000) underpinned this study did consider cultural aspects (attitudes, cultural values, cultural proximity, ideology, language) as possible constraints or facilitators on policy transfer from Scotland to Bangladesh (Discussed in section 3.4 of the Chapter 3). Therefore, to develop a culturally competent dementia care policy based on the policy learning and policy transfer of Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches, Bangladesh needs to appreciate and consider the cultural differences between Scotland and Bangladesh and adapt policies based on the attitudes, beliefs, customs, values, and cultural context of Bangladesh. Accordingly, recommendations arising from this research are tempered with caution and appreciation that direct transfer or imposition of Western centric policy without cultural and local adaptation would be naïve.

7.5.1 Recommendations for Dementia Care Policy and Workforce Development

The findings of this study are significant in developing a policy proposition for future dementia care and workforce development in Bangladesh. For example, to develop dementia services and improve the quality of life for people living with dementia and their carers, policymakers of Bangladesh can learn from the Scottish success experiences of developing and implementing dementia care policies and workforce development approaches. However, there are known differences between Scotland and Bangladesh that must be appreciated and considered in determining opportunities for policy learning and transfer.

This study's findings confirm that multiple stakeholders' perspectives and views are helpful to plan services that are welcomed, wanted and deliverable for people living with dementia, their family members, carers, health and social care professionals, academician, researchers, and policymakers.

The findings also demonstrate the value of a national workforce development framework aligned to the skills and knowledge that practitioners in different roles require to provide good quality dementia care. Such a framework has perceived merit and could be adapted for Bangladesh, and would have the potential to improve practitioner knowledge and skills and thereby enhance the competencies of health and social care workers to improve dementia care services and quality of life for people living with dementia, their families, and carers.

In addition, this study found a need for government commitment and consensus among the different political parties to develop and implement a national dementia care policy in Bangladesh.

7.5.2 Recommendations for Research

The following recommendations for future research in Scotland and Bangladesh are derived from this study:

This study found no comprehensive research on implementing and evaluating Scottish dementia care policies. Future research to evaluate the impact of dementia care policies on the life of people living with dementia and their carers can contribute to identifying the barriers and facilitators of dementia care policy implementation at the national level.

Further, this study found a lack of comprehensive research-based evidence on practice models of dementia care policies in Scotland. Therefore, research is needed to evaluate the success of innovative dementia care practice models to improve the quality of life for people living with dementia, their families, and carers.

In addition, the documentary policy analysis and key informant interviews found that the Charter of Rights for people with dementia and their carers has contributed to developing the foundation base of national dementia care policy and workforce development approaches in Scotland. However, there is no comprehensive research to evaluate the role of the Charter of Rights for people with dementia and their carers. Therefore, future research needs to evaluate the role of the human rights-based dementia care approach in developing and implementing national dementia care policy, and workforce development approaches in Scotland.

Moreover, this study's findings show that health and social care integration faces challenges in implementing dementia care policy in Scotland. Future research needs to identify barriers and facilitators of health and social care integration in Scotland and explore the prospects of lesson drawing for other countries like Bangladesh to develop a health and social care integration system to implement dementia care policy.

This study found no research-based evidence about dementia service provisions and practices in Bangladesh. Research is required to identify the existing dementia care services and priorities with the involvement of different stakeholders to develop an evidence base knowledge for future dementia care policy in Bangladesh.

Although the initial study design intended to identify the barriers and facilitators of dementia care policy transfer from Scotland to Bangladesh, this objective/question did not explore due to the COVID-19 pandemic impact and time constraints. Therefore, future studies are required to examine the barriers and facilitators of dementia care policy learning and transfer from Scotland to Bangladesh.

7.5.3 Recommendations for Practice and Practice Education

This study proposed the following recommendations for practice and practice education:

The Nominal Group Technique (NGT) findings of this study emphasise developing specialised dementia hospitals and health care infrastructure to provide dementia care services in

Bangladesh. So, the government of Bangladesh needs to take the necessary initiatives to establish specialised dementia care services and improve health and social care infrastructure.

In addition, the findings of the documentary policy analysis and key informant interviews found that successful implementation of dementia care policies requires specific staff and sufficient funding. Therefore, the government must ensure dedicated funding and specific staff to implement national dementia care policies successfully.

The NGT findings of this study revealed that in Bangladesh, there is a lack of knowledge and understanding about dementia among health and social care professionals, including doctors, nurses, social workers, and therapists. The NGT findings also emphasised that health and social care professionals need expertise in dementia care and treatment. Such findings suggest the need to introduce dementia care and treatment in the education and training curriculum for health and social care professionals in Bangladesh. There is evidence that health and social care workers require culturally relevant and dementia specific education and training to provide quality care for the people living with dementia and their carers (Clark *et al.*, 2018; Hulko *et al.*, 2021; Hulko, Wilson and Balestrery, 2019). Therefore, the need for culturally appropriate dementia care education and training is recommended as a priority for Bangladesh. In addition, the NGT findings also identified a lack of knowledge and understanding of the family members and informal carers in Bangladesh. Moreover, the integrative literature review identified the need to provide appropriate knowledge and training for family members and informal carers of people living with dementia in Scotland. Therefore, to develop knowledge and understanding of the family members and informal carers, education and training need to be provided for them in Scotland and Bangladesh. This study findings also revealed that Dementia Champions Programme supports the health and social care workers to develop the necessary knowledge and skills to promote the quality of care for people living with dementia in acute healthcare sectors. Therefore, other countries like Bangladesh can develop similar programmes to develop the knowledge and skills of health and social care professionals.

7.6 Conclusion

This explorative sequential mixed methods study investigated and analysed Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches to determine the utility for application

within Bangladesh. Moreover, the present study identified the issues and priorities of future dementia care policy and workforce development approaches in Bangladesh. This study identified a bottom-up approach and direct involvement of a wide range of stakeholders in the policy-making process, a Right-based dementia care approach, bold commitment of the government and ambitious and innovative practice models, Promoting Excellence Framework for developing a dementia workforce and recognising dementia as a national public health priority and political parties consensus to improve dementia care are the potentially useful elements of Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Bangladesh to develop national dementia care policy and workforce development approach. However, the transferability of these successful elements of Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Bangladesh may not be easy and smooth. Further, there are differences in health and social care structure, culture, people's perceptions and expectations and government capacity between Scotland and Bangladesh. Therefore, the transferability of these potentially useful elements of Scottish dementia care policies, and workforce development approaches in Bangladesh is tentative and needs to be adapted based on the context of Bangladesh and considered as voluntary policy transfer and lesson drawing from the Scottish experiences. Moreover, there should be an inspiration rather than a direct copy of the Scottish dementia care policy experiences.

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Appendices

Appendices Chapter Two-Literature Review

Appendix 2.1: Details Result of Selected Databases and Search Terms

SL No	Database	Search Terms/ Query	Limiters/Expanders	Results	Last Run Via
01	Social Science Citation Index	(Dementia OR Alzheimer OR "Alzheimer's disease") AND ALL=("care home" OR "care homes" OR "care facility" OR "care settings" OR "residential home" OR "residential care" OR "nursing home" OR "nursing homes" OR "nursing care" OR "long term care" OR "home care" OR "social care" OR "community care") AND ALL=("workforce development" OR "workforce education" OR "workforce planning" OR "workforce training" OR "professional training" OR "nursing training") AND ALL=(policy OR guidelines OR plan OR "action plan" OR directions Or program OR legislations OR act OR law OR regulation OR circular OR "constitutional directions") AND ALL=(approaches OR strategies OR framework OR model OR intervention OR "quality improvement" OR "service planning" OR "human re-source planning" OR "service reform" OR "strategic planning") AND ALL=(Development OR Implementation) AND ALL=(Research OR Study OR Studies OR Survey OR Investigation)	LANGUAGE: (English) AND DOCUMENT TYPES: (Article) Timespan: 2010-2020.	09	Full search string
02	PubMed	(Dementia OR Alzheimer OR "Alzheimer's disease" AND ("care home" OR "care homes" OR "care facility" OR "care settings" OR "residential home" OR "residential care" OR "nursing home" OR "nursing homes" OR "nursing care" OR "long term care" OR "home care" OR "social care" OR "community care") AND ("workforce development" OR "workforce education" OR "workforce planning" OR "workforce training" OR "professional training" OR "nursing training") AND (policy OR guidelines OR plan OR "action plan" OR directions Or program OR legislations OR act OR law OR regulation OR circular OR "constitutional directions") AND (approaches OR strategies OR framework OR model OR intervention OR "quality improvement" OR "service planning" OR "human resource planning" OR "service reform" OR "strategic planning") AND (Development OR Implementation) AND (Research OR Study OR Studies OR Survey OR Investigation)	LANGUAGE: (English) AND DOCUMENT TYPES: (Article) Timespan: 2010-2020.	06	Full search string
03	emerald	(Dementia OR Alzheimer OR "Alzheimer's disease" AND ("care home" OR "care homes" OR "care facility" OR "care settings" OR "residential home" OR "residential care" OR "nursing home" OR "nursing homes" OR "nursing care" OR "long term care" OR "home care" OR "social care" OR "community care") AND ("workforce development" OR "workforce education" OR "workforce planning" OR "workforce training" OR "professional training" OR "nursing training") AND (policy OR guidelines OR plan OR "action plan" OR directions Or program OR legislations OR act OR law OR regulation OR circular OR "constitutional directions") AND (approaches OR strategies OR framework OR model OR intervention OR "quality improvement" OR "service planning" OR "human re-source planning" OR "service reform" OR "strategic planning") AND (Development OR Implementation) AND (Research OR Study OR Studies OR Survey OR Investigation))	LANGUAGE: (English) AND DOCUMENT TYPES: (Article) Timespan: 2010-2020.	1953	Full search string

SL No	Database	Search Terms/ Query	Limiters/Expanders	Results	Last Run Via
04	Social Care Online	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - JournalTitle:'Dementia OR Alzheimer OR "Alzheimers disease" - AND JournalTitle:"care home" OR "care homes" OR "care facility" OR "care settings" OR "residential home" OR "residential care" OR "nursing home" OR "nursing homes" OR "nursing care" OR "long term care" OR "home care" OR "social care" OR "community care" - AND JournalTitle:"workforce development" OR "workforce education" OR "workforce planning" OR "workforce training" OR "professional training" OR "nursing training" - AND JournalTitle:'policy OR guidelines OR plan OR "action plan" OR directions Or program OR legislations OR act OR law OR regulation OR circular OR "constitutional directions" - OR JournalTitle:'approaches OR strategies OR framework OR model OR intervention OR "quality improvement" OR "service planning" OR "human re-source planning" OR "service reform" OR "strategic planning" - AND JournalTitle:'Development OR Implementation' - AND JournalTitle:'Research OR Study OR Studies OR Survey OR Investigation' 	LANGUAGE: (English) AND DOCUMENT TYPES: (Article) Timespan: 2010-2020.	103	Using selected words/ combination of individual words (applied full search terms only use AND between Policy and Approaches)
05	Scopus	(dementia OR alzheimer OR "Alzheimer's disease") AND ("care home" OR "care homes" OR "care facility" OR "care settings" OR "residential home" OR "residential care" OR "nursing home" OR "nursing homes" OR "nursing care" OR "long term care" OR "home care" OR "social care" OR "community care") AND ("workforce development" OR "workforce education" OR "workforce planning" OR "workforce training" OR "professional training" OR "nursing training") AND (policy OR guidelines OR plan OR "action plan" OR directions OR program OR legislations OR act OR law OR regulation OR circular OR "constitutional directions") AND (approaches OR strategies OR framework OR model OR intervention OR "quality improvement" OR "service planning" OR "human resource planning" OR "service reform" OR "strategic planning") AND (development OR implementation) AND (research OR study OR studies OR survey OR investigation)	LANGUAGE: (English) AND DOCUMENT TYPES: (Article) Timespan: 2010-2020.	229	Full search string
06	CINAHL Complete	(Dementia OR Alzheimer OR "Alzheimer's disease") AND ("care home" OR "care homes" OR "care facility" OR "care settings" OR "residential home" OR "residential care" OR "nursing home" OR "nursing homes" OR "nursing care" OR "long term care" OR "home care" OR "social care" OR "community care") AND ("workforce development" OR "workforce education" OR "workforce planning" OR "workforce training" OR "professional training" OR "nursing training") AND (policy OR guidelines OR plan OR "action plan" OR directions Or program OR legislations OR act OR law OR regulation OR circular OR "constitutional directions") AND (approaches OR strategies OR framework OR model OR intervention OR "quality improvement" OR "service planning" OR "human re-source planning" OR "service reform" OR "strategic planning") AND (Development OR Implementation) AND (Research OR Study OR Studies OR Survey OR Investigation)	Limiters - Published Date: 20100101-20201231; Peer Reviewed Expanders - Also search within the full text of the articles; Apply equivalent subjects Narrow by Language: - English Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	467	Full search string

SL No	Database	Search Terms/ Query	Limiters/Expanders	Results	Last Run Via
07	Medline	(Dementia OR Alzheimer OR "Alzheimer's disease") AND ("care home" OR "care homes" OR "care facility" OR "care settings" OR "residential home" OR "residential care" OR "nursing home" OR "nursing homes" OR "nursing care" OR "long term care" OR "home care" OR "social care" OR "community care") AND ("workforce development" OR "workforce education" OR "workforce planning" OR "workforce training" OR "professional training" OR "nursing training") AND (policy OR guidelines OR plan OR "action plan" OR directions Or program OR legislations OR act OR law OR regulation OR circular OR "constitutional directions") AND (approaches OR strategies OR framework OR model OR intervention OR "quality improvement" OR "service planning" OR "human resource planning" OR "service reform" OR "strategic planning") AND (Development OR Implementation) AND (Research OR Study OR Studies OR Survey OR Investigation)	Limiters - Scholarly (Peer Reviewed) Journals; Date of Publication: 20100101-20201231 Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	05	Full search string
08	SocINDEX with Full Text	(Dementia OR Alzheimer OR "Alzheimer's disease") AND ("care home" OR "care homes" OR "care facility" OR "care settings" OR "residential home" OR "residential care" OR "nursing home" OR "nursing homes" OR "nursing care" OR "long term care" OR "home care" OR "social care" OR "community care") AND ("workforce development" OR "workforce education" OR "workforce planning" OR "workforce training" OR "professional training" OR "nursing training") AND (policy OR guidelines OR plan OR "action plan" OR directions Or program OR legislations OR act OR law OR regulation OR circular OR "constitutional directions") AND (approaches OR strategies OR framework OR model OR intervention OR "quality improvement" OR "service planning" OR "human resource planning" OR "service reform" OR "strategic planning") AND (Development OR Implementation) AND (Research OR Study OR Studies OR Survey OR Investigation)	Limiters - Scholarly (Peer Reviewed) Journals; Date of Publication: 20100101-20201231 Expanders - Also search within the full text of the articles; Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	176	Full search string
09	Health Source: Nursing/Academic Edition	(Dementia OR Alzheimer OR "Alzheimer's disease") AND ("care home" OR "care homes" OR "care facility" OR "care settings" OR "residential home" OR "residential care" OR "nursing home" OR "nursing homes" OR "nursing care" OR "long term care" OR "home care" OR "social care" OR "community care") AND ("workforce development" OR "workforce education" OR "workforce planning" OR "workforce training" OR "professional training" OR "nursing training") AND (policy OR guidelines OR plan OR "action plan" OR directions Or program OR legislations OR act OR law OR regulation OR circular OR "constitutional directions") AND (approaches OR strategies OR framework OR model OR intervention OR "quality improvement" OR "service planning" OR "human re-source planning" OR "service reform" OR "strategic planning") AND (Development OR Implementation) AND (Research OR Study OR Studies OR Survey OR Investigation)	Limiters - Scholarly (Peer Reviewed) Journals; Published Date: 20100101-20201231; Publication Type: Academic Journal Expanders - Also search within the full text of the articles; Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	116	Full search string
10	APA PsycArticles	(Dementia OR Alzheimer OR "Alzheimer's disease") AND ("care home" OR "care homes" OR "care facility" OR "care settings" OR "residential home" OR "residential care" OR "nursing home" OR "nursing homes" OR "nursing care" OR "long term care" OR "home care" OR "social care" OR "community care") AND ("workforce development" OR "workforce education" OR "workforce planning" OR "workforce training" OR "professional training" OR "nursing training") AND (policy OR guidelines OR plan OR "action plan" OR directions Or program OR legislations OR act OR law OR regulation OR circular OR "constitutional directions") AND (approaches OR strategies OR framework OR model OR intervention OR "quality improvement" OR "service planning" OR "human resource planning" OR "service reform" OR "strategic planning") AND (Development OR Implementation) AND (Research OR Study OR Studies OR Survey OR Investigation)	Limiters - Published Date: 20100101-20201231; Scholarly (Peer Reviewed) Journals Expanders - Also search within the full text of the articles; Apply equivalent subjects	26	Full search string

SL No	Database	Search Terms/ Query	Limiters/Expanders	Results	Last Run Via
		"service planning" OR "human re-source planning" OR "service reform" OR "strategic planning") AND (Development OR Implementation) AND (Research OR Study OR Studies OR Survey OR Investigation)	Narrow by Language: - english Search modes - Boolean/Phrase		
11	Education Source	(Dementia OR Alzheimer OR "Alzheimer's disease") AND ("care home" OR "care homes" OR "care facility" OR "care settings" OR "residential home" OR "residential care" OR "nursing home" OR "nursing homes" OR "nursing care" OR "long term care" OR "home care" OR "social care" OR "community care") AND ("workforce development" OR "workforce education" OR "workforce planning" OR "workforce training" OR "professional training" OR "nursing training") AND (policy OR guidelines OR plan OR "action plan" OR directions Or program OR legislations OR act OR law OR regulation OR circular OR "constitutional directions") AND (approaches OR strategies OR framework OR model OR intervention OR "quality improvement" OR "service planning" OR "human re-source planning" OR "service reform" OR "strategic planning") AND (Development OR Implementation) AND (Research OR Study OR Studies OR Survey OR Investigation)	Limiters - Scholarly (Peer Reviewed) Journals; Published Date: 20100101-20201231 Expanders - Also search within the full text of the articles; Apply equivalent subjects Narrow by Language: - english Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	90	Full search string
12	Psychology and Behavioral Sciences Collection	(Dementia OR Alzheimer OR "Alzheimer's disease") AND ("care home" OR "care homes" OR "care facility" OR "care settings" OR "residential home" OR "residential care" OR "nursing home" OR "nursing homes" OR "nursing care" OR "long term care" OR "home care" OR "social care" OR "community care") AND ("workforce development" OR "workforce education" OR "workforce planning" OR "workforce training" OR "professional training" OR "nursing training") AND (policy OR guidelines OR plan OR "action plan" OR directions Or program OR legislations OR act OR law OR regulation OR circular OR "constitutional directions") AND (approaches OR strategies OR framework OR model OR intervention OR "quality improvement" OR "service planning" OR "human re-source planning" OR "service reform" OR "strategic planning") AND (Development OR Implementation) AND (Research OR Study OR Studies OR Survey OR Investigation)	Limiters - Peer Reviewed; Published Date: 20100101-20201231 Expanders - Also search within the full text of the articles; Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	159	Full search string
13	EThOS	Dementia AND Care AND Policy	LANGUAGE: (English) AND DOCUMENT TYPES: (Thesis) Timespan: 2010-2020.	62	Using selected words/ combination of individual words
14	Google Scholar	(Dementia OR Alzheimer) AND ("care home" OR "residential care") AND ("workforce development" OR "workforce education") AND (policy OR plan OR program) AND (approaches OR strategies) AND (Development OR Implementation) AND (Research OR Study)	LANGUAGE: (English) AND DOCUMENT TYPES: (Article) Timespan: 2010-2020.	989	Using selected words/ combination of individual words
			Total	4390	

Appendix 2.2: Examples of the Quality Appraisal Process Using JBI Critical Appraisal Tools

A. Integrating People with Dementia and Their Carers into Service Design

Authors: Caine

Year of publication: 2014

Publisher: Journal of Integrated Care/ Emerald Group Publishing Limited

Study Design: Qualitative

SI. No	JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist for Qualitative Research	Yes	No	Unclear	Not applicable
1	Is there congruity between the stated philosophical perspective and the research methodology?	Yes			
2	Is there congruity between the research methodology and the research question or objectives?	Yes			
3	Is there congruity between the research methodology and the methods used to collect data?	Yes			
4	Is there congruity between the research methodology and the representation and analysis of data?		No		
5	Is there congruity between the research methodology and the interpretation of results?			Unclear	
6	Is there a statement locating the researcher culturally or theoretically?			Unclear	
7	Is the influence of the researcher on the research, and vice-versa, addressed?	Yes			
8	Are participants, and their voices, adequately represented?	Yes			
9	Is the research ethical according to current criteria or, for recent studies, and is there evidence of ethical approval by an appropriate body?	Yes			
10	Do the conclusions drawn in the research report flow from the analysis, or interpretation, of the data?	Yes			
Total		07			

Overall appraisal: Included

B. What Works in Delivering Dementia Education or Training to Hospital Staff? A Critical Synthesis of the Evidence

Authors: Surr and Gates

Year of publication: 2017

Publisher: International Journal of Nursing Studies/ Elsevier Ltd

Study Design: Systematic Review

SI. No	JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist for Systematic Reviews and Research Synthesis	Yes	No	Unclear	Not applicable
1	Is the review question clearly and explicitly stated?	Yes			
2	Were the inclusion criteria appropriate for the review question?	Yes			
3	Was the search strategy appropriate?	Yes			
4	Were the sources and resources used to search for studies adequate?		No		
5	Were the criteria for appraising studies appropriate?	Yes			
6	Was critical appraisal conducted by two or more reviewers independently?	Yes			
7	Were there methods to minimize errors in data extraction?	Yes			
8	Were the methods used to combine studies appropriate?	Yes			
9	Was the likelihood of publication bias assessed?			Unclear	
10	Were recommendations for policy and/or practice supported by the reported data?	Yes			
11	Were the specific directives for new research appropriate?	Yes			
Total		09			

Overall appraisal: Included

C. Dementia Advocacy in a Time of Austerity

Authors: Brown, Standen and Khilji

Year of publication: 2013

Publisher: Working with Older People/ Emerald Group Publishing Limited

SI. No	JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist for Qualitative Research	Yes	No	Unclear	Not applicable
1	Is there congruity between the stated philosophical perspective and the research methodology?			Unclear	
2	Is there congruity between the research methodology and the research question or objectives?			Unclear	
3	Is there congruity between the research methodology and the methods used to collect data?	Yes			
4	Is there congruity between the research methodology and the representation and analysis of data?	Yes			
5	Is there congruity between the research methodology and the interpretation of results?	Yes			
6	Is there a statement locating the researcher culturally or theoretically?			Unclear	
7	Is the influence of the researcher on the research, and vice-versa, addressed?			Unclear	
8	Are participants, and their voices, adequately represented?	Yes			
9	Is the research ethical according to current criteria or, for recent studies, and is there evidence of ethical approval by an appropriate body?		No		
10	Do the conclusions drawn in the research report flow from the analysis, or interpretation, of the data?	Yes			
Total		05			

Overall appraisal: Excluded-due to low quality.

Appendix 2.3: Examples of the Quality Appraisal Process Using Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool

A. Experiences of Dementia Care Workers in Nursing Homes: An Exploratory Study Comparing Canada, Scotland, and the United States

Authors: Johnson

Year of publication: 2014

Publisher: University of Stirling, Scotland

Study Design: Mixed Methods

Types of mixed methods study components or primary studies	Methodological quality criteria	Responses			
		Yes	No	Can't tell	Comments
Screening questions (for all types)	Are there clear qualitative and quantitative research questions (or objectives*), or a clear mixed methods question (or objective*)?	Yes			
	Do the collected data allow address the research question (objective)? E.g., consider whether the follow-up period is long enough for the outcome to occur (for longitudinal studies or study components).	Yes			
	Further appraisal may be not feasible or appropriate when the answer is 'No' or 'Can't tell' to one or both screening questions.				
1. Qualitative	1.1. Are the sources of qualitative data (archives, documents, informants, observations) relevant to address the research question (objective)?	Yes			
	1.2. Is the process for analyzing qualitative data relevant to address the research question (objective)?	Yes			
	1.3. Is appropriate consideration given to how findings relate to the context, e.g., the setting, in which the data were collected?	Yes			
	1.4. Is appropriate consideration given to how findings relate to researchers' influence, e.g., through their interactions with participants?	Yes			
4. Quantitative descriptive	4.1. Is the sampling strategy relevant to address the quantitative research question (quantitative aspect of the mixed methods question)?	Yes			
	4.2. Is the sample representative of the population understudy?	Yes			
	4.3. Are measurements appropriate (clear origin, or validity known, or standard instrument)?	Yes			
	4.4. Is there an acceptable response rate (60% or above)?	Yes			
5. Mixed methods	5.1. Is the mixed methods research design relevant to address the qualitative and quantitative research questions (or objectives), or the qualitative and quantitative aspects of the mixed methods question (or objective)?	Yes			
	5.2. Is the integration of qualitative and quantitative data (or results*) relevant to address the research question (objective)?	Yes			
	5.3. Is appropriate consideration given to the limitations associated with this integration, e.g., the divergence of qualitative and quantitative data (or results*) in a triangulation design?	Yes			
Total		4			

Overall appraisal: Included

B. Priorities for the Professional Development of Registered Nurses in Nursing Homes: A Delphi Study

Authors: Cooper et al.

Year of publication: 2017

Publisher: Age and Ageing/ Oxford University Press on behalf of the British Geriatrics Society.

Study Design: Quantitative

Types of mixed methods study components or primary studies	Methodological quality criteria	Responses			
		Yes	No	Can't tell	Comments
Screening questions (for all types)	Are there clear qualitative and quantitative research questions (or objectives*), or a clear mixed methods question (or objective*)?	Yes			
	Do the collected data allow address the research question (objective)? E.g., consider whether the follow-up period is long enough for the outcome to occur (for longitudinal studies or study components).	Yes			
	Further appraisal may be not feasible or appropriate when the answer is 'No' or 'Can't tell' to one or both screening questions.				
1. Qualitative	1.1. Are the sources of qualitative data (archives, documents, informants, observations) relevant to address the research question (objective)?				
	1.2. Is the process for analyzing qualitative data relevant to address the research question (objective)?				
	1.3. Is appropriate consideration given to how findings relate to the context, e.g., the setting, in which the data were collected?				
	1.4. Is appropriate consideration given to how findings relate to researchers' influence, e.g., through their interactions with participants?				
4. Quantitative descriptive	4.1. Is the sampling strategy relevant to address the quantitative research question (quantitative aspect of the mixed methods question)?	Yes			
	4.2. Is the sample representative of the population understudy?	Yes			
	4.3. Are measurements appropriate (clear origin, or validity known, or standard instrument)?	Yes			
	4.4. Is there an acceptable response rate (60% or above)?		No		
5. Mixed methods	5.1. Is the mixed methods research design relevant to address the qualitative and quantitative research questions (or objectives), or the qualitative and quantitative aspects of the mixed methods question (or objective)?				
	5.2. Is the integration of qualitative and quantitative data (or results*) relevant to address the research question (objective)?				
	5.3. Is appropriate consideration given to the limitations associated with this integration, e.g., the divergence of qualitative and quantitative data (or results*) in a triangulation design?				
Total		3			

Overall appraisal: Included

C. Improving End-of-life Care in Nursing Homes: Implementation and Evaluation of an Intervention to Sustain Quality

Authors: Finucane et al.

Year of publication: 2013

Publisher: Palliative Medicine

Types of mixed methods study components or primary studies	Methodological quality criteria	Responses			
		Yes	No	Can't tell	Comments
Screening questions (for all types)	Are there clear qualitative and quantitative research questions (or objectives*), or a clear mixed methods question (or objective*)?	Yes			
	Do the collected data allow address the research question (objective)? E.g., consider whether the follow-up period is long enough for the outcome to occur (for longitudinal studies or study components).	Yes			
	Further appraisal may be not feasible or appropriate when the answer is 'No' or 'Can't tell' to one or both screening questions.				
1. Qualitative	1.1. Are the sources of qualitative data (archives, documents, informants, observations) relevant to address the research question (objective)?	Yes			
	1.2. Is the process for analyzing qualitative data relevant to address the research question (objective)?		No		
	1.3. Is appropriate consideration given to how findings relate to the context, e.g., the setting, in which the data were collected?	Yes			
	1.4. Is appropriate consideration given to how findings relate to researchers' influence, e.g., through their interactions with participants?		No		
4. Quantitative descriptive	4.1. Is the sampling strategy relevant to address the quantitative research question (quantitative aspect of the mixed methods question)?	Yes			
	4.2. Is the sample representative of the population understudy?		No		
	4.3. Are measurements appropriate (clear origin, or validity known, or standard instrument)?	Yes			
	4.4. Is there an acceptable response rate (60% or above)?		No		
5. Mixed methods	5.1. Is the mixed methods research design relevant to address the qualitative and quantitative research questions (or objectives), or the qualitative and quantitative aspects of the mixed methods question (or objective)?			Can't tell	
	5.2. Is the integration of qualitative and quantitative data (or results*) relevant to address the research question (objective)?	Yes			
	5.3. Is appropriate consideration given to the limitations associated with this integration, e.g., the divergence of qualitative and quantitative data (or results*) in a triangulation design?			Can't tell	
Total		2			

Overall appraisal: Excluded-due to low quality.

Appendix 2.4: Summary of Reviewed Findings

S.L.No	Title of the article/study	Author(s), year of publication and publisher	Study design and methods	Primary aim/s and question/s	Ethical consideration	Sample population and size/participants	Themes related to review purpose	Setting (Country)/Context	Data collection techniques/ Methods/ Key measurements	Data Analysis methods	Key findings	Strength and weaknesses	MMAT - score/ JBI Score
01	Leveraging everyday technology for people living with dementia: a case study	Authors: Astell et al. Year of publication: 2014 Publisher: Journal of Assistive Technologies	Qualitative Study (Case Study)	The purpose of this paper is to present the self-described "journey" of a person with dementia (Brian; author 3) in his re-learning of old technologies and learning of new ones and the impact this had on his life.	No evidence of ethical approval	a single case study	Provision of Post Diagnostic Support Development of Service and Care Infrastructure	The Alzheimer Scotland Resource Centre Dundee, Scotland	The subsequent interview, an online blog and diary entries.	Qualitative analysis- Brian's blogs were analysed using NVivo 9 (NVivo), a Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software by QSR International, to facilitate analysis and reinforce methodological rigour.	This case study presents the experiences of a person with dementia and a researcher, working together with currently available mainstream technology. This study investigated the impact of technology use on Brian's life and how this might translate to other people living with dementia.	Strengths: The paper provides an example of how learning and technology improved the life of one person with dementia. By sharing the approach the authors hope to encourage others to embrace the challenge of designing and developing innovative solutions for people with a dementia diagnosis by leveraging	JBI= 06/10

											<p>both current mainstream technology and creating novel bespoke interventions for dementia.</p> <p>Weakness: Generalisation of findings from a case study is difficult in terms of other people with dementia, who may have different types and stages of dementia and of course each person and their experience is unique.</p>	
02	Integrating people with dementia and their carers into service design	<p>Authors: Caine</p> <p>Year of publication: 2014</p> <p>Publisher: Journal of Integrated Care/ Emerald Group</p>	Qualitative Study (Participatory Action Research)	The purpose of this paper is to reflect upon the method of using a participatory action research (PAR) approach and offer some insight into the processes of integrated working with service users and carers.	Ethical approval was sought from Alzheimer Scotland and approved.	Five people with dementia and their carers	Development of Service and Care Infrastructure	Research undertaken with PROP in partnership between the Centre for Research on Families and Relationships	Methods were designed to involve participants at every stage of the process from drawing up the initial contract to identifying	Not explicitly specified	<p>This paper offers insights from a practitioner-research project which the author conducted within the author's own practice. It is a reflection on the process of</p> <p>Strengths: A person-centred approach to service user participation in the research process has valuable insights for</p>	JBI= 07/10

		Publishing Limited						ps (CRFR) at the University of Edinburgh and the Institute for Research and Innovation in Social Services (IRISS), Scotland	prescription times, music choices, discussion groups, semi-structured interviews to designing a feedback form and carers' diaries		using PAR with five people with dementia and their carers in a research project on the use of music to increase wellbeing for both the person with dementia and their carer. PAR helps to gain service user views but supports service users and providers to work in an integrated way.	the integration of service users in the design and delivery of health and social care. Weakness: Collaborating with participants took a lot of planning and rigorous thinking about the research process and the best way to engage with people with dementia.	
03	Priorities for the professional development of registered nurses in nursing homes: a Delphi study	Authors: Cooper et al. Year of publication: 2017 Publisher: Age and Ageing/Oxford University Press on behalf of the British Geriatrics Society.	Quantitative Study (modified Delphi survey)	To establish a consensus on the care and professional development needs of registered nurses (RNs) employed by UK care homes.	Study was considered and approved by the University of York's Research Governance Committee	A panel (n = 352) of individuals with experience, expertise or interest in care home nursing: (i) care home nurses and managers; (ii) community healthcare professionals (including general practitioners, geriatricians	Implementation of the Principles of Public Health Policy Development of Service and Care Infrastructure Preparation and	The study was conducted in four localities across the UK (Scotland)	Two round Delphi survey was administered online, accessible via email or website link	Quantitative analysis (ranking)	RNs employed by nursing homes require particular skills, knowledge, competence and experience to provide high quality care for older residents. The most important responsibilities for the nursing home nurse were promoting dignity, personhood and wellbeing, ensuring resident safety	Strengths: This is the first study to report on the care delivery and professional development needs of care home nurses using a consensus method with a range of stakeholders including	MMAT (Quan) = 3/4

						, specialist and district nurses); and (iii) nurse educators in higher education.	Development of Dementia Workforce				and enhancing quality of life. Continuing professional development priorities included personal care, dementia care and managing long-term conditions. The main barrier to professional development was staff shortages. Nursing degree programmes were perceived as inadequately preparing nurses for a nursing home role. Nursing homes could improve by providing supportive learning opportunities for students and fostering challenging and rewarding careers for newly RNs.	care home nurses and managers, general practitioners, geriatricians, specialist and district nurses and nurse educators in higher education. Weakness: However, it is worth noting under representation of the macro-level (government).	
04	Evidence of what works to support and sustain care at home for people with dementia:	Authors: Dawson et al. Year of publication: 2015	Systematic Review	This paper synthesises research evidence about the effectiveness of services intended to support and sustain people with dementia to live at home, including supporting carers. The review was commissioned	No evidence of ethical approval	131 publications evaluated	Dementia as a Public Health Concern Implementation of the Principles	UK (Scotland)	A systematic search of relevant bibliographic databases to ensure the necessary broad	Thematic analysis	Review findings grouped under five main topic headings including: Early intervention and post	Strengths: Review is equally important that service commissioners, service providers and those researching this area:	JBI= 10/11

<p>A literature review with a systematic approach</p>	<p>Publisher: BMC Geriatrics</p>		<p>to support an inspection regime and identifies the current state of scientific knowledge regarding appropriate and effective services in relation to a set of key outcomes derived from Scottish policy, inspection practice and standards.</p>			<p>of Public Health Policy</p> <p>Provision of Post Diagnostic Support</p> <p>Development of Service and Care Infrastructure</p> <p>Preparation and Development of Dementia Workforce</p>		<p>coverage of areas of interest, crossing medical, psychological and social scientific literatures.</p>		<p>diagnostic services.</p> <p>Community-based services supporting people with dementia living in their own homes.</p> <p>Hospital-related areas of interest.</p> <p>Informal/unpaid care; and</p> <p>Workforce and service delivery.</p>	<p>are able to appreciate the limitations of existing evidence; seek to review local evidence that approaches really work; understand and act on what evidence is available; and respond to service users, engage with them, and involve informal carers.</p> <p>Weakness: The texts included in the review represent the breadth but not necessarily the depth of the evidence base in all areas;</p> <p>Policy and practice developments are proceeding on a limited</p>	
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05	Components of a community model of dementia palliative care	Authors: Fox et al. Year of publication: 2020 Publisher: Journal of Integrated Care/ Emerald Group Publishing Limited	Qualitative approach -An exploratory design using a survey method	The Model for Dementia Palliative Care Project will develop a service-delivery model for community-based dementia palliative care	This study received ethical approval from the Cork Research Ethics Committee (reference: ECM4(h)/E CM3 (zzzz)).	Overall 112 target population including health and social care professionals, policymakers, and academics interested in dementia and palliative care.	Implementation of the Principles of Public Health Policy	A web-based survey was developed, piloted (n 55), revised, and distributed within five healthcare jurisdictions: The Republic of Ireland, Northern Ireland, England, Scotland, and Wales	For identifying what stakeholders consider "a posteriori" to be important in a model of dementia palliative care (based on their experience), a de novo survey (open-ended and closed-ended questions asked respondent) was developed based on a literature review and the expert opinion of the project advisory group, consisting of academics and clinicians from dementia and	Content analysis of open-ended questions identified common themes; descriptive statistics were applied to the closed-ended questions	Key care principles incorporated the philosophies of palliative care and dementia care; many described "holistic" and "person-centred care" as the core. Important individual service components were the support for carers, advanced care planning, information, education and training, activities for "meaningful living", comprehensive disease management, coordinated case management, and linking with community health services and social activities. Barriers included poor availability and organisation of healthcare	Strengths: Potential core components of the model were identified as person-centred care, comprehensive care, integrated care, accessible care, timely care, and care for carer. Weakness: the components represented in the logic model are tentative, and the final model will need to be informed by further research, including site visits and evaluations and further in-depth stakeholder consultation to include PwD	JBI= 07/10
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									palliative care.		services, stigma, misconceptions around dementia prognosis, insufficiently advanced care planning, and dementia-related challenges to care. Facilitators included education, carer support, and therapeutic relationships.		
06	Exploring the experience of dementia from a participatory perspective: from experience to theory and back again: realist explanatory theory building method	Authors: Górska Year of publication: 2018 Publisher: Queen Margaret University, Edinburgh, Scotland	Qualitative approach	This thesis aims to develop a preliminary theoretical model, inclusive of concepts of adaptation and participation and reflecting the complexity of dementia experience, to inform policy and practice in dementia.	This study received ethical approval from the South East Scotland Research Ethics Service who provided an ethical statement (NR/1109A B20; Appendix 2) and QMU Research Ethics Panel.	Thirty-one adults were recruited to this study. This includes twelve PWD (38.7%) and nineteen FM (61.3%).	Dementia as a Public Health Concern Provision of Post Diagnostic Support Development of Service and Care Infrastructure	Scotland	Individual semi-structured, narrative Interviews	Framework analysis was managed within the NVivo software	Overall, the findings reflect the uniqueness of dementia experience for each individual, related to the complexity of dynamic, multidirectional relationships between contributory factors. Accordingly, the results focus on the key factors shaping people's experience in dementia and causal dynamics that determine adaptive processes and their potential	Strengths: Within the national context, the findings of the current research support the commitment to integrated care delivered through coordinated, multidisciplinary diagnostic services and post-diagnostic support; aimed at the needs of both PWD and their carers;	JB1= 08/10

										<p>outcomes. Additionally, points of difference between PWD and FM are also considered, as these may be crucial for the practical implications of this research.</p> <p>and delivered within people's local communities for as long as possible; put forward in the Scotland's National Dementia Strategy 2017-2020 (Scottish Government 2017).</p> <p>Weakness: First, the differences in how PWD and the FM experience and understand the considered concepts were not the primary focus of this study. They were identified as part of in-depth analysis and represent the author's understanding and interpretation of participants' accounts.</p>
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												Further research would be required to investigate in detail contextual factors and mechanisms behind these differences and their impact in terms of adaptive outcomes	
07	Service-related needs of older people with dementia: perspectives of service users and their unpaid carers.	Authors: Górska et al. Year of publication: 2013 Publisher: International Psychogeriatrics	Qualitative Study	This study aimed to develop a deeper understanding of the lived experience of people with dementia regarding their service-related needs.	The study has been reviewed by the South East Scotland Research Ethics Service (SESRES)	Thirty-one participants were included in the study. The sample comprised 12 persons with dementia (39%) and 19 unpaid carers (61%)	Dementia as a Public Health Concern Provision of Post Diagnostic Support Development of Service and Care Infrastructure	Midlothian, Scotland.	This study made use of the data gathered through individual semi-structured, narrative interviews of people with experience of dementia and their unpaid carers	The data analysis involved thematic content analysis using the constant comparative method	Although participants were generally satisfied with the services they received, a number of unmet needs related to service provision were identified. In terms of diagnostic procedures the findings of this study indicate the need for early diagnosis delivered through a comprehensive assessment package. The participants also highlighted the need for well-coordinated post-diagnostic	Strengths: This study contributes to a better understanding of service-related needs of people with dementia in relation to diagnostic procedures and post-diagnostic support. Weakness: Although informative in terms of identification of service-related needs of people with dementia, the current findings	JBIC= 07/10

											support, greater continuity of care concerning the personnel involved, and enhanced access to non-pharmacological interventions to support identity and social engagement	represent the views of a group of users within one geographical area.	
08	Experiences of dementia care workers in nursing homes : an exploratory study comparing Canada, Scotland, and the United States	Authors: Johnson Year of publication: 2014 Publisher: University of Stirling, Scotland	Mixed method approach. (Cross-national comparative methods - Ethnographic methods)	This study seeks to explore and understand the work experiences of dementia care workers in nursing homes in Canada, Scotland and the USA.	This research was granted approval from the University of Stirling, Department of Applied Social Science ethics committee on 9 October 2007	59 dementia care workers in Canada, Scotland, and the United States.	Development of Service and Care Infrastructure Preparation and Development of Dementia Workforce	Canada, Scotland, and the United States	Ethnographic research tools (for care workers) consisted of a short-structured interview followed by a long-open-ended interview and then observations.	A comparative framework and symbolic interactionist approach is used to analyse data collected using ethnographic methods	The comparative findings underscore the importance of work conditions that provide care workers with sufficient resources to do their job and enough time to complete their work. The absence of these critical components creates stressful work conditions for the care workers. The lack of time, staff and supplies such as towels, wash cloths, and continence products do not allow the residents" choices in their care and	Strengths: This study established that care workers require adequate resources to do their job and sufficient time to complete their work. This comparative research has identified relevant findings critical for policy makers to engage with dementia care providers. Weakness: The results of this study are not	MMAT = 4/4

											disregard their dignity and rights.	generalizable due to the small sample. Moreover, the small number of nursing homes in this research could lead to conclusions that were more speculative.	
09A	Comparative study of carers of older people with dementia in Scotland and Korea	Authors: Lee Year of publication: 2011 Publisher: The University of Edinburgh, Scotland	Qualitative Study	This study aims to explore Scottish and Korean carers' attitudes towards the diagnosis of dementia in their relative, family care, community care and to residential care in Scotland and Korea respectively, also under examination was the origin of different carers' attitudes between Scotland and Korea.	School of Social and Political Studies Research and Ethics Committee [SSPSREE]).	In order to develop this argument, this thesis has carried out interviews with 14 Scottish carers and 28 Korean carers.	Dementia as a Public Health Concern Development of Service and Care Infrastructure	Scotland and Korea	Data collection was done in two ways: documents and qualitative interviews (semi-structured interviews)	This thesis is based on a theoretical analysis framework. The semi-structured interview schedule has been organised based on the theoretical framework, and the data on the diagnosis of dementia, family care, social services in the community and residential care were	Findings explain that the origin of carers' attitudes in this study is based on social policy rather than culture. These findings are consistent with institutional perceptions as an explanation for family care, rather than a cultural perception. Study findings examined carers' attitudes towards the diagnosis of dementia, family care, community care, and residential care.	Strengths: This study contributes to the comparative study of Scotland and Korea as well as being a qualitative study in Korea. In addition, it will provide a new perspective on attitudes towards studies on East Asia. Weakness: the interviews in this study are with people from very specific groups,	JBI= 09/10

										organised according to how the culture and social policy affects the attitudes in each topic.		family carers of older people with dementia living at home. It is not wise to generalise findings to other carers.	
10	Post-diagnostic support for dementia: What can be learned from service providers' experiences, model variation and information recording?	Authors: Levin et al. Year of publication: 2018 Publisher: Health Education /Emerald Publishing Limited	Mixed methods (A sequential mixed-method approach)	The purpose of this paper is to examine three interpretations of post-diagnostic support (PDS) for dementia, to understand how best to support people recently diagnosed with dementia	Followed ethical considerations (Using the UK NHS Health Research Authority decision tool, ethics approval was not require).	In all, 755 PDS records of people referred to the service in Glasgow City between August 2014 and September 2015 were included in the quantitative analysis. Semi-structured interviews were carried out with a Lead Nurse and OT from each sector's OPMH team, Glasgow City's PDS manager and Adult Health Services manager (a	Provision of Post Diagnostic Support	The study was conducted in PDS services across Glasgow City, Scotland.	Records analysis, Interviews, and the focus group	The data were analysed using thematic framework analysis to develop themes, categories and concepts	Interviews and the focus group explored the following aspects of PDS service provision: knowledge of guidelines and recording systems, availability of services, development of services, variation in services and client group by sector, perceptions and experiences of service provision, barriers and enablers of service provision and opportunities for improvement. Interviews with staff additionally	The study found that a guidance framework should describe the role of link workers and have at its centre a person-centred ethos, in keeping with Alzheimer's Scotland PDS model, and therefore should include both one to one support and groupwork to clients.	MMAT = 3/4

						total of eight leads). A focus group was conducted comprised of 2 PDS link workers from each sector (a total of six).					covered the topic of management of the service, model selection, determinants of person-centred outcomes and decision making		
11	Facilitating independence: the benefits of a post-diagnostic support project for people with dementia	Authors: Kelly and Innes Year of publication: 2016 Publisher: Dementia /SAGE	Mixed methods (A comparative design)	The aim of the comparative design (T1 and T2) was to ascertain whether there was any difference in experience of using a post-diagnostic support service over time	Ethical approval was obtained from a Local NHS Research Ethics Committee (LREC). All participants had capacity to give informed consent.	Twenty-seven participants (14 people newly diagnosed with dementia and 13 family carers)	Provision of Post Diagnostic Support	A region of Scotland	Methods included semi-structured interviews with people with dementia and their family caregivers and administration of quality of life questionnaires, QoL-AD , to people with dementia and coping with stress questionnaires, called COPE , to family caregivers	A comparative thematic analysis	This paper reports on key findings from an evaluation of a post-diagnostic support pilot project in Scotland addressing local service gaps, namely information provision, emotional and practical support and maintaining community links. Findings from an evaluation of a post-diagnostic support pilot project in a region of Scotland show that it was valued by people with dementia and family members who received support from	Strengths: The strength of the project was its focus on the person with dementia as well as on the family member, with solutions and strategies aimed to meet both their needs. Weakness: The project had limited success in facilitating and promoting advanced care planning. This was due to participants' reported reluctance	MMAT = 3/4

											the project workers	in thinking too far ahead, while still adapting to the diagnosis.	
12	Experiences of advanced dementia care in seven European countries: implications for educating the workforce	Authors: Lillo-Crespo et al. Year of publication: 2018 Publisher: Global Health Action/ Taylor & Francis Group	Qualitative Study (Case Study)	To identify the strengths and weaknesses in daily life perceived by people with dementia and family caring across Europe by exemplifying the experiences and the range of typical care settings for advanced dementia care in seven partner countries.	All the informants in this study signed an informed consent, though the conditions established by the ethical committees in each country were different.	This paper presents data from 22 case studies that explored the experience of advanced dementia care in the 7 countries across a range of care settings considered typical within that country. A total of 56 interviews was conducted; 21 of these were with people with dementia, 23 were with family members and 12 with paid staff from healthcare and social fieldwork.	Dementia as a Public Health Concern Implementation of the Principles of Public Health Policy Development of Service and Care Infrastructure Preparation and Development of Dementia Workforce	This paper presents data from 22 case studies that explored the experience of advanced dementia care in the 7 countries involved: Scotland (overall project lead), Spain (case study lead), Sweden, Finland, Slovenia, Czech Republic, and Portugal.	A qualitative approach was taken. All interviews were face to face, conducted in a setting and at a time convenient to the interviewee. The interviews were conducted in the country's mother language.	A constant comparative method of analysis through thematic synthesis was used to identify the common themes.	Eight key themes were identified: Early diagnosis, good coordination between service providers, future planning, support and education for carers, enabling the person with dementia to live the best life possible and education on advanced dementia for professional and family caregivers were all significant and recurring issues considered important for care experiences to be positive	Strengths: Building on what the case studies tell us about what works well, study discuss the potential for integrating the findings into interprofessional learning solutions for the professional workforce across Europe to champion practice-based change. Weakness: This study did not include young people or people with other pre-existing conditions such as intellectual disability who had	JBI= 10/10

											advanced dementia		
13	The development of quality indicators for Taiwanese institutional dementia care	Authors: Lin Year of publication: 2010 Publisher: University of Stirling	Mixed Methods	This research aims to set up institutional care standards to evaluate quality of care and to inform the improvement of the QOL for people with dementia living in Taiwanese care homes.	Approved by the Ethics Committee in the Department of Applied Social Science in the University of Stirling	24 experts in dementia care in Scotland and Taiwan and 122 residents with dementia and 115 family members	Development of Service and Care Infrastructure	Scotland and Taiwan	Data were collected in two stages: The Delphi exercise (stage one) involving 24 experts in dementia care in Scotland and Taiwan and the fieldwork (stage two) collected 237 questionnaires (from 122 residents with dementia and 115 family members) in 14 Taiwanese care homes for people with dementia (including special care units within care homes).	Quantitative and qualitative data from the Delphi panel were analysed. The field test data were analysed using reliability and item analysis, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), and descriptive and inferential statistics	This study constructed a dementia care model that integrated the person-centred care model and the TQM approach focused on institutional care. In practice, the findings of this research developed guidelines for service receivers to select an appropriate care home.	Strengths: The indicators have important policy implications for the Taiwanese Government and regulations intended to ensure that care homes meet the requirements of service receivers. Weakness: The findings found the current study only represented a snapshot of the dynamic but small participant cohort at a single point in time.	MMAT = 4/4
14	"They're just who they've always been": the	Authors: Mullay	Qualitative Study (Ethnographic)	This thesis documents a study which set out to explore the links between culture,	Approval has been obtained from the relevant	Sixteen social care workers and nurses took part, as did	Dementia as a Public Health Concern	It involved six care homes in Scotland, three of	Participant observation and ethnographic interview	An ethnographic approach to data	It was found that culture as an aspect of selfhood is a much more	Strengths: This study found that sociocultural diversity	JBI= 09/10

<p>intersections of dementia, 'person-centred care', and cultural contexts in Scottish Care Homes</p>	<p>Year of publication: 2012 Publisher: University of Aberdeen</p>	<p>Approach)</p>	<p>dementia and long-term residential care in Scotland. A key aim of the work was to gain insights into manifestations of individual formative culture as part of selfhood in people with dementia in care homes, and how service providers take account of this in constituting „person-centred“ care processes (which are claimed by virtually every such provider in Scotland). Another aim was to explore the contexts influencing care processes at individual care home/theoretical/government policy levels</p>	<p>ethics committee for this project. The completed requirements were sent to the Scotland A REC sub-committee. Ethical approval was then confirmed in a letter of 22nd February 2010.</p>	<p>eleven care home residents with significant dementia.</p>		<p>which were in large urban centres and three of which were in a remote island group</p>		<p>gathering and analysis, combined with a post structural discourse analysis in interpreting initial findings, represented the research methods used</p>	<p>reducible phenomenon than is represented by traditional metanarratives of diversity, and failure to take account of this can have substantial implications for „person-centred care“ (especially for people who are progressively losing the ability to adapt to new sociocultural environments because of cognitive impairment). Failure to acknowledge these very individual formative sociocultural contexts in people with dementia who are in long-term care, may lead to a failure to acknowledge personhood</p>	<p>often impacted upon people with dementia in a different way than people with no cognitive impairment. Weakness: Only six residential units were involved, which represents a fraction of the 900-plus care homes in Scotland for older people, and this is perhaps the greatest limitation on the work</p>	
<p>15 What works in delivering dementia education or training to hospital staff? A critical</p>	<p>Authors: Surr and Gates Year of publication: 2017 Publisher: International</p>	<p>Systematic Review-Critical synthesis and included qualitative, quantitative</p>	<p>The purpose of this literature review was to examine published evidence on the most effective approaches to dementia training and education for hospital staff.</p>	<p>No evidence of ethical approval</p>	<p>A total of 20 papers were included</p>	<p>Preparation and Development of Dementia Workforce</p>	<p>The majority of studies were conducted in the UK (n = 12), with the remainder</p>	<p>A total of 20 papers were included in the review, the majority of which were low or medium</p>	<p>Kirkpatrick's four-level model for the evaluation of training interventions was</p>	<p>Training that was directly relevant to hospital staff and their practice, which included practical tools or care</p>	<p>Strengths: This review has demonstrated that specific features of dementia training that</p>	<p>JBIC= 09/11</p>

	synthesis of the evidence	Journal of Nursing Studies/ Elsevier Ltd	ve and mixed/multi-methods studies					carried out in the US (n = 3), Australia (n = 3) and Canada (n = 2)	quality, impacting on generalisability	used as the underpinning structure for the analysis.	strategies directly applicable in the workplace and which utilised the direct voices of people with dementia and their carers, was particularly valued by staff attending training	may be associated with greater pedagogical, practice or clinical effectiveness can be identified from the evidence base and suggestions for the design of future training programmes for hospital staff made Weakness: This review are only including papers published in English, since 2000, therefore, information extracted on each programme may not include all published details if they were reported elsewhere,	
16	Enriching the care of patients with dementia in acute	Authors: Banks et al.	Mixed methods	To develop, deliver, and evaluate a training programme to prepare NHS and Social Service Dementia	Ethical approval for the programme evaluation	113 health professionals: 78 nurses, 20 allied health professional	Preparation and Development of	Scotland	Distance travelled approach; Approaches to Dementia	Analysis of data derived from the ADQ and 100	This paper presents the findings from analysis of the qualitative and quantitative	Strengths: The Dementia Champions programme was	MMAT = 3/4

settings? The Dementia Champions Programme in Scotland	Year of publication: 2014 Publisher: Dementia		Champions working in acute settings as Change Agents for practice.	was granted by the University of the West of Scotland Research Ethics Committee	s, 10 occupational therapists, 6 physiotherapists, 2 speech and language therapists, 2 dieticians, 7 education/ practice development staff, 3 managers, 1 Consultant Physician	Dementia Workforce		Questionnaire at T1 (prior to training) and T2 (last day of training); Self- efficacy scale at T2 only Achievement of learning outcomes via work- based tasks and assignments during training	reflective reports of the community experience indicate that participants' perceptions of people with dementia shifted significantly during the Programme	data derived from programme participants. Participants identified a range of issues which should be addressed with a view to improving the experiences of people with dementia in acute settings, and put in place actions to bring about change. The format of the programme provided a cost effective means to prepare NHS and Social Service Dementia Champions as Change Agents for practice within a relatively short period of time, and would be transferrable to other staff groups as well as different organisational structures in other countries.	designed for health and social care professionals and, although all participants in the first cohort were health professionals, it provides a unique and appropriate vehicle for health and social care professionals, who have been included in subsequent cohorts, to come together to identify ways in which the care of people with dementia in acute care can be improved. Weakness: The short duration of the programme meant that it was not possible to gauge impact on patient care	
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											or outcomes.		
17	Improving the care of people with dementia in hospital	Authors: Waugh et al. Year of publication: 2011 Publisher: Nursing Standard.	Mixed methods	This article describes the multi-faceted, educational approach to improving the care of adults with dementia.	Not specified	35 hospital staff attended training with n = 26 completing evaluation	Preparation and Development of Dementia Workforce	Scotland	Paper-based questionnaires and focus groups.	Not explicitly specified	Those involved in the Dementia Champions Programme are dedicated to improving the care of people with dementia in hospital. The collaborative approach adopted by all members of the training team will help to maintain ongoing commitment and contribution from the carer support group, healthcare education and NHS staff	This will ensure that the training programme recognises and addresses the ever-changing needs of people with dementia and their carers. Looking to the future, it is hoped that the carers and the training team will continue to develop the programme, forging strong communication links with practising dementia champions, as well as participating in the ongoing development and evaluation of the programme NS	MMAT = 3/4

<p>18 The barriers and facilitators to implementing dementia education and training in health and social care services: a mixed-methods study</p>	<p>Authors: Surr et al. Year of publication: 2020 Publisher: BMC Health Services Research</p>	<p>A mixed-methods design</p>	<p>This study aimed to investigate the barriers and facilitators to implementation of dementia education and training in health and social care services using the Theoretical Domains Framework (TDF) and COM-B model of behaviour change</p>	<p>Ethical approval was given by the Yorkshire and the Humber – Bradford – Leeds NHS Research Ethics Committee [REC Ref 15/YH/0488]. All participants gave written informed consent to participate.</p>	<p>Methods were an online audit of care and training providers, online survey of trained staff and individual/group interviews with organisational training leads, training facilitators, staff who had attended dementia training and managers</p>	<p>Preparation and Development of Dementia Workforce</p>	<p>The research took place in a range of health and social care provider organisations in the UK, who were delivering dementia care. These included acute hospitals, Mental Health Trusts, social care services (care homes), and</p>	<p>Audit n = 463; Survey n = 576; and Case studies n = 10</p>	<p>Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and thematic template analysis.</p>	<p>Barriers and facilitators were analysed according to the COM-B domains. “Capability” factors were not perceived as a significant barrier to training implementation. Factors which supported staff capability included the use of interactive face-to-face training, and training that was relevant to their role. Factors that increased staff “motivation” included skilled facilitation of training, trainees’ desire to learn and the provision of incentives (e.g. attendance during paid working hours, badges/certifications). “Opportunity” factors were most prevalent with lack of resources</p>	<p>The TDF and COM-B model have provided a useful framework for identifying broader relevant factors. A wide range of factors may present as barriers to or facilitators of dementia training implementation and behaviour change for staff. Health and social care provider organisations may benefit from utilising these to support staff in relation to the range of capability, opportunity and motivational factors that need to be addressed for staff to be successful</p>	<p>MMAT = 4/4</p>
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											(time, financial, staffing and environmental) being the biggest perceived barrier to training implementation . The presence or not of external support from families and internal factors such as the organisational culture and its supportiveness of good dementia care and training implementation were also influential.	y implement their learning into practice. These should be considered by health and social care providers in the context of dementia training design and delivery in order to maximise potential for implementation.	
19A	collective case study of the features of impactful dementia training for care home staff	Authors: Surr et al. Year of publication: 2019 Publisher: BMC Geriatrics	Qualitative Study (Case Study)	This study aimed to investigate the features and contextual factors associated with an effective approach to care home staff training on dementia	Ethical approval for the study was given by the Yorkshire and the Humber – Bradford Leeds NHS Research Ethics Committee [REC Ref 15/YH/048 8].	A 'case' was defined as a care home provider organisation, which could include a single care home or multiple sites, as long as staff at all sites accessed the same training programme s. Eighteen social care providers in	Preparation and Development of Dementia Workforce	England and Scotland, including fourteen care home providers and four domiciliary care organisations	Semi-structured interviews; Individual, small/focus group interviews; Observations; Audit; and Satisfaction cards	Interview, focus group and training observation data were analysed using the thematic analysis method, template analysis using NVivo 11	Findings across the three sites strongly support the use of face-to-face delivery, interactive and engaging teaching methods and the tailoring of training to the setting and staff roles of those attending.	Strengths: This study has added to our understanding of effective dementia education and training for care home staff. Weakness: The sample is not representative of the typical or	JBI= 06/10

						England and Scotland, including fourteen care home providers and four domiciliary care organisations who had responded to the audit were considered for inclusion.						average care home	
20	Achieving prudent dementia care (palliative): an international policy and practice imperative	Authors: Tolson et al. Year of publication: 2016 Publisher: International Journal of Integrated Care	A mixed-methods design	This paper examines the provision of integrated advanced dementia care within seven European countries and critically reviews the potential contribution of the Prudent Healthcare perspective as a starting point for reform.	Local research teams were responsible for securing the ethical and management permissions to research with this vulnerable group of people	The Policy Review; an integrative review methodology; 22 in-depth case studies were constructed using open questioning approaches with the case study informants; and the educational gap analysis used a combination of desk based research supported by discussions led by local team	Dementia as a Public Health Concern Implementation of the Principles of Public Health Policy Development of Service and Care Infrastructure Preparation and Development of	The Palliative partnership comprised interdisciplinary teams from Scotland UK, Czech Republic, Finland, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden	The Policy Review; an integrative review methodology; 22 in-depth case studies were constructed using open questioning approaches with the case study informants; and the educational gap analysis used a combination	Qualitative and quantitative analysis	All seven countries reported existence of some type of national action plan for generic palliative care. The literature review concluded that healthcare needs should be foregrounded within Dementia Palliative, and revealed an evidence base for practice of variable quality. Early diagnosis, good coordination between service providers,	Strengths: the Prudent Healthcare perspective can give useful structure to debates about principles to underpin reform of advanced dementia care Weakness: Recognized an inherent risk that in advanced dementia care prudence might inadvertently serve to perpetuate	MMAT = 4/4

						members with key informants, mainly education providers	Dementia Workforce		n of desk-based research supported by discussions led by local team members with key informants, mainly education providers		future planning, support and education for carers, enabling the person with dementia to live the best life possible and education on advanced dementia for professional and family caregivers were all significant issues considered important for positive care experiences through the cases explored. The education gap analysis demonstrated limited input on dementia care and even less on advanced dementia care in undergraduate and postgraduate health and social care programmes across the seven partner countries	the 'inverse care law' where those who need the most care receive the least.	
21	Caring with integrity : developing the conceptua	Authors: Watson	Qualitative Study (Ethnographic	The aim was to understand this from the perspective of both people with dementia and the staff caring for them,	It has been reviewed by the ESRC, the University of	01 care home, Conducted interviews with 24 staff (3 pairs and	Implementation of the Principles of Public	Scotland	Participant observation; group discussion and Interviews;	Narrative analysis	The findings presented in this study point to a heightened need for 'organised	Strengths: This thesis makes an original contribution to	JBI= 08/10

<p>underpinning of relationships p-centred palliative dementia care in care homes</p>	<p>Year of publication: 2015 Publisher: The University of Edinburgh</p>	<p>Approach)</p>	<p>rooting this in the local care home context but considering how this might be shaped by the wider health and social care context in Scotland.</p>	<p>Edinburgh and the NHS Scotland A Research Ethics Committee .</p>	<p>18 one to one)</p>	<p>Health Policy</p>		<p>documenta tion</p>	<p>emotional care' in the context of palliative dementia care because of the heightened interdependenc y between the feelings of the care staff and the feelings of people with dementia. The empirical analysis revealed three keys facets which shape the caring relationship: body work (direct hands-on bodily care); recognising and supporting selfhood; witnessing and responding to suffering. These three facets of palliative dementia care are examined and reveal the way that people with dementia, even in the advanced stages, continue to experience and respond to the world, and those around them, until they die.</p>	<p>knowledge by combining theory with empirical work to develop the conceptual underpinnin g of relationship -centred palliative dementia care in care homes. Weakness: This research was carried out in one care home and cannot, therefore, claim to be generalizab le</p>	
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22	Recognising and supporting self in dementia: a new way to facilitate a person-centred approach to dementia	Authors: Kelly Year of publication: 2010 Publisher: Ageing and Society	Qualitative Study (multi-method observational study)	This paper reports findings from a three-year study which integrated Kitwood's (1997) person-centred and Sabat's (2001) selfhood approaches in the design, fieldwork and analysis of a multi-method observational study that explored the social worlds of 14 people with dementia in continuing-care.	Ethical approval was granted from the Multi-centre Research Ethics Committee (Scotland), the National Health Service Local Research Ethics Committee and the Research Ethics Committee of the Department of Nursing and Midwifery, University of Stirling	14 people with dementia in continuing care	Development of Service and Care Infrastructure	Scotland	The types of interaction that participants experience in everyday ward life and during creative sessions were identified by observing, video-recording and engaging with them and by Dementia Care Mapping.	The data were managed using qualitative data-management software (NVivo7)	The findings indicate that by developing the selfhood approach and integrating it with the person-centred approach, it is argued that recognising and supporting selfhood (or not) during interactions can lead to qualitatively different staff behaviours, with consequences for the well-being of people with dementia	There is scope for incorporating this developed selfhood framework into staff training, for it has the potential to transform practice and the experiences of people with dementia in receipt of care.	JB1=08/10
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Appendices Chapter Four-Methods

Appendix 4.1: Ethical Approval by UWS Health and Life Sciences School Ethics Committee

25/11/2020 (Dr Gordon Mackay, ethics co-chair)

Dear Mohammad Mollah,

Your application 13336: Workforce Development and Dementia Care in Bangladesh: Policy Learning from the Scottish Context, submission reference 11822, has been approved, with conditions, by the Health and Life Sciences SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below:**

The decision is as follows: Key informant interviews are approved with conditions as noted. Stage 2 and 3 should seek approval through an amendment to this application when more information is available. This should relate to 1) the final version of the questionnaire to be used in the Delphi Study (stage 2) and 2) it is clear whether the Nominal Group Technique work can be delivered face-to-face given the current restrictions.

Please work closely with your supervisor to ensure that the change requests detailed here are completed.

Title	Comment
Please provide details below and how you propose to deal with such issues:	Change request: The researcher has stated he will offer counselling or emotional support to encourage the participation of family members in the process. This is not appropriate.
What is the expected duration of participation in the study for each participant?	the key informant interview schedule is still very long, what is the basis for saying interviews will last up to 60 minutes? is this a realistic estimate of participant's time?
Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)	Is there a point in the study in which participants can no longer withdraw their data? the forms state If you withdraw from the study the information you provide will be removed from the study, will this still be possible after analysis?
Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)	Change request: Please ensure the participant information sheets and consent forms are proof read for typos and grammatical errors.
Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)	Change request: Please review the participant information sheets to ensure that the information given is relevant to what the participant needs to know to participate in the study. Essential information only, for example the full study aims are listed, but it is not clear what the Delphi study aims are specifically, i.e. what is the aim of this part of the study.
Please upload a copy of your Consent Form(s)	Change request: Please review the consent forms to ensure that there is no repetition in the points of consent.
Please upload a copy of your Consent Form(s)	Change request: Please ensure that each document is clearly marked with the version number and date.
What measures will you put in place to ensure the confidentiality of personal data gathered during your study?	Change request: Please confirm that personal data (e.g. consent forms) will be stored separately from anonymised research data.

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Gary Boyd

Appendix 4.2: Selected Policy Items (List of documents, Strategies and Framework 2009-2021)

Year of Publication	Publisher/ Author(s)	Title/Name	Short Summaries	Available at
2009	The Scottish Parliament Cross Party Group on Alzheimer's	The Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers in Scotland	The Scottish Parliament <i>Cross Party Group on Alzheimer's</i> publish a national charter of rights for people with dementia and their carers in Scotland, based on the PANEL Framework.	https://www.alzscot.org/sites/default/files/images/0000/2678/Charter_of_Rights.pdf
2009	The Scottish Government	The National Dialogue on Dementia: Dementia Strategy Consultation Paper	The Scottish Government arrange local and national events and discussions with different stakeholders to inform the national dementia strategy 2010.	https://www.sehd.scot.nhs.uk/publications/DC20090930dementia.pdf
2010	The Scottish Government	Scotland's National Dementia Strategy	The Scottish Government publish the first national strategy for dementia in the UK and the first to incorporate a Human Rights-Based Approach (HRBA) to dementia.	http://www.wdhscp.org.uk/media/1270/dementia-strategy-2010.pdf
2011	The Scottish Government	Standards of Care for Dementia in Scotland: Action to support the change programme, Scotland's National Dementia Strategy	The Scottish Government produce the first set of national standards for dementia care in Scotland.	https://www.gov.scot/publications/standards-care-dementia-scotland-action-support-change-programme-scotlands-national-dementia-strategy/
2011	The Scottish Government	Promoting Excellence: A framework for all health and social services staff working with people with dementia, their families and carers	Following the publication of the National Dementia Strategy & National Care Standards, NHS Education for Scotland & Scottish Social Services Council published a national service framework for dementia health and social care services.	https://www.gov.scot/publications/promoting-excellence-framework-health-social-services-staff-working-people-dementia-families-carers/

Year of Publication	Publisher/ Author(s)	Title/Name	Short Summaries	Available at
2011	The Scottish Government	Scotland's National Dementia Strategy: One Year on Report	Dementia Strategy's Implementation and Monitoring Group publish an evaluation report to illustrate the progress made over the last year since the Scottish Government published the first national dementia strategy in 2010.	https://www.webarchive.org.uk/wayback/archive/20150219072405/http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2011/06/01142419/14
2012	The Scottish Government	Scotland's National Dementia Strategy: Two Years on Report	Dementia Strategy's Implementation and Monitoring Group publish an evaluation report to illustrate the progress made from 2011 to 2012.	https://www.webarchive.org.uk/wayback/archive/20150218204332/http://www.gov.scot/Topics/Health/Services/Mental-Health/Dementia/report-June-2012
2013	The Scottish Government	Scotland's National Dementia Strategy 2013-2016	The Scottish Government publish the second national strategy for dementia to improve post-diagnostic support and strengthen integrated and person-centred care.	http://www.wdhscp.org.uk/media/1269/scotlands-national-dementia-strategy-2013-16.pdf
2014	NHS Education for Scotland/ Ellison, S., Watt, G. and Christie, I.	Evaluating the impact of the Alzheimer Scotland Dementia Nurse Consultants/Specialists & Dementia Champions in bringing about improvements to dementia care in acute general hospitals	NHS Education for Scotland published an evaluation report to explore the role of Alzheimer Scotland Dementia Nurse Consultant/Specialist (ASN) and Dementia Champion (DC) in improving dementia care in acute general hospitals.	https://vdocument.in/evaluating-the-impact-of-the-alzheimer-scotland-dementia-evaluation-period.html?page=1

Year of Publication	Publisher/ Author(s)	Title/Name	Short Summaries	Available at
2015	The Scottish Government	Technology Charter for People Living with Dementia in Scotland	Following the Charter of Rights, the Scottish Government published the Technology Charter for People Living with Dementia to promote the use of technology in health and social care and to support people living with dementia to live as full citizens in society.	https://www.alzscot.org/sites/default/files/images/0002/0289/Technology Charter for People with Dementia in Scotland .pdf
2015	Life Changes Trust	Dementia Friendly Communities in Scotland Report 2 - The First Year April 2015 - March 2016	The Life Changes Trust made a commitment to develop a dementia friendly community across Scotland and improve the quality of life and well-being of people living with dementia and their carers.	https://www.lifechangestrust.org.uk/sites/default/files/publication/files/Dementia%20Friendly%20Communities%20Report%20Designed_1.pdf
2015	Marie Curie Cancer Care	Living and dying with dementia in Scotland: Barriers to care	The Marie Curie Cancer Care publish an evaluation report to identify the progress and challenges with the implementation of the Scottish Government's two national dementia strategies, standards of care, and post-diagnostic support.	https://www.mariecurie.org.uk/globalassets/media/documents/policy/policy-publications/february-2015/living-and-dying-with-dementia-in-scotland-report-2015.pdf
2016	The Scottish Government	Estimated and Projected Diagnosis Rates for Dementia in Scotland: 2014-2020	For the first time, the Scottish Government published a report to estimate the annual dementia diagnosis incidence rate to contextualise post-diagnostic performance data against the Scottish Government's national commitment to post-diagnostic support.	https://www.gov.scot/publications/estimated-projected-diagnosis-rates-dementia-scotland-2014-2020/

Year of Publication	Publisher/ Author(s)	Title/Name	Short Summaries	Available at
2016	Glasgow City Council	Glasgow City Dementia Strategy 2016-19	The Glasgow City Health and Social Care Partnership (GCHSPC) publish a city dementia strategy to improve health and social care services for people with dementia and their carers.	https://www.glasgow.gov.uk/CHttpHandler.ashx?id=35385&p=0
2017	The Scottish Government	Connecting People, Connecting Support: Transforming the allied health professionals' contribution to supporting people living with dementia in Scotland, 2017-2020	The Scottish Government develop a framework for restructuring and integrating the contribution of allied health professionals (AHPs) to dementia care. Connecting People, Connecting Support is the first policy of its kind for Scotland and, indeed, the UK.	https://www.alzscot.org/sites/default/files/images/0002/9408/AHP_Report_2017_Web.pdf
2017	The Scottish Government	Scotland's National Dementia Strategy 2017-2020	The Scottish Government publish the third national dementia strategy based on learning from the previous two strategies to maintain a focus on improving the quality of care for people living with dementia and their carers.	https://www.gov.scot/publications/scotlands-national-dementia-strategy-2017-2020/
2017	Care Inspectorate	My life, my care home: The experiences of people living with dementia in care homes in Scotland	The Care Inspectorate publish an inspection report to examine the quality of dementia care in care homes in Scotland against the standards for dementia care.	https://www.careinspectorate.com/images/documents/4162/Dementia%20IFA%20FINAL.pdf
2019	The Scottish Government	A Fairer Scotland for Older People: A Framework for Action	The Scottish Government publish a framework to challenge the inequalities among older people in Scotland. This framework commits to coordinating national dementia care and ensuring the active participation of people living with dementia in their communities and ongoing national activity on dementia.	https://www.gov.scot/publications/fairer-scotland-older-people-framework-action/
2020	The Scottish Government	Dementia and Covid-19- National Action Plan to Continue to Support Recovery for People with Dementia and their Carers	The Scottish Government develop a bridging plan alongside the existing third national dementia strategy to support people with dementia and their families to continue to get the right care, treatment and support at the right time during the COVID-19 pandemic.	https://www.gov.scot/publications/dementia-covid-19-national-action-plan-continue-support-recovery-people-dementia-carers/

Year of Publication	Publisher/ Author(s)	Title/Name	Short Summaries	Available at
2021	The Scottish Government	Dementia and COVID-19-National Action Plan to Continue to Support Recovery for People with Dementia and their Carers: Equality Impact Assessment Record	The Scottish Government publish an assessment report and outlines a set of recommendations to continue to support people with dementia and their carers during the pandemic.	https://www.gov.scot/publications/summary-equality-impact-assessment-dementia-covid-19-national-action-plan-continue-support-recovery-people-dementia-carers/pages/1/
2021	The Scottish Government	Independent Review of Adult Social Care in Scotland	The Scottish Government publish an independent review to explore current situations and recommend improvements to adult social care support in Scotland, including dementia care.	https://www.gov.scot/publications/independent-review-adult-social-care-scotland/#:~:text=The%20Independent%20Review%20of%20Adult%20Social%20Care%20in,Panel%20comprising%20Scottish%20and%20International%20experts.%20Supporting%20documents
2021	The Scottish Government	Promoting Excellence 2021: A framework for all health and social services staff working with people with dementia, their families and carers	NHS Education for Scotland & Scottish Social Services Council published a new version of the national service framework for dementia health and social care services reflecting the actions, priorities and commitments of the dementia strategies and ongoing national activity on dementia.	https://www.gov.scot/publications/promoting-excellence-2021-framework-health-social-services-staff-working-people-dementia-families-carers/

Appendix 4.3: Invitation letter for policy stakeholders to participate in the Key Informant Interviews

INVITATION LETTER

Policy Stakeholders of Key Informant Interviews

School of Health and Life Sciences, UWS.

Study Title: Workforce Development and Dementia Care in Bangladesh: Policy Learning from the Scottish Context

Sub: Request to participate in the Key Informant Interviews

Dear.....

I want to introduce myself. My name is Mohammad Mainuddin Mollah, Assistant Professor in the Institute of Social Welfare and Research at the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. I am also PhD Student in the Alzheimer's Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice (ASCPP) in the School of Health and Life Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland, Lanarkshire Campus, Hamilton International Technology Park, Stephenson Place, South Lanarkshire, Scotland.G72 0LH.

I am carrying out a research study on Scottish dementia care policies, and workforce development approaches to determine the utility for application within Bangladesh. This part of the study is a "Documentary Policy Analysis Framework with Key Informant Interviews". Documentary analysis framework will be used in combination with key informant interviews with policy stakeholders/actors to provide an informed and in-depth view of policy development in Scotland.

I want to invite you to participate in the Key Informant Interview in this research project which forms part of my PhD, funded by the Bangabandhu Overseas Scholarship Program of the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. If you agree to participate in the study, you will be invited

to participate in a virtual (Webex, Teams or Zoom) or telephone interview. Semi-structured key informant interviews will help build an understanding of the influences, background stories, challenges, and lessons on dementia policy development. Key Informant Interviews will be audio-recorded. I hope you will agree to participate in the Key Informant Interview. A Key Informant Interviews guideline with open-ended questions will be followed, but there are also opportunities for you to add your comments. The interview will be last up to sixty minutes. The interview will be carried out at your convenience and suggested dates and times are in your email.

I very much appreciate your offer to participate in the key informant interview of this study and look forward to meeting you soon and hearing your views.

Yours sincerely,

Mohammad Mainuddin Mollah

Ph.D. in the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice

School of Health and Life Sciences

University of the West of Scotland

Lanarkshire Campus

Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire

G 72 0LH. Email: [REDACTED]

Appendix 4.4: Information sheet for Key Informants Interviews Participants

Verson-03 and Date-20.01.2021

PARTICIPANT'S INFORMATION SHEET

Policy Stakeholders of Key Informant Interviews

School of Health and Life Sciences, UWS.

Study Title: Workforce Development and Dementia Care in Bangladesh: Policy Learning from the Scottish Context

I want to invite you to participate in the Key Informant Interview in this research project which forms part of my PhD, funded by the Bangabandhu Overseas Scholarship Program of the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. Before you decide whether you want to take part, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what your participation will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. If you decide you want to take part in this study and permit me to use your views in the PhD thesis and any subsequent publications or reports, the completion of the attached consent form is necessary for this interview. Please see the attached consent form.

Name of Principal investigator and affiliation of the researcher:

I am Mohammad Mainuddin Mollah, Assistant Professor in the Institute of Social Welfare and Research at the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. I am also a PhD Student in the Alzheimer's Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice (ASCPP) in the School of Health and Life Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland, Lanarkshire Campus, Hamilton International Technology Park, Stephenson Place, South Lanarkshire, Scotland.G72 0LH.

What is the purpose of the study?

The purpose of this study is to investigate and analyse Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches to determine the utility for application within Bangladesh.

The study will seek to:

- To critically review the evidence base shaping dementia care and dementia workforce development policy and policy implementation within Scotland and Bangladesh;
- To determine Scottish dementia policy scope, indicators of success and lessons for possible policy transfer to Bangladesh;
- To scope with multi-sectorial stakeholders in Bangladesh their aspirations and priorities for the development of dementia care policy; and
- To make recommendations to inform future dementia policy development in Bangladesh.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because you have played a key role in the development and implementation of dementia care policies and workforce development approaches in Scotland and have expertise and experience in dementia care.

Do I have to take part in the study?

No. It is up to you whether you choose to take part in the study or not. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and will be asked to sign a consent form. You can participate, not participate or withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason. If you withdraw from the study the information you provide will be removed from the study.

If you wish to withdraw your participation, please do so within three months of our interview. Anonymised data cannot be withdrawn after 3 months as it will have been included in the analysis and design of the next stage of the study.

What will taking part involve?

This research will use the "Key Informant Interviews". The key informant interviews aim is to explore an informed and in-depth view of dementia care policy development in Scotland. If you agree to participate, you will be invited to take part in a virtual (WebEx, Teams or Zoom) or telephone interview at a date and time of your choosing. Semi-structured questions will help me develop an understanding of the influences, background stories, challenges, and lessons

on dementia policy development within Scotland. And, there will be opportunities for your reflections on your experience. The interview will be audio-recorded and anonymised on transcription. Interview will last up to sixty minutes. Participation is voluntary. You are under no obligation to take part in the Key Informant Interview, and you can stop or withdraw at any time.

Are there any risk involved?

This research will not place you at any risk. Your online Key Informant Interview responses will be used only to compile research findings. You will not be asked to reveal anything of a personal or sensitive nature. I am seeking information from key policy stakeholders in Scotland to identify the origins and development of dementia care and workforce development policy in Scotland.

What are the potential benefits of taking part?

By participating in this study, you will support the development of evidence underpinned policy proposition for workforce development and dementia care in Bangladesh. Therefore, contributing to improving the quality of life for people living with dementia and their family carers in Bangladesh.

Will the information shared be kept confidential?

Yes, pseudonyms will be used in place of your name, and this cannot be linked to you in any publication or report from this study. All electronic data will be saved in a password-protected computer within premises of the University of the West of Scotland. Data will be accessible only by the researcher and supervisory team for at least 36 months after completion of the study to allow for analysis, thesis completion and publication disseminations according to UKRIO Code of Practice for Research and UWS privacy and confidentiality policy. After 36 months, I will delete all electronic data. All hardcopy information will be saved in a locked cabinet in the researcher's office at the university for 36 months after completion of the study. At the end of this time, I will shred and trash all hard copies.

The School has approved this study of Health and Life Sciences, School Ethics Committee (SEC) at the University of the West of Scotland (Reference Number: 11822). Your views will be held confidentially. Data collected will only be used for this study and will not be used to identify any individuals. All results will be presented in an aggregated and anonymised form. The results of this study will be presented at scientific meetings or published in scientific journals.

Any questions?

If you wish to discuss the study further or have any questions, then please contact me the researcher, Mohammad Mainuddin Mollah, email: [REDACTED] or the Director of Studies, Professor Dr Debbie Tolson, email: [REDACTED].

If you have any complaints, then contact the Director of Studies, Professor Dr Debbie Tolson, email: [REDACTED]

Thank you for reading this information sheet and for considering taking part in the Key Informant Interview of this study.

Yours sincerely,

Mohammad Mainuddin Mollah

Ph.D. in the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice

School of Health and Life Sciences

University of the West of Scotland

Lanarkshire Campus

Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire

G 72 0LH. Email: [REDACTED]

Appendix 4.5: Consent Form for Key Informants Interviews Participants

Verson-03 and Date-20.01.2021

PARTICIPANT'S CONSENT FORM

Policy Stakeholders of Key Informant Interviews

School of Health and Life Sciences, UWS.

Study Title: Workforce Development and Dementia Care in Bangladesh: Policy Learning from the Scottish Context

Please initial each box to indicate that you have read and understood the information provided and that you are willing to take part in this study.

- 1. I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the study.
- 2. I know what the study is about and what taking part will involve. -----
- 3. I have been given the opportunity to ask questions via virtual (webex, Teams or Zoom) or telephone -----
- 4. I have had the opportunity to ask questions and discuss the study. -----
- 5. I understand that my participation in the Key Informant Interview is voluntary and I know that I am free to withdraw from this study at any time without having to give any reason for withdrawing.-----
- 6. I agree that any data collected before my withdrawal from the research will be removed from the study -----

7. I understand that if I want to withdraw my participation and therefore the data, I must do so within three months of our interview. Anonymised data cannot be withdrawn after 3 months as it will have been included in the analysis and design of the next stage of the study-----
8. I agree to the interview/discussion being audio-recorded. -----
9. I consent to the storage of my contact details and anonymised data in UWS secure systems for the duration of 36 months after completion of the study-----
10. I agree that the researcher can present my opinions in the PhD thesis and any related publications or reports as long as they are kept anonymous. -----
11. I agree for the researcher to discuss this information at scientific meetings and academic conferences. -----

Name of participant:.....

Signature:.....

Date: 04th February 2021

Name of researcher taking consent: Mohammad Mainuddin Mollah

Email: [REDACTED]

Appendix 4.6: Key Informant Interview Schedule for Policy Stakeholders

Verson-03 and Date-20.01.2021

Semi-structured Interview Schedule for Key Informants

School of Health and Life Sciences, UWS.

Study Title: Workforce Development and Dementia Care in Bangladesh: Policy Learning from the Scottish Context

Preparation

Welcome by Researcher and thank you (Researcher will introduce himself and then will request the participant to introduce her/himself).

Introductions

Explain how the recording will be done

Repeat purpose of the study and Key Informant Interview

Re-establish consent

Ground rules – confidentiality and anonymity issues

Re-introduce topic and begin the interview

Background

1. Could you please tell me about your career background and how it is you came to work in the dementia policy area?

2. From your perspective, what were the critical reasons for the introduction of the national dementia policy/ strategy in Scotland back in 2010?

Policy development

3. Do you feel that the dementia strategy was in any way politically contentious, or was there general agreement across political parties in Scotland? Why?

Researcher Prompts:

- Key individuals/people:
- National ministries/departments/organisations:
- International organisations:
- Interest groups:
- Contribution of stakeholders in the development of initial national dementia policy/ strategy:

4. Do you have any insights into which individuals /groups or agencies influenced the care and workforce development aspects of the strategy?

5. How such actors have influenced the strategy?

Researcher Prompts:

- Policy meetings:
- Personal relationships:
- Networking:

Implementation and evaluation of the strategy

6. With the strategy in mind, based on your perspective, what were the barriers to the development and implementation of national dementia care and workforce development policies in Scotland?

Prompts:

Barriers to the development

- Preserving government policy goals and instruments:
- Legitimacy in the formation of choices:
- Conferring legitimacy on the policy /Passage of legislation:
- Political sustainability:
- Innovation and influence:
- Role of health and social care integration

- Availability of expertise/involvement of the right people

Barriers to the implementation

- Operational (implementation in line with objectives):
- Outcome (achievement of desired outcomes):
- Resource (efficient use of resources):
- Actor/interest (creating benefit for target groups):
- Meets policy domain criteria:
- Role of health and social care integration
- Availability of expertise/involvement of the right people

7. Also, what were the facilitators or enablers to the development and implementation of national dementia care and workforce development policies?

Prompts:

Facilitators to the development

- Preserving government policy goals and instruments:
- Legitimacy in the formation of choices:
- Conferring legitimacy on the policy /Passage of legislation:
- Political sustainability:
- Innovation and influence:
- Role of health and social care integration
- Availability of expertise/involvement of the right people

Facilitators to the implementation

- Operational (implementation in line with objectives):
- Outcome (achievement of desired outcomes):
- Resource (efficient use of resources):
- Actor/interest (creating benefit for target groups):
- Meets policy domain criteria:
- Role of health and social care integration
- Availability of expertise/involvement of the right people

8. If we could go back in history and formulate the dementia strategy then what should be done differently?

9. From your perspective, has there been a shift in dementia care and workforce development policies (early diagnosis to palliative) in Scotland since -2010?

10. Are you aware of evaluations of the workforce development aspect of the dementia strategy? How robust are these (if they have been done?).

Researcher Prompts:

- General thoughts on workforce development issues:
- Concerns about best practice:

Policy learning and transfer issues

11. What are the key lessons that other countries should learn from Scotland when it comes to formulating dementia care policies, particularly in terms of workforce development? (prompts: taking an evidence-based approach, not politicising the area, coalition building)

12. In terms of the governance of dementia strategies, what would be the key criteria that you would identify which makes for policy success in this area based on the experience of the Scottish context?

13. If we were going to co-create opportunities for sharing learning on best practice between those countries with developed policies and systems (such as Scotland) and countries which are developing their dementia policies then what would be the best ways of sharing policy knowledge and good practice?

Do you have any other thoughts that you would like to share before we conclude the interview?

Conclusion of the interview

Researcher switches off the audio-recorder

Researcher thanks the participant for their contribution

The researcher asks the participant whether they would like to receive a copy of their interview transcript for verification.

Thank you for sharing your valuable insights and expertise.

Appendix 4.7: Initial Thematic Framework for Data Analysis of Policy Documents and Key Informant Interviews

A. Process Success of the Scottish dementia strategy

Subthemes:

- Preserving government policy goals and instruments
- Legitimacy in the formation of choices and passage of legislation
- Building a sustainable coalition
- Innovation and influence:
- Opposition to process is virtually non-existent and/or support is virtually universal.

B. Programme Success of the Scottish dementia strategy

Subthemes:

- Operational: implementation in line with objectives
- Outcome: achievement of desired outcomes
- Resource: efficient use of resources
- Actor/interest: creating benefit for target groups
- Opposition to program aims, values, and means of achieving them is virtually non-existent, and/or support is virtually universal.

C. Political Success of the Scottish dementia strategy

Subthemes:

- Government popularity
- Sustaining the broad values and direction of government
- Opposition to political benefits for government is virtually non-existent and/or support is virtually universal.

Appendix 4.8: Working Thematic Framework /Coding Framework (including codebook)

(Descriptions provided in italics)

Themes	Subthemes	Codes	Examples (Interviews and policy documents transcripts)
Process Success of the Scottish dementia strategy	Preserving government policy goals and instruments	Legislative records	<i>'The Charter of Rights, then became the very foundation stone of the first Dementia Strategy' (P 2, Line 194-195).</i>
		Executive minutes	<i>The Scottish Dementia Forum, chaired by the Minister for Public Health and Sport has brought together representatives from the statutory and voluntary sectors as well as people living with dementia and the people who care for them, has been created and has met regularly (First National Dementia Strategy).</i>
		Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders	<i>'Every single political party in Parliament signed up to the Charter of Rights and that was very powerful' (P 1, Line 272-274). This [third dementia] strategy is the product of collaboration between colleagues from across health, social care and the third sector and includes direct input at every stage from people with dementia, their families and carers' (Third National Dementia Strategy).</i>
	Legitimacy in the formation of choices and passage of legislation	Legislative records	
		Executive minutes	

		Analysis of legislative voting patterns	
	Building a sustainable coalition	Analysis of support from ministers	
		Analysis of support from stakeholders	
	Innovation and influence	Legislative records	
		Executive minutes	
		Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders	
		Academic and practitioner reports	
	Opposition to process is virtually non-existent and/or support is virtually universal	Legislative records	
		Executive minutes	
		Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders	
Programme Success of the Scottish dementia strategy	Operational: Implementation in line with objectives	Programme/policy evaluation	
		Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders	
	Outcome: Achievement of desired outcomes	Programme/policy evaluation	
		Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders	

	Resource: Efficient use of resources	Programme/policy evaluation	
		Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders	
	Actor/interest: Creating benefit for a target group	Qualitative and quantitative studies with policy beneficiaries	
	Opposition to program aims, values, and means of achieving them is virtually non-existent, and/or support is virtually universal	Programme/policy evaluation	
Absence of significant criticism from stakeholders			
Political Success of the Scottish dementia strategy	Government popularity	Opinion polls	
		Election results	
	Sustaining the broad values and direction of government	Analysis of manifestoes	
		Policy strategy documents	
	Opposition to political benefits for government is virtually non-existent and/or support is virtually universal	Manifestos of opposition political parties	

**Appendix 4.9: Example of Data Indexing Table of Policy Documents of Process
Success**

SL. No	Title of Document	Publisher	Year	Process Success and Indicators(sub-themes)				
				Preserving government policy goals and instruments	Legitimacy in the formation of choices and Passage of legislation	Building a sustainable coalition	Innovation and influence	Opposition to process is virtually non-existent and/or support is virtually universal
01	The Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers in Scotland	Alzheimer Scotland/ The Scottish Parliament Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer's	2009		To empower people with dementia and their carers to assert their rights in every parts of their daily lives and...ensure the highest quality of service provision to people with dementia and their carers.	The Charter reflects the views of over 500 people (including people with dementia, their carers, and professionals) who took part in the widespread consultation carried out on behalf of the Cross-Party Group by Alzheimer Scotland between May-July 2009.	The Scottish Parliament adopted the human rights-based approach to dementia, PANEL in 2009, which is also endorsed by the United Nations and represents the basic principles of human rights. PANEL provides a framework of Participation, Accountability, Non-discrimination, Empowerment, and Legal aspects which underpin the respect for the rights of people living with dementia.	In Scotland, for example, to develop the Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers, the Cross-Party Group in the Scottish Parliament on Alzheimer's brought together Members of the Scottish Parliament with organisations representing the interests of people with dementia. The group worked towards ensuring high quality support, services and

								<p>treatment are in place to assist people living with dementia and their carers throughout Scotland. As part of this work the group has considered how to ensure that the rights of people living with dementia and their carers are fully recognised at all levels of government and by individuals and non-governmental organisations, regardless of where they are and in every part of their daily lives.</p>
02	The National Dialogue on Dementia: Dementia Strategy Consultation Paper	The Scottish Government	2009					
03	Scotland's National Dementia Strategy	The Scottish Government	2010	The first dementia strategy emphasised to deliver world-class dementia care and		The Scottish Dementia Forum, chaired by the Minister for Public Health and Sport has brought		

				treatment in Scotland, ensuring that people living with dementia and their families are supported in the best possible way to live well with dementia.		together representatives from the statutory and voluntary sectors as well as people living with dementia and the people who care for them, has been created and has met regularly.		
04	Standards of Care for Dementia in Scotland: Action to support the change programme, Scotland's National Dementia Strategy	The Scottish Government	2011					
05	Promoting Excellence: A framework for all health and social services staff working with people with dementia, their families and carers	The Scottish Government	2011	The Scottish Government also developed Promoting Excellence Framework, which included updating professional qualifications, enhancing existing workforce capability and developing leadership within the dementia workforce.				
06	Scotland's National Dementia Strategy: One Year on Report	The Scottish Government	2011					

07	Speech by Nicola Sturgeon at Scotland's Dementia Awareness Week Conference, 2011	The Scottish Government	2011					
08	Scotland's National Dementia Strategy: Two Years on Report	The Scottish Government	2012					
09	Scotland's National Dementia Strategy: 2013-16	The Scottish Government	2013			The key outcomes for this Strategy, which emerged from the National Dementia Dialogue as priorities were: more people with dementia living a good quality life at home for longer, dementia-enabled and dementia-friendly local communities, that contribute to greater awareness of dementia and reduce stigma, timely, accurate diagnosis of dementia, better post-diagnostic support for people with dementia and their families, more people with dementia and their families and carers being involved as equal partners in care throughout the journey of the illness, better respect and		

						promotion of rights in all settings, together with improved compliance with the legal requirements in respect of treatment, people with dementia in hospitals or other institutional settings always being treated with dignity and respect.		
10	Evaluating the impact of the Alzheimer Scotland Dementia Nurse Consultants/Specialists & Dementia Champions in bringing about improvements to dementia care in acute general hospitals	NHS Education for Scotland/ Ellison, S., Watt, G. and Christie, I.	2014					
11	Technology Charter for People Living with Dementia in Scotland	The Scottish Government et al	2015					
12	Dementia Friendly Communities in Scotland Report 2-The First Year April 2015 - March 2016	Life Changes Trust	2015					
13	Living and dying with dementia in Scotland: Barriers to care	Marie Curie Cancer Care	2015					

14	Estimated and Projected Diagnosis Rates for Dementia in Scotland: 2014-2020.	The Scottish Government	2016					
15	Glasgow City Dementia Strategy 2016-19	Glasgow City Council	2016					
16	Scotland's National Dementia Strategy 2017-2020	The Scottish Government	2017			This strategy is the product of collaboration between colleagues from across health, social care and the third sector and includes direct input at every stage from people with dementia, their families and carers.		
17	Connecting People, Connecting Support: Transforming the allied health professionals' contribution to supporting people living with dementia in Scotland, 2017-2020	The Scottish Government	2017					
18	My-life-my-care-home-The experiences of people living with dementia in care homes in Scotland	Care Inspectorate	2017					

19	A Fairer Scotland for Older People: A Framework for Action	The Scottish Government	2019					
20	Dementia and Covid-19- National Action Plan to Continue to Support Recovery for People with Dementia and their Carers	The Scottish Government	2020					
21	Dementia and COVID-19- National Action Plan to Continue to Support Recovery for People with Dementia and their Carers: Equality Impact Assessment Record	The Scottish Government	2021					
22	Independent Review of Adult Social Care in Scotland	The Scottish Government	2021					
23	Promoting Excellence: A framework for all health and social services staff working with people with dementia	The Scottish Government	2021	The Scottish Government has updated the Promoting Excellence Framework in 2021, which sets out the knowledge and skills needed for new ways of working for all health and social care staff to help people living with dementia, their families and carers to maximise their rights, choices, and health and				

			<p>wellbeing at all stages of their own dementia journey. It works alongside other standards and frameworks, such as the NHS Knowledge and Skills Framework, the Social Services Continuous Learning Framework and the National Occupational Standards for Health and Social Care. The framework also has relevance and applicability to other sectors, such as housing.</p>				
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**Appendix 4.10: Example of Data Charting Table of Policy Documents of Process
Success**

SL. No	Title of Document	Publisher	Year	Process Success and Indicators(sub-themes)				
				Preserving government policy goals and instruments	Legitimacy in the formation of choices and Passage of legislation	Building a sustainable coalition	Innovation and influence	Opposition to process is virtually non-existent and/or support is virtually universal
01	The Charter of Rights for People with Dementia and their Carers in Scotland	Alzheimer Scotland/ The Scottish Parliament Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer's	2009		The Charter of Rights has provided a legislative framework in Scotland to develop dementia policy.	The Scottish Government and Alzheimer Scotland hosted a series of national dementia dialogues and consultation events since 2009 in developing a national dementia strategy.	The first National Dementia Strategy has emphasized a Human Rights-Based Approach to ensure the rights of people living with dementia and their carers.	Political commitment across the political parties and public support to establish dementia care as a national public health priority reinforced the development of dementia policy in Scotland. The Cross-Party Group has worked with organisations representing the interests of people with dementia and their carers.

02	The National Dialogue on Dementia: Dementia Strategy Consultation Paper	The Scottish Government	2009					
03	Scotland's National Dementia Strategy	The Scottish Government	2010	The first dementia strategy committed to deliver world-class dementia care and treatment in Scotland,		There was a close collaboration with a wide range of stakeholders including people living with dementia, their carers and families in developing the dementia care strategies.		
04	Standards of Care for Dementia in Scotland: Action to support the change programme, Scotland's National Dementia Strategy	The Scottish Government	2011					
05	Promoting Excellence: A framework for all health and social services staff working with people with dementia, their families and carers	The Scottish Government	2011	The Promoting Excellence Framework supports the development of professional qualifications and expertise of health and social care workers in dementia care.				
06	Scotland's National Dementia Strategy: One Year on Report	The Scottish Government	2011					

07	Speech by Nicola Sturgeon at Scotland's Dementia Awareness Week Conference, 2011	The Scottish Government	2011					
08	Scotland's National Dementia Strategy: Two Years on Report	The Scottish Government	2012					
09	Scotland's National Dementia Strategy: 2013-16	The Scottish Government	2013			The national dementia dialogues and consultation events identified several priorities in discussions with a wide range of key stakeholders for developing national dementia strategies.		
10	Evaluating the impact of the Alzheimer Scotland Dementia Nurse Consultants/Specialists & Dementia Champions in bringing about improvements to dementia care in acute general hospitals	NHS Education for Scotland/ Ellison, S., Watt, G. and Christie, I.	2014					
11	Technology Charter for People Living with Dementia in Scotland	The Scottish Government et al	2015					
12	Dementia Friendly Communities in Scotland Report 2-The First Year April 2015 - March 2016	Life Changes Trust	2015					
13	Living and dying with dementia in Scotland: Barriers to care	Marie Curie Cancer Care	2015					

14	Estimated and Projected Diagnosis Rates for Dementia in Scotland: 2014-2020.	The Scottish Government	2016					
15	Glasgow City Dementia Strategy 2016-19	Glasgow City Council	2016					
16	Scotland's National Dementia Strategy 2017-2020	The Scottish Government	2017			The national dementia dialogues and consultation events involved a wide range of key stakeholders in developing national dementia strategies.		
17	Connecting People, Connecting Support: Transforming the allied health professionals' contribution to supporting people living with dementia in Scotland, 2017-2020	The Scottish Government	2017					
18	My-life-my-care-home-The experiences of people living with dementia in care homes in Scotland	Care Inspectorate	2017					
19	A Fairer Scotland for Older People: A Framework for Action	The Scottish Government	2019					
20	Dementia and COVID-19- National Action Plan to Continue to Support Recovery for People with Dementia and their Carers	The Scottish Government	2020					

21	Dementia and COVID-19-National Action Plan to Continue to Support Recovery for People with Dementia and their Carers: Equality Impact Assessment Record	The Scottish Government	2021					
22	Independent Review of Adult Social Care in Scotland	The Scottish Government	2021					
23	Promoting Excellence: A framework for all health and social services staff working with people with dementia	The Scottish Government	2021	The Scottish Government updated the Promoting Excellence Framework, which sets out the knowledge and skills needed for new ways of working for all health and social care staff to help people living with dementia and their carers and families.				

**Appendix 4.11: Example of Data Indexing Table of Key Informant Interviews of
Process Success**

Key Informant Interviews	Process Success and Indicators(sub-themes)				
	Preserving government policy goals and instruments	Legitimacy in the formation of choices and Passage of legislation	Building a sustainable coalition	Innovation and influence	Opposition to process is virtually non-existent and/or support is virtually universal
KII 01		<p>... we [the Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer's] worked with...Scottish Human Rights Commissioner to take all these challenges that people have brought to us and barriers and said what would,...a document look like that could empower people and give them rights, and this Scottish Human Rights Commissioner, Alzheimer Scotland and myself [ALLIANCE] put together all...and it distilled all the information that we've collected from...over 1000 people from the Roadshows and turned it into a Charter of</p>	<p>'we [the Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer's] managed to get to be...parliament group about the Procedures Committee agreed to it' (P 1, Line 104-106).</p> <p>'every single political party in Parliament signed up to the Charter of Rights and that was very powerful' (P 1, Line 272-274).</p>	<p>There are too many people who are not able to access services who have needs, just because their needs relatively speaking are not as bad as other peoples needs, so they need to access rest by, you know they need to access day care while we're in the middle of a pandemic just now [2021]. But, even when we're not in a pandemic, not everyone can access day care services, not everyone can access respite services. And, yet people are in...desperate need' (P 1, Line 424-429).</p>	<p>'but the thing was, we've [the Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer's] done a lot of lobbying behind the scenes...and picked all the political parties...to support...it [the Charter of Rights]' (P 1, Line 237-258).</p>

		<p>Rights (P 1, Line 185-192).</p> <p>'...then we [the Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer's] wanted to make sure it [the Charter of Rights] wasn't a document that sat on a shelf. That was something...that followed on the National Dementia Strategy and then the workforce plan and then...the Standards' (P 1, Line 259-262).</p> <p>...having that Charter of Rights,...I think that was quite powerful...and... it just gives ammunition to groups like Alzheimer Scotland to just really take up the fight and to argue for national dementia strategies' (P 1, Line 270-275).</p>			
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<p>KII 02</p>	<p>'...having dementia recognizes as a political priority...is important. It allows us as a campaigning organization to continually remind the Scottish Government that this is one of their own priorities' (P 2, Line 556-559).</p>	<p>'the Charter of Rights, then became the very foundation stone of the first Dementia Strategy' (P 2, Line 194-195).</p>	<p>We engaged with a whole cross-sector...from individual members of the public living with dementia, carers, carers organisations...academics were involved in the consultation,..That happened every time that we've had a National Dementia Strategy (P 2, Line 259-263).</p> <p>'in the Parliament,... the whole of the political spectrum in Scotland supported the Charter of Rights' (P 2, Line 192-194).</p>	<p>Human Rights-based Approach...recognizing...the rights of people living with dementia and their carers. It's about their rights as citizens and the recognition that they have the same human and other legal rights, as everybody else' (P 2, Line 452-456).</p>	<p>'...we [Alzheimer Scotland] as an organization had been campaigning for a National Dementia Strategy... At the same time, we [Alzheimer Scotland] had developed an election manifesto calling for a Scottish National Dementia Strategy' (P 2, 132-157).</p> <p>'at that time...that was quite a difficult thing, because... the Scottish Government were planning their own Charter for Patients' Rights and they...weren't quite so supportive of the Charter of Rights [for People with Dementia and their Carers]' (P 2, Line 187-190).</p>
<p>KII 03</p>	<p>the Alzheimer Scotland then took on the mantle of trying to develop an overall strategy...for Scotland and,...that coupled with the voice of the Scottish Dementia Working Group,...sort of recaptured...the minds of the Scottish Government...So, there was a lot of government support...And there's a lot</p>				

	<p>of initiatives...from Alzheimer Scotland ...That then became the basis of that first strategy' (P 3, Line 114-124)</p>				
<p>KII 04</p>		<p>A key driver, for Scotland's dementia strategy and then the subsequent workforce, development... was the Charter of Rights for people with dementia, families and carers...So, people living with dementia found...their voice and... identifying issues that were going wrong for them...and their aspirations, and that's really what the Charter kind of...' (P 4, Line 100-112).</p>	<p>...another key driver in Scotland in terms of the...strategy was the involvement of partners (P 4, Line 112-113).</p>	<p>So, stakeholder partnerships pushing absolutely inclusive and meaningfully involve people with lived experience of dementia and families, and carers a Human Rights- Based Approach,...was absolutely kind of underpinning things and then. The use of PANEL principles to guide structures for meaningful stakeholders engagement,...So,...what happened with dementia strategy in Scotland a... movement was created to large extend' (P 4, Line 433-444)).</p>	

KII 05			One of the keys, very early on, was to.. involve every single potential stakeholder developing and implementing strategies, in particular, directly involving people with dementia and carers...which we've done consistently, and we've actually managed to do it (P 5, Line 213-217).		
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**Appendix 4.12: Example of Data Charting Table of Key Informant Interviews of
Process Success**

Key Informant Interviews	Process Success and Indicators (sub-themes)				
	Preserving government policy goals and instruments	Legitimacy in the formation of choices and Passage of legislation	Building a sustainable coalition	Innovation and influence	Opposition to process is virtually non-existent and/or support is virtually universal
KII 01		<p>The CPGA jointly worked with different stakeholder groups (the Scottish Human Rights Commission (SHRC), Alzheimer Scotland (AS) and ALLIANCE) to develop a draft of the CR (P 1, Line 185-192).</p> <p>The CR has become the basis of <u>the national dementia strategy and then the workforce plan and then...the standards of dementia care.</u> (P 1, Line 259-262).</p> <p>The CR facilitated raising voices for developing a national</p>	<p>The Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer's (CPGA) was formed with the representation of all political parties in the Scottish parliament (SP) (P 1, Line 104-106)</p> <p>The Charter of Rights (CR) was approved by all political parties in the SP without any reservation (P 1, Line 272-274)</p>	<p>People with dementia, their family members, and carers living in the community have been facing challenges accessing different support services to ensure their rights and maintain quality of life (P 1, Line 424-429).</p>	<p>The CPGA has been lobbying with the representative of all political parties in SP to get support for the CR (P 1, Line 237-258).</p>

		dementia strategy in Scotland. (P 1, Line 270-275)			
KII 02	Political recognition of dementia care supports the successful development and implementation of dementia care policies. (P 2, Line 555-559).	The CR developed the <u>foundation stone of the first Dementia Strategy</u> (P 2, Line 194-195).	National-level dementia consultation events involved a wide range of stakeholders to identify the priorities of the national dementia strategy. (P 2, Line 259-263) Through negotiation and debate in the SP, all political parties <u>supported the Charter of Rights</u> (P 2, Line 192-194).	Human rights-based approach recognises the same human and other legal rights for people living with dementia and their carers (P 2, Line 452-456)	Alzheimer Scotland campaigned and created pressure on the Scottish Government to introduce National Dementia Strategy in Scotland (P 2, 132-157). The SG were less interested in the Charter of Rights for dementia as they were planning to prepare patients' charter. (P 2, Line 187-190)
KII 03	Alzheimer Scotland along with other national organisations representing people living with dementia and their carers influenced the government to				

	introduce a dementia strategy (P 3, Line 114-124)				
KII 04		The CR was the key driver in developing dementia strategy and workforce development framework for dementia health and social care services (P 4, Line 100-112)	Involvement of key partners played a significant role to develop a national dementia strategy in Scotland (P 4, Line 112-113).	Human rights-based dementia care approach supports a larger movement and meaningful stakeholder engagement in developing and implementing dementia care policies and workforce development approaches. (P 4, Line 433-444)	
KII 05			The SG ensured the direct involvement of stakeholders in the development and implementation of dementia care policies. (P 5, Line 213-217).		

Appendix 4.13: Invitation letter for stakeholders to participate in the Nominal Group Technique (NGT)-Group Discussion

(নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক(এনজিটি)-গ্রুপ আলোচনায় অংশ নেওয়ার জন্য
স্টেকহোল্ডারদের আমন্ত্রণ পত্র)

INVITATION LETTER (আমন্ত্রণ পত্র)

Stakeholders of Nominal Group Technique-Group Discussion

(নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক-গ্রুপ আলোচনার স্টেকহোল্ডার)

School of Health and Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland (UWS), UK
(স্কুল অফ হেলথ অ্যান্ড লাইফ সায়েন্সেস, ইউনিভার্সিটি অফ দ্য ওয়েস্ট অফ স্কটল্যান্ড
(ইউডব্লিউএস), যুক্তরাজ্য

Study Title: Workforce Development and Dementia Care in Bangladesh: Policy Learning from the Scottish Context (গবেষণার শিরোনাম: বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন এবং কর্মী উন্নয়ন: স্কটিশ প্রেক্ষিত থেকে পলিসি শিক্ষা)

Sub: Request to participate in the Nominal Group Technique-Group Discussion
(বিষয়: নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক-গ্রুপ আলোচনায় অংশ নেওয়ার অনুরোধ)

Dear

I want to introduce myself. My name is Mohammad Mainuddin Mollah, Assistant Professor in the Institute of Social Welfare and Research at the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. I am also PhD Student in the Alzheimer's Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice (ASCPP) in the School of Health and Life Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland, Lanarkshire Campus,

Hamilton International Technology Park, Stephenson Place, South Lanarkshire, Scotland.G72 0LH. I am carrying out a research study on "Workforce Development and Dementia Care in Bangladesh: Policy Learning from the Scottish Context". This part of the study is a "Nominal Group Technique (NGT)-Group Discussion". The main aim of NGT is to identify what you see as the priorities for dementia care and workforce development policy in Bangladesh.

I want to invite you to participate in the Nominal Group Technique-Group Discussion in this research project which forms part of my PhD, funded by the Bangabandhu Overseas Scholarship Program of the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. If you agree to participate in the study, you will be invited to participate in a face to face or virtual meeting. Nominal Group discussion will help to identify priorities for dementia care and workforce development policy in Bangladesh. I hope you will agree to participate in the Nominal Group discussion. A User guideline will be followed, but there are also opportunities for you to add your comments. The group discussion will be last up to 02 hours with a refreshment break. The discussion will be carried out at your convenience and suggested venue, dates and times are in your email.

I very much appreciate your offer to participate in the Nominal Group Technique-Group Discussion of this study and look forward to meeting you soon and hearing your views.

Yours sincerely,

Mohammad Mainuddin Mollah
Assistant Professor
Institute of Social Welfare and Research
University of Dhaka, Bangladesh.
Email: [REDACTED]
Mobile: [REDACTED]

&

Ph.D. in the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice
School of Health and Life Sciences
University of the West of Scotland
Lanarkshire Campus
Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire
G 72 0LH. Email: [REDACTED]
Mobile: [REDACTED]

প্রিয় মহোদয়, -----

শুভেচ্ছা গ্রহণ করুন। আমি মুহাম্মদ মাইনউদ্দিন মোল্লা, বাংলাদেশের ঢাকা বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়ের ইনস্টিটিউট অফ সোশ্যাল ওয়েলফেয়ার অ্যান্ড রিসার্চের একজন সহকারী অধ্যাপক। পাশাপাশি আমি ইউনিভার্সিটি অফ দ্য ওয়েস্ট অফ স্কটল্যান্ডের, স্কুল অফ হেলথ অ্যান্ড লাইফ সায়েন্সেস এর অধীন অ্যালবাইমার স্কটল্যান্ড সেন্টার ফর পলিসি অ্যান্ড প্র্যাকটিস (এএসসিপিপি)-এর একজন পিএইচডি গবেষক। আমি " বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন এবং কর্মী উন্নয়ন: স্কটিশ প্রেক্ষিত থেকে পলিসি শিক্ষা " বিষয়ে একটি গবেষণা পরিচালনা করছি। গবেষণার এই অংশটি একটি " নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক (এনজিটি)-গ্রুপ আলোচনা"। এনজিটির মূল লক্ষ্য হ'ল বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন এবং কর্মী উন্নয়ন নীতির অগ্রাধিকার হিসাবে আপনি যেসব বিষয় গুরুত্বপূর্ণ মনে করেন তা সনাক্ত করা।

আমি আপনাকে এই গবেষণা প্রকল্পে নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক-গ্রুপ আলোচনায় অংশ নেওয়ার জন্য আমন্ত্রণ জানাচ্ছি। আমার পিএইচডি গবেষণাটি বাংলাদেশের ঢাকা বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়ের বঙ্গবন্ধু ওভারসিজ স্কলারশিপ প্রোগ্রামের অর্থায়নে পরিচালিত হচ্ছে। আপনি যদি গবেষণায় অংশ নিতে সম্মত হন তবে আপনাকে ভার্সুয়াল মিটিংয়ে অংশ নিতে আমন্ত্রণ জানানো হবে। নমিনাল গ্রুপ আলোচনা বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন এবং কর্মী উন্নয়ন নীতির অগ্রাধিকার চিহ্নিত করতে সহায়তা করবে। আমি আশা করি আপনি নমিনাল গ্রুপ আলোচনায় অংশ নিতে সম্মত হবেন। নমিনাল গ্রুপ আলোচনায় একটি ব্যবহার নির্দেশিকা অনুসরণ করা হবে, তবে আপনার কোনো মন্তব্য থাকলে তা সংযোজন করার সুযোগ রয়েছে। গ্রুপ আলোচনাটি একটি রিফ্রেশমেন্ট বিরতিসহ সর্বোচ্চ ০২ ঘন্টা পর্যন্ত স্থায়ী হবে। গ্রুপ আলোচনাটি আপনার সুবিধাজনক তারিখ এবং সময়ে সম্পন্ন করা হবে। আপনার জন্য প্রস্তাবিত ভার্সুয়াল মিটিংয়ের সম্ভাব্য একাধিক তারিখ এবং সময় আপনার ইমেলে উল্লেখ করা হয়েছে।

আমি এই গবেষণার নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক-গ্রুপ আলোচনায় অংশ নেওয়ার জন্য এবং শীঘ্রই আপনার সাথে ভার্সুয়াল মিটিংয়ে অংশগ্রহণ করে আপনার মতামত শোনার জন্য আপনার নিকট থেকে ইতিবাচক প্রস্তাবের প্রশংসা করি।

আপনার আন্তরিকতায়,

মুহাম্মদ মাইনউদ্দিন মোল্লা

সহকারী অধ্যাপক

ইনস্টিটিউট অফ সোশ্যাল ওয়েলফেয়ার অ্যান্ড রিসার্চ

ঢাকা বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়, বাংলাদেশ।

ইমেইল: [REDACTED]

মোবাইল: [REDACTED]

এবং

অ্যালবাইমার স্কটল্যান্ড সেন্টার ফর পলিসি অ্যান্ড প্র্যাকটিস- পিএইচডি গবেষক

স্কুল অফ হেলথ অ্যান্ড লাইফ সায়েন্সেস, ইউনিভার্সিটি অফ দ্য ওয়েস্ট অফ স্কটল্যান্ড

লনার্কশায়ার ক্যাম্পাস, স্টিফেনসন প্লেস, হ্যামিল্টন ইন্টারন্যাশনাল টেকনোলজি পার্ক, সাউথ লনার্কশায়ার

জি ৭২ ওএলএইচ। ইমেইল: [REDACTED] , [REDACTED]

Appendix 4.14: Information sheet for Nominal Group Technique (NGT) -Group Discussion Participants

(নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক (এনজিটি)-গ্রুপ আলোচনায় অংশগ্রহণকারীদের জন্য তথ্যপত্র)

Verson-03 and Date-02.06.2021

PARTICIPANT'S INFORMATION SHEET

(অংশগ্রহণকারীর তথ্যপত্র)

Stakeholders of Nominal Group Technique-Group Discussion

(নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক-গ্রুপ আলোচনার স্টেকহোল্ডার)

School of Health and Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland (UWS), UK

(স্কুল অফ হেলথ অ্যান্ড লাইফ সায়েন্সেস, ইউনিভার্সিটি অফ দ্য ওয়েস্ট অফ স্কটল্যান্ড

(ইউডব্লিউএস), যুক্তরাজ্য

Study Title: Workforce Development and Dementia Care in Bangladesh: Policy Learning from the Scottish Context (গবেষণার শিরোনাম: বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন এবং কর্মী উন্নয়ন: স্কটিশ প্রেক্ষিত থেকে পলিসি শিক্ষা)

I want to invite you to participate in the Nominal Group Technique-Group Discussion in this research project which forms part of my PhD, funded by the Bangabandhu Overseas Scholarship Program of the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. Before you decide whether you want to take part, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what your participation will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. If you decide you want to take part in the Nominal Group Technique-Group Discussion of this study and permit me to use your views in the PhD thesis and any subsequent publications or reports, the completion of the attached consent form is necessary for this discussion. Please see the attached consent form.

(আমি আপনাকে এই গবেষণা প্রকল্পে নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক-গ্রুপ আলোচনায় অংশ নেওয়ার জন্য আমন্ত্রণ জানাতে চাই যা আমার পিএইচডি অংশ এবং গবেষণাটি বাংলাদেশের ঢাকা বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়ের বঙ্গবন্ধু ওভারসিজ স্কলারশিপ প্রোগ্রামের অর্থায়নে পরিচালিত হচ্ছে। আপনি অংশ নিতে চান কিনা তা সিদ্ধান্ত নেওয়ার আগে, গবেষণাটি কেন করা হচ্ছে এবং আপনার অংশগ্রহণের সাথে কী কী জড়িত থাকবে তা আপনার জানা গুরুত্বপূর্ণ। অনুগ্রহ করে নিম্নলিখিত তথ্যগুলো মনোযোগ সহকারে পড়তে সময় নিন এবং আপনি চাইলে অন্যদের সাথে আলোচনা করুন। আপনি যদি সিদ্ধান্ত নেন যে আপনি এই গবেষণার নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক-গ্রুপ আলোচনায় অংশ নিতে চান এবং আমাকে পিএইচডি থিসিস এবং পরবর্তী কোনও প্রকাশনা বা প্রতিবেদনে আপনার মতামত ব্যবহার করার অনুমতি দেন, তবে এই আলোচনার জন্য সংযুক্ত সম্মতি ফর্মটি পূরণ করা প্রয়োজন। দয়া করে সংযুক্ত সম্মতি ফর্মটি দেখুন)

Name of Principal investigator and affiliation of researcher (প্রধান গবেষকের নাম এবং গবেষকের সম্পৃক্ততা):

I am Mohammad Mainuddin Mollah, Assistant Professor in the Institute of Social Welfare and Research at the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. I am also a PhD Student in the Alzheimer's Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice (ASCPP) in the School of Health and Life Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland, Lanarkshire Campus, Hamilton International Technology Park, Stephenson Place, South Lanarkshire, Scotland.G72 0LH.

(আমি মুহাম্মদ মাইনউদ্দিন মোল্লা, বাংলাদেশের ঢাকা বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়ের ইনস্টিটিউট অফ সোশ্যাল ওয়েলফেয়ার অ্যান্ড রিসার্চের সহকারী অধ্যাপক। পাশাপাশি আমি ইউনিভার্সিটি অফ দ্য ওয়েস্ট অফ স্কটল্যান্ডের, স্কুল অফ হেলথ অ্যান্ড লাইফ সায়েন্সেস এর অধীন অ্যালঝাইমার স্কটল্যান্ড সেন্টার ফর পলিসি অ্যান্ড প্র্যাকটিস (এএসসিপিপি)-এর একজন নিয়মিত পিএইচডি ছাত্র)

What is the purpose of the study? (গবেষণার উদ্দেশ্য কী ?)

The purpose of this study is to investigate and analyse Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches to determine the utility for application within Bangladesh. The study will seek to:

- To critically review the evidence base shaping dementia care and dementia workforce development policy and policy implementation within Scotland and Bangladesh;

- To determine Scottish dementia policy scope, indicators of success and lessons for possible policy transfer to Bangladesh;
- To scope with multi-sectorial stakeholders in Bangladesh their aspirations and priorities for the development of dementia care policy; and
- To make recommendations to inform future dementia policy development in Bangladesh.

এই গবেষণার প্রধান উদ্দেশ্য হল বাংলাদেশের প্রেক্ষিতে স্কটিশ ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন নীতি এবং কর্মী উন্নয়ন পদ্ধতির প্রয়োগের উপযোগিতা নির্ধারণের জন্য তথ্য অনুসন্ধান এবং বিশ্লেষণ করা। এছাড়াও গবেষণাটি নিম্নোক্ত বিশেষ উদ্দেশ্যে পরিচালিত হবে:

- স্কটল্যান্ড এবং বাংলাদেশের মধ্যে ডিমেনশিয়া কেয়ার এবং ডিমেনশিয়া কর্মী উন্নয়ন নীতি এবং নীতি বাস্তবায়নের প্রমাণের ভিত্তি সমালোচনামূলকভাবে পর্যালোচনা করা;
- স্কটিশ ডিমেনশিয়া পলিসির পরিধি, সাফল্যের সূচক এবং বাংলাদেশে সম্ভাব্য নীতি হস্তান্তরের পাঠ নির্ধারণ;
- ডিমেনশিয়া কেয়ার পলিসির উন্নয়নে বাংলাদেশের বহু-সেক্টরাল স্টেকহোল্ডারদের আকাঙ্ক্ষা এবং অগ্রাধিকারের সুযোগ প্রদান; এবং
- বাংলাদেশে ভবিষ্যত ডিমেনশিয়া পলিসি ডেভেলপমেন্ট সম্পর্কে অবহিত করার জন্য সুপারিশ করা।

Why have I been chosen? (কেন আমাকে বেছে নেওয়া হয়েছে?)

You have been chosen because you have either:

- considerable experience in dementia care, workforce development and policymaking or
- been involving in dementia care practices in the community and research in universities or
- are a family carer of a person living with dementia

I appreciate your participation in my Nominal Group Technique-Group Discussion.

(আপনাকে বেছে নেওয়া হয়েছে কারণ আপনি:

- ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন, কর্মী উন্নয়ন এবং নীতি নির্ধারণে যথেষ্ট অভিজ্ঞ ; অথবা

- সমাপ্তিতে ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন অনুশীলন এবং বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়ে গবেষণার সাথে জড়িত; অথবা
- ডিমেনশিয়া আক্রান্ত ব্যক্তির পারিবারিক যত্ন প্রদানকারী

আমি আমার নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক-গ্রুপ আলোচনায় আপনার অংশগ্রহণের প্রশংসা করি।)

Do I have to take part in the study? (আমাকে কি গবেষণায় অংশ নিতে হবে?)

No. It is up to you whether you choose to take part in the study or not. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and will be asked to sign a consent form. You can participate, not participate or withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason. If you withdraw from the study the information you provide will be removed from the study.

If you wish to withdraw your participation, please do so within three months of our Group Discussion. Anonymised data cannot be withdrawn after 3 months as it will have been included in the analysis and design of the next stage of the study.

নো। আপনি গবেষণায় অংশ নিতে চান কি না তা আপনার উপর নির্ভর করে। আপনি যদি অংশ নেওয়ার সিদ্ধান্ত নেন তবে আপনাকে এই তথ্য পত্রটি রাখার জন্য দেওয়া হবে এবং একটি সম্মতি ফর্মে স্বাক্ষর করতে বলা হবে। আপনি এই গবেষণায় অংশ নিতে বা কোনও কারণ না দিয়ে যে কোনও সময় গবেষণা থেকে সরে আসতে পারবেন। আপনি যদি গবেষণা থেকে সরে যান তবে আপনার সরবরাহ করা তথ্য গবেষণা থেকে অপসারণ করা হবে।

আপনি যদি আপনার অংশগ্রহণ প্রত্যাহার করতে চান তবে দয়া করে আমাদের গ্রুপ আলোচনার তিন মাসের মধ্যে এটি করুন। আপনার প্রদত্ত অজ্ঞাত তথ্য তিন মাস পরে প্রত্যাহার করা যাবে না কারণ উক্ত সময়ের পর এটি গবেষণার পরবর্তী পর্যায়ে তথ্য বিশ্লেষণ এবং নকশায় অন্তর্ভুক্ত করা হবে।)

What will taking part involve? (অংশ নেওয়ার সাথে কী জড়িত থাকবে?)

This research will use the "Nominal Group Technique-Group Discussion". If you agree to participate, you will be invited to take part in the Nominal Group Discussion (NGT). The main aim of NGT is to identify what you see as the priorities for dementia care and workforce development policy in Bangladesh.

Individually and silently, you will be invited to write down ideas that are important to you. You will then be asked to share one idea at a time with the group. This approach is described as a 'round-robin'. Meaning one person shares one idea at a time. After initial discussion, clarification and ideas sharing, you will be asked to select and then rank your top five ideas.

You will be provided with a ranking sheet, where you will be asked to select your top five ideas from the entire set of generated ideas and then rank those five ideas. The facilitator will specify that a number will be allocated to each selected item, with larger numbers reflecting greater importance. For example, for five selected ideas, five points will be allocated to their top priority and one point to their lowest priority. Although there is no anonymity for participants during nominal group discussions, individual scoring on a ranking sheet is confidential. The scores for each idea will be summed and ideas listed in order by total scores. The five ideas with the highest scores will be defined as the most important for the group.

Nominal group discussion will be recorded and written and anonymised. The Nominal group discussion will last up to 02 hours with a refreshment break. I very much hope you will be able to participate in the Nominal group discussion at -----on the -----th of -----2021. Participation is voluntary. You are under no obligation to take part in the group discussion and you can stop or withdraw at any time.

এই গবেষণায় "নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক-গ্রুপ আলোচনা" ব্যবহার করা হবে। আপনি যদি অংশগ্রহণ করতে সম্মত হন, তাহলে আপনাকে নমিনাল গ্রুপ আলোচনায় (এনজিটি) অংশ নিতে আমন্ত্রণ জানানো হবে। এনজিটির মূল লক্ষ্য হল বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন এবং কর্মী উন্নয়ন নীতির অগ্রাধিকার হিসাবে আপনি যেসব বিষয় গুরুত্বপূর্ণ মনে করেন তা সনাক্ত করা।

প্রথমে আপনাকে আপনার জন্য গুরুত্বপূর্ণ ধারণাগুলি একটি কাগজে নীরবে লিখতে বলা হবে। তারপরে আপনাকে গ্রুপের সাথে সময়মতো একটি করে ধারণা শেয়ার করতে বলা হবে। এই পদ্ধতিকে 'রাউন্ড-রবিন' হিসাবে বর্ণনা করা হয়। অর্থাৎ একজন অংশগ্রহণকারী একবারে একটি করে ধারণা শেয়ার করার সুযোগ পাবেন। সকল অংশগ্রহণকারীর ধারণা শেয়ার করার পর, প্রাপ্ত ধারণাগুলোর প্রাথমিক আলোচনা, স্পষ্টীকরণ এবং শ্রেণীবদ্ধকরণ করা হবে। এরপর আপনাকে একটি পর্যায়ক্রম শীট সরবরাহ করা হবে, যেখানে আপনাকে নমিনাল গ্রুপ আলোচনায় বাছাইকৃত ধারণাগুলির পুরো তালিকা থেকে আপনার মতে শীর্ষ পাঁচটি ধারণা বাছাই করতে বলা হবে। তারপরে সেই পাঁচটি ধারণার গুরুত্ব অনুসারে পর্যায়ক্রম ঠিক করতে বলা হবে। উদাহরণস্বরূপ, আপনার মতে সর্বাধিক গুরুত্বপূর্ণ ধারণার জন্য পাঁচ নম্বর এবং সর্বনিম্ন অগ্রাধিকারের জন্য এক নম্বর প্রদান করবেন। যদিও নমিনাল গ্রুপ আলোচনার সময় অংশগ্রহণকারীদের নাম গোপন করার সুযোগ নেই, তবে পর্যায়ক্রম শিটে আপনার প্রদত্ত তথ্যের গোপনীয়তা রক্ষা করা হবে। প্রতিটি ধারণার জন্য সকল অংশগ্রহণকারীর প্রদত্ত নম্বরগুলো যোগ করা হবে এবং প্রাপ্ত নম্বরের ভিত্তিতে ধারণাগুলির একটি চূড়ান্ত তালিকা করা হবে। সর্বোচ্চ নম্বর প্রাপ্ত পাঁচটি ধারণা গ্রুপের জন্য সবচেয়ে গুরুত্বপূর্ণ হিসাবে সংজ্ঞায়িত করা হবে।

নমিনাল গ্রুপ আলোচনা রেকর্ড করা হবে এবং লিপিবদ্ধ করা হবে এবং আপনার প্রদত্ত তথ্য বেনামী রাখা হবে। নমিনাল গ্রুপ আলোচনার সময়কাল ০২ ঘন্টা (রিফ্রেশমেন্ট বিরতিসহ)। আমি আশা করি আপনি ২০২১ এর ----- তারিখে ----- নমিনাল গ্রুপ আলোচনায় অংশ নিতে পারবেন। আপনার অংশগ্রহণ স্বেচ্ছামূলক। গ্রুপ আলোচনায় অংশ নেওয়ার জন্য আপনার কোনও বাধ্যবাধকতা নেই এবং আপনি যে কোনও সময় আলোচনায় থেকে নিজেকে প্রত্যাহার করতে পারবেন।)

Are there any risk involved? (এর সাথে কি কোন ঝুঁকি জড়িত আছে?)

This research will not place you at any risk. Your responses shared in the Nominal Group discussion will be used only to compile research findings. You will not be asked to reveal anything of a personal or sensitive nature. I am seeking information from stakeholders related to dementia care and workforce development in Bangladesh to identify the priorities and perceived barriers and facilitators to transferring dementia care workforce development policies and approaches from Scotland to Bangladesh.

(এই গবেষণা আপনাকে কোনও ঝুঁকিতে ফেলবে না। নমিনাল গ্রুপ আলোচনায় শেয়ার করা আপনার মতামতগুলো কেবল গবেষণার ফলাফল সংকলন এবং বিশ্লেষণ করতে ব্যবহৃত হবে। আপনাকে ব্যক্তিগত বা সংবেদনশীল প্রকৃতির কোন তথ্য প্রকাশ করতে বলা হবে না। আমি বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন এবং কর্মী উন্নয়ন সম্পর্কিত স্টেকহোল্ডারদের কাছ থেকে তথ্য সংগ্রহ করতে চাইছি যাতে স্কটল্যান্ড থেকে বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন ও কর্মী উন্নয়ন নীতি এবং পদ্ধতি স্থানান্তরের অগ্রাধিকার এবং অনুভূত বাধা এবং সুবিধাগুলো চিহ্নিত করা যায়।)

What are the potential benefits of taking part? (অংশ নেওয়ার সম্ভাব্য সুবিধাগুলি কী কী?)

By participating in this study, you will support the development of evidence underpinned policy proposition for workforce development and dementia care in Bangladesh. Therefore contributing to improving the quality of life for people living with dementia and their family carers in Bangladesh.

(এই গবেষণায় অংশ নিয়ে আপনি বাংলাদেশে কর্মী উন্নয়ন এবং ডিমেনশিয়া যত্নের জন্য প্রমাণের উপর ভিত্তি করে নীতি প্রস্তাব প্রণয়নে সহায়তা করবেন। এর ফলে বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়া আক্রান্তদের এবং তাদের পারিবারিক যত্ন প্রদানকারীর জীবনযাত্রার মান উন্নত করতে অবদান রাখবেন।)

Will the information shared be kept confidential? (শেয়ার করা তথ্য কি গোপন রাখা হবে?)

Yes, pseudonyms will be used in place of your name, and this cannot be linked to you in any publication or report from this study. All electronic data will be saved in a password-protected computer within premises of the University of the West of Scotland. Data will be accessible only by the researcher and supervisory team for at least 36 months after completion of the study to allow for analysis, thesis completion and publication disseminations according to UKRIO Code of Practice for Research and UWS privacy and confidentiality policy. After 36 months, I will delete all electronic data. All hardcopy information will be saved in a locked cabinet in the researcher's office at the university for 36 months after completion of the study. At the end of this time, I will shred and trash all hard copies.

The School has approved this study of Health and Life Sciences, School Ethics Committee (SEC) at the University of the West of Scotland (Reference Number: 11822). Your views will be held confidentially. Data collected will only be used for this study and will not be used to identify any individuals. All results will be presented in an aggregated and anonymised form. The results of this study will be presented at scientific meetings or published in scientific journals.

হ্যাঁ, আপনার নামের জায়গায় ছদ্মনাম ব্যবহার করা হবে, এবং এই গবেষণা থেকে কোনও প্রকাশনা বা প্রতিবেদনে আপনার নাম উল্লেখ করা হবে না। সমস্ত ইলেকট্রনিক তথ্য ইউনিভার্সিটি অফ দ্য ওয়েস্ট অফ স্কটল্যান্ড-এর পাসওয়ার্ড-সুরক্ষিত একটি কম্পিউটারে সংরক্ষণ করা হবে। ইউডব্লিউএস-এর গোপনীয়তার নীতি এবং ইউকেআরআইও-এর গবেষণার কোড অফ প্র্যাকটিস অনুসারে প্রাপ্ত তথ্যের বিশ্লেষণ, থিসিস সমাপ্তি এবং প্রকাশনা প্রচারের অনুমতির জন্য গবেষণা শেষ হওয়ার পরে কমপক্ষে ৩৬ মাসের জন্য গবেষক এবং তত্ত্বাবধায়ক দল দ্বারা তথ্য ব্যবহারযোগ্য হবে। গবেষণা শেষ হওয়ার ৩৬ মাস পরে সমস্ত ইলেকট্রনিক তথ্য মুছে ফেলা হবে। এছাড়াও গবেষণা শেষ হওয়ার পরে ৩৬ মাসের জন্য বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়ে গবেষকের অফিসে একটি তালাবন্ধ কেবিনেটে সমস্ত হার্ডকপি তথ্য সংরক্ষণ করা হবে। এই সময়ের শেষে, সমস্ত হার্ড কপি নষ্ট করা হবে।

ইউনিভার্সিটি অফ দ্য ওয়েস্ট অফ স্কটল্যান্ড, স্কুল অফ হেলথ অ্যান্ড লাইফ সায়েন্সেস, স্কুল নৈতিকতা কমিটি (এসইসি) এই গবেষণা অনুমোদন করেছে (যার রেফারেন্স নম্বর: 11822)। আপনার মতামতের গোপনীয়তা সংরক্ষণ করা হবে। সংগৃহীত তথ্য কেবলমাত্র এই গবেষণার জন্য ব্যবহার করা হবে এবং কোনও অংশগ্রহণকারীকে সনাক্ত করতে ব্যবহার করা হবে না। সমস্ত ফলাফল একটি সম্মিলিত এবং অজ্ঞাত আকারে উপস্থাপন করা হবে। এই গবেষণার ফলাফল বৈজ্ঞানিক সভায় উপস্থাপন করা হবে বা বৈজ্ঞানিক জার্নালে প্রকাশিত হবে।)

Any questions? (কোনো প্রশ্ন?)

If you wish to discuss the study further or have any questions, then please contact me the researcher, Mohammad Mainuddin Mollah, email: Mohammad.Mollah@uws.ac.uk or the Director of Studies, Professor Dr Debbie Tolson, email: Debbie.Tolson@uws.ac.uk.

If you have any complaints, then contact the Director of Studies, Professor Dr Debbie Tolson, email: Debbie.Tolson@uws.ac.uk.

(আপনি যদি গবেষণাটির বিষয়ে আরও আলোচনা করতে চান বা কোনও প্রশ্ন করতে চান, তবে দয়া করে গবেষক মুহাম্মদ মাইনউদ্দিন মোল্লা, ইমেল: [REDACTED] গবেষণা পরিচালক, অধ্যাপক ডঃ ডেবি টলসন, ইমেল: [REDACTED] এর সাথে যোগাযোগ করতে পারবেন।

যদি আপনার কোন অভিযোগ থাকে, তাহলে গবেষণা পরিচালক, প্রফেসর ডঃ ডেবি টলসনের সাথে যোগাযোগ করতে পারবেন, ইমেল: [REDACTED]।)

Thank you for reading this information sheet and for considering taking part in the Nominal Group Technique-Group Discussion of this study.

(এই তথ্য পত্রটি পড়ার জন্য এবং এই গবেষণার নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক-গ্রুপ আলোচনায় অংশ নেওয়ার কথা বিবেচনা করার জন্য আপনাকে ধন্যবাদ।)

Yours sincerely,

Mohammad Mainuddin Mollah

Ph.D. in the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice

School of Health and Life Sciences

University of the West of Scotland

Lanarkshire Campus

Stephenson Place, Hamilton International Technology Park, South Lanarkshire

G 72 0LH. Email: [REDACTED]

Appendix 4.15: Consent Form for Nominal Group Technique (NGT) - Group Discussion Participants

(নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক (এনজিটি)- গ্রুপ আলোচনায় অংশগ্রহণকারীদের জন্য জন্য সম্মতি ফর্ম)

Verson-03 and Date-02.06.2021

PARTICIPANT'S CONSENT FORM

(অংশগ্রহণকারীর সম্মতি ফর্ম)

Stakeholders of Nominal Group Technique-Group Discussion

(নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক -গ্রুপ আলোচনার স্টেকহোল্ডার)

School of Health and Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland (UWS), UK

(স্কুল অফ হেলথ অ্যান্ড লাইফ সায়েন্সেস, ইউনিভার্সিটি অফ দ্য ওয়েস্ট অফ স্কটল্যান্ড

(ইউডব্লিউএস), যুক্তরাজ্য

Study Title: Workforce Development and Dementia Care in Bangladesh: Policy Learning from the Scottish Context

(গবেষণার শিরোনাম: বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন এবং কর্মী উন্নয়ন: স্কটিশ প্রেক্ষিত থেকে পলিসি শিক্ষা)

Please initial each box to indicate that you have read and understood the information provided and that you are willing to take part in this study (অনুগ্রহ করে প্রতিটি বক্স নির্দেশ করুন যাতে বোঝা যায় আপনি প্রদত্ত তথ্য পড়েছেন এবং বুঝতে পেরেছেন এবং আপনি এই গবেষণায় অংশ নিতে ইচ্ছুক)

01. I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the study (আমি নিশ্চিত করছি যে, আমি এই গবেষণার জন্য তথ্য পত্রটি পড়েছি এবং বুঝতে পেরেছি)

02. I know what the study is about and what taking part will involve (আমি জানি এই গবেষণাটি কী বিষয়ে এবং অংশ নেওয়ার সাথে কী কী জড়িত হবে) -----

03. I have been given the opportunity to ask questions (face to face or virtual) (গবেষণা নিয়ে আমাকে প্রশ্ন জিজ্ঞাসা করার সুযোগ রয়েছে (মুখোমুখি বা ভার্চুয়াল)-----

04. I have had the opportunity to ask questions and discuss the study (গবেষণা নিয়ে আমার প্রশ্ন জিজ্ঞাসা করার এবং আলোচনা করার সুযোগ রয়েছে) -----

5. I understand that my participation in the NGT is voluntary and I know that I am free to withdraw from this study at any time without having to give any reason for withdrawing (আমি বুঝতে পারছি যে, এই এনজিটি-তে আমার অংশগ্রহণ স্বেচ্ছামূলক এবং আমি জানি যে প্রত্যাহারের কোনও কারণ না দিয়ে আমি যে কোনও সময় এই গবেষণা থেকে সরে আসতে পারব) -----

6. I agree that any data collected before my withdrawal from the research will be removed from the study (আমি সম্মত আছি যে, গবেষণা থেকে নিজেকে প্রত্যাহার করলে প্রত্যাহারের আগে সংগৃহীত যে কোনও তথ্য গবেষণা থেকে অপসারণ করা হবে) -----

7. I understand that if I want to withdraw my participation and therefore the data, I must do so within three months of our group discussion. Anonymised data cannot be withdrawn after 3 months as it will have been included in the analysis and design of the next stage of the study (আমি বুঝতে পারছি যে, আমি যদি আমার অংশগ্রহণ এবং আমার প্রদত্ত তথ্য প্রত্যাহার করতে চাই, তবে আমাদের গ্রুপ আলোচনার তিন মাসের মধ্যে আমাকে তা করতে হবে। অজ্ঞাত তথ্য তিন মাস পরে প্রত্যাহার করা যাবে না কারণ উক্ত

সময়ের পর এটি গবেষণার পরবর্তী পর্যায়ের তথ্য বিশ্লেষণ এবং নকশায় অন্তর্ভুক্ত করা হবে)-

8. I agree to the discussion being recorded and written (আমি এই আলোচনা রেকর্ড করা এবং লিপিবদ্ধ করার বিষয়ে সম্মত আছি) -----

9. I consent to the storage of my contact details and anonymised data in UWS secure systems for the duration of 36 months after completion of the study (আমি গবেষণা শেষ হওয়ার পরে ৩৬ মাসের জন্য ইউডব্লিউএস এর নিরাপদ সিস্টেমে আমার যোগাযোগের বিশদ এবং অজ্ঞাত তথ্য সংরক্ষণ করতে সম্মতি আছি)-----

10. I agree that the researcher can present my opinions in the PhD thesis and any related publications or reports as long as they are kept anonymous (আমি সম্মত আছি যে, সংশ্লিষ্ট গবেষক পিএইচডি থিসিস এবং এই সম্পর্কিত যে কোনও প্রকাশনা বা প্রতিবেদনে আমার মতামত উপস্থাপন করতে পারবেন যতক্ষণ পর্যন্ত উক্ত তথ্য বেনামী রাখা হয়)

11. I agree for the researcher to discuss this information at scientific meetings and academic conferences (আমি সম্মত আছি যে, সংশ্লিষ্ট গবেষক যে কোনও বৈজ্ঞানিক সভা এবং একাডেমিক সম্মেলনে এই তথ্য নিয়ে আলোচনা করতে পারবেন)-----

Name of participant (অংশগ্রহণকারীর নাম):.....

Signature (স্বাক্ষর):.....

Date (তারিখ):.....

Name of researcher taking consent: Mohammad Mainuddin Mollah

(সম্মতি গ্রহণকারী গবেষকের নাম: মুহাম্মদ মাইনউদ্দিন মোল্লা)

Email:

Appendix 4.16: Sample Protocol for Nominal Group Technique (NGT)-Group Discussion

(নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক (এনজিটি)-গ্রুপ আলোচনার জন্য নমুনা প্রোটোকল)

Verson-03 and Date-02.06.2021

Facilitator Protocol for Nominal Group Technique-Group Discussion
(নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক-গ্রুপ আলোচনা পরিচালনার জন্য ব্যবহারকারীর প্রোটোকল)

School of Health and Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland (UWS), UK
(স্কুল অফ হেলথ অ্যান্ড লাইফ সায়েন্সেস, ইউনিভার্সিটি অফ দ্য ওয়েস্ট অফ স্কটল্যান্ড
(ইউডব্লিউএস), যুক্তরাজ্য)

Study Title: Workforce Development and Dementia Care in Bangladesh: Policy Learning from the Scottish Context
(গবেষণার শিরোনাম: বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন এবং কর্মী উন্নয়ন: স্কটিশ প্রেক্ষিত থেকে পলিসি শিক্ষা)

Preparation (প্রস্তুতি)

Welcome by Researcher/ Facilitator and thank you (Researcher/ Facilitator will introduce himself and then will request the participant to introduce her/himself) (গবেষক / ফেসিলিটেটর কর্তৃক স্বাগতম এবং ধন্যবাদ জ্ঞাপন (গবেষক / ফেসিলিটেটর নিজেদের পরিচয় দেবেন এবং অংশগ্রহণকারীদের নিজের পরিচয় দেওয়ার জন্য অনুরোধ জানাবেন)

Introductions (পরিচিতি)

Explain how the recording will be done (রেকর্ডিং কিভাবে করা হবে তা ব্যাখ্যা করবেন)

Repeat purpose of study and Nominal Group Discussion (গবেষণার এবং নমিনাল গ্রুপ আলোচনার উদ্দেশ্য পুনরাবৃত্তি করবেন)

Re-establish consent (গবেষণায় অংশগ্রহণের সম্মতি পুনরায় প্রতিষ্ঠা করবেন)

Reinforce support available (সহায়ক সুযোগ-সুবিধার নিশ্চিত করবেন)

Ground rules – Each participant will speak in turn, without interrupting other participants; do not argue against others' ideas; confidentiality (গ্রাউন্ড রুলস - প্রত্যেক অংশগ্রহণকারী অন্য অংশগ্রহণকারীদের বাধা না দিয়ে পর্যায়ক্রমে কথা বলবেন; অন্যের মতামতের বিরুদ্ধে তর্ক করবেন না; এবং গোপনীয়তা বজায় রাখবেন)

Re-introduce topic and begin the discussion (আলোচনার বিষয় পুনরায় উল্লেখ করবেন এবং আলোচনা শুরু করবেন)

First Stage: Silent Generation of Individual Ideas (প্রথম পর্যায়: ব্যক্তিগত ধারণার নীরব অনুশীলন)

(Use prompt cards, flip chart notes, white board, sticky coloured stars and ranking sheets as required) (প্রম্পট কার্ড, ফ্লিপ চার্ট নোট, সাদা বোর্ড, আঠালো রঙ্গীন তারকা এবং প্রয়োজন অনুযায়ী পর্যায়ক্রম শীট ব্যবহার করবেন)

The Researcher will briefly explain the purpose of the study and the NGT aim (in a manner appropriate to each Stakeholder Group). Following a brief context setting introduction by the Researcher, participants will be asked to individually consider one questions shown on a flip chart (see below for questions)/ and read out loud. Participants will be encouraged to seek clarification if unclear of the terms in the question, but otherwise to refrain from discussing their thoughts out loud.

(গবেষক সংক্ষেপে গবেষণার উদ্দেশ্য এবং এনজিটির লক্ষ্য ব্যাখ্যা করবেন (প্রতিটি স্টেকহোল্ডার গ্রুপের জন্য উপযুক্ত পদ্ধতিতে)। গবেষক কর্তৃক গবেষণার একটি সংক্ষিপ্ত বক্তব্য উপস্থাপন করার পর, অংশগ্রহণকারীদের পৃথকভাবে একটি ফ্লিপ চার্টে / Power Point Presentation (PPT)-এ প্রদর্শিত একটি প্রশ্ন বিবেচনা করতে বলা হবে (প্রশ্নের জন্য PPT দেখবেন)/ এবং পাশাপাশি গবেষক প্রশ্নটি জোরে পড়ে শোনাবেন। অংশগ্রহণকারীদের জন্য প্রশ্নটির শর্তাবলী অস্পষ্ট হলে ব্যাখ্যা চাইতে উৎসাহিত করা হবে, তবে অন্যথায় তাদের চিন্তাভাবনা উচ্চস্বরে আলোচনা করা থেকে বিরত থাকতে অনুরোধ করা হবে।)

Brainstorm (ব্রেইন স্টর্ম):

NGT-01: Family members and informal carers of people living with dementia

(এনজিটি-০১: ডিমেনশিয়া আক্রান্ত ব্যক্তিদের পরিবারের সদস্য এবং অনানুষ্ঠানিক যত্নপ্রদানকারী)

What do family members and informal carers need to improve the dementia care and living standards for people living with dementia in Bangladesh?

(বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়ায় আক্রান্ত ব্যক্তিদের যত্ন এবং তাদের জীবনযাত্রার মান উন্নত করতে পরিবারের সদস্য এবং অনানুষ্ঠানিক যত্নপ্রদানকারী হিসেবে আপনি কী কী বিষয় প্রয়োজন বলে মনে করেন?)

NGT-02: Health and social care practitioners

(এনজিটি-০২: স্বাস্থ্য ও সামাজিক যত্ন অনুশীলনকারী)

What are the most important aspects need to consider to improve dementia care in health and social care settings in Bangladesh?

(বাংলাদেশে স্বাস্থ্য ও সামাজিক পরিচর্যা সেক্টরে ডিমেনশিয়ায় আক্রান্ত ব্যক্তিদের যত্ন উন্নত করার জন্য সবচেয়ে গুরুত্বপূর্ণ কী কী বিষয় বিবেচনা করা দরকার?)

NGT-03: Academics (educators and researchers)

(এনজিটি-০৩: শিক্ষাবিদ (শিক্ষাবিদ ও গবেষক))

What do academics (educators and researchers) consider important to improve the dementia care and workforce development in Bangladesh?

(শিক্ষাবিদ ও গবেষক হিসেবে আপনি বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়ায় আক্রান্ত ব্যক্তিদের যত্ন এবং তাদের যত্ন প্রদানের জন্য কর্মী উন্নয়নের ক্ষেত্রে কী কী বিষয় গুরুত্বপূর্ণ বলে মনে করেন?)

NGT-04: Care providers

(এনজিটি-০৪: যত্ন প্রদানকারী)

What do care providers need to improve the dementia care for the people living with dementia and their family carers in Bangladesh?

(বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়ায় আক্রান্ত ব্যক্তিদের এবং তাদের পারিবারিক যত্নপ্রদানকারীদের ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন উন্নত করার জন্য যত্ন প্রদানকারী হিসেবে আপনি কী কী বিষয় গুরুত্বপূর্ণ বলে মনে করেন?)

NGT-05: Policy planners

(এনজিটি-০৫: নীতি পরিকল্পনাকারী)

What are the most important aspects need to consider in dementia policy to improve the dementia care and workforce development in Bangladesh?

(বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়ায় আক্রান্ত ব্যক্তিদের যত্ন এবং তাদের জন্য কর্মী উন্নয়নের ক্ষেত্রে ডিমেনশিয়া নীতিতে সবচেয়ে গুরুত্বপূর্ণ কী কী বিষয় বিবেচনা করা দরকার?)

Silent Generation of Ideas (ধারণার নীরব অনুশীলন)

- Individually and silently, participants will write their answers or ideas that are important to them on individual note pads provided by the project team (প্রথমে অংশগ্রহণকারীরা তাদের জন্য গুরুত্বপূর্ণ ধারণাগুলি একটি কাগজে নীরবে লিখবেন।)
- They will be asked to write down the things that they consider are important in response to the question. An individual's list can be as long and as short as they like. A volunteer scribe will work with anyone who needs support preparing a written list (প্রতিটি দলের সাথে সংশ্লিষ্ট প্রশ্নের উত্তরে অংশগ্রহণকারীরা যে বিষয়গুলি গুরুত্বপূর্ণ বলে মনে করবেন তা একটি কাগজে নীরবে লিখতে বলা হবে। একজন ব্যক্তির তালিকা যতটা পছন্দ হয়

ততটাই দীর্ঘ এবং সংক্ষিপ্ত হতে পারে। একজন স্বেচ্ছাসেবক লিপিকার এমন কারও সাথে কাজ করবেন যার লিখিত তালিকা প্রস্তুত করতে সহায়তা প্রয়োজন)

Second Stage: Round-robin Recording of those Ideas (দ্বিতীয় পর্যায়: রাউন্ড-রবিন-ধারণার লিপিবদ্ধকরণ)

- In the second stage, participants will then be asked to share one idea with the group, taking it in turns to share a single idea from their list. In the initial round participants share their first idea, after everyone in the group has shared an idea, the person you started the round shares their second idea and so on, until all ideas have been shared. Participants will be able to think of new ideas during this process but must wait for their turn before they can share with the group. There will be no discussion at this stage and ideas will be recorded verbatim on a flipchart or white board (দ্বিতীয় পর্যায়, অংশগ্রহণকারীদের গ্রুপের সাথে একটি করে ধারণা শেয়ার করতে বলা হবে, অর্থাৎ এই পর্যায় পালক্রমে তাদের নিজস্ব তালিকা থেকে একটি করে ধারণা শেয়ার করতে বলা হবে। প্রাথমিক রাউন্ডে অংশগ্রহণকারীরা তাদের প্রথম ধারণা শেয়ার করবে। গ্রুপের প্রত্যেকে একটি করে ধারণা শেয়ার করার পরে, যিনি প্রথমে রাউন্ড শুরু করেছিলেন তিনি তার দ্বিতীয় ধারণাটি শেয়ার করবেন। যতক্ষণ পর্যন্ত না অংশগ্রহণকারীদের সমস্ত ধারণা শেয়ার করা শেষ হয়, ততক্ষণ পর্যন্ত রাউন্ড-রবিন ধাপটি চলমান থাকবে। অংশগ্রহণকারীরা এই প্রক্রিয়ার সময় নতুন কোনো ধারণা ভাবতে পারবেন, তবে গ্রুপের সাথে সেই নতুন ধারণা শেয়ার করার আগে তাদের সময়ের /পর্যায়ের জন্য অপেক্ষা করতে হবে। এই পর্যায় কোন ধরনের আলোচনা করা হবে না এবং ধারণাগুলি একটি ফ্লিপচার্ট বা সাদা বোর্ডে বা ওয়ার্ড ফাইলে লিপিবদ্ধ করা হবে)
- This stage will be continued until no new ideas are forthcoming (যতক্ষণ পর্যন্ত নতুন ধারণা আসতে থাকবে, ততক্ষণ পর্যন্ত এই পর্যায়টি অব্যাহত থাকবে)

Third Stage: Clarification/Discussion (তৃতীয় পর্যায়: ব্যাখ্যা/আলোচনা)

- The third stage is to group the ideas that are similar together to create a shorter list (তৃতীয় পর্যায় ইতোপূর্বে প্রাপ্ত ধারণাগুলো থেকে অনুরূপ ধারণাগুলো নিয়ে একটি সংক্ষিপ্ত তালিকা তৈরি করা হবে)

- All ideas will be discussed to obtain clarification about meaning and the wording of statements to ensure participant understanding (অংশগ্রহণকারীদের বোঝার সুবিধার্থে প্রতিটি ধারণার অর্থ এবং বিবৃত শব্দসম্পর্কে আলোচনা করা হবে।)
- Similar ideas will be grouped with agreement from all participants (অংশগ্রহণকারীদের মতামত এবং ঐক্যমতের ভিত্তিতে অনুরূপ ধারণাগুলি শ্রেণীবদ্ধকরণ করা হবে।)
- Participants may also exclude, include, or alter ideas (অংশগ্রহণকারীরা প্রাপ্ত ধারণাগুলি প্রয়োজনে বাদ, অন্তর্ভুক্ত বা পরিবর্তন করতে পারবেন।)
- Participants do not have to agree with all ideas listed (অংশগ্রহণকারীদের তালিকাভুক্ত সমস্ত ধারণার সাথে একমত হতে হবে না।)
- Ideally a short list of the key 8-12 points will be generated by the group processes (আদর্শগতভাবে ৮-১২ পয়েন্টের একটি সংক্ষিপ্ত তালিকা দলীয় মতামতের ভিত্তিতে প্রস্তুত করা হবে।)

Fourth Stage: Priority Voting or Ranking (চতুর্থ পর্যায়: অগ্রাধিকার নির্বাচন বা পর্যায়ক্রম নির্ধারণ)

After initial discussion, clarification and ideas sharing, each participant will select and then vote or rank his/ her top five ideas. There are two common approaches used to facilitate NGT priority voting or ranking exercises (প্রাথমিক আলোচনা, স্পষ্টীকরণ এবং ধারণা শেয়ার করে নেওয়ার পরে, প্রত্যেক অংশগ্রহণকারী তার অগ্রাধিকার নির্বাচন করে, শীর্ষ পাঁচটি ধারণার পর্যায়ক্রম নির্ধারণ করবেন। এনজিটি-র অগ্রাধিকার নির্বাচন বা পর্যায়ক্রম নির্ধারণ অনুশীলনের সুবিধার্থে দুটি সাধারণ পদ্ধতি ব্যবহার করা হয়।)

Priority Voting Approach-One (অগ্রাধিকার নির্বাচন পদ্ধতি-এক)

- Participants will be provided with a sticky coloured star, which they will place against the most important issues for them on the list (অংশগ্রহণকারীদের এক ধরনের আঠালো রঙিন তারকা সরবরাহ করা হবে, যা তারা সংক্ষিপ্ত তালিকা থেকে তাদের জন্য সবচেয়ে গুরুত্বপূর্ণ বিষয়গুলির পাশে রাখবেন)

- The number of stars provided will be less than the full numbers of items of the list so forcing participants to make choices (প্রদত্ত তারার সংখ্যা সংক্ষিপ্ত তালিকায় উল্লেখিত ধারণাগুলো থেকে কম হবে, যাতে অংশগ্রহণকারীরা তাদের অগ্রাধিকার নির্বাচন করতে পারেন)
- Participants will be provided with five sticky coloured stars, where they will be asked to place sticky coloured stars against the most five important ideas for them on the entire set of generated ideas (অংশগ্রহণকারীদের পাঁচটি আঠালো রঙিন তারকা সরবরাহ করা হবে, যেখানে তাদের প্রণীত ধারণার পুরো সেট থেকে তাদের জন্য সবচেয়ে গুরুত্বপূর্ণ পাঁচটি ধারণার পাশে আঠালো রঙিন তারকা রাখতে বলা হবে)
- The item with the highest number of stickers will be ranked 1 as top priority, and the least stars will be the lowest or least important item (সর্বাধিক সংখ্যক রঙিন তারকা যুক্ত ধারণাটি শীর্ষ অগ্রাধিকার হিসাবে প্রথম স্থান এবং সর্বনিম্ন রঙিন তারকা যুক্ত ধারণাটি সর্বনিম্ন গুরুত্বপূর্ণ ধারণা হিসেবে বিবেচিত হবে)
- The five items with the highest number of stickers will be defined as the most important for the group (সর্বাধিক সংখ্যক তারকা যুক্ত পাঁচটি ধারণাকে গ্রুপের জন্য সবচেয়ে গুরুত্বপূর্ণ ধারণা হিসাবে সংজ্ঞায়িত করা হবে।)

Ranking Approach-Two (পর্যায়ক্রম নির্ধারণ পদ্ধতি-দুই)

- Participants will be provided with a ranking sheet, where they will be asked to select their top five ideas from the entire set of generated ideas and then rank those five ideas (অংশগ্রহণকারীদের একটি পর্যায়ক্রম শীট সরবরাহ করা হবে, যেখানে তাদের প্রণীত ধারণাগুলির পুরো সেট থেকে তাদের শীর্ষ পাঁচটি ধারণা নির্বাচন করতে বলা হবে এবং তারপরে সেই পাঁচটি ধারণার পর্যায়ক্রম নির্ধারণ করতে বলা হবে।)
- The facilitator will specify that a number will be allocated to each selected item, with larger numbers reflecting greater importance. For example, for five selected ideas, five points will be allocated to their top priority and one point to their lowest priority (নমিনাল গ্রুপ আলোচনায় বাছাইকৃত ধারণাগুলির পুরো তালিকা থেকে অংশগ্রহণকারীদের মতে শীর্ষ পাঁচটি ধারণা বাছাই করতে বলা হবে। তারপরে সেই পাঁচটি ধারণার গুরুত্ব অনুসারে

পর্যায়ক্রম ঠিক করতে বলা হবে। উদাহরণস্বরূপ, অংশগ্রহণকারীরা সর্বাধিক গুরুত্বপূর্ণ ধারণার জন্য পাঁচ নম্বর এবং সর্বনিম্ন অগ্রাধিকারের জন্য এক নম্বর প্রদান করবেন।)

- Individual scoring on a ranking sheet is confidential (পর্যায়ক্রম শিটে ব্যক্তিগত স্কোরিং গোপনীয়।)
- The scores for each idea will be summed and ideas listed in order by total scores (প্রতিটি ধারণার জন্য সকল অংশগ্রহণকারীর প্রদত্ত নম্বরগুলো যোগ করা হবে এবং প্রাপ্ত নম্বরের ভিত্তিতে ধারণাগুলির একটি চূড়ান্ত তালিকা করা হবে)
- The five ideas with the highest scores will be defined as the most important for the group (সর্বোচ্চ নম্বর প্রাপ্ত পাঁচটি ধারণা গ্রুপের জন্য সবচেয়ে গুরুত্বপূর্ণ হিসাবে সংজ্ঞায়িত করা হবে।)

Conclusion of the group discussion (গ্রুপ আলোচনার উপসংহার)

Researcher/ Facilitator thanks the participant for their contribution (গবেষক/ ফেসিলিটেটর অংশগ্রহণকারীদের গবষণায় তাদের অবদানের জন্য ধন্যবাদ জ্ঞাপন করবেন।)

The Researcher/ Facilitator asks the participant whether they would like to receive a copy of the list of priorities of group discussion for verification (গবেষক/ ফেসিলিটেটর অংশগ্রহণকারীকে জিজ্ঞাসা করবেন যে তারা যাচাইকরণের জন্য গ্রুপ আলোচনার অগ্রাধিকারের তালিকার একটি অনুলিপি পেতে চান কিনা।)

Thank you for sharing your valuable insights and expertise (আপনার মূল্যবান অন্তর্দৃষ্টি এবং দক্ষতা শেয়ার করার জন্য আপনাকে অসংখ্য ধন্যবাদ)

Appendix 4.17: A Brief PowerPoint Presentation to Conduct Virtual NGT

Slide 1

Alzheimer Scotland
UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

Title: Workforce Development and Dementia Care in Bangladesh: Policy Learning from the Scottish Context (গবেষণার শিরোনাম: বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন এবং কর্মী উন্নয়ন: স্কটিশ প্রেক্ষিত থেকে শিখার শিক্ষা)

PHD Student: Mohammad Mainuddin Mollah | Mohammad.Mollah@uws.ac.uk

Supervisors: Professor Dr Debbie Tolson (Lead Supervisor)
Professor Dr John Connolly
Dr Anna Jack-Waugh
Professor Dr Golam Rabbani (Local Supervisor)

Slide 2

Background and Rationale of the Study
(গবেষণার 'Background and Rationale' চর্চা)

- ▶ In Bangladesh, societal awareness about dementia is minimal, and people living with dementia often go undiagnosed (Kabir et al., 2013; Sultana, 2015). (বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়া সম্পর্কে সামাজিক সচেতনতা খুবই কম এবং ডিমেনশিয়ার অনেক ব্যক্তির প্রায়শই রোগ নির্ণয় করতে পারে না (কারি এট আল, ২০১৩; সুলতানা, ২০১৫))
- ▶ Accessing appropriate healthcare and social support for people with dementia is difficult in Bangladesh, and there are growing calls for a skilled and experienced dementia workforce. (বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়ার অঙ্গীকারমূলক জনসংক্রমণে উপযুক্ত স্বাস্থ্যসেবা এবং সামাজিক সহায়তা প্রাপ্য কঠিন, এবং এর ফলে দক্ষ ও অভিজ্ঞ ডিমেনশিয়া কর্মীদের চাহিদা দিন দিন বৃদ্ধি পাচ্ছে।)

Slide 3

Background and Rationale of the Study
(গবেষণার 'Background and Rationale' চর্চা)

- ▶ It is recognised that healthcare workers, nurses, practitioners, family members and caregivers all need appropriate education and training about dementia (Alzheimer Society of Bangladesh, 2018). (এটি স্বীকৃত যে স্বাস্থ্যসেবা কর্মী, নার্স, প্রক্টিশনার, পরিবারের সদস্য এবং যত্নপ্রদানকারীদের ডিমেনশিয়া সম্পর্কে উপযুক্ত শিক্ষা এবং প্রশিক্ষণ প্রয়োজন (আলজাইমার সোসাইটি অব বাংলাদেশ, ২০১৮))
- ▶ However, there is currently an absence of dementia care policy and a lack of workforce development planning and policy; dementia care is yet to be included and prioritised in the country's national healthcare policy (Rahman et al., 2017). (যদিও বর্তমানে বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন শীতের অপর্যাপ্তি এবং কর্মী উন্নয়ন পরিকল্পনা এবং শীতের অভাব রয়েছে; দেশের জাতীয় স্বাস্থ্যসেবা নীতিতে ডিমেনশিয়া যত্ন এখনও অন্তর্ভুক্ত এবং অগ্রাধিকার দেওয়া হয়নি (রহমান এট আল, ২০১৭))

Slide 4

Background and Rationale of the Study (গবেষণার ঐতিহ্যিক পটভূমিকা)

- ▶ In Scotland, the first national strategy for dementia was developed in 2010 after the production of a Charter of Rights for people with dementia which have been followed by many other countries (Jackson and Tolson, 2019). (উল্লেখ্য, ২০১০ সালে ডিমেনশিয়ায় আক্রান্তদের জন্য প্রথম জাতীয় কৌশল প্রণয়ন করা হয়েছিল যা অন্যান্য অনেক দেশ অনুসরণ করে থাকে (জ্যাকসন এবং টলসন, ২০১৯))
- ▶ As Scotland is known around the world for its progressive dementia care and workforce development policies, this study will focus on transferable policy lessons from Scotland to Bangladesh. (যেহেতু স্কটল্যান্ডে তরুণ প্রগতিশীল ডিমেনশিয়ায় তত্ত্ব এবং কর্মী উন্নয়ন নীতিনে কেন্দ্রীয় নিয়ন্ত্রণে পরিচালিত, এই গবেষণাটি স্কটল্যান্ড থেকে বাংলাদেশে হস্তান্তরযোগ্য ডিমেনশিয়ায় নীতি প্রয়োগের উপযোগিতা নির্ধারণের উপর মনোনিবেশ করবে।)

Slide 5

Purpose of the Study (গবেষণার উদ্দেশ্য)

- ▶ The purpose of this study is to investigate and analyze Scottish dementia care policies and workforce development approaches to determine the utility for application within Bangladesh. The study will seek to (এই গবেষণার প্রধান উদ্দেশ্য হল বাংলাদেশের প্রেক্ষিতে স্কটিশ ডিমেনশিয়ায় তত্ত্ব নীতি এবং কর্মী উন্নয়ন পদ্ধতির প্রয়োগের উপযোগিতা নির্ধারণের জন্য তথ্য অনুসন্ধান এবং বিশ্লেষণ করা।)

Slide 6

Purpose of Nominal Group Discussion (নমিনাল গ্রুপ আলোচনার উদ্দেশ্য)

- ▶ Purpose of Nominal Group Discussion: The main aim of Nominal Group Discussion is to identify the priorities for dementia care and workforce development policy in Bangladesh.
- ▶ (নমিনাল গ্রুপ টেকনিক-গ্রুপ আলোচনার মূল উদ্দেশ্য হল বাংলাদেশে ডিমেনশিয়ায় তত্ত্ব এবং কর্মী উন্নয়ন নীতির অগ্রাধিকার হিসাবে আপনি ফেসব বিষয় গুরুত্বপূর্ণ মনে করেন তা সনাক্ত করা।)

Slide 7

Stages of Nominal Group Discussion (নমিনাল গ্রুপ ডিস্কাসন)

- ▶ **Nominal Group Discussion includes four stages** (নমিনাল গ্রুপ আলোচনায় চারটি পর্যায় অন্তর্ভুক্ত রয়েছে):
 - Stage one: silent generation of individual ideas;** (প্রথম পর্যায়: ব্যক্তিগত ধারণার নীরব অনুশীলন;)
 - Stage two: round-robin recording of those ideas;** (দ্বিতীয় পর্যায়: মাউট-রবিন ধারণার লিপিবদ্ধকরণ;)
 - Stage three: clarification/discussion;** and (তৃতীয় পর্যায়: ব্যাখ্যা/আলোচনা; এবং)
 - Stage four: priority voting or ranking.** (চতুর্থ পর্যায়: অগ্রাধিকার নির্ধারণ বা পর্যায়ক্রম নির্ধারণ)

Slide 8

First Stage: Silent Generation of Individual Ideas (প্রথম পর্যায়: ব্যক্তিগত ধারণার নীরব অনুশীলন)

- ▶ Individually and silently, participants will write their answers or ideas that are important to them on individual note pads in response to the question (see the next slide for relevant group question) (প্রথমে অংশগ্রহণকারীরা তাদের জন্য গুরুত্বপূর্ণ ধারণাগুলি একটি কাগজে নীরবে লিখবেন।) (প্রতিটি দলের সাথে সংশ্লিষ্ট প্রশ্নের জন্য পরবর্তী স্লাইডগুলি দেখুন)
- ▶ An individual's list can be as long and as short as they like. (একজনের ব্যক্তির তালিকা যতটা পছন্দ হয় ততটাই দীর্ঘ এবং সংক্ষিপ্ত হতে পারে।)

Slide 9

First Stage: Silent Generation of Individual Ideas (প্রথম পর্যায়: ব্যক্তিগত ধারণার নীরব অনুশীলন)

- ▶ **NOT-01 Family members and informal carers of people living with dementia** (একটি-০১) (সিদ্ধেশ্বরী ব্রহ্মচারী পরিবারের সদস্য এবং অননুষ্ঠানিক যত্নপ্রদাতারা)

What do family members and informal carers need to improve the dementia care and living standards for people living with dementia in Bangladesh? (বাংলাদেশে ডিমেন্টার ব্যক্তিদের যত্ন এবং জীবন মান উন্নত করার জন্য পরিবারের সদস্য এবং অননুষ্ঠানিক যত্নপ্রদাতারদের কিভাবে সাহায্য করা উচিত তা নির্ধারণ করতে হবে)
- ▶ **NOT-02 Health and social care practitioners** (একটি-০২) (স্বাস্থ্য ও সামাজিক যত্ন প্রদাতারা)

What are the most important aspects need to consider to improve dementia care in health and social care settings in Bangladesh? (বাংলাদেশে স্বাস্থ্য ও সামাজিক পরিবেশে ডিমেন্টার ব্যক্তিদের যত্ন এবং জীবন মান উন্নত করার জন্য বিবেচনা করা উচিত গুরুত্বপূর্ণ দিকগুলি কী?)
- ▶ **NOT-03 Academics (educators and researchers)** (একটি-০৩) (শিক্ষকগণ, গবেষকগণ এবং পঠনকারীরা)

What do academics (educators and researchers) consider important to improve the dementia care and workforce development in Bangladesh? (শিক্ষকগণ, গবেষকগণ এবং পঠনকারীরা ডিমেন্টার ব্যক্তিদের যত্ন এবং কর্মসূচি উন্নয়ন উন্নত করার জন্য বিবেচনা করা উচিত গুরুত্বপূর্ণ দিকগুলি কী?)

Slide 10

First Stage: Silent Generation of Individual Ideas (প্রথম পর্যায়: ব্যক্তিগত ধারণার নীরব অনুশীলন)

- ▶ **NGT-04 Care providers (সংশ্লিষ্ট-০৪ স্বাস্থ্য প্রদানকারী)**
What do care providers need to improve the dementia care for the people living with dementia and their family carers in Bangladesh? (কোনসব উপকরণের প্রয়োজন রয়েছে ডিমেন্টিয়া রোগে ভোগা ব্যক্তিদের এবং তাদের পরিবারিক যত্নপ্রদানকারীদের দিকে মনোযোগ সহকারে করা হয় প্রত্যেককেই নিজে স্বাধীন ভাবে নীরব ওজনপূর্ণ করে হবে।)
- ▶ **NGT-04 Policy planners (সংশ্লিষ্ট-০৪ নীতি পরিকল্পনাকারী)**
What are the most important aspects need to consider in dementia policy to improve the dementia care and workforce development in Bangladesh? (কোনসব উপকরণের প্রয়োজন রয়েছে ডিমেন্টিয়া রোগে ভোগা ব্যক্তিদের দিকে মনোযোগ সহকারে ওজনপূর্ণ ভাবে নীরব দিকের করা হবে।)

Slide 11

Second Stage: Round-robin Recording of those Ideas (দ্বিতীয় পর্যায়: রাউন্ড-রবিন-ধারণার লিপিবদ্ধকরণ)

- ▶ Participants will then be asked to share one idea at a time with the group, taking it in turns to share a single idea from their list (দ্বিতীয় পর্যায়, অংশগ্রহণকারীদের গ্রুপের সাথে একটি করে ধারণা শেয়ার করতে বলা হবে, অর্থাৎ এই পর্যায় পালনকালে তাদের নিজস্ব তালিকা থেকে একটি করে ধারণা শেয়ার করতে বলা হবে।)
- ▶ There will be no discussion at this stage (এই পর্যায় কোন ধরনের আলোচনা করা হবে না)

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Second Stage: Round-robin Recording of those Ideas (দ্বিতীয় পর্যায়: রাউন্ড-রবিন-ধারণার লিপিবদ্ধকরণ)

- ▶ All ideas will be recorded verbatim on a flipchart or white board or note book by the facilitator/ researcher (ধারণাগুলি একটি ফ্লিপচার্ট বা সাদা বোর্ডে বা ওয়ার্ড ফাইলে লিপিবদ্ধ করা হবে)
- ▶ This stage will be continued until no new ideas are forthcoming. (যতক্ষণ পর্যন্ত নতুন ধারণা আসতে থাকবে, ততক্ষণ পর্যন্ত এই পর্যায়টি অব্যাহত থাকবে)

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Third Stage: Clarification/Discussion (তৃতীয় পর্যায়: ব্যাখ্যা/আলোচনা)

- ▶ All ideas will be discussed to obtain clarification about meaning and the wording of statements to ensure participant understanding. (অংশগ্রহণকারীদের বোঝার সুবিধার্থে প্রতিটি ধারণার অর্থ এবং বিবৃতি শব্দসম্পর্কে আলোচনা করা হবে।)
- ▶ Similar ideas will be grouped with agreement from all participants. (অংশগ্রহণকারীদের মতামত এবং ঐক্যমতের ভিত্তিতে অনুরূপ ধারণাগুলি শ্রেণীবদ্ধ করা হবে।)
- ▶ Ideally a short list of the key 8-12 points will be generated by the group processes. (আদর্শভাবে ৮-১২ পয়েন্টের একটি সংক্ষিপ্ত তালিকা দলীয় মতামতের ভিত্তিতে প্রস্তুত করা হবে।)

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Fourth Stage: Priority Voting or Ranking (চতুর্থ পর্যায়: অগ্রাধিকার নির্বাচন বা পর্যায়ক্রম নির্ধারণ)

- ▶ Participants will be asked to select their top five ideas from the entire set of generated ideas and then rank those five ideas. (এই পর্যায়ে দলীয় মতামতের ভিত্তিতে প্রস্তুতকৃত সংক্ষিপ্ত তালিকা থেকে অংশগ্রহণকারীদের শীর্ষ পাঁচটি ধারণা নির্বাচন এবং জরুরি সেই পাঁচটি ধারণার পর্যায়ক্রম নির্ধারণ করার জন্য অনুরোধ জানানো হবে।)
- ▶ For example, for five selected ideas, five points will be allocated to their top priority and one point to their lowest priority (উদাহরণস্বরূপ, অংশগ্রহণকারীরা সর্বাধিক গুরুত্বপূর্ণ ধারণার জন্য পাঁচ নম্বর এবং সর্বনিম্ন অগ্রাধিকারের জন্য এক নম্বর প্রদান করবেন।)

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Fourth Stage: Priority Voting or Ranking (চতুর্থ পর্যায়: অগ্রাধিকার নির্বাচন বা পর্যায়ক্রম নির্ধারণ)

- ▶ The scores for each idea will be summed and ideas listed in order by total scores (প্রতিটি ধারণার জন্য সকল অংশগ্রহণকারীর প্রদত্ত নম্বরগুলো যোগ করা হবে এবং প্রাপ্ত নম্বরের ভিত্তিতে ধারণাগুলির একটি চূড়ান্ত তালিকা করা হবে।)
- ▶ The five ideas with the highest scores will be defined as the most important for the group and will be shared the findings/ final priority list with participants for feedback and discussions (সর্বোচ্চ নম্বর প্রাপ্ত পাঁচটি ধারণা গ্রুপের জন্য সবচেয়ে গুরুত্বপূর্ণ হিসাবে সংজ্ঞায়িত করা হবে এবং প্রতিক্রিয়া এবং আলোচনার জন্য অংশগ্রহণকারীদের সাথে ফলাফল চূড়ান্ত অগ্রাধিকার তালিকা শেয়ার করা হবে।)

